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EDITORIAL NOTE

Zamfara International Journal of Education (ZIJE) is the official Journal of the Faculty of Education, Federal University Gusau, Zamfara State, Nigeria. The Journal publishes article of diverse fields of interest in education. Papers reporting original research and extended version of already established conference and journal articles are welcomed. Papers for publication are selected through peer review process to ensure originality, relevance and readability. ZIJE is published bi-annually June and December.

The aim and scope of the journal is to provide an academic medium and an important reference for the advancement and dissemination of information that supports high level learning, teaching and research in the fields of education.

This edition, Volume 3, Number 1, June, 2023 is poised to present research reports in the following fields of education: Educational Foundations, Science Education, Educational Psychology, Curriculum & Instructional Technology, Guidance & Counselling, Philosophy & History of Education, Sociology of Education, Entrepreneurship Education, Special and Inclusive Education, Physical & Health Education, Religious Education, Gender Studies, Peace & Security Education among others. The articles in this volume are academic and professional discourse written by reputable scholars in their areas of specialization.

The Board remain indebted to its editorial members for the ceaseless support given towards successful publication of the Journal. In the same vain, we acknowledge quite sincerely the assistance and support of our esteemed consulting editors for ensuring the credibility of this edition. Also worthy of appreciation are the authors and their immense contributions to this publication.

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CALL FOR ARTICLES

The Editorial Board of Zamfara International Journal of Education (ZIJE) calls for scholarly articles for review and possible publication in its next edition (Volume 4). ZIJE publishes articles that emphasize on research development and application within the field of Education. All manuscripts are reviewed by editorial review committee. Contributions must be original, not previously or simultaneously published elsewhere, and are critically reviewed before they are published. Papers, which must be written in English Language, should have good grammar and proper terminologies. Also note that prospective articles are subjected to plagiarism assessment to estimate the percentage of originality of the papers. Hence, plagiarism threshold of $\leq 20\%$ is recommended.

Editorial Guidelines

1. Manuscripts including references, appendices, tables and diagrams should be double-spaced and single coded on A4 paper with generous margins (at least 1”/2.5cm).
2. Title should be explicit and not more than 19 words.
3. Title page should be arranged as follows: Title, author(s) full name, affiliation, full addresses, email addresses and phone numbers.
4. Abstract should be single line and not more than 250 words.
5. For conceptual papers, the body should have appropriate headings where necessary.
6. For empirical papers, it should be presented in the following order: Introduction, Objectives of the study, Research Questions and/or Hypotheses, Methodology, Results, Discussion of Findings, Conclusion and Recommendations.
7. Acknowledgement (if any).
8. Quotations of more than 40 words should be indented and typed single spacing with indication of the pages where the quotes were lifted.
9. In-text citations should follow the APA 7th edition format.
10. References should be in range with 7th edition of APA Style.
11. Each table and figure should be presented within the manuscripts, with a brief and self-explanatory title.
12. All text within the table should be clearly legible, and all graphics and legends should be easily distinguished when printed in black and white.
13. Tables should be in horizontal lines only, with only blank space to separate columns.
14. Tables and figures that may be included in the main text of the paper should be numbered separately, in the sequence that they are mentioned in the text.
15. Figures should be saved in a neutral data format such as JPEG, TIFF or EPS.

Submission of Manuscripts & Assessment Fee

Manuscripts should be submitted directly to the Editor-in-Chief or Publication Editor through the following e-mail address: zijefugusau@gmail.com. Articles can be submitted between the periods of January to April ending for June publication, while July to October ending for December publication. Assessment fee for manuscript is #5,000.00 only.

Dr. Abubakar Sadiq Haruna

Publication Editor

Table of Contents

SN	Paper Title and Authors	Page
1	An overview of the Effect of Banditry and Kidnapping on Management of Secondary Schools in Zamfara State https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367091 Abubakar, H. A.	1
2	Challenges of ICT Use by Teachers and Students on Online Study during School Closure amidst COVID-19 Pandemic https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367630 Mafara, R. M. & Adamu, N. K. H.	8
3	Colleges of Education Pre-service Mathematics Teachers' Attitude as Correlate of Self-efficacy in Learning mathematics in Northwest Nigeria https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367817 Muhammad, A.	19
4	Comparison of Implementation of School Feeding Programmes in Public Primary Schools in Ondo and Osun States, Nigeria https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367850 Adepoju, A. A., Omotoyinbo, O. E. & Adebayo, O. W.	25
5	Demographic Differentials in the Use of Information and Communication Technologies among Lecturers in Colleges of Education in Ondo State https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367879 Ayelaagbe, S. & Kareem, I. A.	33
6	Effects of Flipped Classroom on Students Performance in Cell Physiology Concepts among Senior Secondary Schools in Gusau, Zamfara State, Nigeria https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367904 Yahaya, H.	40
7	Factors Hindering the Effective Integration of Almajiri Schools in Niger State, Nigeria https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367965 Mohammed, I. B.	46
8	Impact of School Feeding Program and Teaching Methods on School Attendance among Junior Secondary School Students in Kebbi State https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8368563 Ibrahim, M. & Abdulsalam, Z. M.	54
9	Islamic Mutual Financial Assistance (<i>Takaful</i>): Benefits and Challenges of the Association of Model Islamic Schools (AMIS), Taraba State Chapter https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8368600 Abdullahi, Y. U. & Umar, L	62

-
- 10 Lecturers' Perception on the Use of Schoology Web Application for Instruction in Colleges of Education in South-West, Nigeria 68
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8368613>
Alabi, A. J.
- 11 Overlooking the challenges of Sustainable Development Amidst COVID-19 Pandemic in Nigeria 74
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8370705>
Garba, A. M.
- 12 Parents' Social Variables and Youths' Dispirit for Tertiary Education in Anambra State, Nigeria 82
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8370751>
Onwuhanze, J. U., Adiewere, A. N., & Ajuru, S. U.
- 13 Python Coding amongst Undergraduate Student Teachers in a Nigeria Post-Secondary Institution: An Exploratory Study 88
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8370787>
Bakare, O. O. & Opara, C. M.
- 14 Reconsidering Policy Implementation of Vocational Technical Education using 6-3-3-4 System of Education in Curbing Societal Problems 96
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8370830>
Suleiman, J. H., Ibrahim, H. A., Nuhu, J. & Muhammad, I. Y.
- 15 Relationship between Child Abuse and Academic Achievement of Junior Secondary School Students in Southern Kaduna Senatorial District, Kaduna State 103
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8371017>
Adikwu, M. J. & Aruwa, S. M.
- 16 Reliability Index of Revised Two-Factor Study Process Questionnaire (R-SPQ-2F) for Assessing Learning Approaches of Nigerian University Education Students 110
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8371058>
Gurjiya, S. A. & Muhammad, S.
- 17 Students' Psycho-social Disposition and its Influence on Mathematics Achievement of Senior Secondary Schools in FCT, Abuja 115
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8371115>
Adikwu, M. J. & Aruwa, S. M.
- 18 The Role of Educational Psychology in Achieving Sustainable National Development: A Review of Literature 123
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8371137>
Yusuf, Zainab
-

-
- 19 Towards Enhancing Literacy and Numeracy Skills among Students in Inclusive Education Settings 127
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8371316>
Yusuf, Zainab
- 20 Trends in the Use of Wireless Fidelity on Campus among Undergraduates in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto 132
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8371330>
Idris, I. S. & Isah, A.
- 21 Use of Instructional Methods and Materials in Teaching Fine and Applied Arts in Colleges of Education in South-West, Nigeria 140
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8371344>
Kareem, I. A. & Ayelaagbe, S. O.
-

An overview of the Effect of Banditry and Kidnapping on Management of Secondary Schools in Zamfara State

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Abstract

Banditry and kidnapping in secondary schools of Zamfara state is mind blowing, these have become a global issues and threats to school management and administration. Therefore, the paper examines the concepts of banditry and kidnapping, some effects of banditry and kidnapping on management of secondary schools in Zamfara which includes fear and psychological trauma, ineffective school administration, brain drain among others. At the end some recommendations on how to tackle the menace were made such as Counseling psychologists should be prepared and deployed to institutions of learning to rehabilitate students suffering from fear and psychological trauma among others. The paper concludes that for education to continue as a right to every child, government and school management has to provide a safe and favorable teaching and learning environment.

Keywords: Banditry, Kidnapping and school management

Introduction

Nigeria is facing crucial of challenges which are affecting its national growth and development. One of the challenges is the issue of armed banditry and kidnapping on its educational sectors that is threatens the peace of the state and have rampantly contributed to set back in the management and administration of schools in the northwestern Nigeria states. Dahiru (2022) opined that Nigeria has been experiencing, high rate of violence against public schools. Armed banditry, kidnapping of school teachers, learners, and members of school-based local communities, destruction of school infrastructural facilities, *et cetera*; are among the violent activities threatening the sustenance of educational development in the country.

Banditry and kidnapping are among the current societal problems that are negatively affecting the Northern states of Nigeria. Therefore, the pervasive banditry and its associated threats to security, which have enveloped the Northwest region of Nigeria, particularly, Zamfara, Katsina, Kaduna, Sokoto and Niger States, have become a worrisome national security issue of public concern (Olaniyan and Yahaya, 2016). Armed conflicts affect education negatively; they can expose learners to trauma, psychological crises, mental health disorders and physical abuse. Disruption can lead to suspension of classes, which can last for long periods, and schools may end up being used as temporary evacuation centers (NPSSVFS 2021). According to Anka (2017) the acts of banditry and cattle rustling has also limited the chances of many children from accessing basic primary and secondary education as majority of educational structures are either damaged, destroyed or abandoned by people due to constant harassment and fear from both site of the parties.

The current dimension of banditry and kidnapping became worrisome, disheartening and alarming in the Zamfara state when In the early hours of Friday, February 26, 2021, about 279 students (Girls Only School) were kidnapped by armed bandits from their dormitories at Government Girls Secondary School, Jangebe, in Talata Mafara Local Government Area (News Agency of Nigeria, 2021); and in the month of September, 2021, about 73 Students of Government Day Secondary School, Kaya in Maradun Local Government Area of the State (Zamfara State Police Command, 2021; cited by Vanguard News, 2021). A teacher was also among the abductees. Attacks on students and schools are not only reprehensible but a violation of the right of children to an education. It is a right that any society can ill-afford to violate (UNICEF, 2021). This unfortunate circumstance has forced some parents, particularly the well to do, to transfer their children from the school in the Local Government of the State to other states of the federation, while the less privileged had no alternative than to watch their children playing, watching movies, and video games at home, a situation that if unchecked will not augur well for the educational development of the peoples living in the area, which already has been tagged as educationally backward. (Kachallah, Mohammed, Babagana and Musa, et.al, 2021).

Banditry and kidnapping destruct and destabilized the educational activities of the state. The high rate of kidnapping and banditry in certain area of the state has made such area high risk zone for Management of secondary schools in Zamfara State to be effective. The researchers observed that banditry and kidnapping impact negatively on the management of secondary schools which may result to, fear and psychological trauma in both staff, parents, and students, poor quality of education, closure

An overview of the Effect of Banditry and Kidnapping... (Abubakar, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367092>

of educational institutions, brain drain, destruction of school calendar among others both members of staff and students in the various secondary schools in the affected areas seem to be relocating elsewhere or even if they stay, they constantly live in fear hence managing the schools becomes difficult.

Considering education to be one of the fundamental human right and most of the children attending public schools are of less advantage to go elsewhere and seek for education. The effect of these attacks has further exacerbated the fragile school system which is antithetical to a sustainable national development. Several measures have been implemented to tackle this menace but there are still frequent attacks being experienced in the school environs. If these incessant attacks are not proactively dealt with, it will portend a serious danger to quality of labor force and human capital needed to drive a sustainable economy (Chinedu, Joseph, Chukwuke and Ukwunna, et.al. 2019). The action taken by government and management have deprived a lot of children the right to education because all the boarding schools and schools along the border areas are closed till further notice and this make it difficult for most of the students to attend schools. Therefore, other measures need to be put in place to create a secure and safe environment for teaching and learning. It's in the light of the above that the researcher seeks to examine the effect of banditry and kidnapping on management of secondary schools in Zamfara state.

Concept of Banditry

The term banditry simply means criminal offence that are threatening the safety of the nation. Akinyetun, (2022) refers to banditry as a type of organized crime that includes kidnapping, armed robbery, murder, rape, cattle rustling, and the exploitation of environmental resources. According to Wikipedia.org, Banditry is a type of organized crime committed by outlaws typically involving the threat or use of violence. A person who engages in banditry is known as a bandit and primarily commits crimes such as extortion, robbery, and murder, either as an individual or in groups.

Banditry refers to as the totality of incidences of armed robbery or allied violent crimes, such as kidnapping, cattle rustling, village raids as well as highway raids which involves the use of force, or threat to that effect, to intimidate a person or a group of persons in order to rob, rape, kidnap or kill the victims (Olapeju and Peter, 2021). However, Uche and Iwuamadi, (2018) state that banditry is reflected in criminal escapades like cattle rustling, kidnapping, armed robbery, drug abuse, arson, rape and the brazen and gruesome massacre of people of agrarian communities with sophisticated weapons by suspected herdsmen and reprisal attacks from surviving victims, a development that has been brought to the front burner of national security. In addition, Kangyang and Aipe (2021) opine that banditry encompasses a range of criminal activity allied to various non-ethnic and ethnic factors, many of the recent large scale armed attacks are suspected to have been carried out by Fulani assailants.

Concept of Kidnapping

Kidnapping as defined by various authors simply means to abduct, capture, carry off, remove or steal away a person (Ogabido 2009). According to Asuquo (2009) the term "kidnapping" is difficult and complex to define with precision, because it varies from State to State scenario as well as jurisdiction to jurisdiction. In any case, it is seen as the forceful seizure, taking away and unlawful detention of a person against his/her will. It is a common law offence and the key part is that, it is an unwanted act on the part of the victim. It is a restriction of someone else's liberty which violates the provision of freedom of movement as enshrined in the constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, where every other law takes its cue from. For this reason, Inyang and Abraham (2013) defined it as the forcible seizure, taking away and unlawful detention of a person against his/her will. It is a common law offence and the key part is that it is unwanted act on the part of the victim.

Kidnapping can be defined as the act of seizing and detaining or carrying away a person's by unlawful force or by fraud and often with a demand for ransom, for an act to be deemed Kidnapping, it must involve coercive movement of a victim from one place to another detention or seizure of that person be it a child or an adult (Eyikomisan, et al., 2021). Thus, Kidnapping is the act of holding a person captive in order to make them offer something in return for their release. The motivation may be economic, political, or ideological. He states that there is different pattern of kidnapping, among them are kidnap for ransom, kidnap for ritual, kidnap for strategic bargain, and child abduction (Okoli, 2022). In addition, Ibrahim and Muktar 2017 view that kidnapping is usually motivated by financial gain or political benefit. Thus, opportunist or traditional criminals as well as political dissidents can resort to kidnapping in order to illegally obtain economic gains or have their demands granted. Therefore, the act of kidnapping may include snatching, capturing seizing and abduct a person in order to collect a ransom in return or settle some disagreement among people.

An overview of the Effect of Banditry and Kidnapping... (Abubakar, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367092>

Effect of banditry and kidnapping on management of secondary schools in Zamfara State

The act of banditry and kidnapping affect the lives of many Nigeria more especially those victims living in various community of Zamfara state, which also affect the number of schools located in such areas. The effects of banditry and kidnapping on management and administration of secondary schools in Nigerian educational institutions include fear and psychological trauma, ineffective school administration, poor quality of education, disruption of academic calendar, brain drain, and closure of educational institutions.

1. Fear and Psychological trauma

In a society where the rate of banditry and kidnapping is high, people will be affected with a lot of fear and psychological trauma. The insurgent activities have injected fear into the minds of many parents and created psychological trauma among the students (Kilcullen, 2006; Metz, 2007; Paul, Clarke & Grill, 2011; Murtada, 2013). Attacks on schools in Zamfara is discouraging parents and students from going to schools especially in the areas affected. Many parents due to fear have decided to keep their children at home instead of been killed and kidnapped at schools where safety is not guaranteed. The students may not go to school due to fear of been kidnapped even if they go they will find it difficult to pay attention and concentrate in the classroom or school activities. Fear produced by banditry and kidnapping interferes with effective learning and constitutes a hitch to academic success and creates unstable behaviour among students. Most of school administrator's teachers, principal and vice have the fear of going to schools that are located in the affected areas which may cause anxiety and traumatic. The traumatic experience that the victims of kidnapping and banditry undergo usually leaves an indelible mark on them that last a life time. This has a negative psychological effect, especially in children and in most cases leads to depression, anxiety and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) which unfortunately has a long lasting effect (Chukwueme, et al., 2019)

2. Ineffective School administration

One of the objectives of schools' administration is to secure the live and property of its people. School administrators also provide healthy and conducive atmosphere for teaching, learning, experiment and research. Arockiasamy (2017) opined that school administration is not merely set of rules, regulations of orders to be followed by all concerned. It is humane, flexible, constructive, result oriented and goal oriented. It is not one-man show. This implies that School administration involves managing, administering the curriculum and teaching, pastoral care, discipline, assessment, evaluation and examinations, resources allocation, costing and forward planning, staff appraisal relationship with the community, use of practical skills necessary for surveying the policies of organization such as decision-making, negotiation, bargaining, communication, conflict handling, running meetings and so on (Okereke, 2008).

The insecurity in the Northern Nigeria has led to disruption of school administration (Ogunode & Kolo 2021). They also observed that school administration deals with the internal supervision of teaching and learning programme. It implies the coordination of all human and materials resources within the schools for the implementation of the schools programme for the realization of the objectives of the schools. The effect of banditry and kidnapping in the region have led to suspension of school programme such as school monitoring, supervision and inspection, teaching and learning, execution programme, examination and sport and all other gathering activities. School administrators were unable to go to school's inspection and teachers' activities were disrupted which affect the improvement of educational system.

3. Poor Quality of Education

Children have a right to education, a quality education which among them includes: environments that are healthy, safe, protective and gender-sensitive (UNICEF, 2000). Insecurity in Nigeria is contributing to poor quality education because, school scheme of work and syllables are not covered in most educational institutions due to school closed down. Many educational institutions in the country are always been closed down due to insecurity. The inability of these educational institutions to cover their scheme of work and syllables is reducing the quality of education (Ogunode, et.al. 2021). The entire educational institutions in Zamfara State were closed down because of attacked by bandit and kidnapper, many students were forced to go home and teaching and learning stopped and on resumption, the students were asked to start their examinations without revision or continuation of the term. Insurgency, forces students to graduate without completion of scheme of work and move others from one form of class to another class without covering the stipulated scheme of work for the time due to school closure, as a result of attacked. Schools are not able to spend stipulated number of months per term. Schools in unsafe areas lack adequate qualified teachers. As such, students are not properly taught (Oluyomi, & Grace, 2016). Paul (2015) submitted that the graduates produced through insecurity end up not having the requisite knowledge and skill to operate in the workplace; they rather become a liability. The ultimate effect is poor performance of organizations and hence the national economy. This could be one of the greatest problems facing the Nigerian economy today since the incidences of insecurity in the educational system are quite high

An overview of the Effect of Banditry and Kidnapping... (Abubakar, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367092>

4. Disruptions of Academic Calendar

The academic calendar of secondary schools in Zamfara has been affected by the insurgency challenges. Jacob and Ndubuisi (2021) observed that educational institutions operate on planned academic calendar which specifies the academic session, terms and weeks that school will open for teaching and learning. Scheme of work and syllables are there to be covered within the school calendar. These academic calendar and programmes of educational institutions are poorly implemented due to closure of school which is unhealthy for the development of education because, teaching and learning and other academic activities are intermittently disrupted. The government had shut down all the schools in Zamfara state both private and public for almost a term thousand students and pupils are at home after the incidence of GGSS Jangebe was school students' kidnap. Schools write first term, second term and term internal examinations. Some of these internal exams across the region have been disrupted. Most of the final year students are unable to cover their syllabus and scheme of work and they sat for the secondary schools leaving certificate, without considering the effects on management and learner's academic performance which disrupt the academic calendar.

5. Brain-Drains

The management of education in Nigeria depends on the effectiveness of professional administrators, teachers and non-teaching staff available to carry out the educational activities or services within the school. The act of banditry and kidnapping in Zamfara is affecting the management of secondary school education because most of the teachers are leaving the teaching profession since most of the schools are not secure and conducive for teaching and learning to take place due to this problem mass movement of professional teachers from one state to another leaving many educational institutions without qualified teachers. Many teachers are resigning their appointment due to insurgency in state and fitting on in other state or other profession that is safe. According to Ogunode, et.al. 2021 the implication of this mass migration of teachers from this region is that, less teachers will be available to teach and this will affect the quality of education because, there will be inadequate professional teachers to attend to the students.

Closures of Educational Institutions

Management of educational institution cannot be achieved in an empty space. This implies that noble goal of education can never be achieved in a vacuum. They would be achieved in a conducive and peaceful school environment. If there is a feeling of insecurity within and outside the school environment, both students and teachers are likely to be deterred and this inhibits academic performance of the students. Attacks on secondary schools in Nigeria have led many states government order closure of all educational institutions in their states to prevent further attacks (Lehr, 2004). More states in Northern Nigeria have ordered all schools to close following kidnapping of hundreds of pupils in Katsina State as reported by (BB.C, 2020). Zamfara state government ordered the closure of ten (10) secondary schools across the border line of Zamfara with Katsina state in bid to prevent the abduction of students by armed bandits until security situation improves. The affected schools were Government secondary school Zurmi, Government secondary school Birnin Magagi, Government Arabic secondary school Shinkafi, Science secondary school Shinkafi, Science secondary school Dansadau, Science secondary school Bukkuyum, Government Day secondary schools Nasarawa Mailayi, Government Day secondary school Gusami and Government Day secondary school Gurbin Bore. All the principal of the affected schools has been directed to ensure immediate closure of the affected school which greatly affect the management and administrations of all the affected schools as a result of this, most students have to move to other places to pursue education which will affect the quality of education.

On Friday 26, February 2021 Government girls' secondary school Jangebe was attacked by armed bandit and about 276 were abducted or kidnap following this abduction the governor ordered the immediate closure of all the boarding secondary schools in the state until date. This abduction really shocks the government, management, parents and students. This attacked created an unstable learning environment, discouraged parents from sending their children to school more especially the Girl-child. The girl-child is also negatively affected. She is kept at home for a long time or given out for early marriage (Oluyomi, & Grace, 2016). Zamfara state has on September, 2021 ordered the closure of all the schools within the state, both primary and secondary schools following Wednesday 1 September, 2021 abduction of 73 students and a teacher from public school in the state. The schools were closed for 4months, the schools resume on 17 January, 2022 this has really disrupted the academic school calendar and student's education on resumption not all the schools are resume. The private and public schools that were categorized as green and yellow by the ministry should resume normal activities while schools in the red category remain closed until the security situation improves. Nnamdi (2021) observed that the attacks could curtail attendance once schools reopen. Already, many parents say they no longer consider schools safe. Many Muslim parents in the North West are skeptical of what they perceive as a Western model of education; it is likely that some won't allow their children to return. Moreover, given the

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wider insecurity in the region, the abductions could prompt teachers and other staff to quit and look for employment elsewhere. Many students have been displaced and kept out of school as submitted by (Gustafsson-Wright, & Smith, 2014; Nwachukwu, et.al. 2015).

Conclusions

The school as a centered of attention is becoming more difficult to handle by school management due to banditry and kidnapping attacked on schools and community which instill fear and trauma in the lives of the school management, students and staff, disruption of school calendar, poor quality of education, closure of schools among others. Therefore, for education to continue as a right to every child government and the school management has to provide a safe and favorable environment through the following deployed counseling psychologists to all educational institutions, installed modern technology to monitored all schools, improve administrators and teacher's quality of work life, proving of security guards to safe guard life and property of all educational institutions among others. Therefore, successful management of schools depends on the security situation of the environment, security of teachers and students as well as the security of the school administrators.

Recommendations

To solve the identified problems, the following are recommended: -

- 1 Counseling psychologists should be prepared and deployed to institutions of learning to rehabilitate students suffering from fear and psychological trauma. Counselors should be able to adopt various strategies among include the use Rational Emotive Behavioural Therapy to alleviate stress, fear, and anxiety, psychological disturbance that both the teachers and students face as a result of the activities of insurgency.
- 2 Government should liaise with the school management to develop strategies that will improve the security and safety of teachers and learners in educational institution. The school administrators and teachers should be sensitized to ensure that once children are in school, they have to be monitor to prevent them from loitering outside the school and to also be watchful to know the kind of visitors that come to the schools not everyone should be allowed into the educational institution. Installation of modern technology like CCTV will help to improve the security condition. Therefore, safety learning and teaching environment encourage teamwork between management and teachers as well as effect school programme will be executed. This would encourage the school administrator to discharge their responsibilities of monitoring, supervision, inspection among others effectively and efficiently.
- 3 The government and school management should encourage teachers to engage in an advocacy campaign to provide online training or through the media training to educate students when at home so that whenever school resumes not all will be forgotten. Other programme should be initiated by the government to teach those students at home in a safe and secure place in different community by some educational aspect before school resumed in order to improve quality education.
- 4 Government and school management create awareness regarding security and safety for learners and its implication. This can be done through sensitization and enlightenment campaign through newspapers, radio, television and social media handles so that parents will be aware of why some of the schools in their community are closed down and will not be open, that there are certain criteria approved and recognized only those schools that meet the minimum standards in safety and security requirement will be open. That is why the government and school management open schools with green and yellow and closed all in red zones.

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Challenges of ICT Use by Teachers... (Mafara & Adamu, 2023) Doi: [https://doi.org/ 10.5281/zenodo.8367630](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367630)

Challenges of ICT Use by Teachers and Students on Online Study during School Closure amidst COVID-19 Pandemic

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Abstracts

ICT-based learning is kind of learning that use Information and Communication Technology (ICT) to foster, optimize, enhance and support gaining knowledge. Covid-19 has caused the full transformation to ICT-based learning. This study aimed to investigate the advantages, opportunities and challenges of ICT-BL during the pandemic. Systematic analysis of the qualitative results indicated that possibility of Online learning, saving time and money, communication and motivation tool, usage of social media, sharing and processing the knowledge and improving the quality of education were the highest ranked advantages of the ICT-based learning and remote learning, extra time, adoption of new skills and more technologies and MOOCs in addition to family gathering were the most opportunities while internet accessibility, electricity problems, maintenance of infrastructure, high cost of ICT device and lack of expertise, ability to manage classrooms and plagiarism were the high ranked challenges for both students and lecturers to continue online learning. Developing countries need to develop new strategies and techniques to promote ICT-based learning based on innovation, socio-cultural and socio-economic aspects not only financial support.

Keywords: ICT use, Online learning, School closure, COVID-19

Introduction

ICT applications plays significant role in education in new technological era especially during covid-19 pandemic. Although, applications and practices of ICT-based learning (ICT-BL) are not adopted in developing countries as developed countries, but many of developing countries have been forced to adopt ICT-based learning. Developing countries have adopted ICT as part of educational system over the past two decades of the twenty-one century (Shen & Ho, 2020). However, a very few progresses have been made. Indeed, a small percentage of schools /universities in some developing countries including Indonesia have achieved middle levels of effective use of information and communication technology (Lestari & Prasetyo, 2019) to support and change the teaching and learning process in many areas of study. Others are struggling in the first stage of adopting information and communication technologies related to many problems and challenges such as poverty, conflicts, wars and sociocultural procedures Janssen et. al (2019) that hinder the progress in education in developing world. Implementing ICT in learning process in most of educational institutions in developing countries faces some challenges including little to no computer experience, poorly equipped classrooms, most rural schools are not on the electrical grid, expensive and slow internet connections, most schools with computers are not using them as a medium of instruction and shortage of e-learning materials for students (Kettunen & Sampson, 2019; Hinostroza, 2018). On the other hand, implementing ICT in learning has many benefits such as improving engagement and knowledge retention, encouraging individual's learning and collaboration and learning different skills in flexible time.

According to the report from UNESCO 2020, the pandemic has a devastating impact on global education (Statista, 2020). By May 2020, 95% cent students around the world have been affected by the outbreak of the virus, representing 1.7 billion of the students worldwide, from kindergarten to postgraduate, in more than 200 countries (UN, 2020) where governments around the world ordered closures of schools and universities. Based on this fact, many schools and universities world-wide began to adopt online learning. Adoption of ICT-based learning resulted many advantages, opportunities and challenges and that was the reason to write this paper.

Challenges of ICT Use by Teachers... (Mafara & Adamu, 2023) Doi: [https://doi.org/ 10.5281/zenodo.8367630](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367630)

Figure 1. Number of students affected by school closures globally, source: (Statista, 2020)

ICT- based learning have many advantages and components such as quality of content, supporting learning system, ability of such system to interactive, ease of use and educational evaluation (Binyamin, Rutter, & and S. Smith, 2019). Besides, advantages could be different modes based on the type of learning such as availability in time and place, equity, enhancing collaboration between students and educators, direct access to different resources, ability to enhance service of education dimensions globally and ability to determine the progress rate in educational courses (Talebian, et al, 2014). Use of ICT has positive impact on learning in high schools and ICT factors such as infrastructure, devices, techniques, methods and applications have more affective influence to learning in undergraduate and graduate levels (Al-Ansi, et al., 2019). In the other hand, penetration of electronic devices in learning such as laptops, cell-phones and tablets and availability of these devices for students facilitated the ability of learning. Some of studies stated that number of mobile devices are more than the people in the globe were reached more than 7.9 billion devices. This enables usage of m-learning effectively and offers many of opportunities in learning anywhere anytime regardless some limitations in use of mobile device as learning tool (Criollo-C, Luján-Mora, & A. Jaramillo-Alcázar, 2018). Advantages of ICT usage in learning include control of the content, control the approaches of presentation, creativity and modernity, ability to give feedback anytime and Adaptability (Padurean, 2009).

Regardless the negative impact of Covid-19 in our life today, ICT-Based learning has many opportunities during this pandemic including saving more time and expenses, adoption more technologies to learning, learning new skills and availability of learning materials online all the time in addition to the gathering with family while studying/teaching. Different previous studies discussed the opportunities of ICT-Based learning in enhancing the abilities and competencies of students/educators and facilitating learning process (Al Ansi & Al-Ansi, 2020). The use of social networking tools to enhance collaborative learning activities is seen as an effective way for students to experience a sense of ownership of the learning process. (Kurtz, 2014), and guide the student to discuss problems with their classmates. Other studies discussed the importance of collaborative learning role in saving time of students and educators in sending emails, saving, revising and editing materials and other activities which leads to improve their productivity (Huang, 2017). In another hand, social media plays an important role in ICT-based learning at the pandemic time and social distancing. Using of social media and sharing various information in the same platforms would significantly increase students' understanding of complex subject (Erturk, 2016) and able them to post and share their ideas. In addition, teleconferencing applications became the main tool for conducting online classes such as zoom and google teams. Besides, a chatting is a useful approach to mitigate some problems students may be facing when they learn a specific topic. This is due to saving these chatting and students have the ability to read and review anytime they need (Subramani, 2015).

Challenges of ICT Use by Teachers... (Mafara & Adamu, 2023) Doi: [https://doi.org/ 10.5281/zenodo.8367630](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367630)

On the other hand, ICT-based learning in developing countries faces many challenges (Garad & Al-Ansi, 2021). Some of these challenges are about the speed, coverage and cost of internet, electricity problems, high cost of infrastructure, managing and organizing classrooms, maintenance of hardware and software, lack of expertise and sometimes plagiarism. One Study by Çakici (2016) mentioned some problems related to using ICT in classrooms such as inability to use software and hardware of ICT, shortage of technical support, no enough time to use ICT, some difficulties related to access resources, restriction of content and insufficient resources Technology. Another study by Manda and Dhaou (2019) investigated the challenges in the 4th industrial revolution which included potential job loses, skill challenges, Infrastructure challenges, security and privacy. In fact, challenges of ICT-based learning differ among nations. Developed countries experience social challenges such as loss of jobs, disqualified HR, new kinds of stress and some problems related to increasing insecurity in social system (European Parliament, 2016) in addition to Changing business models, data issues, legal issues of liability and intellectual property, and mismatch of standards and skills (Dregger, 2016) while developing countries are more concern about infrastructure, advances in technology and manufacturing techniques, Low e-readiness levels, lack of digital connectivity, skills, knowledge, and innovation (Manda & Backhouse, 2016).

Different research has investigated the role of ICT in education, in addition to exploring benefits and challenges or ICT-based learning and comparing technologies development and implementations in developing and developed countries. This research is unique due to current condition of ICT-based learning. ICT-based learning became the only learning tool because of Covid-19 pandemic. Online learning depends on ICT applications and techniques (Al Ansi A. M., 2017). Many governments in developing countries invested in infrastructure of online learning during past few years where some universities were conducting some classes online through LMS of university. Covid-19 has caused many serious problems to our health system (Al-Ansi, 2021), economy and learning system as well. It is important to mention that adoption and implementation of ICT in education in developed countries are more effective and the problem that educational systems has or policies' makers face are not the same as in developing world. So, investigating the real problems related to ICT-based learning systems in developing countries after the total transforming of learning to be online is what makes this study significant.

This research aims to investigate the opportunities, challenges and advantages of using ICT in learning as solution to face outbreak of the virus worldwide. To get this aim, the following question is raising: what are the advantages, opportunities and challenges of ICT-based learning in developing countries such as Indonesia during the Covid-19 pandemic? Although many developing countries have promoted such technologies effectively since time ago but these countries have not adopted technologies in education as developed countries. To answer this question, direct interviews with students, lecturers, administrative staff and ICT specialist in Islamic schools, Malang city- Indonesia were conducted to explain the advantages, opportunities and challenges of ICT-based learning process in their schools.

According to Stewart et al. (2011), online learning refers to a system of learning where the students learn virtually through the use of the Internet. Dhawan (2020) defines online education as the ability of learners to use devices connected to a network, offering them the possibility to learn with any means, in any rhythm, anytime, and from anywhere. In another piece of research, Singh & Thurman (2019) refer to online learning as "learning experiences in synchronous or asynchronous environments using different devices (e.g., mobile phones, laptops, etc.) with internet access. In these environments, Students can be anywhere (independent) to learn and interact with instructors and other students."

Rapantar et al. (2020) define online learning as internet-enabled learning, which includes collaboration between experts, content creators, a networked community of learners, management of learning experiences, and content delivery. In his research, Kundu (2018) defines online learning as the delivery of course materials via electronic methods such as CDs, television, video or audio tape, satellite broadcast, extranets, intranets, and the internet. Combining these definitions, online learning can be referred to as the internet-based delivery of course content to learners through the use of internet-enabled devices such as laptops and phones. Online learning has been accelerated by fast internet development and globalization, making many institutions of higher learning start to focus on online learning. Mart (2017) says that institutions all over the world have been trying to deviate their spending towards infrastructural development to have distance learning in place as the next best alternative to the traditional classroom teaching method. For its implementation to succeed, online education has to be acceptable to all the stakeholders, or at least a majority of them, such as students, teachers, administrators, parents, and the education ministries. In their study, Shearer et al. (2020), while examining the student's perception of and motivation towards online education, noted that curriculum developers and policymakers should understand the students' limitless perspectives so that they can offer student-centric instructional techniques while increasing students' satisfaction and engagement.

While the developed world has embraced online learning to a greater extent, developing countries have yet to provide schools with relevant infrastructural development to integrate virtual learning as a supplement to face-to-face learning. The gap

Challenges of ICT Use by Teachers... (Mafara & Adamu, 2023) Doi: [https://doi.org/ 10.5281/zenodo.8367630](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367630)

in access to ICT between the rich and the poor in developing countries is quite wide (Venkatesh and Sykes, 2013). In their research, Srivastava and Shainesh (2015) found out that the set-up of the societies in these countries is grounded on a compound geographical spread and socioeconomic levels where most of the people lack access to basics such as education and healthcare, which makes access to ICT less of a priority. This means that stopping physical learning abruptly to introduce online learning from home had a big effect on the poor. Similarly, considering gender-based differences, females are more affected than their male counterparts, which, according to Cutter (2017), could have placed them among the have-nots considering that at home, they are required to participate in feminine gender roles such as caregiving, cleaning, and cooking. In another study, there were four major factors that should be considered while implementing online learning and that influence its acceptance among the various stakeholders. The first factor is accessibility.

According to Park (2009), online learning accessibility refers to the level of ease with which students in an institution can receive and use the school's online learning system as an organizational factor. He says that to ensure high rates of acceptance among students, schools must ensure that internet accessibility is high enough, so the priority should be to provide students with access to computers and internet connectivity. The next factor is appropriateness, which refers to the fitness of online learning for a student's needs. d'Antoni (2002) says that any e-learning strategy that a school adopts should be best-fit to the needs of a student, depending on their academic level and other needs at the time of its implementation. In their study of open educational resources and open content, Stewart et al. (2011) say that comprehensive online learning for both synchronous and asynchronous communication modes make sure that the implemented strategy is appropriate for all learners. Synchronous teacher-learner and learner-learner communication is enhanced by chat techniques such as message boards and bulletin boards. On the other hand, asynchronous communication is enhanced by the use of less time-sensitive platforms such as emails. To formulate the most appropriate strategy, a school must be able to overcome barriers related to access such as electricity, internet connectivity, and infrastructural redundancy (Laskaris et al., 2017).

Thirdly, schools should consider accreditation of the adopted strategies. Different strategies are guided by the geographical location of a school; for instance, a school's country of origin determines the ease of implementation. Finally, affordability should be considered any time there is an online learning implementation, which is also influenced by the specific location of a school. With these factors in mind, researchers show that online learning implementation in institutions of higher learning should be regarded as an important educational reform.

The above four factors show that effective and efficient implementation calls for huge attention and care to achieve success. In a study looking into the factors that lead to acceptance of ICT in the classroom, Lawrence & Tar (2018) found that successful adoption of online learning requires that teachers and school heads become part of the decision-making process. Their findings were in line with those of Baydas & Goktas (2016) and Mirzajani et al. (2016), who believe that support from senior management plays a significant role during the implementation process. Similarly, in their review, Akkara and Mallampalli (2020) stated that e-learning cannot happen in a vacuum as it needs two of the most important pillars: internet connectivity and the existence of relevant infrastructure. Shehab and Khalifa (2021) carried out a study in Kurdistan to determine the challenges student nurses were facing while studying online. In interviews with 25 students and educators, the researchers found out that Kurdistan faces immense problems, which require that the region invest heavily to boost its infrastructure to allow for the successful implementation of e-learning systems, as the public universities in the region rely on funding from the KRG. Due to these issues, researchers have identified that some schools have opted for blended learning, which requires less capital for implementation (Rassul & Wali, 2020; Shabila et al., 2021).

There are some difficulties felt in the implementation of the change process in the education system that has arisen after the COVID-19 crisis; these difficulties are related to the novel perspectives of online education and their technological complexities. Earlier in this pandemic, online education was considered the education provided by open universities in India. But in the COVID-19-induced time, online teaching and learning became a massive challenge to deal with, and stakeholders are not potentially fit to adjust to the sudden educational change as they are not technologically competent to embrace the current situation. Therefore, for the successful implementation of educational change,

Challenges of ICT Use by Teachers... (Mafara & Adamu, 2023) Doi: [https://doi.org/ 10.5281/zenodo.8367630](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367630)

Fig. 2 describes how to decide on the implementation process of online teaching and learning.

The journey begins with the collective vision of UGC and MHRD (supra-system), universities and Colleges (system), and different academic departments (sub-system) in favor of implementing online teaching and learning in the education system. In the face of COVID-19, the shared vision of education system realized that during the pandemic period, teachers and students are motivated to adapt online teaching- learning platforms in fulfilling the current educational needs. Everyone, either teachers or students, was friendly and skilled in using social media apps such as WhatsApp, Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram, which turned into smooth facilitation of using online educational platforms such as Zoom, Cisco WebEx, Google Meet, etc. as a sign of positive transfer of learning. Also, there are some useful educational apps such as Office 365, Google Classroom, and much more user-friendly videoconferencing apps that can be downloaded free of charge and are easy to use (FutureLearn, 2020), so to some extent, it seems that there is no reason to get into a panic to get new technology all of a sudden as some of the apps are already embedded in our HEIs. The majority of stakeholders possessed smartphones, and only a considerable number had laptops. These are the needed resources to implement online teaching and learning.

Mizoram University has an ICT center and LMS that help in seamless monitoring of online teaching and learning modes. The central and State governments unanimously agreed upon implementing online education across the country, keeping in mind the need of the hour. Various national, state, and university-level teachers' and students' associations half-heartedly and hesitatingly supported the vision of online teaching-learning modes with mixed bags of opinion as a result of curiosity to trial new technology and the new mode of the teaching-learning process in the education system; it is due to the lack of preparedness, orientation, and incentives of stakeholders in using the online mode of teaching.

The action plan was prepared keeping in view our readiness for online teaching mode, our drive for change in this pandemic, and the availability of resources for implementing online teaching mode. To go with the action plan, teachers prepared and trained themselves independently to become accustomed to the technology required for using online teaching modes. At the university level, system administrators and Information and Communication Technology (ICT) experts provided necessary assistance to stakeholders and managed the change process. However, while many pieces of research have been conducted on online teaching and learning and its effectiveness, no such studies were conducted during the COVID-19 lockdown period. Hence, the researcher is insightfully interested in doing this study with the following objectives:

Just like their teachers, students also had challenges adjusting to online learning from traditional class-based learning. In the study of barriers to online learning in the time of COVID-19, Ronnie et al. (2020) discovered that students found it difficult to adjust to online learning styles due to having to perform responsibilities at home and poor communication between them and lectures. Students were generally not prepared for online learning. While it was found that social issues and lecturer issues affect students' intentions to study online, access to online learning platforms was a demonstrable major challenge for many students (Aboagye et al., 2020; Chung, 2020; Rapanta et al., 2020).

In particular, technical issues may occur in the middle of online learning, yet most students do not have access to technical support and advanced technologies that facilitate online learning (O'Keefe, 2020). Access to digital learning devices such as laptops and tablets and access to data for internet connections were found to be barriers to online learning for some students (Adnan & Anwar, 2020; Dhawan, 2020; Moawad, 2020). Lack of access to online learning systems is common among students from poor families living in underdeveloped communities. The study that was conducted in West Bengal, India, shows that 30.6% of students studied through reading textbooks by themselves and did not participate in e-learning, mainly due to a

Challenges of ICT Use by Teachers... (Mafara & Adamu, 2023) Doi: [https://doi.org/ 10.5281/zenodo.8367630](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367630)

lack of access to online learning platforms (Kapasia et al., 2020). As also understood by Dawadi et al. (2020), access to online learning for some students in these difficult times is a major problem for the higher education sector as it increases the already existing inequalities among its citizens in terms of their socio-economic status and education or literacy. While some students are dissatisfied with the existing online teaching platforms (Chen et al., 2020), others have more serious challenges to overcome, such as those concerning access to online learning platforms (Ronnie et al., 2020).

Online teaching and learning require a fast and reliable internet connection. Therefore, the shift from traditional face-to-face learning to online learning meant that students and academics had to stay connected to the internet. However, under some circumstances, this may be impossible; hence, teaching and learning would be affected. Challenges with connectivity were highlighted as the leading factor undermining e-learning and e-teaching during lockdown as a result of Covid-19 pandemic outbreak (Aboagye et al., 2020; Bao, 2020; Berezha et al., 2020; Dawadi, 2020; Jena, 2020). In their study of barriers to online learning, Ronnie et al. (2020) found the availability of a fast and reliable internet connection to be a greater concern than either device ownership or technical aptitude. The critical challenge of a reliable internet connection for online learning was also reported in the literature (Mamun et al., 2020; Naciri, 2020) as the main cause of non-participation in online learning by the majority of students. This drawback for online learning, according to Demuyakor (2020), was attributed to a lack of internet data among Ghanaian international students in China. The unavailability of suitable hardware and software to access online learning was also identified as a barrier by some students (Crawford et al., 2020).

In an attempt to ensure that all students have equal access to online learning, Student Representative Councils (SRCs) in various universities demanded the provision of digital learning devices (smartphones, tablets, and laptops) and internet data to all students (Kwabena & Boateng, 2020). However, some students could not access online tools despite having digital learning devices and internet data because of a poor network at home (Aboagye et al., 2020; Rose, 2020; Wargadinata et al., 2020). The poor network problem is particularly common in developing countries where ICT and telecommunications systems are not properly developed (Aboagye et al., 2020). Correspondingly, Chang and Fang (2020) discovered that 60%–70% of teachers agree that "network speed and stability are poor", leading to challenges with accessing online learning tools. This literature evidence suggests that reliable network infrastructure, availability of internet data, and availability of digital learning devices such as smart phones, tablets, and laptops to students are important to ensure smooth online teaching and learning.

The lack of physical learning space and environment also presented itself as a challenge for some students learning online during lockdown. In most poor households, students do not have a private room where they can peacefully study without disturbance (Ronnie et al., 2020). Learning from home therefore becomes difficult for this disadvantaged group of students. The research conducted by Demuyakor (2020) shows that some students have to rush to the toilets to answer calls from their professors or to turn off video feeds because of the noisy background. Similarly, Kapasia et al. (2020) found that, of 232 students, 103 (44.4%) had no separate reading room for the study. Without a conducive learning environment, students are unable to concentrate on their schoolwork, and study productivity is reduced as a result (Chang & Fang, 2020). As argued by Daniel (2020), it is therefore necessary that institutions and educational systems consider the concerns of students whose parents are unsupportive and whose home environments are not conducive to study. The shift to online education during COVID-19 overlooked this reality of an unconducive learning environment, which negatively affects learning outcomes.

The mental health issues associated with COVID-19 and the sudden shift from class-based to online learning are also demonstrable in the literature. Such issues include stress, anxiety, and depression, which occur due to a sudden change in one's lifestyle and uncertainty about the future (Rajkumar, 2020; Ronnie et al., 2020; Rossi et al., 2020; Tandon, 2020; Xiong et al., 2020). Learning loss and drop-out rates, among other harder-to-quantify factors due to COVID-19, cause social and emotional disruption for the general public and worse for students (Dorn, 2020). In addition, students whose family income or livelihood strategy was impacted by COVID-19 and its regulations were found likely to suffer from stress, anxiety, and depression, which in turn affect motivation to engage in online learning (Cao et al., 2020; Husky et al., 2020; Son et al., 2020; Wu et al., 2020; Zolotov et al., 2020). While COVID-19 created fear and other mental health issues among Israeli university students, Zolotov et al. (2020) further discovered that students who were psychologically affected turned to substance use in order to cope. This coping mechanism during these difficult times has a negative impact on learning. Among Chinese students, 24.9% have experienced anxiety because of this COVID-19 outbreak (Pragholapati, 2020). Anxiety was often associated with having a relative or acquaintance who is infected with COVID-19 (Pragholapati, 2020).

There is limited research evidence on the impact of COVID-19 on students' academic performance. This is probably due to the lack of data that measures academic outcomes during the COVID-19 period. However, it is expected that as academic results become available, more research will be conducted in this area. Gonzalez et al. (2020) studied the academic performance of students before and after COVID-19 confinement. Their study results show that students achieved significant improvements

Challenges of ICT Use by Teachers... (Mafara & Adamu, 2023) Doi: [https://doi.org/ 10.5281/zenodo.8367630](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367630)

in their scores even in tests that were performed in an online format in previous years (Gonzalez et al., 2020). Moreover, this improvement is only significant when comparing data after the COVID-19 confinement (i.e., there are no significant differences in on-line tests that were performed before the confinement) (Gonzalez et al., 2020). Therefore, these findings reveal that the new assessment process cannot be the reason for the improvement in students' performance because the learners also achieved better scores when the format of the assessment did not change (Gonzalez et al., 2020). Although Gonzalez et al.'s study did not find the effect of COVID-19 confinement on students' academic performance, it is expected the COVID-19 outbreak will not only cause poor performance among students but also increase the dropout rate (Dorn et al., 2020).

While COVID-19 has created a lot of problems for the higher education sector, it has been recognized that this pandemic has, on the positive side, created opportunities. Such opportunities involve new approaches and tools for learning online and capacity development. For instance, lockdown implemented as a result of COVID-19 pushed universities that previously used traditional teaching methods into the digital world (Ratten, 2020). This means universities must develop innovative ways to deliver teaching without compromising quality (Ratten, 2020).

Also, new challenges associated with online teaching and learning will create a space for innovative thinking and innovative solutions within the sector (Bryson & Andres, 2020). It is also argued that due to online teaching and learning, both students and teaching staff will further develop their online communication and interpersonal skills through regular exposure to online platforms (Beech & Anseel, 2020). The COVID-19 outbreak also presented opportunities for new research in a new area with the increased use of digital data collection methods and a wider exposure to the virtual dissemination of research results. This provided researchers and academics with new experiences in the digital world necessary for their capacity development (Gardner, 2020; Shahzad et al., 2020; Zhu & Liu, 2020). Therefore, not all is bad about COVID-19; however, challenges and problems far exceed opportunities.

One of the theories that guided the current study is Classical Liberal Theory of Equal Opportunities. According to Von Mises (2012), liberalism is an aspect in which equality and individual liberty are considered the most important objectives by emphasizing equality and individual rights. Liberal theories advocate the provision of basic rights for everyone while seeking to avoid favoritism or unfairness. Therefore, the classical liberal theory of equal opportunities holds that an individual matters most and that in any society, an individual must be allowed to live the best life in their own unique way. As such, it is clear that society must take deliberate steps to ensure all individuals receive equal opportunities in any societal realm. In the current study, this theory will be used to elucidate the need for providing learners with equal opportunities despite their coming from different socioeconomic backgrounds. The pandemic has widened economic inequality in the region, which could limit access to education.

The equivalence theory holds that for distance learning to be considered a success, it must provide learning experiences for every student, either locally or distantly. The model states that distance learning is not the same as physical learning, but the two approaches are equivalent (Lapsley et al., 2008). This means that the term equivalency should not be confused with mean equal, but it is a situation in which learning experiences that students receive are considered to give them similar experiences for similar outcomes. However, the main emphasis of the theory is not to expect that every student will be taught or learn in a similar manner (Garratt-Reed et al., 2016). According to Goldie, J. G. S. (2016), connectivism is, to a certain degree, a new theory of Learning suggests that learners need to combine general manners, theories, and thoughts in a useful manner. The theory emphasizes that technology is a key part of the learning process and that persistent connectedness provides people with opportunities to make choices about their learning. The theory states that some of the digital technology features, such as web browsers and search engines, are significant tools that help in online learning implementation. As such, education, being an important aspect of people's lives, is a subject of technology. As Strong & Hutchins (2009) state, learning only happens within ever-changing networks, only after information sources and specialized nodes are connected, and can occur in non-human appliances. In online education, learning happens when various stakeholders interact; an example is the interaction between students and teachers. For this reason, this theory was selected.

Researchers have agreed on the fact that the technology acceptance model (TAM) has been the most influential of all the theories explaining the acceptance of digital transformation. The theory illustrates and describes how people in different societal realms come to accept and widely use a given technology. The actual use of a system is the result of how people use the technology. People are forced by behavioral intention (BI) to embrace technology. But BI is affected by attitude, which is the general impression of the technology. One of the factors that influence acceptance is Perceived usefulness, which has to do with how the users view the technology in question. To accept a given technology, a user must perceive it as useful in their lives, and in this case, the general education Another factor that users consider is ease-of-use, which is defined as "the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would be free from effort (Al-Marroof & Al-Emran, 2018). The

Challenges of ICT Use by Teachers... (Mafara & Adamu, 2023) Doi: [https://doi.org/ 10.5281/zenodo.8367630](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367630)

hindrances are removed only if the user thinks that the technology in question is easy to use. This theory will be useful for the current study in explaining why there could have been resistance during the initial stages of the implementation of online learning in Nigeria.

The COVID-19 pandemic presented a demand for online education in a manner that the Ahmadu Bello University and Zaria institutions of higher learning could not keep up with. In a situation where such a demand is experienced, abrupt transitioning could prove impossible, particularly in regions where the resources needed are not readily available. Teachers were not well-versed in the art of distance learning and ensuring that the syllabus was completed on time. Administrators may also need vast training on how to manage teams remotely and have all tasks completed on time. On their side, the parents and society may not accept the instant transition, and they may not be well-versed in guidelines to help their children cope.

Finally, resistance from students could hinder any government efforts to integrate virtual learning methods. With the difficulty that the pandemic presents in the region and beyond and the possible impacts that could be experienced from future pandemics, it is clear that Kurdistan's ability to quickly leverage the available technology, mobilize stakeholders to devise relevant emergency mechanisms to adapt to any new norms and offer the pertinent infrastructural adjustments will determine the continuation of learning in all schools. The impacts of COVID-19 on the education sector have been felt in all countries globally, including Iraq and Kurdistan. The reason is that there was an abrupt disruption of pedagogical processes across all the learning institutions, both K–12 and institutions of higher learning alike. The most affected students are the grade 12 students, who were expecting their national exams at the end of the year. Although they were allowed to attend school normally while others were learning from home, they were psychologically affected, which could greatly impact their test results in this crucial season of their lives.

The disparity in home-based learning poses a huge problem to the acquisition of online learning programs. The inequality is primarily presented by a difference in the socio-economic aspects of the Zaria community, which has been a major issue for a long time. The socioeconomic status of a family affected how well a student received online classes. Those living in impoverished conditions do not have the relevant resources, locking them out of accessing the learning materials shared remotely. This explains the resistance that the adoption of online learning faced from parents whose students studied in public schools, as their situations are already dire. According to Ali et al. (2021), a student's or parent's choice of school in Zaria is heavily influenced by their socio-economic status. Therefore, those living in poor conditions have limited abilities to navigate the disrupted educational landscape in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Many researchers have tried to cover the critical issues that affect the successful implementation of e-learning strategies in developed, developing, and undeveloped countries. A vast number of studies have also been carried out on the challenges that came as a result of the abrupt implementation of e-learning in the wake of COVID-19. The only information available is in news articles and articles from other countries, especially the developed world. News is not scientific and, therefore, may not be used as a source of information during policy recommendations. On the other hand, the literature from Western nations cannot be used since the technological environment and socio-economic factors in the West and Kurdistan differ immensely. Some issues experienced in Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, such as unreliable power supply in remote areas, slow telecommunications infrastructure development, and low bandwidth, may not be experienced in other countries, while they might be extreme in others. Thus, a successful transition from traditional methods of learning towards a technology-based education system needs documented scientific evidence from research like the current one. Understanding the challenges towards a successful integration of e-learning as an emergency option. Therefore, the current paper presents the findings from a study investigating the challenges that hindered the successful implementation of online learning in Nigerian public universities when schools were massively closed during the COVID-19 era. The research included the gathering of data from various officials as major stakeholders in various public universities in an interview to present their perceptions on the matter.

Objectives of Study

The objective of the study was to “Examine the challenges faced by teachers and students in adapting to the online teaching and learning process during the COVID-19 pandemic”.

Research Question

What are the challenges faced by teachers and students in adapting to the online teaching and learning process during the COVID-19 pandemic?

Challenges of ICT Use by Teachers... (Mafara & Adamu, 2023) Doi: [https://doi.org/ 10.5281/zenodo.8367630](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367630)

Methodology

This study employed survey research in order to assess the respondent’s feelings concerning the issues online education has faced since the start of the pandemic. The population of the study comprises of lecturers and students of tertiary institutions in Northwest Nigeria. The sample consists of 160 participants drawn from among lecturers and students in Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. The sampling approach used for the current research was convenience-type non-probability sampling. Here, the researcher draws a sample from a group of people who are easy to contact or reach. The reason for choosing non-probability sampling and not randomization is because some of the education experts have busy schedules and it would take a long time to book an appointment with them. Due to the time constraint of the research, convenience sampling was the best alternative for the current research. The researcher chooses groups based on their capacity to produce categories (variables) and category attributes and connects them with their qualities. The researcher selected lecturers, ICT technical staff lecturers, and students who had enough knowledge of the online teaching sector to participate in the study. The sample was 65% male and 35% female. One of them is a professor, an associate professor for high information and communication technology staff, senior lecturers, junior lecturers, and students of all types for the province. Looking at their educational attainments, 7.1% of them were Bachelor’s holders, 21.4% were master’s holders, and the remaining 71.4% were Ph.D. holders. The oldest was 66 years old, and the youngest was 36. The researchers distributed one hundred and sixty (160) copies of questionnaires to both lecturers and students of Ahmadu Bello University. Zaria and one hundred and fifty (150) copies of the questionnaire were returned duly completed, representing 96% turn-over. The main reason for the high response was the commitment of the research assistants to ensuring that all distributed questionnaires were collected.

The researchers adopted a quantitative approach using mean and standard deviation to allow for a deeper and broader understanding of the topic in question. The researcher chose to use semi-structured interviews to collect data from the participants. One advantage of this method is that the researcher formulates questions prior to the meeting so that the conversation can be smooth and have the direction to avoid loss of focus. Besides, participants could respond to the open-ended questions in the best possible way to provide in-depth data. To equally get answers from the participants, the researcher asked the same questions to all of them. Lindlof (1995) argues that "by asking the same questions of all participants in roughly the same order, the researcher minimizes interviewer effects and achieves greater efficiency of information gathering".

Results

Research Question

What are the challenges faced by teachers and students in adapting to the online teaching and learning process during the COVID-19 pandemic?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of responses on challenges in adapting to online learning amidst COVID-19

Statement of Assessment	Mean	Std. Dev	Frequency	%	Decision
Teachers, ICTs, and students faced challenges in adapting to the online teaching-learning process during the Covid-19 pandemic.	2.05	0.99	150	100%	Disagree

The mean score of 2.05 indicates that respondents disagreed with the statement that teachers, ICT professionals, and students easily adapted to the online teaching and learning process. This finding highlights the difficulties faced by these stakeholders in adjusting to the new virtual learning environment. The challenges might include technological issues, limited access to resources, and the need for training and support. Addressing these challenges through targeted interventions and professional development programs can improve the effectiveness of online teaching and learning. The respondents disagreed that teachers, ICT staff, and students faced challenges in adapting to the online teaching-learning process. This implies that there is a consensus among the participants that challenges were encountered during the transition to online education.

Discussion of Findings

This discussion provides insights into the perceptions and experiences of teachers, ICT staff, and students regarding various aspects of online teaching and learning during the Covid-19 pandemic. The disagreements and undecided responses suggest areas of concern and potential areas for improvement in terms of resources, training, support, student participation, and technical management. Based on the analysis of the data, several trends and patterns emerge. The findings indicate that there were generally negative perceptions and challenges associated with online teaching and learning during the Covid-19 pandemic.

Challenges of ICT Use by Teachers... (Mafara & Adamu, 2023) Doi: [https://doi.org/ 10.5281/zenodo.8367630](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367630)

Respondents expressed disagreement or uncertainty regarding various aspects, such as the effectiveness of different teaching modes, perceptions of teachers and students, adaptation challenges, and government implementation challenges.

Respondents disagreed that their schools had constant internet connectivity, indicating potential issues with access to stable internet connections. Additionally, there was disagreement regarding the availability of resources for effectively implementing online teaching programs. These findings suggest that improvements in internet infrastructure and resource allocation are necessary to support successful online learning experiences. Respondents expressed disagreement regarding teachers' allocation of periods per week, their effectiveness in enlightening students about the importance of participation, and their attitudes towards students during online learning. These findings suggest a potential need for enhancing teacher-student interaction and engagement strategies in the online learning environment. Respondents generally agreed that the participation of every student is crucial for the success of effective online lessons/learning. This finding emphasizes the significance of fostering active engagement and involvement of students in online learning activities. While respondents disagreed about the impact of students' platform initiatives and the support provided by executive management for online teaching and learning, they were undecided about whether teachers performed necessary monitoring and data backups or if teachers and ICT staff regularly updated systems and security measures. These findings suggest a need for effective management practices, administrative support, and regular system maintenance to enhance the online teaching and learning experience. Respondents disagreed with the statement that ICT staff-regulated learning activities are more effective than teachers-regulated online learning during the Covid-19 pandemic. This finding suggests that there might be a perception among respondents that teachers play a more significant role in facilitating online learning compared to ICT staff.

The analysis highlights the need for addressing concerns related to the effectiveness of ICT staff, guidance and support for students, positive attitudes of teachers and ICT staff, executive management support, regular updates, and security measures. These areas can be further explored and targeted for improvement to enhance the overall online teaching and learning experience during school closures and the Covid-19 pandemic. Also, the analysis of the data indicates several areas of concern and opportunities for improvement in the context of home-based learning during the Covid-19 pandemic. The findings highlight the need for addressing challenges related to internet connectivity, resource availability, ICT training, teacher-student interaction, student participation, and effective management and support. By addressing these areas, educational institutions can enhance the quality and effectiveness of online teaching and learning experiences.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it can be concluded that the COVID-19 pandemic presented various challenges and uncertainties in the implementation of online teaching and learning. The perceptions and experiences of teachers, students, and ICT staff differed, indicating the need for further research and collaboration to improve online education practices.

Recommendations:

1. Enhance internet connectivity and access to technology resources to overcome the challenges of ICTs application during home-based online learning.
2. Foster collaboration between education stakeholders to develop strategies for effective online teaching and learning.
3. Continuously update and improve online teaching practices based on feedback and lessons learned during the pandemic.

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Colleges of Education Pre-service Mathematics Teachers' Attitude as Correlate of Self-efficacy in Learning mathematics in Northwest Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper examined pre-service mathematics teachers' attitude toward learning mathematics and their mathematics self-efficacy in learning mathematics among Nigerian colleges of education pre-service teachers. The study employed correlational design, questionnaires were distributed through personal visit to all the 366 final year pre-service mathematics teachers of COEs in the northwest, Nigeria who were selected as sample for this study from the population of 2761 colleges of education pre-service mathematics teachers using Cochran formula. The questionnaire used for this study was adapted from previously validated instruments after receiving written permission from the original authors of the used questionnaire. Cronbach alpha value of 0.86 was obtained as internal consistency of the instrument. The data collected was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics (correlation). The findings of this study revealed that pre-service teachers' attitude towards learning mathematics is high and there exist a significant relationship between pre-service teachers' attitude towards learning mathematics and their mathematics self-efficacy among other findings. The researcher's recommendations among others is government and all stakeholders in education need to support and retain these highly confident and well determined future qualified mathematics teachers in education sector as they will play a vital role in solving problem of poor achievement in mathematics and low desire to accept mathematics as a course of study at tertiary institutions by students, which previous studies attributed to negative attitude and low self-efficacy in learning mathematics.

Keyword: Pre-service teachers, Attitude, Mathematics self-efficacy, Colleges of Education Mathematics learning.

Introduction

Attitude is one of the significant factors that characterizes human distinctiveness. In every culture people like or dislike, love or hate, favour or oppose, agree, or disagree, encourage or discourage, claim or disclaim and so on. All these are judgmental reactions to an object. Thus, attitudes are summary appraisal of an object of thought. People's belief or perception they have about their capabilities to carry out or accomplished certain tasks successfully motivates them to do so.

Self-efficacy was defined by Gavora (2010) as one's conviction about their capabilities to accomplish certain tasks in an appropriate and effective manner. Han, et al (2015) defined self-efficacy as one's belief or perception about one's ability to perform at a certain level on a job. Therefore, self-efficacy is the individual's conviction or confidence that they can successfully accomplish given activity at designated level. Having high level of self-efficacy about one's ability is important as it motivates one to succeed in life. Researchers in field of education have been conducting studies on self-efficacy over the last four decades (Bandura, 1977). Educational research on self-efficacy stemmed from the theory of Bandura. According to Bandura (1997), self-efficacy beliefs affect one's ways of thinking and feelings, which may allow or stop actions. Meaning that if a person has high level of self-efficacy about his capabilities, it will motivate him to put more effort on the activity, while low level of self-efficacy will lead to idleness and non-performance. Bandura (1994) defined mathematics self-efficacy as one's beliefs or perceptions with respect to their abilities in mathematics. Mathematics self-efficacy is one's conviction or confidence in their abilities to solve problems in mathematics. Ferla, et al (2015) posited that mathematics self-efficacy indicates individual's self-perceived confidence to successfully accomplish a particular mathematics activity (Briley, 2012). In Nigerian context, studies related with mathematics self-efficacy (Adedeji, 2011; Ayotola & Adedeji, 2009).

Mathematics is made a compulsory subject from primary to senior secondary schools in Nigeria and a foundation for scientific and technological expansion (Azuka, 2000). To this end, well-trained mathematics teachers must be produced at Colleges of Education in Nigeria to teach the subject at the basic education level in Nigeria. In order to attain the mission of establishing the colleges of education (COEs) thus. The mission of colleges of education in Nigeria is to produce highly motivated and well-trained Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE) teachers' worthy of character and learning through effective teaching, research, and public service for the Basic Education level (NCCE, 2012; Isiyaku, et al (2015). In recent times, the

Colleges of Education Pre-service Mathematics... (Muhammad, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367817>
attitude, enrolment, and desire to accept mathematics as a course of study by students at tertiary institutions and COEs in particular in Nigeria has not been encouraging (Salman, et al 2011). In Nigeria, several studies revealed that students' attitude toward mathematics influenced the effort they put in understanding and practicing mathematical concepts and skills (Enu, et al 2015; Adedolun 2014), students' attitude toward learning mathematics is generally negative, this negative attitude contributed to their low desire to accept mathematics as a course of study at the tertiary institutions (Suleiman & Muhammad, 2016; Musa & Dauda, 2014). Based on this, many students have perceived mathematics as a very difficult school subject to study because of the negative impression they have had from their past generations who have had bad experience with unqualified mathematics teachers. That mathematics is the most difficult subject in school, it is not meant for everyone and not everybody passes it, based on these many students do not concentrate in learning the subject and spend little time practicing it (Dauda, et al 2016; Eraikhuaman & Omoregbe, 2017). More so, the study of Awofala (2016) revealed that university pre – service mathematics teachers' attitude toward learning mathematics were positive and high. Based on this the current study intends to examine the pre-service teachers' attitude as it correlates to self-efficacy in learning mathematics and to investigate whether there exists any relationship between pre-service teachers' attitude and self-efficacy among colleges of education pre-service mathematics teachers in Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to examine the relationship between Colleges of Education Pre-service Mathematics Teachers Attitudes and Self-efficacy in learning mathematics. Specifically, the study aimed to

1. Examine the attitude of colleges of education pre-service mathematics teachers toward learning mathematics.
2. Ascertain the confidence level of colleges of education pre-service mathematics teachers to the learning of mathematics.
3. Determine the extent do colleges of education pre-service mathematics teachers' attitude toward learning mathematics relates to their self-efficacy in learning mathematics.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised by the researchers to guide the current study.

1. What is the attitude of colleges of education pre-service mathematics teachers toward learning mathematics?
2. What is the confidence level of colleges of education pre-service mathematics teachers to the learning of mathematics?
3. To what extent do colleges of education pre-service mathematics teachers' attitude toward learning mathematics and mathematics self-efficacy are related?

Research Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis was formulated by the researchers in the conduct of this study

1. There is no significant relationship between colleges of education pre-service mathematics teachers' attitude towards learning mathematics and mathematics self-efficacy in learning mathematics.

Methodology

The current study employed correlational research design to investigate the extent of relationship between attitude toward learning mathematics and mathematics self-efficacy among colleges of education preservice mathematics teachers.in learning mathematics. 366 final year mathematics pre-service teachers' of 2018/2019 academic session from federal and states own colleges of education (12 COEs) in the northwest geo-political zone participated in the research. However, 339 valid questionnaires were used for this study. The selection of sample was done based on Cochran 1977 formular. Data was collected using a survey questionnaire from randomly selected pre-service mathematics teachers (mathematics students) that are willing to participate in the research. For the purpose of this study, the researcher used a questionnaire as an instrument for data collection tagged "Colleges of Education Mathematics Students' Attitude and Self-efficacy Questionnaire (COEMSAS), with a total of 16 item statements (Attitude toward learning Mathematics 7, Self-efficacy in learning Mathematics 9). The questionnaire was structured on 5-points Likert scale with Strongly Agreed which takes 5 points, Agreed 4, Somewhat Agreed 3, Dis Agreed 2 and Strongly Disagreed 1 point. The criterion mean value of acceptance is 3.0 any statement with a mean value less than 3.0 is indicating rejection (disagreement) by respondents. the questionnaire was adapted from previously validated instrument. Mathematics self-efficacy will assess colleges of education mathematics students' assessment of their capability to solve mathematics problems effectively, as well as the students' confidence in their skill to solve mathematics problems. Nine items were adapted from Vandecandelaere, et al (2012). Attitude toward learning mathematics aims at investigating the COEs' mathematics students' set of feelings (favourable or unfavorable feelings) and trends that influence their decision to learn mathematics. Seven items were adapted from Zsoldos-Marchis (2015).

Colleges of Education Pre-service Mathematics... (Muhammad, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367817>

A pilot test was conducted with 52 final year (NCE III) mathematics students selected from three colleges of education in the northwest, Nigeria. The reliability coefficient, Cronbach Alpha of each construct is greater than 0.80 using SPSS version 25 (Table 1). The internal consistency of the instrument is considered reliable; therefore, the questionnaire items are acceptable since all the values of the Cronbach Alpha of each construct is greater than 0.70 according to George & Mallery (2003).

Table 1. Construct Reliability

Construct	No. of Item	α -value for pilot study (n = 52)
Mathematics Self-efficacy	9	0.88
Attitude toward Mathematics	7	0.84

SPSS V25

Result

Research Question 1

What is the attitude of Colleges of Education pre-service mathematics teachers?

Table 2. Mean and Standard deviation of Attitude towards Mathematics

Items	Mean	Std. Dev
I like mathematics	4.32	0.72
Mathematics will be useful to me in the future.	4.42	0.79
*Mathematics is one of the most boring subjects in school.	4.36	0.76
If I practice more, I would be better in mathematics	4.40	0.79
*When I study mathematics courses, I feel more uncomfortable than when I study other courses.	4.34	0.73
I feel happy when solving mathematics problems.	4.33	0.81
*No matter what I do, I always get low grade in mathematics courses.	4.39	0.76
Overall Mean and Std. Dev.	4.37	0.77

*Represent negative statement

In answering this research question, pre-service mathematics teachers' responses on attitude toward learning mathematics scale were analyzed using descriptive statistics where mean and standard deviation of each statement under the attitude construct of the respondents were calculated. The result of the analysis is presented in table 2. From table it is clear that the mean response on each item is greater than 4.0 and the overall mean of the attitude toward learning mathematics is 4.37 (see table 2) indicating high level of acceptance by the respondents. Hence, this result indicated that pre -service mathematics teachers at Colleges of Education in Nigeria have high and positive attitude toward learning mathematics. Please note that all items with stars (*) are negative statement but re-coded before the analysis.

Research Question 2

What is the confidence level of Colleges of Education pre-service mathematics teachers?

Table 3. Mean and Standard deviation of Mathematics Self-efficacy

Items	Mean	Std. Dev.
I am very good at mathematics	4.28	0.73
I usually do well in mathematics.	4.30	0.76
I am sure of my ability to study mathematics.	4.31	0.69
I am confident in my ability to study mathematics in any university.	4.31	0.68
I learn mathematics quickly.	4.32	0.67
*Mathematics is more difficult for me compared to my classmate.	4.32	0.81
I have necessary skills to continue my education in mathematics.	4.24	0.82
*I am always afraid when ever remember that I am going to become mathematics teacher.	4.31	0.79
I would like a course that involved mathematics.	4.39	0.77
Overall Mean and Std. Dev.	4.31	0.75

*Represent negative statement

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To answer research question two in this study data obtained through the questionnaire under the construct of mathematics self-efficacy were analyzed using descriptive statistics where mean and standard deviation of each item of mathematics self-efficacy is obtained and used in determining the level of mathematics self-efficacy of pre-service mathematics teachers of Colleges of Education. The analysis was showed in Table 3. Form the table it is clear that all item under the mathematics self-efficacy construct has the mean response of greater than 4.0. This revealed that huge majority of respondents have showed high level of confidence in their learning of mathematics. More so, the overall mean of this scale (mathematics self-efficacy) is 4.31 which indicated that in general pre-service mathematics teachers of Colleges of Education (colleges of education) have high level of confidence in the learning of mathematics. Please note that all items with stars (*) are negative statement but re-coded before the analysis.

Research Question 3

To what extent do Colleges of Education pre-service mathematics teachers' attitude toward learning mathematics and mathematics self-efficacy are related?

In answering this research question, Pearson product moment correlation coefficient was calculated, and the result of the analysis is showed in the Table 4. As indicated in the table 4 it reveals a positive relationship between attitude toward learning mathematics and mathematics self-efficacy of the pre-service mathematics teachers at Colleges of Education. To further confirm whether the relationship observed between attitude toward learning mathematics and mathematics self-efficacy significant or not? The null hypothesis formulated was tested at 0.05 confidence level.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between Colleges of Education pre-service mathematics teachers' attitude towards learning mathematics and mathematics self-efficacy in learning mathematics.

Table 4. Correlation between independent and dependent variable

Constructs	Attitude toward learning mathematics	Mathematics self-efficacy
Attitude toward learning mathematics	1	.350** P <.001
Mathematics self-efficacy	.350** P <.001	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

On the correlation coefficient between attitude toward learning mathematics and mathematics self-efficacy Table 4 reveals that there was a positive correlation between mathematics self-efficacy with attitude toward learning mathematics ($r = .350$; $p < .001$). From the result of this analysis, it clearly showed that the positive relationship between attitude and mathematics self-efficacy is significant.

Discussion of Findings

The result of this study indicated that colleges of education preservice mathematics teachers' attitude toward learning mathematics is positive. This finding is in line with the previous literature (Awofala & Ojaleye, 2018; Eraikhuaman & Omoregbe, 2017; Awofala, 2016; Zsoldos-Marchis, 2015; Adelodun, 2014; Briley, 2012; Marchis'(2011). The study of Awolala (2016) that was conducted on university pre-service mathematics teachers with the aim of investigating their attitude towards learning mathematics and his findings revealed that the attitude of university pre-service mathematics teachers towards mathematics was positive and high. Therefore, the findings of this study indicated that colleges of education pre-service mathematics teachers' attitudes are also positive and high like that of their counterpart in the universities. Although some literature reported that the poor achievement of Nigerian students in mathematics was because of their negative attitude toward learning mathematics (Enu, Agyman, & Nkum, 2015; Musa & Dauda, 2014). However, with the research findings of Awofala (2016) and the result of this current study that was all conducted on pre-service mathematics teachers (future trained mathematics teachers) the future of Nigeria students and Nigerian education sector in general will be bright, because this future qualified mathematics teachers' attitude is positive and high, then they will have the zeal of putting their best in training their students to their understanding without getting angry.

Further more, another finding in this study is the result of pre-service mathematics teachers level of confidence in learning mathematics. Where the findings revealed that colleges of education pre-service mathematics teachers have high level

Colleges of Education Pre-service Mathematics... (Muhammad, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367817> of confidence in learning mathematics. This finding is also in agreement with the findings of Zuya, Kwalat and Attah (2016) where in their study they investigated the mathematics self-efficacy of university pre-service mathematics teachers and their results among others revealed that university pre-service mathematics teachers have above average confidence level in learning mathematics. Other literature which the current study is in agreement with their findings are Ayotola and Adedeji (2009), Adedeji (2011). From the findings of this study it is clear that colleges of education pre-service mathematics teachers have high confidence level in learning mathematics like their colleagues in the universities that was reported to have above average confidence level in learning mathematics by Zuya et al. (2016). The implication of this finding to the Nigerian government is that if this well trained qualified mathematics teachers with high mathematics self-efficacy and positive attitude toward learning mathematics will be employed to teach mathematics with good condition of service the poor performance and low achievement of students in mathematics will be come history in Nigeria.

In addition, another very significant finding of the research is that the positive relationship that was found between colleges of education pre-service mathematics teachers' attitude towards learning mathematics and their mathematics self-efficacy. Meaning that the positive feelings about learning mathematics the pre-service mathematics teachers have correlated positively with the conviction and confidence they have in their capability to do or accomplish any mathematics task successfully. The finding is in harmony with the findings of Han, Liou-Mark, Yu and Zeng (2015). The result of the overall mean of the construct of attitude towards learning mathematics is higher than that of mathematics self-efficacy construct, even though all the two constructs revealed high level of acceptance. However, the need to do more in instilling confidence of learning mathematics on the pre-service mathematics teachers of colleges of education.

Conclusion

The present study was conducted with the main aim of examining the pre-service teachers' attitude toward learning mathematics and their mathematics self-efficacy. Its findings had shown that the preservice mathematics teachers' attitudes toward mathematics were at high level even at the subscale levels of attitudes toward mathematics. More so, pre-service mathematics teachers' self-efficacy in mathematics were also at the high level of acceptance, as all the scales under the mathematics self-efficacy have indicated high level of acceptance by the respondents. Despite the low performance of the students in mathematics according to previous literature However, colleges of education preservice mathematics teachers that participated in this study had confidence toward teaching/learning mathematics, and their attitude was positive and high.

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Comparison of Implementation of School Feeding Programmes in Public Primary Schools in Ondo and Osun States, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study compared if difference exists in the implementation of school feeding programmes between Ondo and Osun States, Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive research design. The population of the study consisted primary school teachers, head teachers, Local, Government Education Offices and parents. The samples of the study were made up of one hundred primary school teachers, two head teachers, two Local Government Education Offices and two parents. Data were analyzed using independent t-test statistical method. The findings showed that the school feeding programme is better implemented in Osun State than Ondo State. Also, there was no significant difference in the implementation in the two states. The study concluded that a myriad of challenges is confronting the programme and recommended that more funds should be provide, corrupt vendors be disengaged and proper monitoring should be put in place.

Keywords: Implementation, School Feeding, Challenges, Programme, Funds

Introduction

Nigerian is a developing country with poverty-stricken population who cannot afford three square meals, let alone financing education of their children (Ogunwole, 2016). The poor economic status of parents made it impossible for them to provide reading materials for their wards (Adepoju, 2018) and this is the reason for introducing free and compulsory primary education in Nigeria, National Policy on Education (NPE, 2014). Right from inception of Primary Education in Nigeria, proprietors and providers have been making frantic efforts to make it affordable to the entire citizenry because it is the foundation level upon which other levels are built. Igboanusi and Peter (2016), stated that if the foundation at the primary school is not well laid, pupils might not get it right in future. This accounts for the reason why governments, at all levels, leave no stone unturned and put incentives on ground to encourage pupils and parents so that the syndrome of out of school children will be reduced to its barest minimum. To achieve this, Lawani (2011), stressed that Primary Education was made free to beneficiaries when it was introduced by the missionaries. In the 19th century, the missionaries gave free books, slates and clothes (Adepoju & Olugboji 2020). Similarly, Ogbodo (1995), alluded that government dedicated 95% of allocation to education to Primary Education in 1955 when Universal Primary Education was introduced.

Reducing the number of out of school children, increasing enrolment and stabilising school children in the school environment have always been the cardinal factors for introducing motivational programmes to pupils and parents in public primary schools. The latest of these is the introduction of School Feeding Programme by the Federal Government in line with the provision of the National Policy on Education (NPE, 2014). According to the (NPE, 2014), School Feeding Programme is to ensure healthy development, retention and absorption of children in schools. Similarly in Kenya, school feeding programme is an economic bail out for indigent families to enrol their children in primary schools (Karaba, et al., 2019).

School Feeding Programme is a social package designed to provide food for hungry school children in order to safeguard their physical and mental well-being (Tijjani, et al., 2017). This study sees it as a planned policy that provides pupils with free meals provided daily by governments, communities or philanthropic organisations in schools. School feeding started as a philanthropic donour intervention in Europe in the 1700's, by 1900 Netherlands was the first nation to legislate it, it was officially introduced in the United Kingdom and the United States of America in 1930 and officially launched in Nigeria in September, 2005 under the supervision of the Federal Ministry of Education to alleviate hunger, increase enrolments in schools and boost students' performance (Adekunle & Christianah, 2016; Salifu, et al., 2018). The reason behind this programme was

Comparison of Implementation of School ... (Adepoju & Omotoyinbo) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367851>

to reduce hunger and malnutrition among school children because according to Kiilu and Mugambi (2019), about eight hundred and forty two million (8,420,000) million people in the world have difficulties in getting food to eat; children are no exceptions in this regard. Corroborating this, Tijjani, et al., (2017) say sixty (60) million children go to school without food and a reasonable number of Nigerian children suffer from malnutrition because they lack important food nutrients such as vitamin A and iron. Similarly, Santrock (2014), remarks that malnutrition is inimical to all round development of children. The hazards inherent in malnutrition propelled governments and organisations to put in place School Feeding Programmes and the likes in different countries.

Poverty is a major cause of lateness to school (Adegunju, et al, 2019). To curtail this and other educational maladjustments, the study of Adekunle & Christianah (2016), reveals that School Feeding Programme, an initiative of MDG, was introduced to reduce hunger and malnutrition among school children. According to the scholars, meals given in schools, provide nutrients, boost punctuality and mental ability, reduces cost of funding by parents, and motivate parents to send their children to schools thereby increasing enrolment in schools as witnessed in Brazil, Philippine, Cambodia and Mali. Similarly, Kiilu & Mugambi, (2019) argue that school meals increase enrolment, attendance, academic performance and reduce rate of drop out. School feeding is divided into two, namely, in-school feeding and take home. The in-school food is served hot/warm while the take home is cooked at home as found out by these scholars. Home Grown School Feeding Programme provides employments for local farmers and food vendors employed to cook under the supervision of government officials (Adekunle & Christianah, 2016). Yardsticks for effective School Feeding Programme include policy formulation, proper implementation, funding and competent personnel (Kiilu & Mugambi, 2019).

Nutritional programmes are put in place by government to improve food security, prevention of malnutrition and reduction of poverty among children (Ogunwole, 2016). If nourishment is to be ensured, the quality and the quantity of food served should be good and adequate. Poor nutrition in children leads to health challenges such as Marasmus and Kwashiorkor which result in loss of body weight and swollen abdomen/feet respectively and that is why a body called Women, Infants and Children (WIN) programme in United States of America provides funds for the supply of nutritious meals to children from low-income homes (Santrock, 2014).

Food is any liquid or solid substance eaten by man for essential nourishment, reproduction, building/repair of worn-out body cells, respiration, supply of energy and body growth (Soyinbo, et al., 1997; Ogunwole, 2016). Foods are grouped according to their sources, that is, vegetarian and non-vegetarian (Sasikala & Chanchalor, 2016), according to the nutrients they supply and according to the functions they perform in the body system (Ukeagbu, et al., 2014 and Micheal, 2018). These classifications are hereby presented in this study in these tabular forms:

Table 1: Classifications According to Sources

S/N	Classes	Sources
A	Vegetarian	Vegetables, fruits, roots, tubers
B	Non-vegetarian	Eggs, meat, fish,

Table 2: Classifications According to Nutrients

S/N	Classes	Sources
A	Vitamins	Vegetables, eggs, milk etc
B	Mineral salts	Vegetables, fruits
C	Carbohydrate	Yam, bread, rice etc
D	Fats	Butter, palm oil, groundnut etc
E	Proteins	Egg, fish, meat
F	Water	Beverages, mineral water, beer

Table 3: Classifications According to Functions

S/N	Classes	Functions
A	Carbohydrate and fats	Energy giver/suppliers
B	Proteins	Body builders
C	Vitamins, mineral salts and water	Protections, mobility
D	Roughages	Regulation, prevention

The functions of these classes of food are interwoven in the sense that some body building foods such as eggs and milk are also rich in vitamins and mineral salts (Ukeagbu et al, 2014). Food should not only be taken, balanced diet should also

Comparison of Implementation of School ... (Adepoju & Omotoyinbo) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367851>

be ensured in the meals eaten to avoid malnutrition in children. Oladele (1999), defines balanced diet as meal that contains the right proportion of nutrients for effective maintenance of the body. It is against this background that Sasikala & Chanchalor (2016), comment that poor nutrition makes the body system vulnerable to diseases.

Like other educational programmes, school feeding is bedevilled with a myriad of problems, such as lack of correlation between its funding and its manifestation and corruption (Salifu, et al., 2018). Similarly, in Kenya, the study of Kiilu & Mugambi (2019), reveal that in the community where the study was carried out, the community shoulders the responsibility of school feeding programme which implies that government does not show much commitment to the programme. Also, in Kenya, school feeding programme suffers financial crises (Karaba, et al, 2019).

Studies before this left a gap that this study sought to fill. The study of Sasikala & Chanchalor (2016), examined the nutritional status of school boys and girls in a school in India. The study conducted by Adekunle & Christianah (2016) and Tijjani, et al (2017), looked at the effects of School Feeding Programmes on enrolment, retention and academic performance in Osun State and Maiduguri, Nigeria and the work of Kiilu & Mugambi (2019) considered the level of implementation and the programme sponsors in an area in Kenya. This study sought to compare the implementation of School Feeding Programmes in Ondo and Osun States, Nigeria with a view to determining the similarities and differences.

The study relied on behaviourism as its theoretical base because the theory has a direct correlation with this study. Behaviourism focuses on observable behaviours that are responses to stimuli in the learning environment (Bakare, 2015). Experiments by behaviourists yielded two types of conditionings, namely, classical and operant conditionings. Classical conditioning, propounded and ventilated by Ivan Pavlov, is Stimulus-Response theory that theorises that learners naturally response to stimulus when provided through his experiment that which showed that dogs salivate when they see food (unconditioned stimulus) when they hear sound of a bell (conditioned stimulus) (Tella, et al., 1990). Operant conditioning, propounded by B.F Skinner and ventilated by Edward Thorndike, hypothesises that when a response to a stimulus is rewarded, that behaviour will be repeated (Adedayo & Dunapo, 2016). Expatriating further on this, Cruikshank, Jenkins, & Metcalf (2009), comment that operant conditioning is learning by reinforcement when an action is rewarded, it will be rewarded but when not rewarded, there is the likelihood of it not being repeated. Food served (stimulus) motivates pupils to come to school regularly and punctually (response) since their coming is rewarded.

School feeding programme was introduced to cater for the nutritional needs of pupils and discourage out of school child syndrome. This makes the Federal Government to budget for it annually and implement it through various state governments. At inception, one meal was given to each child daily, which served as mid-day meal, that is, brunch that attracted and retained pupils in schools. Unfortunately, in one of the studies conducted by the researcher, it was observed that in some primary schools meals were not being served, in some it is epileptic and in some primary schools only certain grades are being fed. To add insult to the injury, the quality and quantity of food served is worrisome. Government only awards the contracts to contactors who are not forth coming and execute shady jobs. Head teachers are not even in control of the caterers assigned to their schools. It was as a result of this that this study set out to examine the implementation of the school feeding programme in Ondo and Osun States of Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The purpose of the study was to compare the implementation of school feeding programmes in primary schools in Ondo and Osun States. In doing this the following were the objectives of the study.

1. To assess the extent of implementation of school feeding programme in Ondo and Osun States
2. To assess the quality of food served to primary school pupils in Ondo and Osun States; and
3. To determine the effects of school feeding programme in Ondo and Osun States.

Research Questions

To get this done, the study raised the following research questions in line with the objectives to guide the study.

1. What is the extent of implementation of school feeding programme in Ondo and Osun States?
2. What is the quality of food served to primary school pupils?
3. To what extent does school feeding programme impact on primary school pupils in Ondo and Osun States?

Hypothesis

One research hypothesis was also formulated for this study as thus:

There is no significant difference between implementation of school feeding programmes in Ondo and Osun States.

Methodology

The study used mixed method approach because numerical and non-numerical data were needed for the study and for data method triangulation to achieve accuracy in the study. The design was a descriptive survey of two selected local government areas in Ondo and Osun States of Nigeria. The population of the study were primary school teachers, head teachers, local government education officials and parents. To obtain quantitative data one hundred primary school teachers were randomly selected while two head teachers, two Local Government Education Authority Officials and two literate parents were purposively selected to obtain qualitative data from the states making one hundred and six samples. Two research instruments were designed for this study, namely, a fifteen item structured 4 point likert scale questionnaire was used to obtain responses from teachers and a five item semi-structured questions completed by head teachers, Local Government Education Authority Officials and the literate parents. The time of the study fell within the COVID 19 pandemic which restricted the movement of people and this necessitated the researcher to mail the research instruments to academic colleagues, herein in this study referred to as research assistants, whose places of abode were in the areas chosen for the study. The research assistants personally administered the instruments on the one hundred and six samples, collated the data and mailed them to the researcher.

The validity of structured questionnaire was ensured by giving the draft to research experts who made necessary corrections and adjustments to determine face validity, content validity and construct validity while the semi-structured questions were made error free through thorough proof reading. Linkert ranking scale and T-test were used for quantitative data analysis while thematic analysis was used for qualitative data. To establish credibility of study, data triangulation, anonymity and confirmability were employed. Thus Participant A, Participant, Participant C Participant D, Participant E and Participant F were used to label the participants

Results

Research Question 1

What is the extent of implementation of school feeding programme in Ondo and Osun States?

Table 4: Implementation of School Feeding Programme in Ondo State

S/N	Item:	Very often	Often	Rare	Very rare	X	SD
1	School meals are provided everyday.	5	10	24	11	2.18	5.358
2	Enough foods are given to pupils.	4	5	13	28	1.7	4.725
3	Government monitors school feeding programmes.	6	17	18	9	2.4	5.388
4	Government finances school feeding programme.	19	20	7	4	3.02	7.85
5	All school benefit from school feeding programme.	3	13	7	27	1.84	4.900
Total		37	65	69	79	2.23	5.430

Table 4 shows that the calculated mean (X) of 2.23 is less than the cut off mean (X) of 2.50. This implies that school feeding programme is not well implemented in Ondo State. For this table, the standard deviation is 5.430

Table 5: Implementation School Feeding Programme in Osun State

S/N	Item:	Very often	Often	Rare	Very rare	X	SD
1	School meals are provided everyday.	32	18	0	0	3.64	9.39
2	Enough foods are given to pupils.	34	14	2	0	3.64	9.55
3	Government monitors school feeding programmes.	38	12	0	0	3.76	10.64

Comparison of Implementation of School ... (Adepoju & Omotoyinbo) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367851>

4	Government finances school feeding programme.	46	4	0	0	3.92	12.44
5	All school benefit from school feeding programme.	20	20	4	6	3.08	6.47
Total						3.61	48.49

On Table 5, the calculated mean (\bar{X}) of 3.61 is greater than the cut off mean (\bar{X}) of 2.50. This implies that School Feeding Programme is well implemented in Osun State. On this table, the standard deviation is 48.49

Research Question 2

What is the quality of food served to primary school pupils?

Table 6: Quality and Quantity of food provided in Ondo State

S/N	Item:	Very often	Often	Rare	Very rare	X
1	Foods served include eggs, milk and meat	2	18	13	17	2.36
2	Provision of food such as yam, bread and rice	4	8	24	14	2.04
3	Provision of food such as butter, palm oil and vegetable oil	13	2	9	26	2.04
4	Inclusion of vegetables and fruits.	1	6	23	20	1.76
5	Water and juice are served	1	1	8	40	1.26
Total		21	35	77	117	1.84

As shown on Table 6, the calculated mean (\bar{X}) of 1.84 is less than the cut off mean (\bar{X}) of 2.50. The implication is that food served in Ondo State in the School Feeding Programme is poor in terms of quality and quantity.

Table 7: Quality and Quantity of food provided in Osun State

S/N	Item:	Very often	Often	Rare	Very rare	X
1	Foods served include eggs, milk and meat	40	10	0	0	3.8
2	Provision of food such as yam, bread and rice	35	10	5	0	3.5
3	Provision of food such as butter, palm oil and vegetable oil	32	8	10	0	3.44
4	Inclusion of vegetables and fruits.	40	10	0	0	3.8
5	Water and juice are served	42	8	0	0	3.84
Total						3.68

Table 7 shows that the calculated mean (\bar{X}) of 3.68 is greater than the cut off mean (\bar{X}) of 2.50. This implies that food provided in School Feeding Programme in Osun State is good in terms of quality and quantity.

Research Question 3

To what extent does school feeding programme impact on primary school pupils in Ondo and Osun States?

Table 8: Impacts of School Feeding Programme in Ondo State

S/N	Item:	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Disagree Strongly	X
1	School meals encourage parents to send their children to school.	19	19	12	0	3.38
2	Pupils stay in schools because of the meals served.	19	20	10	1	3.14

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3	School meals enhance academic performance.	10	30	10	0	3.0
4	School meals make pupils to be punctual in schools	21	19	7	3	3.1
5	School meals reduce malnutrition among pupils.	12	31	4	3	3.04
Total		81	119	43	7	3.92

The calculated mean (X) of 3.92 on Table 8 is greater than the cut off mean (X) of 2.50. This implies that the respondents agreed that School Feeding Programme in Ondo State is beneficial to the pupils.

Table 9: Benefits of School Feeding Programme in Osun State

S/N	Item:	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Disagree Strongly	X
1	School meals encourage parents to send their children to school.	40	10	0	0	3.8
2	Pupils stay in schools because of the meals served.	38	6	6	0	3.64
3	School meals enhance academic performance.	28	22	0	0	3.76
4	School meals make pupils to be punctual in schools	44	6	0	0	3.88
5	School meals reduce malnutrition among pupils.	42	4	4	0	3.76
Total		192	48	10	0	3.77

Table 9 shows that the calculated mean (X) of 3.77 is greater than the cut off mean (X) of 2.50. Therefore, the respondents agreed that pupils benefit immensely from school feeding programme in Osun State.

Hypothesis (Ho)

There is no significant difference between implementation of school feeding programmes in Ondo and Osun States.

Table 10: t-test analysis of the implementation of school feeding programmes in Ondo and Osun States

States	N	X	SD	Df	t-cal.	t-critical	Decision
Ondo	50	2.23	5.43	98	0.85	1.96	Not significant
Osun		3.61	9.70				

Table 10 shows that t-calculated of 0.85 is less than t-critical of 1.96, hence, the hypothesis is retained. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the implementation of School Feeding Programmes in Ondo and Osun states.

Discussion of Findings

Though the respondents agreed that school feeding is helpful to pupils in Ondo State, according to Table E, which shows that the calculated mean (X) of 3.92 is greater than the cut-off mean (X) of 2.50. This is in line with Kiilu and Mugambi (2019) who opined that school feeding increases enrolment, attendance and boost performance. Table A above shows that school feeding programme is not well implemented in Ondo state since the calculated mean (X) 2.23 is less than the cut-off mean (X) of 2.50 which corroborates the situation in Kenya where the programme suffers neglect (Karaba, et al., 2019) and the quality of food served is very poor because the food lacked basic nutrients which make pupils vulnerable to diseases (Sasikala & Chanchalor, 2016) and also confirms the views of Tijjani, et al., (2017) and Santrock (2014) who remarked that Nigerian children are undernourished because they lack food nutrients which is dangerous to their well-being.

Table 5 shows that school feeding is well implemented in Osun State as indicated by the calculated mean (X) of 3.61 which is greater than the cut-off mean (X) of 2.50. This enhances enrolment, attendance and performance in schools (Adekunle and

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Christianah, 2016). The respondents also agreed that school feeding is beneficial to pupils as indicated by the calculated mean (X) of 3.77 which is greater than the cut-off mean of 2.50. Food served in the State are of good quality because as they contain vital nutrients for proper maintenance of the body (Oladele, 1999). This is indicated by the calculated mean (X) of 3.37 which is greater than the cut-off mean (X) of 2.50. In a nutshell, Table G shows that t-calculated of 0.85 is less than t-critical of 1.96, hence, the research hypothesis, 'There is no significant difference between implementation of school feeding programmes in Ondo and Osun States' is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the implementation of school feeding programmes in Ondo and Osun states.

From the qualitative data collected in this study, the following themes were derived and discussed: Findings show that the Federal Government of Nigeria, the state governments and the United Nations are the major sponsors of the programme in both states. All the participants attested to this claim in their responses. For examples, Participant B said, 'Federal Government in conjunction with state counterpart fund.' while Participant E said, 'United Nations is responsible jointly funding by the Federal Government of Nigeria. This finding aligns with the views of Adekunle and Christianah, (2016) and Salifu, et al, (2018) who remarked that government in different countries provide meals for school children.

School Feeding Programme is of immense benefits to school children in the two states under this study. These benefits include but not limited punctuality and regularity in school, enhanced academic performance, increase in enrolment and nourishment of the school children. The responses of the participants to question 3 above are indicators of this. Though Participant C said, 'It has no effects because the food is too small.' other participants remarked that the programme nourishes the pupils, boosts enrolment, prevents ailments/diseases and increase their academic performance. This finding confirms the studies of Adekunle and Christianah (2016) and Kiilu and Mugambi (2019), who revealed that school feeding programme, among others, encourages enrolment, attendance, punctuality, academic performance and spared the parents the burden of feeding their wards.

The participants confirmed the view of (Salifu, et al., 2018) who lamented shambolic implementation of school feeding programme. The comment of these two participants to question four (4): What are the constraints against school feeding programme in your area?, revealed this pathetic situation. Participant E: Very numerous: Irregularity in the funding, Lack of experienced stewards, distances from home, high prices of food stuffs. Participant A: Bad roads. Delay in finance. Unfaithfulness. There was a vendor who packed remnant from a party and took it to a school to feed the pupils. There were many cases in which the vendors would collect money and not supply the pupils with food meant for them. These responses expose the corrupt practices associated with the programme and the health implication on school children who are served left over food by unscrupulous vendors.

Conclusion

The study shows that school feeding programme is bedevilled with some challenges, most especially in Ondo State where the quality, spread and finance are poor. Lack of monitoring also affects the programme. This noble project should not be handled with levity so that its aims and objectives will not be defeated.

Recommendations

Based on the above awful findings, the study hereby makes the following recommendations so that this befitting educational programme will not be a white elephant's project:

1. More funds should be allocated to cushion the effect of shortage of funds;
2. Corrupt vendors should be relieved of their positions to guide against poor quality and quantity of food served to pupils;
3. The programme should be well monitored to see that its implementation is well spread most especially in Ondo State;
4. The quality and quantity of food prepared should be screened by nutritionists, most especially in Ondo State to prevent health hazards.

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Demographic Differentials in the Use of Information and Communication Technologies among Lecturers in Colleges of Education in Ondo State

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Abstract

This study investigated into demographic differentials in the use of information and communication technologies (ICTs) among lecturers in colleges of education in Ondo state. The study investigated the differences that exist between the gender, lecturer's qualification(s) and age of lecturers and the use of ICTs. The objectives of the study were to: (i) to determine the difference in ICTs usage between male and female Colleges of Education (COE) lecturers. (ii) to investigate the difference in ICTs usage among COE lecturers with varied academic qualification(s) (iii) Find out the difference in ICTs usage among COE lecturers with varied age. The study was conducted using a descriptive method. The title of the questionnaire used to collect data is "Demographic Differentials of ICTs usage among COE Lecturers" (DDIACL). Three (3) research hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. Two hundred (200) respondents were sampled using simple random technique. The instrument for data collection was researcher's designed questionnaire based on a 5-point Likert scale items. Five (5) experts in the field of Educational Technology validated the instrument to ensure content and face validity of the instrument. The reliability of the constructs was examined using the Cronbach's Alpha and it yielded 0.78 value. Data collected were analyzed using mean, standard deviation, t-test and ANOVA from the results analyzed. It was revealed from the study that COE lecturers' gender, academic qualification(s) and age has no significance difference in the use of ICTs. The study concluded that lecturers in COE have been using ICTs for teaching, research and management regardless of their gender, academic qualification(s) and age. It was therefore recommended that lecturers in COE should actively participates in ICTs training and by putting favourable attitudes towards technology.

Keywords: Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs), College of Education, Lecturers' Demography

Introduction

Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) are defined as all devices, tools, contents, resources, forums, and services, digital and those that can be converted into or delivered through digital forms, which can be deployed for realizing the goals of teaching and learning, enhancing access to and reach of resources, building of capacities, as well as management of the educational system. (Abba & Adamu, 2019). These will not only include hardware devices connected to computers and software applications but also interactive digital content, internet and other satellite communication devices, radio and television services, web-based content repositories, interactive forums, learning management systems, and management informant in systems. These will also include processes for digitization, deployment and management of platforms and processes for capacity development and creation of forums for interaction and exchange. (Abba & Adam, 2019).

The College of Education is a unit of tertiary education in Nigeria saddled with the responsibility of training teachers to obtain qualitative professional certification in education. The philosophy underpinning teacher education at the College of Education as opined by Isiyaku (2007), included the desire of the Nigerian Government to ensure uniformity of the content and educational standard. It also aimed at producing teachers with highly personal and professional discipline and integrity, teachers who are dedicated and with appropriate skills and intellectual depth that would facilitate easy achievement of the national goal. This is more critical when we note government's decision that the NCE shall ultimately be the minimum entry qualification into the teaching profession in Nigeria. Lecturers in the colleges of education are required to integrate Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) into their classroom activities. ICTs proficiency is the ability of lecturer to use ICTs

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appropriately to access, manage, integrate, and evaluate information, develop new understanding, and communicates with others in order to participate effectively in the society (Ministerial Council on Education, Development, and Youth Affairs, (MCEECD)2008).

It was opined by Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development OECD (2014) that majority of teachers choose to develop their ICTs related skills during their own spare time which may include various means of professional development such as training provided by school staff and participation in online communities. Teachers' age, gender and qualification(s) are factors associated with ICTs use. ICTs skills, age, gender and qualification(s) in combination, are accepted precursors for effective use of ICTs (Migliorino & Maiden, 2004) Therefore, there is need to determine the ICTs usage amongst lecturers in Colleges of Education, (COE) in Ondo State, Nigeria.

Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) are now used in various educational aspects for enriching the quality of teaching and learning. The availability of ICTs tools in higher institutions has proven to enhance teaching and learning; enabled self-paced learning; removed the time and space barriers for learning. (Oyovwe-Tinuoye & Adogbeji, 2013). Also, studies have shown that students' learning and teachers' teaching are enhanced when ICTs are used efficiently and effectively (Apagu & Wakili, 2015). Gender comparisons are needed to give a better understanding of lecturers' use of ICTs. Recently ICTs is gradually replacing the traditional teacher-centered teaching and learning environment in education and emphasis has shifted from the teacher to the learner, this becomes pertinent that both male and female teachers adopt the use of ICTs in facilitating learning (Fomsi & Orduah, 2017).

A study carried out by Hallberg et.al., (2011) found out that male lecturers used ICT facilities mostly as compared to the female counterpart. Similarly, Tezci (2009) found significant influence of gender on the level of utilization of ICT facilities by teachers. Also, Agbatogun (2013) did not find any significant influence of gender on lecturers' use of ICT facilities. Not only that Sherman (2013) mentioned that although the majority of internet users was narrowing down. Heimrath and Goulding (2001) found that female students felt that the internet was too big and unstructured thus, searching the internet difficult not enjoyable and would use it only they have to whereas male students were happy to search the internet for relevant information.

In a study by Usun (2003) on the use of ICTs by male and female students. It was found that there is no gender difference in access to the internet. It was found that male spend more time on computers and surfing the internet than female counterparts and it was reported that male students spent on average 5 to 10 hours per week, while female students reported that they spent less than 5 hours average per week (Mahmood & Bokhari, 2012). Sandra and Kurfi (2013) also reiterated that despite the much emphasis placed on the use of ICTs in Nigeria, women are usually underrepresented in terms of access and use of ICTs. They also observed that though women play a pivotal role in the development of their societies, yet their impact has been silenced in this new technology due to lack of access and the necessary skills for the operation. Mahmood and Bokhari (2012) opined that gender equity persists both in access to and experience of learning opportunities with ICT. Shashaani and Khalili (2001) in their study revealed that there is pervasive difference between the ways females and males use technology to socialize. The survey demonstrated that there is a strong gender gap in the way respondents make friend online. Girls are more likely to participate in social networks, create blogs, use instant messaging, use e-mail, and post pictures, keep tabs on family and communicate with one another, and share and research on how to obtain information. In contrast boys are more likely than girls to post online video content. Sherman (2013) opined that girls often place more calls, text more, and generally use social/communicative apps and sites more than boys which reflect broader gender differences in communication beyond just that occur in a technology.

Another factor that was found to play a vital role in the use of information and communication technologies (ICTs) in teaching by lecturers in Colleges of Nigeria is the lecturers' academic qualifications. It was found out by Odigwe and Owau (2020) that there is a significant influence of staff educational qualification on the utilization of ICTs resources for teaching, research and records management in higher educational and qualifications are not good users of ICTs facilities, reason for this to the researchers is that to attain a higher educational qualification, age has a critical role to play. In their research age and rank may have been the reason responsible for this finding. On the contrary, Gombe et.al (2016) found no significant difference in the utilization of ICT based on lecturers' qualification. Onasanya et al., (2010) in their research on higher institutions lecturers' attitude towards integration of ICT into teaching and research in Nigeria was found that the less experience lecturers are more than their senior colleagues.

Also, in a research study carried out by Lubis et.al., (2017), it was found out that years of teaching experiences and educational level of academic staff have no significant influence on the utilization of the technology. However, Herath and Hewagama (2015) stated that teaching experiences is not significantly affecting the ICT usage. The result pointed out that the different teaching experience is not in line with the utilization of ICT. In Nigerian Colleges of Education, lecturers are

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divided into four (4) levels, which are Higher National Diploma (HND) First degree level, master's level and doctoral level (PHD). Morley (2010) confirmed there is a significant different between educational level and teachers using ICT. The higher educational level of lecturers is more frequently to utilize ICT.

Many scholars have been drawn to examine the influence of age on the usage of ICTs in higher education. (Lubis et al., 2017). Albion, et al. (2011) held that age is significant predictor of lecturers' usage of ICTs in higher institutions of learning. Etim (2019) & Alba & Trani, 2018; Amua-sekyi & Asare, 2016) held to the contrary that age does not significantly predict ICTs usage. Odigwe et al., (2020) found out in their research study that younger lecturers demonstrated higher utility of ICT resources in higher education than older lecturers. This finding is unsurprising since younger lecturers are less busy with administrative responsibilities and may have little or no family responsibility to meet compared with older lecturers. Dei (2018) opinion that ICTs purely obeys the law of diminishing returns and posited that the usage of ICTs depreciates as an individual grow older. Manyilizu and Gilbert (2015) indicated that age is a barrier and has no effect on the use of ICTs. It is believed that young people are more curious Jegede (2009) conducted a study that age was not found to affect the time used on ICTs by higher education teachers in Nigeria

The focus of previous studies was on lecturers' attitude towards the use of ICTs in Nigeria. Very few studies have examined the effect of gender, academic qualification(s) and age on the use of ICTs in Colleges of Education in Nigeria. Also, most of these studies were conducted in developing countries where technology was in its high position. The situation may be different if studies are conducted in developing countries or where technology usage is still in its primitive stages. The teachers in these situations face different difficulties that may impede the use of ICTs in teaching and learning in schools. Therefore, the present study explores lecturers related factors that may affect the usage of ICTs in teaching and learning in Colleges of Education (COE) in Ondo state, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The study sought to achieve the following objectives:

1. To assess the difference in ICTs usage between male and female COE lecturers in Ondo State.
2. To assess the difference in ICTs usage among COE lecturers with varied academic qualification(s) in Ondo state.
3. To examine the difference in ICTs usage among COE lecturers with varied age in Ondo state.

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference in ICTs usage between male and female COE lecturers in Ondo State.
2. There is no significant difference in ICTs usage among COE lecturers with varied academic qualification(s) in Ondo state.
3. There is no significant difference in ICTs usage among COE lecturers with varied age in Ondo state

Methodology

The study was a descriptive research type. The population for the study was lecturers in Colleges of Education in Ondo state Nigeria and the total number of lecturers are four hundred and forty. The targeted population of this research consisted of lecturers in Colleges of Education in three Colleges namely: Adeyemi College of Education Ondo, Ondo State is having the total population of three hundred and eighty-nine (389), All State College of Education, Ero is having twenty (20) lecturers and Bethel College of Education, Ijare is having thirty (30) lecturers all in Ondo State. The overall total of lecturers regardless of the of school and gender are four hundred and forty nine (449). In all, a total of (200) two hundred lecturers were selected using simple random technique and they responded to the instrument and data collected was finally processed. The dependent variable of concern was the Colleges of Education lecturers' usage of ICT. Intervening variables of gender, academic qualification(s) and age of lecturers were considered.

The instrument for data collection used for the study was a questionnaire, developed by researcher and titled of the questionnaire is 'Demographic Differentials of ICTs usage among COE lecturers' (DFICCEL). The questionnaire had two sections A and B. Section A was concerned with demographic information while section B sought to know how Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) can be effectively used by Colleges of Education (COE) in Ondo state, Nigeria. The researcher administered copies of questionnaire within four (4) weeks by visiting the Colleges with the help of research assistant in various Colleges. At the end of the exercise two hundred (200) valid copies of the questionnaire were retrieved, upon which analysis of the results was carried. Mean, standard deviation, t-test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to analyze the data collected.

Demographic Differentials in the Use ... (Ayelaagbe & Kareem, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367880>

Five experts from departments of Educational Technology from Department of Educational Technology from University of Ilorin, Ilorin validated the instrument. The experts assessed the appropriateness and adequacy of the content of the instrument. In order to determine the reliability of the instrument a pilot study was conducted among COE lecturers from two Colleges of Education in Ogun state not part of the main sample. The two (2) results of administration were compared using Cronbach’s Alpha co-efficient and the co-efficient of internal consistency was 0.78.

Results

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in ICT usage between male and female colleges of education lecturers using ICTs in Ondo state.

Table 1: Summary of t-test Showing Difference Between Male and Female Lecturers’ ICT Usage in Colleges of Education

Grouping Variable (Gender)	N	Mean	Std. D	Df	T	Sig.	Remark
Male	80	23.50	2.25	198	.159	.874	Not Significant
Female	120	23.45	2.14				

Table 1 shows the difference in the usage of ICT by male and female lecturers in colleges of education in Ondo state. The table shows that the mean score for male lecturers is 23.50 while that of female lecturers’ usage is 23.45. The values of the mean scores do not reveal an appreciable difference. Therefore, there is no significant difference in ICT usage between male and female colleges of education lecturers in Ondo state ($df = 198$; $t = .159$; $p > 0.05$). Hence, hypothesis 1 is retained.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in ICT usage among college of education lecturers with varied academic qualifications in Ondo state.

Table 2: Summary of ANOVA Showing Difference in Lecturers’ Usage of ICT based on Academic Qualification

Qualifications	N	Mean	Std. Dev.
HND	33	22.18	1.91
First Degree	55	24.15	1.89
Master’s Degree	65	23.39	2.28
PhD	47	23.70	2.17
Total	200	23.47	2.18

Analysis of Variance						
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remark
Between Groups	82.860	3	27.620	6.288	.000	Significant
Within Groups	860.960	196	4.393			
Total	943.820	199				

Table 2 shows the difference in lecturers’ usage of ICT based on their academic qualification. The table shows that the mean score for lecturers with HND is 22.18, those with first degree is 24.15, those with master’s degree is 23.38 while that of lecturers with Ph.D is 23.70. The ANOVA results shows that there is significant difference in ICT usage among college of education lecturers with varied academic qualifications in Ondo state ($F_{(3,196)} = 6.288$; $p < 0.05$). Hence, hypothesis 2 is rejected.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference in ICT usage among college of education lecturers with varied age in Ondo state.

Demographic Differentials in the Use ... (Ayelaagbe & Kareem, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367880>

Table 3: Summary of ANOVA Showing Difference in Lecturers' Usage of ICT in College of Education based on Age

Age Range	N	Mean	Std. Dev.
20-25years	6	23.17	.98
26-30years	28	23.93	2.07
31-36years	36	22.89	2.41
37-40years	50	23.84	1.98
41years and Above	80	23.36	2.25
Total	200	23.47	2.18

Analysis of Variance						
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remark
Between Groups	26.366	4	6.592			
Within Groups	917.454	195	4.705	1.401	.235	Not Significant
Total	943.820	199				

Table 4 shows the difference in the lecturers of colleges of education students' usage of ICTs based on their age range. The table shows that the mean score for lecturers between ages of 20 to 25years is 23.17, those between 26 to 30years is 23.93, those between 31 to 36years is 22.89, those between 37 to 40years is 23.84 while that of lecturers aged 41years and above is 23.36. The ANOVA results shows that there is no significant difference in ICT usage among college of education lecturers with varied age in Ondo state ($F_{(4,195)} = 1.401$; $p > 0.05$). Hence, hypothesis 3 is retained.

Discussion of Findings

Result on influence of gender on lecturers' usage of ICTs facilities for teaching purpose showed that there was no statistically significant difference between male and female lecturers on the use of ICT facilities for teaching purpose. The study agrees with previous findings (Fomsi & Orduah, 2017, Tezci, 2009, Halberg et al., 2011, Usun 2013, Mahmood and Bohkam, 2012, Sanda and Kirfi, 2013), it is in the contrast to Heimrath and Goulding 2001 which found a significant difference between the male and female lecturers in using ICTs in teaching and other purposes. Also, Shashaani and Khalili, (2001) in their study revealed that is pervasive difference between the ways females and males use technology to socialize. The result from this investigation also shows the lecturers with PHD and master's qualification had slightly higher mean ratings on level of usage of ICTs in teaching than those with HND and first degree. This result is not surprising because the added qualification of the lecturers must have exposed them to various skills of using ICTs. The ANOVA result showed that there was no significant different between lecturers' level of using ICTs based on qualification. The result agrees with the findings of Odigwe and Owan (2020) that there was a significant influence of staff educational qualification on the utilization of ICTs resources for teaching, research and records management in higher education on the contrary, Gombe et al. (2016) found no significant difference in the utilization of ICTs based on lecturers' qualification.

The result in table three showed the age of lecturers as it influences the use of ICTs among the lecturers of Colleges of Education in Ondo state. The ANOVA indicated that the age of the lecturers does not have significant relationship with the use of ICTs among lecturers. This agrees with Lubis et al., (2017) and Herath and Hewagamase (2015) that teaching experiences is not significantly affecting the ICTs usage. On the contrary, Morley (2010) confirmed that there is a significant different between educational level and teachers using ICTs. The higher educational level of lecturers is more frequently to utilize ICTs.

Conclusion

This study investigated the demographic differentials of lecturers in Colleges of Education (COEs) usage of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) in Ondo state, Nigeria. This study has showed that ICTs were extensively used by lecturers regardless of their gender, qualification(s) and age. It was revealed that both male and female lecturers adequately utilise ICTs for different purposes such as teaching, research, computation of results and management in general. Hence, it can be concluded that factors such as gender, academic qualification(s) and age does not hinder the use of ICTs among lecturers of Colleges of Education in Ondo state.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

Demographic Differentials in the Use ... (Ayelaagbe & Kareem, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367880>

1. Training should be given to both male and female lecturers to enable them effectively use ICTs for research, teaching and for management.
2. Regardless of lecturers age, all lecturers in colleges of education should be ICT compliance in using it to perform different activities.
3. Lecturers across different education, qualification(s) should make conscious efforts to avail themselves of the opportunity of becoming ICT literates through active participation in ICT retraining and by putting forth favourable attitude towards technology

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Effects of Flipped Classroom on Students Performance ... (Yahaya, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367905>

Effects of Flipped Classroom on Students Performance in Cell Physiology Concepts among Senior Secondary Schools in Gusau, Zamfara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated Effect of Flipped Classroom on students 'performance in Cell Physiology Concepts among Senior Secondary Students in Gusau Zamfara State. Quasi-experimental pretest, post-test control group design involving two groups was adopted for the study. The population comprised of all (1225) one thousand two hundred and twenty-five Biology students from 11 public Senior Secondary Schools in Offa, Kwara State. A sample of 137 students from two schools was randomly selected. The study involves two groups-an experimental and a control group. The experimental group was taught Cell Physiology using Flip Classroom Instructional Strategy while the control group was exposed to the same concept using Conventional Method. One instrument was used for data collection Namely Cell Physiology Performance Test (CPPT). The instrument was duly validated by experts and have reliability coefficient of 0.87, using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) statistic Two research questions and two null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. One of the research questions: What is the difference between the mean performance scores of students taught concepts cell physiology concept using flipped classroom instructional strategy and those taught same concept using conventional lecture method? The research questions were answered using Mean and Standard deviation statistics while null hypotheses were tested using Independent Samples t-test at alpha 0.05 level of significance. The major findings reveal a significant difference between mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught cell physiology concept. There is also no significant difference between the mean scores of males and female students. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others, that workshops, seminars and conferences should be organized for Biology teachers on the use of Flipped Class model of Instruction at secondary schools in Kwara State.

Keywords: Flipped Classroom, Cell Physiology, Academic Performance, Secondary School

Introduction

Science is a very important aspect in the development of any nation and is regarded as instrument per excellence for solving socio-economic problems of various kinds (Ghumdia, 2017). Science has helped to meet the minimum needs of human in the society in terms of food, shelter, clothing, water, unemployment, basic education, transportation, communication and healthcare (Ongowo, 2017). Despite the roles played by science in the society, some students still display negative attitudes towards the study of nature of some topics in science subjects (Adegboye, et al, 2017).

As a science subject, biology serves as a prerequisite to the study of medicine, pharmacy, agriculture among others. Biology concepts according to Oyarole, (2023) can sometimes be difficult particularly when describing ideas that are abstract or cannot be fully comprehended by learners for the first time. Research finding by Oyarole (2015); West African Examination Council (2018) have also shown that a number of concepts in biology which include Cell Physiology, Evolution and Cell physiology contains topics that pose difficulty for biology students to understand. Cell physiology is an aspect of the biology syllabus that senior secondary students at SS2 must study. However, it is considered as abstract in nature and difficult to understand which has resulted in poor performance among students (Etobro & Fabinu, 2017).

Despite the importance of Biology as a science subject, empirical studies such as those of Etobro and Fabinu (2017) and Adegboye et al. (2017) have shown that students still perform poorly in Biology at Senior Secondary level. Umar (2015) reported that Biology is one of the science subjects having downward trend in the performance of students at Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE). Timothy (2018) noted that a review of students' enrollment in science subjects at senior secondary schools in Nigeria shows that more students register Biology than any other subject but their academic performance in the subject is comparatively lower at SSCE. The poor performance has been attributed to the method of instruction.

The predominant instructional method used in teaching at all levels of education, is through the use of lecture method (Oyarole,2023). Lecture method on the other hand has **been** reported by Umar (2016) and Wada (2016), to be passive mode of instruction. The use of lecture method entails one way flow of communication from the teacher to the students. It is teacher-centre or teacher dominated apt of the talking is carried out by the teacher while the students remain as passive. Any teaching

Effects of Flipped Classroom on Students Performance ... (Yahaya, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367905>

method that does not encourage positive interaction between the students and the teacher and amongst the students is incomplete (Muokwe and Okeke, 2021). One of such innovative teaching methods is flipped classroom strategy.

Flipped classroom is an instructional strategy and a type of blended learning, which aims to increase students' engagement and leaning by having students complete reading at home and work on problem-solving during class time (Alvarez, 2011). In a flipped classroom, students watch online lectures, collaborate in online discussions, or carry out research at home while engaging in concepts in the classroom with the guidance of a teacher. Jacoub (2019). The flipped classroom intentionally shifts instruction to a learner-centered model in which time in the classroom is used to explore topics in greater depth and create meaningful learning opportunities while students are initially introduced to new topics outside the classroom. This type of instructional strategy content delivery may take a variety of forms, often video lessons prepared by teacher although online collaborative discussions, digital research, and text reading may be used (Nwagbo, &Onah. (2017). A teacher's interaction with students in a flipped classroom can be more personalized and less didactic, especially when males and female students are actively involved in knowledge acquisition and construction as they participate in and evaluate their learning (Sen, Sezen-Vekli, 2016)

Another variable that has been of concern to researcher in science education his gender. Many researchers in science education have conducted studies on gender-related differences with a view to improving science instruction for boy and girls in the secondary schools. Researchers such Sarac (2017) and Musa (2017) in their separate studies reported great concern that girls are not achieving as much as their male counterpart in science education.

Over the years, there has been an upsurge in the number of candidates sitting for public examinations such as Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) and particularly biology papers. This is because of the stipulation that students must offer one of the basic science subjects (Biology, Chemistry and Physics) and biology it is preferred by most students. The results obtained by candidates have been abysmal and do not justify the popularity as observed by researchers (Maikano, et al., 2016) ; and Jack, (2017) The statistics of performance in Biology in the May/June Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) revealed a poor percentage pass at credit level.

Objective of the Study

The objectives of this study were to:

1. Determine the effects of flipped classroom instructional strategy and those taught using conventional teaching method on senior secondary school students' performance in cell physiology concept.
2. Determine the effect of flipped classroom model of instruction on male and female students' performance in cell physiology concept

Research Questions

The study attempted to formulate two research questions for answering:

1. What is the difference between the mean performance scores of students taught concepts cell physiology concept using flipped classroom instructional strategy and those taught same concept using conventional lecture method?
2. What is the difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students taught cell physiology concepts using flipped classroom instructional strategy?

Hypotheses

On the basis of the research questions, the following null hypotheses were stated for testing at $p \leq 0.05$ level of significant:

1. There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of students taught cell physiology concepts using flipped classroom instructional strategy and those taught same concepts using conventional teaching method.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students taught using cell physiology concepts using flipped classroom instructional strategy.

Methodology

The study was quasi-experimental-control group design employing pretest, posttest. Two groups of students were used for data collection; the experimental (EG) and the control groups (CG). A pretest was administered to the two groups in order to determine the equivalence in ability of the two groups. The experimental group was taught cell physiology concept using flipped classroom instructional strategy. The control group was taught same concept using Lecture Method (LM). At the end of the six weeks treatment, a posttest was administered to both groups of students to evaluate the effectiveness of the treatment in enhancing students' academic performance in cell physiology concept.

The population for the study was made up of all the Senior Secondary II student in Offa Metropolis, with a total number of 1225students comprising males and females. In selecting the sample used for the study, the names of the twelve (12) schools in the metropolis were written on pieces of paper and two pieces of paper were picked once at a time. The content

Effects of Flipped Classroom on Students Performance ... (Yahaya, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367905>

was reshuffled each time a piece of paper was picked to ensure equal chance off picking each of the pieces of paper. The two schools whose names were coded on the pieces of paper picked were used as sample schools. Hence the total number of subjects in the two schools was 135 students. This is in accordance with central limit theorem Tuckman (1975); Gay, Mills and Airasian (2009) who proposed 30 as minimum sample size for an experimental study. Cell Physiology Performance Test (CPPT) was the instrument used to collect data for the study.

Cell Physiology Performance Test (CPPT) is a forty (40) items objective test involving multiple choice (a,b,c and d) developed by the researcher. The content validation of the Cell Physiology Performance Test (CPPT) was carried out by a panel of experts comprising the following: two senior lecturers from science education of the department of education Ahmadu Bello University Zaria. One Biology teacher at the secondary school level and a specialist in Educational Statistics In order to ascertain the level to which CPPT was reliable Test-retest method was used to statistically estimate the internal consistency of the items in the instrument. Tuckman (1975), who proposed the minimum interval of two or more weeks between the first and second administration, recommended the use of two weeks interval. Data thus collected from the pilot study were analyzed using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient statistic. The results showed a reliability coefficient of 0.85 which was considered reasonably reliable for this study.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the difference between the mean performance scores of students taught cell physiology concepts using flipped classroom instructional strategy and those taught same concept using conventional lecture method?

Table 1: Means and Standard Deviation of Post Scores for Academic Performance for Experimental and Control Group

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Diff
Experimental	73	21.17	5.89	9.28
Control	64	11.89	3.46	

Table 1 shows that the academic performance means scores for the experimental and control group were 21.17 and 11.89 respectively. The standard deviation for the experimental and control group were 5.89 and 3.46 respectively. The mean difference was 9.28. This means the experimental group achieved higher than the control group.

Research Question 2

What is the difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students taught cell physiology concepts using flipped classroom instructional strategy?

Table 2.: Means and Standard Deviation of Performance Scores for Male and Female in Experimental Group.

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Dev	Mean Diff
Female	73	19.61	5.91	
Male	64	9.48	2.65	10.13

Table 2. Showed the mean scores for male and female students were 19.61 and 9.48 respectively, with mean difference of 10.13 and the standard deviation for the females group achieved higher than the males

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of students taught cell physiology concepts using flipped classroom instructional strategy and those taught using conventional teaching method.

Effects of Flipped Classroom on Students Performance ... (Yahaya, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367905>

Table 3: Summary of Independent t-test Analysis, of Academic Performance Mean Scores of Experimental and Control Group

Gender	N	\bar{X}_1	SD	t-CAL	DF	P	Remark
EXP	73	21.17	5.89	11.04	135	0.00	S
CONRT	64	11.89	3.46				

Table 3 result shows experimental group has higher mean scores of 21.17 as compared to that of control group with mean scores of 11.89. The p-value is 0.00 which is less than 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected. This means flip classroom instructional strategy is effective in enhancing student's performance in cell physiology concepts

Hypothesis 2:

There is no significant difference between retention of ecology concepts between male and female students taught using Flipped classroom strategy.

Table 4. t-test Analysis of Post-posttest Mean Scores of Male and Female Students in Experimental Group

Gender	N	\bar{X}_1	SD	t-CAL	DF	P	Remark
Female	73	19.62	5.95	12.54	135	0.26	NS
Male	64	9.48	9.48				

Table 4 shows that there is no significant difference between male and female student's academic performance scores when exposed to flip classroom strategy i.e treatment. They female and male recorded a mean of 19.62 and 9.48 respectively. The calculated p value of 0.26 is higher than the 0.05 alpha level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference between male and female students exposed to flip classroom instructional strategy is hereby retained.

Discussion of Findings

The result of analysis showed that the students taught cell physiology concept with flip classroom instructional strategy had a higher mean score than the students taught using lecture method. This result is in agreement with the findings of Oyarole, (2015) and whose works found that flipped classroom instructional strategy enhanced students' academic performance in science subjects. The findings of this study are also in agreement with that of Talam and Gulsecen (2019) that the use of flip classroom teaching strategy results in higher achievement of students in Biology concepts. However, the finding is not in agreement with the findings of Arwa, Din & Hussin (2017) who found no significant difference in performance of flip classroom on the concept of physics education.

Females were significantly different from the males, flip classroom learning strategy had impact on performance of the female than the male students who were exposed to it. This finding agrees with the findings of Oyarole, (2023) who reported a significant difference in the academic performance girls than boys who were exposed to flip classroom learning strategy. No significant difference between males and females students exposed to flip classroom learning strategy as revealed by the result of this study may be due to the fact that in flip classroom strategy encourage students to work on the same task, share ideas and experiences freely. This gives equal opportunity for the students to learn together irrespective of their gender differences.

Conclusion

In the light of the findings of the study, the researcher concluded that: flipped classroom instructional strategy enhances student's performance in cell physiology concepts. The findings also revealed that flipped classroom model of instruction were efficacious in eliminating gender related differences in science learning, indicating that the strategy was gender friendly.

Recommendations

Based on the findings in the study, the researcher wished to make the following recommendations.

1. Biology teachers should adopt the use of flip classroom instructional strategy in teaching various concepts in Biology.

Effects of Flipped Classroom on Students Performance ... (Yahaya, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367905>

2. Seminars/Workshops should be organized by ministry of education for Biology teachers to appraise them with the use of flipped classroom model of instruction.

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Factors Hindering the Effective Integration of Almajiri Schools in Niger State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated factors hindering the effective integration of Almajiri schools into formal education in Niger state. The study employed descriptive survey research. The population of the study consisted of Community Based Management Committees (CBMC) members, Mallams/teachers, and learners/pupils from 24 Integrated Islamiyya and Tsanaya schools in Niger state. Six (6) Local Government Areas were selected randomly; two from each senatorial zone. The total population of the respondents is forty-four thousand six hundred (44,800). This comprised of 2,600 for CBMC (6%), 2,000 for teachers (4%), and 40,200 for pupils (90%). A simple of 384 respondents (23 for CBMC, 15 for teachers, and 346 for pupils) was drawn proportionately sampling technique from twenty-four (24) schools. Three research questions guided the study and inventory on factors hindering the effective integration of Almajiri schools was used as the instrument for data collection. The data collected was analyzed using mean and standard deviation with 2.50 point as threshold set for decision. The findings of the study showed that non-availability of food for the Almajirai to concentrate on their school work, non-availability of first aid and medical services to provide treatment for the sick Almajirai in schools and lack of adequate classroom accommodations and learning facilities to provide conducive teaching and learning were factors identified as hindrance to integration of the Almajiri schools in Niger state. The study recommended school feeding programme, provision of first aid equipment, adequate classroom accommodation, learning and recreational facilities, and provision of grants and financial support, among others, for effective integration of the Almajiri schools in Niger State.

Keywords: Factors Hindering, Integration, Almajiri Schools

Introduction

The word Almajiri is derived from an Arabic word 'Al-Muhajir'; meaning a seeker of Islamic knowledge. From the Islamic perspective, the word 'Al-muhajirun' was first used by the Prophet Muhammad (SAW) on those of his companions who migrated with him for the sake of Islam from Makka to Madina. However, the name Al-Muhajirun later came to refer to those who seek for knowledge and move from one place to another in search of knowledge (Goodluck & Juliana, 2017; Taiwo, 2013). Against this background, the word Almajiri was borrowed by the Hausa language which refers to the immigrant children in search of Qur'anic Education which is considered as the pre-primary and primary levels of traditional Islamic Education (Ali, 2022 & Goodluck & Juliana, 2017).

In Northern Nigeria, Almajiri refers to children sent from their homes and entrusted into the care of an Islamic scholar called 'Malam' (teacher), to learn the Islamic Education (Ayuba, 2009 & Yusha'u, et al., 2013). Therefore, the Almajiri education system in this context, refers to a traditional method of acquiring and memorizing the Glorious Qur'an in the Northern part of the country; where boys at their tender ages are sent out by their parents or guardians to other villages, towns or cities for the sake of learning Qur'an education under a knowledgeable Islamic scholar called Malam (Yusha'u, et al., 2013). Hence, the term Almajirai is the plural of the word 'Almajiri', which refers to pupils of traditional Qur'anic schools also called as Tsangaya schools who are mostly school-aged children drawn from rural communities to urban areas with the intention of acquiring Qur'anic knowledge.

Ayuba (2009) and Idriss and Hamza (2021) described Almajirci (the process of acquiring Islamic education) as a semi-formal system of Qur'anic education in which children mostly boys are sent by their parents to take up residence with Islamic scholars (*Malams*), for the purpose of acquiring the knowledge of Qur'an and other Islamic texts. In this respect, the Qur'anic or Islamic education in Nigeria is offered in three types of schools. The first is the traditional form, where boys (pupils) travel to distant places to learn under the tutorship of a teacher; called Malam (who himself is a product of such schools). Secondly, there are non-boarding Qur'anic schools where pupils learn for a few hours and return home. This type of

school is commonly found in the South-western part of Nigeria. Thirdly, the Islamiyya schools that combine both the Qur'anic education and Western education.

Odumosu, et al. (2013) observed that the Almajiri school system was meant to teach children basic Islamic spiritual, moral and social values in order to enhance their sense of responsibility. It was also aimed at inculcating in them the value of caring for those in need. The original objective of the Almajiri system of education therefore was intellectual and moral training as well as life-long discipline before its subsequent adulteration with the beggary institution. Yusha'u, et al. (2013) stated that the aim and objective of the Qur'anic system of education is to produce a faithful and piety man that will be useful to the society. Thus, the Almajiri system of education is designed to train children intellectually and morally.

However, despite the salient benefits of the Almajiri school system, there are some problems associated with it. Muhammad (2010) and Teke, et al. (2022) observed the problems associated with the Almajiri schools to include: Inadequate provision of feeding, over population, lack of payment of salary, begging, enrollment of under aged, poor methods of discipline and lack of organized curriculum. Yusha'u, et al. (2013) also identified the major challenges affecting the Almajiri schools to include; unfriendly environment, over crowdedness, inadequate instructional materials, insufficient teachers and instructors, and inadequate community support to the Qur'anic schools, among others.

Consequently, the poor nature and practice of the Almajiri education system has made the general public to perceive and view it as a trend which breeds child abuse syndrome in the society. It is in view of this negative perception and circumstance surrounding the Almajiri schools that led to intervention programmes in the recent time by both local and international donors, federal, state, and local governments as well as Non-Governmental Organization (NGOs) and individuals' philanthropists to reform the system for better realization of the national goals on education. Against this backdrop, the Federal Government in 1998 made pronouncement that the Almajiri schools would be integrated into the formal system of education. To this end, the Federal Government of Nigeria through the National Council on Education (NCE) at its sitting in Enugu (2001) approved the integration of Qur'anic schools into the Universal Basic Education schools (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2002). Consequent upon this, the Almajiri Integrated Schools (AIS) across the country as one of the interventions of government strategies to curtail the menace of street begging, child abuse and out of school children were established (Paiko, 2013).

In April, 2016, the government of Niger State set a committee to look into the Almajiri and begging syndrome in the state. The outcome of the committee's assignment led to a number of programmes and interventions such as training and re-training of the Malams and sensitization programmes at both urban and rural communities for the integration of the Almajiri schools in the state (Agency for Mass Education, 2021).

Contextually, integration refers to merging of the two systems of education together. That is, a combination of the Western system of education and Qur'anic system of education. Isah (2013) defined integration as the process that involves teaching literacy to learners of Qur'anic schools, at a period agreed upon between the proprietor of the schools and the facilitators without interfering in the running of the Qur'anic education programme. In this case, the two forms of education are expected to be provided hand-in-hand with the existing Qur'anic school programme.

Thus, the purpose of integrating the two systems of education is to provide educational opportunities for the Almajirai through an integrated curriculum that will promote the study of Qur'anic education and Basic Education subjects, to strengthen the ability of the learners to read, write and memorize the Qur'an so as to provide opportunities for the graduates of the schools to further their studies, to provide a conducive and organized learning environment, to provide the Almajirai with opportunities to acquire knowledge and vocational skills that will enable them to be self-reliant and useful to their communities, and to provide health, sanitary, and physical conditions and social security and welfare that ensures protection of the Almajirai from all forms of dangers and risks (Adetoro, 2012; Dukku, 2006; Mahuta, 2009; Mamman, et al., 2020; Muhammad, 2010 & Yusha'u, et al., 2013).

Although the integration policy is widely accepted by stakeholders of the Qur'anic schools, there are contentious issues which hamper its implementation. The challenges include lack of strong political will on the part of government, absence of a sustainable funding framework, scarcity of resources, inadequacy of trained teaching force, high demands of labour practices with the routines of the schools, and perceived irrelevance of curriculum content to the realities of the Almajirai and their communities (Junaid, et al., 2005 & Olutola, et al., 2021). Suleiman (2004) also outlined the hindrances to effective integration of the Almajiri schools to include inadequate classrooms, absence of sitting and writing materials, lack of textbooks and free feeding, resistance by the proprietors of the Qur'anic schools, adverse criticisms against the Almajiri system, vulnerability

Factors Hindering the Effective Integration of... (Mohammed, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367966>

(exposure to contingencies, risks, shocks or hazards, loss of livelihood, death of a parent, acute or chronic poverty, disease, drought, flood, and stress). Other factors that affect the integration policy are poverty, social exclusion (such as denial of rights and privileges), begging and misconceptions and perceptions of Western Education as Westernization of Muslims (Adetoro, 2010; Jimba 2021; Hamza, 2009; Isiaka, 2015; Mahuta, 2009 & Odumosu, et al., 2013). Therefore, the rationale for this study is timely as its findings would be useful to government at all levels, relevant stakeholders, parents, non-governmental organizations, and well-meaning individuals to reinvigorate efforts as well as committing resources to address the challenges.

The Almajiri school system has denied the Almajirai access to formal education. This practice has rendered the Almajirai non-literate and vulnerable; as well as increased the rates of out of school children in Niger State and the country at large. The consequences may include security threats such as engaging in various social ills and unrest, thurggery, delinquent behaviour, kidnapping, banditry, and insurgencies. The Almajiri school system has also exposed the Almajirai to begging syndrome; thereby constituting a great socio-economic threat that requires research to uncover the factors that hinder effective integration of the schools as well as to proffer strategies that will minimize the challenges.

Objectives of the Study

The major purpose of this study is to investigate factors hindering the effective integration of Almajiri schools in Niger state. The specific objectives therefore, include:

1. To examine the views of CBMC members on factors hindering effective integration of Almajiri schools in Niger State.
2. To determine the views of teachers/malams on factors hindering the effective integration of Almajiri schools in Niger State.
3. To assess the views of learners/pupils on factors hindering the effective integration of Almajiri schools in Niger State.

Research Questions

1. What are the views of CBMC members on factors hindering the effective integration of Almajiri schools in Niger State?
2. What are the views of teachers/malams on factors hindering the effective integration of Almajiri schools in Niger State?
3. What are the views of learners/pupils on factors hindering the effective integration of Almajiri schools in Niger State?

Methodology

The design for this study is a descriptive survey research. It is considered appropriate because it involves the use of questionnaire on existing situation among a large number of respondents. The design was relevant because it assisted to investigate the phenomenon of Almajiri school system across a wide range of the respondents and allow for adequate and appropriate sample which the findings were generalized on the entire population. The target population of this study is all the members of Community Based Management Committees (CBMC), teachers/mallams and the learners/pupils in the Integrated Islamiyya and Tradition Qur'anic/Tsangaya schools of Niger state. There are over 15,000 Islamic and Qur'anic schools in Niger state but two hundred (200) are integrated (Niger State Agency for Mass Education, 2021). The total population of the respondents is forty-four thousand six hundred (44,600). This comprised of 2,600 for CBMC (6%), 2,000 for teachers (4%), and 40,200 for pupils (90%). The sample size of the study is 384 respondents. This was determined using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) population table for determining a sample size. The selection includes 23 CBMC members (6%), 15 teachers (4%), and 346 pupils (90%). Simple random sampling technique was used to select six (6) out of the 25 Local Government Areas in the state, and four (4) Integrated Qur'anic and Islamiyya schools were chosen from each Local Government Area; giving a total of 24 schools. A proportionate sampling technique was employed for selection of the respondents presented in Table 1 below:

Table 1: Population and Sample Size

S/No	Respondents	Population	Sample	Total
1.	CBMC	2,600	23	23
2.	Teachers/Malams	2,000	15	15
3.	Learners/Pupils	40,200	346	346
	Total	44,800	384	384

The instrument for collection of data in this study was titled: An inventory on factors hindering effective integration of Almajiri schools in Niger state. This was developed by the researcher. The inventory has two (2) parts: Part one centred on the demographic data of respondents covering category of respondent (CBMC, Malams/teachers, and learners/pupils), Local

Factors Hindering the Effective Integration of... (Mohammed, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367966>

Government Area and Senatorial zone. Part two has 10 items measuring factors hindering integration of Almajiri schools. The items were prepared on four - point's modified Likert's scale namely; Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree which were scored 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively.

The face and content validity of the instrument was ascertained by experts in Educational Psychology, Test and Measurement, and Guidance and Counselling from Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, University of Abuja, and IBB University, Lapai. Cronbach Alpha-20 method was used to determine the reliability of the instrument which had 0.80 index tested at 0.05 levels of significance.

The collection of data in this study was carried out personally by the researcher. Since the research work covered the entire state, five (5) research assistants were trained and used together with the researcher during the data collection process across twenty (24) selected Integrated Almajiri schools in three (3) Local Government Areas. The researcher also visited the State Ministry of Education, State Universal Basic Education Board and State Agency for Mass Education to collect other relevant secondary data which include total number of the schools and records of SBMC, teachers, and pupils. The data collection was by a way of focus group method which lasted for two days. The analysis of the data collected was carried out using mean and standard deviation, with 2.50 point as threshold set for decision.

Results

Research Question 1

What are the views of CBMC members on factors hindering the effective integration of Almajiri schools in Niger State?

Table 2: Views of CBMC members on factors Hindering Effective Integration of Almajiri Schools (n=23)

SN	Factors Hindering Effective Integration	Mean	SD	Decision
1	The Almajiri Schools lack adequate accommodation for conducive teaching and learning	3.73	.659	A Factor
2	There are inadequate facilitators to teach the subjects that are integrated in to the Almajiri school curriculum	3.68	.674	A Factor
3	The Almajiri schools lack regular monitoring and supervision	3.27	.863	A Factor
4	There is no adequate security to protect the Almajiri against rituals and child-traffickers while in school	3.61	.822	A Factor
5	Inadequate provision of teaching materials has hindered the activities of the Almajiri schools.	3.57	.7630	A Factor
6	The Almajiri schools lack means of transportation to ease their programmes.	3.54	.801	A Factor
7	Inadequate funding has hindered the progress of Almajiri schools in terms of motivating facilitators and addressing school problems.	3.63	.756	A Factor
8	Food is not available for the Almajirai to concentrate on their work	3.78	.518	A Factor
9	There is no available first aid and medical services to provide treatment for the sick Almajirai while in school.	3.73	.535	A Factor
10	There is the fear that government may assume the ownership of the Almajiri schools.	3.15	.728	A Factor
Total Mean Score		3.56		A Factor

The results in Table 2 indicated the mean score rating of CBMC members regarding their views of factors hindering integration of Almajiri schools in Niger state. All the factors on the instrument had the mean scores above the criterion mean score of 2.50, the CBMC members perceived 'Food is not available for the Almajirai to concentrate on their work' with a mean score of 3.78 as the highest determinant hampering or hindering integration of the Almajiri schools in Niger state. This was followed by 'There is no available first aid and medical services to provide treatment for the sick Almajirai while in school' and 'The Almajiri schools lack adequate accommodation for conducive teaching and learning. The two indicators had the mean scores of 3.73. Nevertheless, the factor 'there is the fear that government may assume the ownership of the Almajiri schools'

Factors Hindering the Effective Integration of... (Mohammed, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367966>

had the least mean score of 3.15. Based on the cluster mean score of 3.56, it was concluded that CBMC members perceived generally that the factors discussed above had impact on the integration of Almajiri schools in Niger state.

Research Question 2

What are the views of teachers/malams on factors hindering the effective integration of Almajiri schools in Niger State?

Table 3: Views of Teachers/Malams on factors Hindering Effective Integration of Almajiri Schools (n=15)

SN	Factors Hindering Effective Integration	Mean	SD	Decision
1	The Almajiri Schools lack adequate accommodation for conducive teaching and learning	3.51	.822	A Factor
2	There are inadequate facilitators to teach the subjects that are integrated in to the Almajiri school curriculum	3.43	.819	A Factor
3	The Almajiri schools lack regular monitoring and supervision	3.35	.967	A Factor
4	There is no adequate security to protect the Almajiri against rituals and child-traffickers while in school	3.36	1.025	A Factor
5	Inadequate provision of teaching materials has hindered the activities of Almajiri schools.	3.31	.898	A Factor
6	The Almajiri schools lack means of transportation to ease their programmes	3.28	.967	A Factor
7	Inadequate funding has hindered the progress of Almajiri schools in terms of motivating facilitators and addressing school problems.	3.40	.959	A Factor
8	Food is not available for the Almajirai to concentrate on their work	3.70	.597	A Factor
9	There is no available first aid and medical services to provide treatment for the sick Almajirai while in school	3.60	.597	A Factor
10	There is the fear that government may assume the ownership of the Almajiri schools.	3.21	.887	A Factor
Total Mean Score		3.42		A Factor

The findings in Table 3 showed the mean score rating of Teachers/Malams regarding their views of factors hindering effective integration of Almajiri schools in Niger state. Although all the factors on the scale had the mean scores above the criterion mean score of 2.50, the Teachers/Malams perceived ‘Food is not available for the Almajirai to concentrate on their work’ with a mean score of 3.70 as the highest determinant of factors hindering integration of Almajiri schools in Niger state. This was followed by ‘There is no available first aid and medical services to provide treatment for the sick Almajirai while in school’ with a mean score of 3.60, and ‘The Almajiri schools lack adequate accommodation for conducive teaching and learning’ with a mean of 3.51. Nevertheless, there is the fear that government may assume the ownership of the Almajiri schools had the least mean score of 3.21. Based on the cluster mean score of 3.42, it was concluded that Teachers/ Malams perceived generally that the above factors had impact on the integration of Almajiri schools in Niger state.

Research Question 3

What are the views of learners/pupils on factors hindering the effective integration of Almajiri schools in Niger State?

Factors Hindering the Effective Integration of... (Mohammed, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367966>

Table 4: Learners'/Pupils' Views on factors Hindering the Effective Integration of Almajiri Schools (n=346)

SN	Factors Hindering Effective Integration	Mean	SD	Decision
1	The Almajiri Schools lack adequate accommodation for conducive teaching and learning	3.64	.589	A factor
2	There are inadequate facilitators to teach the subjects that are integrated in to the Almajiri school curriculum	3.61	.571	A factor
3	The Almajiri schools lack regular monitoring and supervision	3.35	.772	A factor
4	There is no adequate security to protect the Almajiri against rituals and child-traffickers while in school	3.54	.711	A factor
5	Inadequate provision of teaching materials has hindered the activities of Almajiri schools.	3.53	.649	A factor
6	The Almajiri schools lack means of transportation to ease their programmes	3.53	.649	A factor
7	Inadequate funding has hindered the progress of Almajiri schools in terms of motivating facilitators and addressing school problems.	3.63	.638	A factor
8	Food is not available for the Almajirai to concentrate on their work	3.68	.577	A factor
9	There is no available first aid and medical services to provide treatment for the sick Almajirai while in school	3.68	.552	A factor
10	There is the fear that government may assume the ownership of the Almajiri schools.	3.24	.880	A factor
Total Mean Score		3.54		A factor

The data in Table 4 indicated the mean score rating of learners/pupils regarding their perception of factors hampering/hindering integration of Almajiri schools in Niger state. Although all the factors on the instrument had the mean scores above the criterion mean score of 2.50, the learners/pupils perceived 'Food is not available for the Almajirai to concentrate on their work' and There is no available first aid and medical services to provide treatment for the sick Almajirai while in school both with mean scores of 3.68 as the highest determinant hampering integration of Almajiri schools in Niger state. This is followed by 'The Almajiri Schools lack adequate accommodation for conducive teaching and learning' with a mean of 3.64. However, there is the fear that government may assume the ownership of the Almajiri schools had the least mean score of 3.24. Based on the cluster mean score of 3.54, it was concluded that learners/pupils perceived generally that the factors had impact on the integration of Almajiri schools in Niger state.

Discussion of Findings

The findings in Table 1, 2 and 3 indicated that lack of food for the Almajirai to concentrate on their work was a major factor hampering integration of the Almajiri schools with highest mean scores for the responses of CBMC members, teachers/malams and learners or pupils as (3.78, 3.70 and 3.68) respectively. This finding was in agreement with the studies of Goodluck and Juliana (2017), Hamza (2009), Olutola, et al. (2020), and Yusha'u, et. al. (2013) which found that inadequate feeding of the Almajirai is responsible for their roaming about and begging for food. The finding on lack of adequate accommodation for conducive teaching and learning materials and non-availability of first aid and medical services to provide treatment for the sick Almajirai while in schools corroborated with the study findings of Ayuba (2009), Fahm, Azeez, Imam-Fulani, Mejabi, Faruk, Abdulrahman, and Surajudeen-Bakinde (2022), Isiaka (2015), Mohammed (2010), Teke, Khalid, and Katami (2022), and Suleman (2004) which posited that inadequate classroom accommodation have turned the Almajirai vulnerable to political thugs and child traffickers, as well as victims of insurgencies. Absence of classroom accommodation and parental care has also exposed the Almajirai to the risk of contagious diseases, dirty faces, crusty skin, and bare feet (Abdullahi, 2011; Idriss & Hamzah, 2021; Sule, 2014; and Yahaya, 2007). Consequently, the unfriendly and poor environmental nature of the Almajiri schools showed a reason why there is congestion or overcrowding and insecurity among them (Adetoro, 2010; Jimba (2021; Lawal, 2013; Mohammed, 2010; & Yusha'u, et al., 2013).

In another development, the finding of this study which indicated as factor the non-availability of first aid and medical services to provide medical services for the Almajirai while in school agreed with the study outcomes of Ali (2022), Teke, et

Factors Hindering the Effective Integration of... (Mohammed, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367966>

al. (2022); Odumosu, et al. (2013); and Yahaya (2007) which found that absence of required medical care for the Almajirai is responsible for their developmental challenges; including health hazards, exposure to contingencies and stress, insecurity, and truncated life. It is therefore expedient for government at all levels, civil societies, non-governmental organizations and individual philanthropists to extend humanitarian services to the Almajiri schools in order to fast-track measures toward combating their prevalence challenges.

Conclusion

The integration of Almajiri schools is a good step toward creating access to basic education. However, the challenges and obstacles involved in the policy are enormous. Hence, this study has delved into some of the impending issues that serve as hindrance for realizing the goals of the integration programme in Niger State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are hereby offered:

1. School feeding programme by government at all levels should be introduced in Almajiri schools to boost their interest and to facilitate their concentration on school work for better academic performance.
2. First Aid equipment should be provided at the Almajiri schools by the CBMC, Parents' Teachers' Association, and Non-Governmental associations to provide medical services in order to improve the environmental hygiene and safety of the schools.
3. Government, civil organizations or individuals should take the responsibility of providing affordable medical care and treatment for the sick Almajirai while in schools to guarantee their healthy conditions.
4. Building of classroom accommodations and provision of learning and recreational facilities should be made a priority through intervention funds from governments, international donors and community self-help projects to provide conducive teaching and learning environment at the Almajiri schools.
5. Adequate sensitization and enlightenment should be mounted to educate public and key stakeholders in education sector on the relevance of integrating the Almajiri schools into Basic Education programme to improve the level of public access to education.

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Impact of School Feeding Program and Teaching Methods on School Attendance among Junior Secondary School Students in Kebbi State

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Abstract

School attendance is a global phenomenon that merits consideration among various stakeholders owing to its importance in both human and economic development of any country. This study therefore, focused on the impact of School Feeding Program (SFP) and teaching method on school attendance among Junior Secondary school students in Kebbi state. Three research hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significant. Descriptive research design of expo facto type was used. Three hundred (300) students were randomly selected and formed the participants for the study, 30 each from the 10 randomly selected schools. Three research instruments were adapted and used in the study, they are, School feeding program (0.73), Teaching Method (0.87) and School Attendance scales (0.74). The result shows that the school feeding program, the teaching methods (visual, kinesthetic, and auditory elements), and student attendance are all combined ($R^2 = 30.18$, $F(4,295) = 0.69$, $p < .05$). The school feeding program and the visual, kinesthetic, and auditory components together accounted for 29% of the change in self-reported student attendance. This demonstrated that the school feeding program, together with the visual, kinesthetic, and auditory components, have a significant impact on student attendance. Additionally, only the school feeding program ($\beta = .54$, $t = 10.86$, $p < .05$) was found to be a significant independent predictor of school attendance, while the visual ($\beta = -.02$, $t = -0.31$, $p > .05$), kinesthetic ($\beta = -.01$, $t = -0.16$, $p > .05$), and audio ($\beta = -.07$, $t = -1.109$) methods of teaching were found to be significant independent predictors. $p > .05$. The findings of this study have established that school feeding programs has a significant positive impact on school attendance. Additionally, it has been observed that teaching method has a significant positive relationship on student attendance. It was recommended that, government should consider the sustainability of school feeding program particularly at the basic level. Teachers should use interactive teaching methods such as group discussions, problem-solving method, and hands-on activities to make learning more interesting and engaging.

Keywords: school feeding program, teaching method, school attendance.

Introduction

Student absenteeism is a global phenomenon that merits consideration among various educational stakeholders. According to Freire (2018), education and school attendance serve to promote cultural/political freedom and societal reform. The teaching of skills for students to develop and implement a particular societal norm, the promotion of ethical values, and the development of students' independence ought to be the primary focuses. This is very much represented by humanistic instructional methods of reasoning, for example, the secret educational program, which is fundamental the conventional educational program, considers moral way of behaving and creating qualities like legitimate group working abilities (Martimianakis & Hafferty, 2016).

The implementation of moral, cultural, and behavioral change is significantly influenced by these secondary school education concepts. The transition from the 6-5-4 system of education to the 6-3-3-4 system of education in 1998 has a significant impact on a child's physical and mental development, demonstrating that secondary education is vital to Nigerian higher education. A child can attend primary school for six years, junior secondary school for three years, and senior secondary

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school for three years, and tertiary education for four years under the 6-3-3-4 system. Simply put, the National Policy on Education must be consulted whenever a discussion of the significance of secondary education in Nigeria is initiated. Section 5 of the national policy on education does, however, highlight a portion of the significance of secondary education in Nigeria. This goes a long way toward demonstrating the significance of secondary education in Nigeria from the stage of policy formulation. In addition, it is ideal to take into consideration the enduring significance of secondary education in Nigeria.

1. Give more junior secondary school students, regardless of social, religious, or ethnic background, the chance to pursue higher education.
2. A diversified curriculum to accommodate students' varying talents, opportunities, and roles after secondary school.
3. Provide students with the tools they need to thrive in today's technologically advanced society.
4. Promote Nigerian culture, language, and art, as well as the global cultural heritage.
5. Raise an age of individuals who can have an independent perspective, regard the sensations of others, regard the poise of work, and value those values determined under our expansive public points, and live as one resident.
6. Cultivate Nigerian solidarity with an accentuation on the normal lines that joins us.
7. Inspire students to strive for success and personal growth, both in school and later in life.

In particular, the educational statistics report that was published in 2018 by the National Bureau of Statistics revealed that 1,051,670 students attend private junior secondary schools while 4,787,317 students attend public junior secondary schools. In addition, the report revealed that 911,561 students attend private senior secondary schools and 4,475,309 students attend public senior secondary schools. These numbers were all higher than those recorded in 2015. This shows that auxiliary school training in Nigeria is setting aside more space for additional members. Notably is the fact that these schools are dispersed throughout various communities in Nigeria, providing everyone with equal opportunities. According to available evidence, junior secondary attendance rates in Nigeria are sluggish and somewhat inconsistent. The profile of junior optional school training in Nigeria uncovers that school participation has generally expanding over the course of the years with the most noteworthy development pace of 219.64 percent in 1997 and the least development rate Public Department of Measurements in 2004. However, Nigeria's secondary school attendance changed significantly between 1995 and 2004. This is primarily because of the political crisis, unrest, agricultural conflict, and industrial dispute that occurred during these times. Despite the government's commitment over time to encourage education at all levels through a variety of policy interventions and school feeding programs, school attendance rates for children of school age remain extremely low. Aside from this, documentary evidence of the impact of education on junior secondary school attendance is still very low, particularly in the northern region of Kebbi State. This is due to parents' low literacy levels and lack of awareness of the importance of school attendance; however, rather than encouraging their children to attend school regularly, they engage their children in activities such as farming, fishing, cattle rearing, trading, hawking, and apprenticeships when they are school-age. The majority of children drop out of school early, after primary education, according to other studies. The government has devised a strategy to halt this trend by implementing a school feeding program (SFP) to raise junior secondary school attendance indices. The School Feeding Program is a crucial initiative that has been implemented in a number of developed and developing nations to combat hunger, improve student performance, and increase attendance at school. Adelman, Gilligan, and Lehrer, (2008), concluded that 40% of hungry children in developing countries attend school each day. As a result, providing school meals is detrimental to children's nutrition. Instead of keeping their children at home to work or to care for siblings and engage them in other activities like agriculture, farming, hawking, and fishing, parents are encouraged to send them to school. Poverty and hunger have prevented many children from attending school. In addition, these kids are more likely to drop out of school for the reason that they have to take care of their direct needs for survival before they can prepare for school. As a result, stumpy school appearance, low lesson attendance, and high school dropouts are frequent issues in the education of children from poor homes, particularly in regions with high levels of food insecurity. Even though both private and social returns to education are acknowledged to be high, the level of education achievement has also been stumpy in many emergent nations (Gilligan, 2008). However, it is undisputed that in poor families, in addition to hunger, other forms of poverty also affect school attendance.

The essential goal of the SFP is to diminish hunger among younger students. According to the World Food Report, it is also predictable that school attendance, peer friendship, retention, and completion rates will rise, particularly among children living in poor rural and urban neighborhoods. It improves students' comprehension and learning abilities while also improving the nutritional status of schoolchildren. In order to ensure that every child in Nigeria has access to free, compulsory, and universal basic education, the FGN implemented the SFP. A total of 2.5 million children, or 10% of the population, are expected to participate in the program that aims to provide every child in Nigerian schools with one meal per day. In addition to encouraging local food production and increasing farmers' incomes, the program increased school attendance, particularly

Impact of School Feeding Program ... (Ibrahim & Abdulsalam) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8368564>

among rural and poor urban children. The School Feeding Program was established in the 1930s in the United Kingdom and the United States with the clear intention of enhancing children's development (Richter, Griesel, & Rose, 2000). Baker, Elwood, Jones, Hughes, and Sweetnam (1997), emphasized that it was a program in the UK that provided free milk to schoolchildren began in 1934.

World Food Report describes the organized School Feeding Programme as a program that aids in community development, education, and health while also reducing hunger. If students regularly attended school, school feeding can be provided in the form of meals or snacks to be consumed during school hours or distributed as dry take-home food rations at the end of each day, month, or school term (Uwameiye & Salami, 2013). According to Uwameiye & Salami (2013), it serves as a platform for supporting children and their families in a variety of contexts. The provision of high-quality and sufficient educational facilities for adolescents is one of the pillars upon which a nation is constructed. People's lives are shaped into political leaders, scientists, economists, artists, and free thinkers through education (Food and Agriculture Organization and World Food Program, 2013). Many nations attempting to achieve the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) have prioritized ensuring that all children have access to primary education. That was declared by the World Bank in 1999; People live a little better when you give them a hand or a tool, and when you give them an education, they can change the world. As of now, instruction is the basic right of each and every individual because of its commitment, value, variety and enduring harmony (World Training Gathering, 2000).

The Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) initiative and subsequent conferences by African leaders aimed to address issues such as peace, security, good economic, political, and corporate governance and to make the continent an appealing destination for foreign investment are credited with the introduction of school feeding in Africa. The "New Partnership for African Development" is one of these developments. According to the plan, it is a promise made by African leaders to eliminate poverty, put their countries on the path to sustainable growth and development, and actively participate in the global economy and politics. Additionally, initiatives such as the Millennium Hunger Task Force and the Comprehensive African Agriculture Development Program were intended to link school feeding to agricultural development through the purchase and utilization of locally produced food (Bundy, D., Burbano, C., Grosh, M., Gelli, A. M., Jukes, C.H., and Drake, L.J.2009). One of the nations where hunger has hampered child education significantly is Nigeria. The country has had a very high rate of poverty in the past, and it was recently dubbed the poverty capital of the world (World Poverty Clock, 2019). Most of the poverty is severe in rural areas. Due to their low income, families in these areas typically have trouble sending their children to school. As a result, in order for families to survive, even children need to participate in some kind of activity. As a result, many children of primary and junior secondary school age in food-insecure areas do not attend school. Then again, regardless of whether tutoring is for nothing, families in such regions actually don't possess the ability to take care of certain expenses concerning books, garments, shoes or transportation. These restrictions also prevent children from attending school, encouraging them instead to stay at home and assist their parents with household chores. Therefore, investments in education must target households as well as children in order to address these issues. With the assistance of UNICEF and the New Partnership for Africa's Development (NEPAD), Nigeria was able to implement the school feeding program in 2005 as one of the 12 pilot countries invited by the Africa Agriculture Development Program (AADP) to do so. As a result, three billion naira was set aside for the program's pilot phase. The program was intended for 3.5 million students attending public primary schools in 12 Nigerian states. Tragically, the program never went past the primary stage. From the 12 states that participated in the program, only Osun and Kano remained shortly after its inception (National Home-Grown School Feeding Program, 2017). While the Participating States are to blame for the non-remittance of counterpart funds, which is a condition for the disbursement of school feeding grants to States, the States blame the UBEC for not releasing funds to the pilot States when due. Regardless of the circumstance, Osun State has maintained the school feeding program up to this point, as Kano State did as well when the federal funding ended in 2008 (Jumare, 2020).

The old school feeding program was the subject of a comprehensive evaluation by the Kebbi State Government in 2015. According to Kebbi State Ministry of Education (2018), the Program was repackaged and officially launched in the State in 2015 with students in Public Primary Schools in Grades 1-3. After seven months, in June, 2016 the Central Government re-dined the program from one side of the country to the other, the program started with 12 states and expanded to 14 states, 22 states, 24 states, and 26 states from the Federation by 2019. The goal is to provide all primary school students in Nigeria with one meal per day with the goals of improving students' health, increasing attendance, encouraging retention, and improving performance. Cited in Jumare, 2020) On January 18, 2016, Governor Atiku Bagudu of Kebbi State flagged off the official start of the free school feeding program at Zannan Gwandu secondary School, Birnin Kebbi local government area of the state. The governor made it clear that the free school feeding program was going to be one of the other benefits of providing education

Impact of School Feeding Program ... (Ibrahim & Abdulsalam) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8368564>

and ensuring that every child has access to basic nine years of free education regardless of whether or not his or her parents are financially able. The state's governor also declared free education and free food for junior secondary school students in addition to declaring a state of emergency in the educational sector. This exceptional demonstration added to the expansion in school participation of junior optional school understudies' administration schools (Vanguard News, 2016). However, the Kebbi State Government's School Feeding Program has been the subject of numerous studies. Only a few studies have looked at its effect on attendance, and none of them have combined the impact of SFP and teaching methods on school attendance among junior secondary schools. Subsequently, this study endeavored to fill the gap observed

Education is officially free and compulsory for every child, particularly at the junior secondary stage. The students at this stage were trained to obtain the proficiency that will set them up for a higher degree of schooling. But there is a problem of low attendance especially, in the north-western geopolitical zone of Nigeria in which Kebbi state is inclusive. The north-western states generally and Kebbi state in particular have net attendance rates of 47.7 percent and 29.3 percent, respectively. This indicated that more than half of the children in the region and the state are not in school (UNICEF report, 2021). The education deprivation in Kebbi state is driven by various factors, including economic barriers and socio-cultural norms and practices that discourage attendance in formal education.

Perhaps, Students who attend school regularly have been shown to achieve higher levels in academic attainment than those students who do not have regular attendance. Also, when students attend their classes daily that will install in them the basic value of attending all important event on time. Students, who maintain good attendance, tend to get best in various opportunities that come their way. However, there are several reasons that make some students not attend their classes regularly which could be on health background, economic circumstances, family issues, peer group influence, teachers' poor parental socio-economic status and many more. All of these factors often contribute to the reasons why some students may no longer attend schools regularly and some may eventually drop out totally from schools. Students who missed their classes regularly do not get lucrative career opportunities, and some even turn to a life of crime and even substance abuse as established in many research findings.

To improve school attendance, government introduced school feeding program, the central objective of the program according to Lawal (2011) is to improve school attendance of junior secondary school students in Nigeria and reduce the current dropout rates from junior secondary school, which was estimated to reach 30%. The program also seeks to address the poor nutrition and health status of many children who have been affected as a result of poverty, which has affected the learning outcomes of the children. The Federal Government spent 4.5 billion naira in 2020/21 and 6 billion naira in 2021/22 on school feeding programme. Kebbi State received a total of N499, 985,500 out of which all the junior secondary schools across 21 LGAs in the State were fed (Kebbi State Ministry of Education, 2019). Upon this budgetary allocation, the school attendance is still fall below average, especially at the junior secondary school level

In addition, teaching method is also one of the factors that can affect school attendance. Students will be encouraged to attend school because of good teaching methods of their teachers. Considering the fact that teaching method helps students achieve their learning goals, increases student engagement in the classroom, enhances the quality of feedback to students, improves school relationship with families. Considering the relevance and important of teaching methods in improving school attendance there is need for improvement in budgetary allocation to train and re-train teachers in order to improve on their teaching pedagogy, via in-service training, seminar, conferences and workshops. However, many studies have been conducted on school feeding programs and its impact on attendance, retention, and academic performance. But very little or none have been conducted on comparing feeding programs and teaching methods in Kebbi State. This study aims to fill the observed, by comparing feeding programs and teaching methods. It is against this background that the present study investigated the impact of feeding programs and teaching methods on junior secondary school attendance in Kebbi State.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to investigate the impact of school feeding program and teaching method on junior secondary school students' attendance in Kebbi State. Specifically, the study tends to:

1. Investigate the extent to which SFP influences attendance of junior school students in Kebbi State
2. Examine the extent to which teaching methods influence students' attendance in school.
3. Assess the extent to which school feeding programme affects School attendance in Kebbi State

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant influence of school feeding program on Students' attendance rate in Kebbi State.
2. There is no significant influence of teaching method on Students 'attendance rate in Kebbi State.
3. The School Feeding Program and teaching Method has no significant influence on Students' attendance.

Impact of School Feeding Program ... (Ibrahim & Abdulsalam) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8368564>

Methodology

The study used the descriptive research design of expo facto type. However, this design examines the relationship between a dependent variable and an independent variable (groups of participants who already possess certain characteristics prior to the study). The population of this study comprised of all junior secondary school students in Kebbi State. According to Kebbi State Secondary school management board SSMB, (2022), Kebbi State has 323 junior secondary schools with 74,936 students as at the time of this study. Simple random sampling was used to select 10 Junior Secondary Schools. Fifteen (15) students were selected randomly from each of the 10 selected Schools, making total number of samples to be 300.

Three standardized instruments were utilized for the study. These include; School Feeding Program Scale by Akodu, Patrick and Ayodele, (2019).; Teaching Method Scale by Hurriyetoglu, and Kilicoglu, (2020); School Attendance Scale by Yansong Wang and Ichiko Shoji, (2019). The instrument used to measure the participants' perception on school feeding program was a school feeding program instrument developed by Akodu, Patrick and ayodele, (2019). This instrument was adopted and has ten items using a Likert scale of 1 to 5 where 5= strongly agree, 4 = agree, 3 = neutral, 2 = disagree, and 1 = strongly disagree with Cronbach alpha of 0.73. Teaching method of participants was measured by adapted teaching method scale which was developed by Hurriyetoglu, and Kilicoglu, (2020). This instrument has fourteen (14) items, with three (3) factors, consisting of visual, auditory and Kinesthetic /tactile categories where visual consist of 6 items, auditory have 5 items and 3 items under kinesthetic. The Cronbach alpha of 0.70 and it has a reliability coefficient scale of 0.87 and the reliability coefficient for the sub factors are 0.816 for visuality, 0.760 for auditory and 0.646 for kinesthetic, using a Likert scale of 1 to 5 where 5= strongly agree, 4 = agree, 3 = neutral, 2 = disagree, and 1 = strongly disagree. A test retest was carried out using pilot testing method on 15 students who were not part of the participants and has a Cronbach Alfa of 0.73. The instrument used to measure the participants' view on school attendance was an adapted school attendance scale which was developed by Yansong Wang and Ichiko Shoji, (2019). This instrument comprised twenty-four (24) items, the scale has a total of three (4) factors, consisting of School attraction, Norm, External Pressure and Habit categories. The Cronbach alpha of 0.74 and it has a reliability coefficient scale of 0.832 and the reliability coefficient for the sub factors are 0.80 for school attraction, 0.74 for Norm, 0.75 External pressure and 0.646 for Habit categories, with scoring format of a Likert scale of 1 to 5 where 5= strongly agree, 4 = agree, 3 = neutral, 2 = disagree, and 1 = strongly disagree.

The researches with the assistant of other trained research assistance physically went round all the selected schools and administered the questionnaire on the participants; high rate of return was recorded. Data generated for the study were analyzed using frequency statistical method and linear Regression Analysis

Results

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant influence of school feeding program on Students' attendance rate in Kebbi State.

Table 1: Linear Regression Analysis Showing the Influence of School Feeding Program on Student Attendance

Predictors	B	SEb	B	T	R	R ²	F	P
Constant	33.524	1.851						
School Feeding			.53	10.83	.53	.282	117.25	<.05

Dependent Variable: School Attendance

It was revealed that School Feeding Program has a positive significant influence on Students' attendance rate given the Beta and P value scores to be (B = .531, P = .001). Furthermore, School Feeding Program is responsible for 28.2% variance in Students' attendance (R square = .282). at such we reject the hypothesis which state that "The School Feeding Program has no significant effect on Students' attendance rate in Kebbi State".

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant influence of teaching method on Students' attendance rate in Kebbi State.

Impact of School Feeding Program ... (Ibrahim & Abdulsalam) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8368564>

Table 2: Multiple Regression Analysis Showing the Influence of visual, kinesthetics, and audio on Student Attendance

Predictors	B	SEb	B	T	R	R ²	F	P
(Constant)	53.715	1.959						
Visual	.044	.102	.029	.426				
Kinesthetic	.089	.117	.059	.764	.083	.007	0.69	>.05
Audio	-.109	.076	-.112	-1.438				

Dependent Variable: School Attendance

The result revealed that visual, kinesthetics, and audio did not have joint influence on Student Attendance ($R^2 = 0.01$, $F(3,296) = 0.69$, $p > .05$). When combined, visual, kinesthetics, and audio for accounted for 1% of the change observed in the self-report of student Attendance. This revealed that the collective presence of visual, kinesthetics, and audio did not have significant influence on Student Attendance. The result further revealed that visual method of teaching ($\beta = .03$, $t=0.43$ $p > .05$), Kinesthetic ($\beta = .06$, $t=0.76$ $p > .05$) and Audio method of teaching ($\beta = -.11$, $t=-1.44$ $p > .05$) were not significant independent predictors of student attendance. The hypothesis is thus accepted.

Hypothesis 3

The School Feeding Program and teaching Method has no significant influence on Students' attendance rate in Kebbi State.

Table3: Summary of Multiple Regression Analysis Showing the Influence of visual, kinesthetic, audio and School feeding program on Student Attendance.

Predictors	B	SEb	B	T	R	R ²	F	P
(Constant)	35.932	2.331						
Visual	-.027	.087	-.018	-.306				
Kinesthetic	-.016	.100	-.011	-.159	.54	.29	30.18	<.05
Audio	-.072	.065	-.073	-1.109				
School feeding program	.635	.058	.538	10.856				

Dependent Variable: School Attendance

The result revealed that visual, kinesthetic, audio and school feeding program have joint influence on Student Attendance ($R^2 = 30.18$, $F(4,295) = 0.69$, $p < .05$). When combined visual, kinesthetic, audio and school feeding program for accounted for 29% of the change observed in the self-report of student Attendance. This revealed that the collective presence of visual, kinesthetic, audio and school feeding program have significant influence on Student Attendance. The result further revealed that only school feeding program ($\beta = .54$, $t=10.86$ $p < .05$) have significant independent predictor on school attendance while visual ($\beta = -.02$, $t=-0.31$ $p > .05$), kinesthetic ($\beta = -.01$, $t=-0.16$ $p > .05$) and Audio method of teaching ($\beta = -.07$ $t=-1.109$; $p > .05$) were not significant independent predictors of student attendance. As such we refute the hypothesis which states that "The School Feeding Program and teaching Method has no significant effect on Students' attendance rate in Kebbi State".

Discussion of findings

This study aims to investigate the impact of the school feeding program and teaching method on junior secondary school attendance in Kebbi State. The first hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference between school feeding program and Students' attendance rate in Kebbi State, was confirmed by the results, which showed that the school feeding program has a significant positive impact on the attendance rate of students in Kebbi State, the hypothesis is therefore rejected and alternative hypothesis was accepted that there is significant difference between school feeding program and attendance. The result of this finding is in line findings of Elijah Yendaw and Frederick (2015), which established positive impact of school feeding on attendance among school going children in Ghana. They emphasized that one of the social interference programs established to raise educational values in rural Ghanaian communities is the Ghana School Feeding Programme (GSFP). The principal objective of the program is to sharpen guardians on advantage of school participation, further develop participation, make junior optional school understudies stay in schools and to work on the healthful admission of kids in both rustic and metropolitan regions. Since 2005, the Nyoglo community in the Savelugu-Nantong Municipality, which had the lowest rates of student attendance and retention, has benefited from this social intervention.

The second hypothesis stated that there is no significant difference between teaching method and Students' attendance rate in Kebbi State. The result however confirmed that there is significant difference between teaching method and school

Impact of School Feeding Program ... (Ibrahim & Abdulsalam) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8368564>

attendance, therefore, the hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. The findings of this study is against the resolutions of Enamiroro's (2010) research, which sought to determine the average percentage of students who attended school, their academic performance, and the relationship between attendance and academic performance in secondary schools, the findings showed that the teaching method did not have a significant impact on students' attendance. An agenda was utilized to gather 2860 understudies' rate scores in participation and scholastic execution from 58 optional schools, utilized in this review. Using a percentage mean and a linear regression equation, three research questions were answered. Two speculations were formed and tried utilizing Pearson r. That's what the review uncovered; the mean score for attendance was 68%, and the mean score for academic performance was 66%. Additionally, it demonstrated a moderately positive relationship between academic performance and attendance. The coefficient of determination, $r^2 = 0.22$, indicated that attendance at secondary schools in Delta State, Nigeria, influenced the academic performance of 22% of students, (Enamiroro, 2010).

The third hypothesis stated that the School Feeding Program and teaching Method has no significant effect on Students' attendance rate in Kebbi State. The results therefore confirmed and established a positive relationship between school feeding program, teaching method and school attendance. This is in line with conclusion of Shabani (2018), who assessed the impact of the SFP on the academic performance of students in Mlunduzi ward, Tanzania, it was discovered that the combination of the teaching method and the school feeding program has a significant impact on the school enrolment. The cross-sectional review configuration was utilized for this review. The nature of this study was both qualitative and quantitative. In order to gather data on the impact, a survey was sent to 96 students from four primary schools in the Mlunduzi ward that were chosen at random.

Conclusion

The findings of this study demonstrated that the school feeding program has a significant and positive impact on student attendance. As stated by other studies, despite some studies indicating an increase in the number of meals served, numerous studies have demonstrated the program's positive impact on attendance. Additionally, it has been observed that teaching method has a significant impact on student attendance because students have a greater tendency to look forward to not missing class in the future when they learn and feel at ease with the format or lecture.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The study, recommends that government and other stakeholders in-charge of SFP should remain committed towards the provision of necessary resources for the smooth running of the programme so as to improve the educational infrastructure of rural communities.
2. Government should consider the sustainability of the school feeding program that provides nutritious meals to students. This program can help to improve attendance by addressing the issue of hunger and malnutrition among students. When students have access to healthy and nutritious food, they are more likely to attend school regularly and perform better academically.
3. Effective teaching methods are essential for keeping students engaged and interested in learning. Teachers should use interactive teaching methods such as group discussions, problem-solving exercises, and hands-on activities to make learning more interesting and engaging. This will help to keep students motivated to attend school and participate in classroom activities.
4. Parents and community members can play a vital role in promoting regular attendance among junior secondary school students. Schools should involve parents and community members in school activities and encourage them to take an active role in supporting their children's education. This can include attending parent-teacher conferences, volunteering at school events, and advocating for education in the community.

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Islamic Mutual Financial Assistance (*Takaful*): Benefits and Challenges of the Association of Model Islamic Schools (AMIS), Taraba State Chapter

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Abstract

This paper discusses Islamic mutual financial assistance (*Takaful*): benefits and challenges of the Association of Model Islamic Schools (AMIS), Taraba State Chapter, and how it helps in wealth creation. Most Islamic scholars opined that conventional insurance is unacceptable in Islam because it does not conform to *shari'ah*, for it has some element of uncertainty *al-gharar*. Conventional insurance is based on the concept and practice of charging interest. It is common knowledge among the Muslim society that *riba* interest is something abhorrent in Islam and there is no doubt that the loan facilities available in conventional banks are not meeting the required motives of Muslims as the facilities are surrounded with interest. This paper therefore brings to light the significance of mutual financial assistance among AMIS members which is devoid of interest and its benefits of wealth creation. This is in line with the Islamic principles of (*ta awanu alal-birri*), as enshrined in the Qur'an and Sunnah. The paper concludes that mutual assistance among AMIS Members helps in wealth creation and sustainable economic development. The paper recommends that Muslim organizations, groups and individuals should embrace this spirit of mutual financial assistance by pooling their resources to create wealth.

Keywords: *Takaful*, Practice, Wealth Creation, Sustainable Development.

Introduction

Takaful (التكافل) originates from Arabic word, "*Kafalah*" which means "guaranteeing each other" or joint guarantee". Technically, the concept of *Takaful* in the area of insurance means mutual assurance or guarantee amongst the members of a group. It is basically the pooling of resources to assist brethren who are in need. It is also seen as a mutual agreement between two parties for a mutual cooperation in protecting one's life or property from any unprotected or unavoidable risk, danger or tragedy (Musa A, 2014:24). In other word *takaful* is a co-operative system of re-imbursment or repayment in case of loss, paid to people and companies. It is concerned with mutual assistance among members, who are faced with hazard; from a fund manage by a *takaful* operator (Musa, 2014). It is commonly defined as an Islamic insurance concept which is grounded in Islamic *mu'amalat* (Islamic activities), observing the rules and regulations of Islamic law. Eventually, a number of models of *takaful* have been formulated overtime, namely *mudarabah*, modified *mudarabah*, *wakalah* and *wakalah-waqf*. There is no doubt that the system of *takaful* have recorded a lot of successes among it's operators around the globe. The recent re-emergences of *takaful* companies add up further to the rapid growth in *takaful* operators and funds.

Takaful in the Glorious Qur'an and Sunnah

Different portions in the Glorious Qur'an speak about *takaful* in the context of co-operation and solidarity for the good of society. One generally quoted reference is from *Surah Ma'idah*, where Allah the exalted says:

وَتَعَاوَنُوا عَلَى الْبِرِّ وَالتَّقْوَىٰ وَلَا تَعَاوَنُوا عَلَى الْإِثْمِ وَالْعُدْوَانِ وَاتَّقُوا اللَّهَ إِنَّ اللَّهَ شَدِيدُ الْعِقَابِ (2)

And help one another in righteousness and piety and do not help one another in evil deeds and enmity (Q.5: 2)

The above verse mentions the tradition of mutual assistance in Islam which enhances the spirit of co-operation in the Muslim society. Accordingly, the Madinan charter gave emphasis to the spirit of co-operation between the *Ansar* of Madina and the *Muhajirun* of Makkah, so much so that the mutual dealings among them looks like blood relative i.e. in accordance with the principles of recognized goodness, justice and mutual responsibility. In this regard, Allah the exalted says:

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وَالَّذِينَ تَبَوَّءُوا الدَّارَ وَالْإِيمَانَ مِنْ قَبْلِهِمْ يُحِبُّونَ مَنْ هَاجَرَ إِلَيْهِمْ وَلَا يَجِدُونَ فِي صُدُورِهِمْ حَاجَةً مِمَّا أُوتُوا وَيُؤْتُونَ عَلَى
أَنْفُسِهِمْ وَلَوْ كَانَ بِهِمْ خَصَاصَةٌ وَمَنْ يُوقِ شَحْنًا نَفْسِهِ فَأُولَئِكَ هُمُ الْمُفْلِحُونَ (9)

But those who before them had homes (in Madina) and had adopted the faith, show their affection to such as come to them for refuge, and entertain no desire in their hearts for things given to the (latter), but give them preference over themselves, even though poverty was their (own lot) and those saved from the covetousness of their own souls; they are the ones that achieve prosperity. (Q.59: 9)

Islam aims at establishing social order under universal brotherhood. The fundamental concept is that of mutual co-operation and help. The Prophet (SAW) is reported to have said in the following tradition:

حَدَّثَنَا مُحَمَّدُ بْنُ عَبْدِ اللَّهِ بْنِ نُمَيْرٍ، حَدَّثَنَا أَبِي، حَدَّثَنَا زَكَرِيَاءُ، عَنِ الشَّعْبِيِّ، عَنِ النُّعْمَانِ بْنِ بَشِيرٍ، قَالَ قَالَ رَسُولُ اللَّهِ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ " مَثَلُ
المُؤْمِنِينَ فِي تَوَادُّهِمْ وَتَرَاحُمِهِمْ وَتَعَاطُفِهِمْ مَثَلُ الْجَسَدِ إِذَا اشْتَكَى مِنْهُ عُضْوٌ تَدَاعَى لَهُ سَائِرُ الْجَسَدِ بِالسَّهَرِ وَالْحُمَى "

Nu'man b. Bashir reported Allah's Messenger (ﷺ) as saying: The similitude of believers in regard to mutual love, affection, fellow-feeling is that of one body; when any limb of it aches, the whole-body aches, because of sleeplessness and fever. (Sahih Muslim 2586, Book 45, Hadith 84)

Other relevant references to *Takaful* in the glorious Qur'an are as follows:

الَّذِي أَطْعَمَهُمْ مِنْ جُوعٍ وَأَمَّنَّهُمْ مِنْ خَوْفٍ (4)

(Allah) who prepares nourishment to prevent the fear of hunger and saves / puts at peace those who fear (Q. 106:4)

The verse shows that *takaful* is similar to a protection against any eventual calamity among the contributing members. Muslims are therefore like brothers in their dealings, one part is supporting the other part. As can be seen in the following Qur'anic statement:

إِنَّمَا الْمُؤْمِنُونَ إِخْوَةٌ فَأَصْلِحُوا بَيْنَ أَخَوَيْكُمْ وَاتَّقُوا اللَّهَ لَعَلَّكُمْ تُرْحَمُونَ (10)

The believers are but a single brotherhood: so make peace and reconciliation between your two (contending) brothers; and fear Allah, that you may receive mercy. (Q.49 10)

A fellow Muslim is always supporting his fellow Muslim. He should neither commit oppression upon him, nor ruin him. And he who meets the needs of a brother, Allah would meet his needs and he who relieves his brother from hardship, Allah will relieve him from the hardships to which he could be put on the Day of Resurrection. This is authentically reported in the following Prophetic tradition:

عَنْ أَبِي هُرَيْرَةَ قَالَ قَالَ رَسُولُ اللَّهِ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ مَنْ نَفَسَ عَنْ مُؤْمِنٍ كُرْبَةً مِنْ كُرْبِ الدُّنْيَا نَفَسَ اللَّهُ عَنْهُ كُرْبَةً مِنْ كُرْبِ يَوْمِ الْقِيَامَةِ وَمَنْ
يَسَّرَ عَلَى مُعْسِرٍ يَسَّرَ اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ فِي الدُّنْيَا وَالْآخِرَةِ وَمَنْ سَتَرَ مُسْلِمًا سَتَرَهُ اللَّهُ فِي الدُّنْيَا وَالْآخِرَةِ وَاللَّهُ فِي عَوْنِ الْعَبْدِ مَا كَانَ الْعَبْدُ فِي عَوْنِ أَخِيهِ
وَمَنْ سَلَكَ طَرِيقًا يَلْتَمِسُ فِيهِ عِلْمًا سَهَّلَ اللَّهُ لَهُ بِهِ طَرِيقًا إِلَى الْجَنَّةِ وَمَا اجْتَمَعَ قَوْمٌ فِي بَيْتٍ مِنْ بُيُوتِ اللَّهِ يَتْلُونَ كِتَابَ اللَّهِ وَيَتَادَرَسُونَهُ بَيْنَهُمْ إِلَّا
نَزَلَتْ عَلَيْهِمُ السَّكِينَةُ وَغَشِيَتْهُمُ الرَّحْمَةُ وَحَفَّتْهُمُ الْمَلَائِكَةُ وَذَكَرَهُمُ اللَّهُ فِيمَنْ عِنْدَهُ وَمَنْ بَطَأَ بِهِ عَمَلُهُ لَمْ يُسْرَعْ بِهِ نَسِيهِ
صحيح مسلم كتاب الذكر والدعاء والتوبة والاستغفار باب فضل الاجتماع على تلاوة القرآن وعلى الذكر 2699

On the authority of Abu Huraira (May Allah be pleased with him) from the Prophet (SAW) who said, " Whoever relieves a believer's distress of the distressful aspects of this world, Allah will rescue him from a difficulty of the difficulties of the Hereafter. Whoever alleviates [the situation of] one in dire straits who cannot repay his debt, Allah will alleviate his lot in both this world and in the Hereafter. Whoever conceals [the faults of] a Muslim, Allah will conceal [his faults] in this life and the Hereafter. Allah is helping the servant as long as the servant is helping his brother. (Muslim, Kitab alBirr, Book 32, No.6250)

This tradition of the Prophet, (SAW), shows that Allah rewards His servants in a manner similar to the deeds that they perform. By cooperating and helping the Muslim in difficulty, Allah will surely help a person in return. This also shows what an ideal Islamic society should look like. It is a society in which its members help each other, support each other and encourage each other to do what is good.

Another relevant tradition which encourages *Takaful* is where the Prophet (SAW) is reported to have said:

عَنِ النُّعْمَانِ بْنِ بَشِيرٍ قَالَ قَالَ رَسُولُ اللَّهِ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ " مَثَلُ الْمُؤْمِنِينَ فِي تَوَادُّهِمْ وَتَرَاحُمِهِمْ وَتَعَاطُفِهِمْ مَثَلُ الْجَسَدِ إِذَا اشْتَكَى مِنْهُ عُضْوٌ
تَدَاعَى لَهُ سَائِرُ الْجَسَدِ بِالسَّهَرِ وَالْحُمَى "

صحيح البخاري كتاب الأدب باب رحمة الناس والبهائم 5665

صحيح مسلم كتاب البر والصلة والآداب باب تراحم المؤمنين وتعاطفهم وتعاضدهم 2586

Al-Nu'man ibn Bashir reported: The Messenger of Allah, (SAW), said, "The parable of the believers in their affection, mercy, and compassion for each other is that of a body. When any limb aches, the whole body

Islamic Mutual Financial Assistance ... (Abdullahi & Umar, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8368601>

reacts with sleeplessness and fever. ((Şaḥīḥ al-Bukhārī 6011, Şaḥīḥ Muslim 2586 Book 78, Hadith 42, book 73, hadith 40))

As part of the Prophet (SAW) is reported to have encourages *Takaful* through a person in difficulty where he said:

وَعَنْ أَبِي هُرَيْرَةَ - رَضِيَ اللَّهُ عَنْهُ - قَالَ: قَالَ رَسُولُ اللَّهِ - صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ - { مَنْ نَفَسَ عَنْ مُؤْمِنٍ كُرْبَةً مِنْ كُرْبِ الدُّنْيَا نَفَسَ اللَّهُ عَنْهُ كُرْبَةً مِنْ كُرْبِ يَوْمِ الْقِيَامَةِ . وَمَنْ يَسِّرْ عَلَى مُعْسِرٍ ، يَسِّرَ اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ فِي الدُّنْيَا وَالْآخِرَةِ . وَمَنْ سَتَرَ مُسْلِمًا ، سَتَرَهُ اللَّهُ فِي الدُّنْيَا وَالْآخِرَةِ . وَاللَّهُ فِي عَوْنِ الْعَبْدِ مَا كَانَ الْعَبْدُ فِي عَوْنِ أَخِيهِ } أَخْرَجَهُ مُسْلِمٌ .¹
¹ - صحيح. رواه مسلم (2699)، وتامامه: "ومن سلك طريقا يلتمس فيه علما، سهل الله به طريقا إلى الجنة، وما اجتمع قوم في بيت من بيوت الله، يتلون كتاب الله، ويتدارسونه بينهم، إلا نزلت عليهم السكينة، وغشيتهم الرحمة، وحفتهم الملائكة، وذكرهم الله فيمن عنده... ومن بطا به عمله، لم يسرع به نسبه."

Abu Hurairah (RAA) narrated that the Messenger of Allah (ﷺ) said: "If anyone relieves a Muslim believer from one of the hardships of this worldly life, Allah will relieve him of one of the hardships of the Day of Resurrection. If anyone makes it easy for the one who is indebted to him (while finding it difficult to repay), Allah will make it easy for him in this worldly life and in the Hereafter, and if anyone conceals the faults of a Muslim, Allah will conceal his faults in this world and in the Hereafter. Allah helps His slave as long as he helps his brother. (Muslim Book 16, Hadith 29)

It is also part of *takaful* to help the orphans and relates with them in kindness and compassion as can be seen in the following Qur'anic statement where Allah the Exalted says:

فِي الدُّنْيَا وَالْآخِرَةِ وَيَسْأَلُونَكَ عَنِ الْيَتَامَى قُلْ إِصْلَاحٌ لَهُمْ خَيْرٌ وَإِنْ تُخَالِطُوهُمْ فَإِحْوَانُكُمْ وَاللَّهُ يَعْلَمُ الْمُفْسِدَ مِنَ الْمَصْلِحِ وَلَوْ شَاءَ اللَّهُ لَأَعْتَبْتُمْ إِنْ اللَّهَ عَزِيزٌ حَكِيمٌ (220) ... (Their bearings) on this life and the hereafter they ask you concerning orphans. Say: the best thing to do is what is for their good; if you mix their affairs with yours, they are your brethren; but Allah knows the man who means mischief from the man who means good. And if Allah had wished He could have put you into difficulties: he is indeed exalted in power, wise. (Q.2:220) Additionally, Islam encourages the spirit of *takaful* in the form of goodness and serving ones' parents and relations:

وَاعْبُدُوا اللَّهَ وَلَا تُشْرِكُوا بِهِ شَيْئًا وَبِالْوَالِدَيْنِ إِحْسَانًا وَبِذِي الْقُرْبَى وَالْيَتَامَى وَالْمَسَاكِينِ وَالْجَارِ ذِي الْقُرْبَى وَالْجَارِ الْجُنُبِ وَالصَّاحِبِ بِالْجَنبِ وَابْنِ السَّبِيلِ وَمَا مَلَكَتْ أَيْمَانُكُمْ إِنْ اللَّهَ لَا يُحِبُّ مَنْ كَانَ مُخْتَالًا فَخُورًا (36)

Serve Allah and join not any partners with him and do good to parents, kinsfolk, orphans, those in need, neighbours who are near, neighbours who are strangers, the companion by your side, the wayfarer (you meet) and what your right hands possess: for Allah loves not the arrogant, the conceited (Q.4:36)

Equally important is (Q.3:103) which encourage the spirit of co-operation among the Muslim community. Allah the exalted says:

وَاعْتَصِمُوا بِحَبْلِ اللَّهِ جَمِيعًا وَلَا تَفَرَّقُوا وَاذْكُرُوا نِعْمَتَ اللَّهِ عَلَيْكُمْ إِذْ كُنْتُمْ أَعْدَاءً فَأَلَّفَ بَيْنَ قُلُوبِكُمْ فَأَصْبَحْتُمْ بِنِعْمَتِهِ إِخْوَانًا وَكُنْتُمْ عَلَى شَفَا حُفْرَةٍ مِنَ النَّارِ فَأَنْقَذَكُمْ مِنْهَا كَذَلِكَ يُبَيِّنُ اللَّهُ لَكُمْ آيَاتِهِ لَعَلَّكُمْ تَهْتَدُونَ (103)

And hold fast, all together, by the rope which Allah (stretches out for you), and be not divided among yourselves; and remember with gratitude Allah's favour on you; for you were enemies and He joined your hearts in love, so that by His grace you became brethren; and you were on the brink of the pit of fire, and he saved you from it thus does Allah make His signs clear to you; that you may be guided. (Q.3:103)

Similarly, another tradition shows that the place of relationships and feelings of people with faith, between each other, is just like the body; when one of its parts is afflicted with pain, then the rest of the body will be affected.

عَنْ أَبِي مُوسَى عَنِ النَّبِيِّ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ قَالَ إِنْ الْمُؤْمِنِينَ لِلْمُؤْمِنِينَ كَالْبُنْيَانِ يَشُدُّ بَعْضُهُم بَعْضًا وَشَبَّكَ أَصَابِعَهُمْ صَحِيحُ الْبُخَارِيِّ كِتَابُ الصَّلَاةِ أَبْوَابُ اسْتِقْبَالِ الْقِبْلَةِ بَابُ تَشْبِيكِ الْأَصَابِعِ فِي الْمَسْجِدِ وَغَيْرِهِ 467
صَحِيحُ مُسْلِمٍ كِتَابُ الْبِرِّ وَالصَّلَاةِ وَالْأَدَابِ بَابُ تَرَاحِمِ الْمُؤْمِنِينَ وَتَعَاطُفِهِمْ وَتَعَاذُهُمْ 2585

Abu Musa reported: The Messenger of Allah (SAW), said, "Verily, the believers are like a structure, each part strengthening the other," and the Prophet clasped his fingers together. (Bukhari Book 46, Hadith 7, Vol. 3, Book 43, Hadith 626)

Additionally, it was reported that the Prophet Muhammad (SAW) participated in the *takaful* fund organized for trade journey before the epoch of Islam. The incident happened when some business men in Makkah established a kind of common fund by pooling the resources from all participating members. This form of mutual fund was used to help the victims or survivors of natural hazards during their journey flying their commercial ventures. The Prophet (SAW), also traded with the capital provided by Khadijah (ra), contributed to such fund.

Benefits of *Takaful*

Through the spirit of co-operation and joint-responsibilities among people of common interest, the act of charity and benevolence allows participants the opportunity to obtain two forms of benefits. First the monetary benefits through the *takaful* plan. Secondly the “benefits” in the spiritual sense, through the act of *Tabarru'* (donation), more importantly participants will receive Allah's grace and blessings in this life and in the Hereafter. This is mention in the following prophetic tradition. Abu Huraira reported that the Messenger of Allah, (SAW), is reported to have said:

عَنْ أَبِي هُرَيْرَةَ قَالَ قَالَ رَسُولُ اللَّهِ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ مَا مِنْ
يَوْمٍ يُصْبِحُ الْعِبَادُ فِيهِ إِلَّا مَلَكَانِ يَنْزِلَانِ فَيَقُولُ أَحَدُهُمَا لِلَّهِمَّ أَعْطِ مُنْفِقًا خَلْفًا وَيَقُولُ الْآخَرُ لِلَّهِمَّ أَعْطِ مُمْسِكًا تَلْفًا

On the authority of Abu Hurairah (May Allah be Pleased with Him Who said), The Messenger of Allah (Peace be upon Him) said: There is not a day upon which the servant awakens but that two angels descend. One of them says: O Allah, give repayment to one who spends in charity! The other says: O Allah, give destruction to one who withholds charity! (Ṣaḥīḥ al-Bukhārī 1442, Ṣaḥīḥ Muslim 1010)

Management of *Takaful*

Five models are designed to manage *takaful*, thus:

- i) ***Takaful based on Wakalah Model:*** This is a system whereby an agent is given the power to manage the *takaful* products. Based on this principle, the model describes an agency agreement between the operators, acting as the agent or “wakil” to the participant as the principal to manage the participation of the latter in a variety of *takaful* products provided by the operator.
- ii) ***Takaful based on Mudharabah model:*** Basically, this system involves on profit and lost sharing between the capital provider and the manager of the capital..
- iii) ***Takaful based on Hybrid Model:*** This is a mixture of *wakala* and *Mudarraba* model. Under this model, a relationship between the operator which combines the role of entrepreneur or *Mudharib* as well as the agent or *wakil* of the participant, while the latter in the capacity as both provider of capital or *sahibul-mal* and principal to the agent.
- iv) ***Takaful based on Waqf Model:*** The term “*waqf*” referred for this model explains the contract of *takaful* that underlines the agreement or consent of the participants that the *takaful* contribution paid in return for participating in the *takaful* product to be credited by the operator into the *takaful* fund in accordance with the principle of *waqf* or endowment. In this case, a *waqf* account has to be established by the operator within the *takaful* fund. To this effect the operator is required to relinquish some kind of “seed” money as *waqf* to generate the said *waqf* account. This *waqf* account of the *takaful* fund will be invested similar to the three *takaful* models discussed earlier. (Saleh M. M, 2021:pp.97)
- v) ***Takaful based on Adashe Model:*** The term “*adashe*” referred for this model explains the contract of *takaful* that underlines the agreement or consent of the participants that the *takaful* contribution paid on monthly bases by family members, women groups, Religious organizations, Schools Association, farmers, civil servants e.t.c. and the amount realized will be given to one or two members in the group. In this case, an *adashe* account has to be established by the group where each member will pay at the end of every month.

Nature and Characteristics of *Takaful* in Taraba State

The nature of *takaful* in Taraba is basically on *Adashe* model where family members, women groups, religious organizations, schools Associations, farmers association, civil servants etc. However, there are few *takaful* companies in Jalingo such as *Alhuda*, *Al ta awun* etc. This paper therefore focuses on the Association of Model Islamic Schools (AMIS), Taraba State chapter. The paper therefore examines the nature and benefits of *Takaful* (Islamic insurance) mutual assistance among some proprietors of AMIS.

Association of Model Islamic Schools, (AMIS)

The Association of Model Islamic Schools, (AMIS) was established by the proprietors of private Islamic schools in Nigeria, with the following desire objectives: To exchange ideas and foster mutual cooperation among private Islamic Schools in Nigeria; to engage in the formulation and implementation of policies aimed at assisting in the development and general growth of member school and to serve as training ground for member schools through seminars, workshops and conferences (AMIS Constitution ND), PP. 4-5)

Takaful among Proprietors of AMIS in Jalingo, Taraba

The specific objective of Proprietors of these schools is to compliment the effort of government in the area of education, especially at the elementary level. Part of the challenges facing the proprietor of this type of school is that of funding. Looking at the financial challenges surrounding the general administration of their Schools, AMIS Jalingo branch came up with the idea of *Takaful* among its members.

The *Adashe* model of *Takaful* was adopted, which is characterized with monthly contributions from members. The main objective of establishing this *takaful* group is to organize a system of mutual assistance among members of AMIS in Jalingo, Taraba State whereby each proprietor contributes an agreed amount from monthly earning. The idea of this mutual assistance was prompted during the covid-19 pandemic when all the schools were closed down.

This mutual assistance started in October, 2020 with five members each contributed the sum of fifty thousand Naira (N50,000.00), only. Interestingly, from July, 2021, members agreed to increase the contribution to the sum of One hundred thousand Naira (N100,000).

This shows that at the initial contribution, a benefiting member collects the sum of N250,000, but when the contribution was increased to One hundred thousand Naira (N100,000), a benefiting member goes home with the sum of five hundred thousand Naira N500,000.00.

Benefit of Takaful to Proprietors of Model Islamic Schools in Jalingo

One of the most prominent features that distinguish the Muslim society from other societies is its mutual support, brotherhood and solidarity. This spirit of mutual cooperation and zeal to create wealth through lawful means is what prompted the Association of Model Islamic schools, Jalingo branch to initiate the idea of monthly contributions among its members. This mutual assistance which commenced in October, 2020 has yielded a lot of benefits to the members. The members who benefited outlined a number of projects carried out in their schools with the funds. Below is the result of the interview conducted to assess the benefits of this model of *takaful*.

Challenges of Takaful

In spite of the successes recorded and the benefits accrued through this mutual assistance among members of AMIS, there are however some challenges in its operation. From the interview conducted and the practical experience of the researcher who is a member, the following are recorded as some of the challenges facing these mutual contributions:

- i) Delay in payment of contribution by some members, which in most cases thwart the plans of a benefiting member. Due to the informal nature of this *takaful* and the fact that the contributing members sources of fund are mainly from school fees, hence delay in payment of fees will have direct effect on the contributions.
- ii) Competition in the contribution roster: Sometimes there are disagreements in the roster of benefiting member as to who will the first position.
- iii) Lack of financial discipline among members lead some members delay the payments.
- iv) Death of a member may also be challenge.

Conclusion

As a system of mutual assistance *takaful* remains a viable way for societal growth and development, since it is a system devoid of interest, a system where people cooperate in helping their brethren who are in financial difficulties and creates wealth in lawful ways. It is a common knowledge among Muslims that conventional insurance system is against the teachings of Islamic principles because of its' association with interest (*Riba*) and uncertainty (*Gharar*) Therefore *takaful* Islamic insurance and conventional insurance are diametrically opposed to each other in both substance and form because the former operates in an atmosphere devoid of interest (*Riba*), uncertainty (*Gharar*) and gambling (*Maysir*), the latter has at the very core of its embodiment, the presence of these anti-*Shari ah* features which are integral to the survival of its operations.

Consequently, given the Qur'anic injunctions to "cooperate and assist one another in goodness" and the traditions of the Prophet Muhammad (SAW) regarding mutual assistance, *Takaful* may be understood as an important ingredient in the societal development and an obligation upon Muslims community to put into practice.

Islamic Mutual Financial Assistance ... (Abdullahi & Umar, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8368601>

Recommendations

1. There should be effort from the AMIS members geared towards formalizing *takaful* so as to address some of the challenges arising from its' informal nature.
2. Since *takaful* practices are largely based on Islamic teachings of mutual assistance, Islamic organizations and groups like AMIS should embark on serious campaign to educate its members and general Muslims on the benefits associated with *takaful*.
3. Similarly, there should be concerted effort by Islamic scholars and *Ulama* to encourage the spirit of *takaful* among the people as the best way to resolve the economic recession among the Muslims.
4. Muslims organizations, groups and individuals should embrace this spirit of mutual assistance by pooling their resources to create wealth

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Lecturers' Perception on the Use of Schoology Web Application for Instruction in Colleges of Education in South-West, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examines lecturers' perception on the usefulness of schoology web application for instruction in Colleges of Education in South-west, Nigeria. The sample of the study consisted of 300 lecturers randomly selected from three colleges of education in South West, Nigeria. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The instrument used in the study was a self-developed questionnaire titled Lecturers' Perception on the Usefulness of Schoology Web Application Questionnaire (LPUSWAQ). The instrument was validated and the reliability coefficient of 0.87 was obtained. Two research questions and one research hypothesis were generated for the study. The findings revealed amongst others that; lecturers in college of education have positive perception on the usefulness of schoology web application for instruction with the mean rating of 2.82, using 2.45 as the decision rule. It was also revealed in the study that lecturers have positive perception on the ease of use of schoology web application for instruction with the mean rating of 2.78, using 2.45 as the decision rule. The study therefore recommends that schoology web application should be integrated into the teaching and learning in Colleges of Education in Nigeria. It was also recommended that college of education lecturers should further be encouraged to use schoology web application for instructions.

Keywords: perception, Schoology web application, college of education.

Introduction

The introduction of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) to teaching and learning has led to improving the innovative learning environment and the process of knowledge acquisition and dissemination at all levels of education. In many countries of the world, the use of technology has shifted the learning pattern from traditional methods of instructions to e-learning modes especially in teacher education programme.

E-learning or online learning refers to as the use of internet technologies to deliver a broad array of solutions that enhance knowledge and performance (Abidoye & Fakokunde 2015). This includes the use of ICT technology as a supplement to traditional classrooms. However, the persistence professional development practices in today's fast moving work place environment increasingly involve the use of modern technologies as part of the quest to provide a flexible and responsive learning experience. In an e-learning environment, a variety of tools and technologies are employed, for example, internet mediated teaching, web-based education, TV and radio broadcast, virtual classrooms and distributed learning. Online learning can be more flexible and often involves more technologies, for example, audio chatting, video conferencing and online discussion (Mahanani. (2013). E-learning provides additional opportunities for interactivity between students and tutors during content delivery (Abidoye & Fakokunde 2015).

In this digital era, there are many education-based and online learning or web applications that can be effectively used to make it easier for both students and teachers to access learning resources. One of such online learning or web application is Schoology. Yoshida, (2018) describes Schoology as a collaboration and learning tool and a web-based learning environment that will provide students, parents, and teachers with access to classroom materials and information via the internet. Also, Sicat (2015) defines schoology as a micro blog educational website that can be applied by teacher and students for collaborating about resources, assessment and content on a secure and safe learning management platform. With this web application, teachers can have greater opportunities to communicate broadly to students.

The use of Schoology web application has become increasingly popular in recent years, and educators are discovering many benefits it offers. One of the most significant benefits of Schoology is its ability to enhance communication between students and teachers (Rojabi 2019). Priyatno, (2017) also avers that the platform provides an easy way for teachers to post assignments, updates, and announcements, which students can access from any location with an internet connection. Sicat (2015) posits that with the existence of Schoology web application, students can download subject matter, slide presentations, video tutorials, games, work on assignments, exams, discussions, and assignments given by the teacher. Schoology can also be

Lecturers' Perception on the Use of Schoology Web ... (Alabi, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8368614>

used via a smart phone. Schoology provides teachers, teachers, students, and even students online collaboration in a friendly and secure environment to the user. Students can also ask questions, submit assignments, and receive feedback from their teachers within the platform (Basori, 2013). Manowong, (2016) reported that the use of schoology can develop in students ability to organize their learning effectively and get the best results. Aminoto and Pathoni (2014) also explained that Schoology web application is a website which combines e-learning and social media. They further expressed that it facilitates the teachers and students with many tools that can be utilized to do the learning process and to interact with each other like social media. Moreover, Juniarti (2014) also agrees that Schoology can provide teachers and learners to get involved in the interaction of learning environment like usual class. Furthermore, Mahanani (2013) expresses that with the use of Schoology web application the teacher can sharpen the mindset of students to think critically and creatively.

Perception is one of the factors affecting the use of technology in education especially in teaching and learning process. Obielodan, Amosa, Ala and Shehu (2019) describe perception as the process of explaining sensory impression into an integrated study of the world with the existing situations. Perception of lecturers towards the utilization of schoology web application for instruction can give some evidences about its relevance in instruction. Therefore, perceived usefulness of schoology application for instruction is the lecturers and other users believe in its importance in instruction while its ease of use implies the level of its stress free during utilization Manowong, (2016).

Gender is one of such factors mentioned in the literature to have considerable effects on the use of technology for teaching and learning. Aderale and abidoeye (2022), describe gender as the range of physical, biological, mental and behavioural characteristics pertaining to and differentiating between the feminine and masculine (female and male) population. The importance of examining performance in relation to gender is based primarily on the socio-cultural differences between girls and boys. Abidoeye and Abidoeye (2014) posits that differences existed in gender similarly in both online learning and conventional learning strategies. Hence, males are inquisitive, fully involved in questions, discussions, optimistic, and remain active participants, whereas females were more submissive.

However, the major challenge to the adoption of technology for instructions is the users' perception and commitment towards the integration of technology into the teaching-learning setting, thus this task could discourage the utilization among the users (Aderale and Abidoeye 2022). Therefore, this study examines lecturers' perception on the use of schoology web application for instruction in selected college of education in south-west, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of this paper is to examine lecturers' perception on the use of schoology web application for instruction in Colleges of Education in South-West, Nigeria. While the study focuses on the following specific objectives;

1. To examine lecturers' perception on the usefulness of Schoology web application in Colleges of Education in South-West, Nigeria.
2. To Investigate lecturers' perception on ease of use of Schoology web application for instruction in Colleges of Education in South-West, Nigeria.
3. To examine the relationship between male and female lecturers' perception on the ease of use of Schoology web application for instruction in Colleges of Education in South-West, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised and answered in the study:

1. What is the lecturers' perception on the usefulness of schoology web application in Colleges of Education?
2. What is the lecturers' perception on the ease of use of schoology web application for instruction in college of education?

Hypothesis

There is no significant difference between male and female lecturers' perception on the ease of use of schoology web application for instruction in college of education.

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study consisted all lecturers in the Colleges of Education in South-Western Nigeria. The sample population consisted of 300 participants randomly selected from three Federal Colleges of Education in the six states (Oyo, Ondo, Ogun, Osun, Ekiti and Lagos states) in South-West. 100 lecturers were randomly randomly selected in each of the sampled schools making a total of 300 participants. The instrument for this study was researcher' self-designed questionnaire titled 'Lecturers' Perception on the Usefulness of Schoology Web Application Questionnaire (LPUSWAQ). The instrument was divided into three sections A-C. Section A focuses on

Lecturers' Perception on the Use of Schoology Web ... (Alabi, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8368614>

demographic information covering the participants' gender, school and location. Section B consisted of twelve question items eliciting information on perception of lecturers on the usefulness of schoology web application for instruction. While section C consisted of 10 question item sought information on lecturers' perception on the ease of utilization of schoology web application for instruction for instruction. 4-point Likert Scale response modes: Strongly Agree (SA = 4), Agree (A = 3), Disagree (D = 2) and Strongly Disagree (SD = 1) was used. Two research questions and one hypothesis were answered and tested using mean scores and t-test statistical tools respectively.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the lecturers' perception on the usefulness of schoology web application in college of education?

Table 1: Perception on the Use of Schoology web application for Instruction in colleges of education

Item	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std. D
Schoology web application offers the opportunity to improve teaching.	45	90	90	75	2.35	1.01
Schoology web application makes teaching easier.	60	54	93	93	2.27	1.10
Schoology web application improves learning outcomes/examination scores.	56	75	64	105	2.27	1.12
Schoology web application provides learning anywhere and anytime	65	79	93	63	2.48	1.05
Schoology web application makes posting and sharing of course materials easy.	45	52	98	105	2.42	1.06
Schoology web application enhances monitoring and grading of students.	46	90	45	119	2.21	1.12
Schoology web application will make teachers lose control over the teaching and learning process.	69	56	38	137	2.19	1.23
Providing feedback in schoology web application environment is more time-consuming.	62	104	48	86	2.47	1.11
Schoology web application can be more time consuming than the traditional method.	89	69	64	78	2.56	1.16
Lack of Internet connectivity will affect schoology web application.	72	73	90	65	2.50	1.08
Schoology web application requires IT training.	76	77	67	80	2.49	1.13
The use of schoology web application for instruction is very difficult because it requires ICT knowledge and other special skills.	91	74	63	72	2.61	1.15
Weighted Average					2.41	

Key; SD = Strongly Disagree, D = Disagree, A = Agree, SA = Strongly Agree; **Decision Value:** Negative=0.00-2.44, Positive = 2.45-4.00

Table 1 shows the lecturers' perception on the usefulness of schoology web application for instruction in colleges of education. The table shows that the lecturers disagreed to the following items: Schoology web application offers the opportunity to improve teaching ($\bar{x} = 2.35$), Schoology web application makes teaching easier ($\bar{x} = 2.27$), Schoology web application improves learning outcomes/examination scores ($\bar{x} = 2.27$), Schoology web application makes posting and sharing of course materials easy ($\bar{x} = 2.42$), Schoology web application enhances monitoring and grading of students ($\bar{x} = 2.21$) and Schoology web application will make teachers lose control over the teaching and learning process ($\bar{x} = 2.19$). Furthermore, the table shows that the lecturers agreed to these: Schoology web application provides learning anywhere and anytime ($\bar{x} = 2.48$), providing feedback in schoology web application environment is more time-consuming ($\bar{x} = 2.47$), Schoology web application can be more time consuming than the traditional method ($\bar{x} = 2.56$), lack of Internet connectivity will affect schoology web application

Lecturers' Perception on the Use of Schoology Web ... (Alabi, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8368614>

($\bar{x} = 2.50$), Schoology web application requires IT training ($\bar{x} = 2.49$) and the use of schoology web application for instruction is very difficult because it requires ICT knowledge and other special skills ($\bar{x} = 2.61$). Meanwhile, based on the value of the weighted average (2.41 out of 4.00 maximum value obtainable) which falls, within the decision value for **negative**, it can be inferred that the lecturers' perception on the usefulness of schoology web application in tertiary institutions is negative.

Research Question 2

What is the lecturers' perception on the ease of use of schoology web application for instruction in college of education?

Table 2: Mean scores of **Lecturers' perception on the ease of use of Schoology web application for Instruction**

Item	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std.
I would find it easier to teach my students with schoology web application for instruction	63	76	11 3	48	2.51	.99
Schoology web application is easy to utilize for instruction	88	68	72	72	2.57	1.14
Schoology web application makes my teaching job better and faster	57	91	76	76	2.43	1.06
Schoology web application is user friendly	84	59	97	60	2.55	1.10
The flexibility of schoology web application would ensure speedy dissemination of information to students	45	106	76	73	2.41	1.01
With all the associated factors of internet facilities and poor network coverage, I would do all my best to integrate schoology web application for instruction	30	90	60	120	2.10	1.04
I will advocate for the use of schoology web application in education due to their relevance and convenience	46	119	74	61	2.50	.98
Schoology web application is quite understandable for teaching learning activities	48	85	94	73	2.36	1.02
It is easy to become skillful, if schoology web application is fully integrated	45	75	45	135	2.10	1.13
The use of schoology web application for instruction would enable me cover the course contents within the time frame of the college with ease	75	76	75	74	2.50	1.11
Weighted Average					2.40	

Key; *SD* = Strongly Disagree, *D* = Disagree, *A* = Agree, *SA* = Strongly Agree; **Decision Value:** *Negative*=0.00-2.44, *Positive* = 2.45-4.00

Table 2 shows the lecturers' perception on the ease of use of schoology web application for instruction in tertiary institutions. The table shows that the lecturers agreed to the following items: they would find it easier to teach their students with schoology web application for instruction ($\bar{x} = 2.51$), Schoology web application is easy to utilize for instruction ($\bar{x} = 2.57$), Schoology web application is user friendly ($\bar{x} = 2.55$), they would do all their best to integrate schoology web application for instruction ($\bar{x} = 2.50$) and the use of schoology web application for instruction would enable them cover the course contents within the time frame of the college with ease ($\bar{x} = 2.50$). Also, the table shows that the lecturers disagreed to the following: Schoology web application makes their teaching job better and faster ($\bar{x} = 2.43$), the flexibility of schoology web application would ensure speedy dissemination of information to students ($\bar{x} = 2.41$), with all the associated factors of internet facilities and poor network coverage, will advocate for the use of schoology web application in education due to their relevance and convenience ($\bar{x} = 2.10$), Schoology web application is quite understandable for teaching learning activities ($\bar{x} = 2.36$) and It is easy to become skillful, if schoology web application is fully integrated ($\bar{x} = 2.10$). Meanwhile, based on the value of the weighted average (2.40 out of 4.00 maximum value obtainable) which falls, within the decision value for **negative**, it can be inferred that the lecturers' perception on the ease of use of schoology web application for instruction in colleges of education is negative.

Research Hypothesis

There is no significant difference between male and female lecturers' perception on the ease of use of schoology web application for instruction in college of education.

Lecturers' Perception on the Use of Schoology Web ... (Alabi, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8368614>

Table 3: t-test Showing gender difference in lecturers' perception on the ease of use of schoology web application

Variable (Gender)	N	Mean	STD	Df	T	Sig.	Remark
Male	169	28.53	3.14				Significant
Female	131	26.01	2.90	298	4.315	.000	

Table 3 shows the difference in the perception of male and female lecturers on the ease of use of Schoology web application for instruction in college of education. The table shows that the mean score for male lecturers is 28.53 while that of female lecturers is 26.01. The values of the mean scores revealed an appreciable difference. Therefore, there is significant difference between male and female lecturers' perception on the ease of utilization of schoology web application for instruction in College of Education (df = 298; t = 4.315; p < 0.05). Hence, hypothesis 2 is not accepted. This result implies that the perception of male and female lecturers on the ease of use of Schoology learning platform for instruction is not the same.

Discussion of Findings

From research question one, it was revealed that lecturer's perception towards the usefulness of Schoology web application for instruction in Colleges of Education was negative. This might be due to the facts that majority of the lecturers have little knowledge or not aware of Schoology web application. This was also reflected in their responses. The lecturers strongly disagreed that they find it easier to teach their students with schoology web application for instruction, Schoology web application is easy to utilize for instruction, Schoology web application makes their teaching job better and faster, Schoology web application is user friendly, the flexibility of schoology web application would ensure speedy dissemination of information to students, with all the associated factors of internet facilities and poor network coverage, they would do all their best to integrate schoology web application for instruction, will advocate for the use of schoology web application in education due to their relevance and convenience, Schoology web application is quite understandable for teaching learning activities, It is easy to become skillful, if schoology web application is fully integrated, and the use of schoology web application for instruction would enable them cover the course contents within the time frame of the college with ease, always enjoy class when they use Schoology learning platform, always feel delight to use Schoology web application because it boost and give more intellectual knowledge while using and that Schoology web application is very easy to use. Schoology as one of the online learning tools is an upcoming trend in the field of education for an efficient system of e-learning. The finding from research question one is not in line with the finding of (Priyatno 2017) who submitted that the use of virtual platforms such as Schoology web application tend to increase teachers' level of outputs and facilitates effective teaching and learning especially at this digital age.

The result from the second research question revealed that perception of lecturers on the ease of usefulness of Schoology web application by lecturers in college of education is negative. The reason for this could be that many of the lecturers have not been exposed to the use of online learning platforms such as schoology web application for instructions. This result is in agreement with the finding of Yoshida (2018) who found that lecturers in tertiary institutions find it difficult to use web-based applications such as Google classroom, pullEvyrywhere and schoology for instructions.

The findings of the study also revealed that there was difference in the perception of male and female lecturers on the ease of use of Schoology web application for instruction in college of education. This implies that gender differences had significant effect on lecturers' perception of ease use of schoology web application for instruction. This result is in agreement with Abidoye & Abidoye 2022 who reported that there was significant effect of gender in the pattern of internet use of English language teachers in secondary schools in Ondo State.

Conclusion

Based on the reviewed relevant literatures and the findings of this study, it was concluded that the perception of lecturers in College of Education on the usefulness of schoology web application was negative. Most of the lecturers disagreed that they find it difficult to use schoology web application for instructional delivery. Therefore, the teaching and learning process should embrace various innovative technologies such as schoology web application strategy especially at this digital era.

Lecturers' Perception on the Use of Schoology Web ... (Alabi, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8368614>

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendation were made;

1. Training, workshop and seminar should be organized for lecturers to improve their skills to use various web-based or online learning tools.
2. Lecturers in College of Education should be exposed to the use of ICT gadgets for instructional delivery.
3. Lecturers, in respect of gender should be encouraged to use computer and other ICT tools for instruction.

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Overviewing the challenges of Sustainable Development Amidst COVID-19 Pandemic in Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper titled sustainable development in Nigeria amidst covid-19 pandemic: disparity crises to fight or flight. The paper discusses key issues related to the role of the various school taught subjects as means but not an end to sustainable development in Nigeria. The paper operationalizes the concepts of sustainable development and disparity crises. It further explains in detail a reflection on the past, present and mirrors the future trends in relation to the contributions of the various school subjects towards sustainable development in the country. It equally amplifies the militating challenges and factors surrounding the present state of art regarding sustainable development.

Keywords: Sustainable Development, Disparity Crisis, COVID-19.

Introduction

The purpose of this paper is to reiterate on the roles of natural and applied sciences, education, technology, arts, literature and vocational subjects amidst COVID 19 pandemic for sustainable development. This is important because the status of our national development today is alarming and need thoughts that will address issues and challenges surrounding its improvement and sustenance. Equally speaking it embraces multi-faceted areas of interest where each component stands to be unique and independent, but all are interwoven and mutually coexist to support one another. The interrelations and connectivity among Natural and Applied Sciences, Education, technology, Arts, Literature and vocational subjects augment and supplement the key indices for sustainable development in our present world. In essence no single component of the theme among the various subjects can be said to account for sustainable development in the absence of the remaining subjects. However, focusing on sustainable development amidst COVID-19 pandemic is bounded by many issues. Before the pandemic, development in Nigeria was plagued by multi-faceted problems or crisis which severely affects its sustenance and impeded the standard desired. As the crisis continue to metamorphose and keep changing from one form to another, a sudden calamity befell the attainment of development despite the efforts that had been in place through teaching and learning of these subjects in accordance with their respective curriculum contents. The calamity which looked like unending crisis, has taken Nigeria to a fight or plight position.

The point to be expressed here is that, as natural and applied sciences, education, technology, arts, literature and vocational subjects are been taught at various levels of education yet the expected level of development has not been achieved as a result of many factors surrounding the dissemination of the contents of knowledge across the various disciplines, upon which COVID-19 pandemic came and exposed the disparity and weaknesses of the systems in its entirety, thus making various stakeholders to ponder on what to do: to fight the calamity and ignore the existing disparities first or plight the calamity by repressing its consequences and address the existing shortfalls in order to pave the way forward?

There is numerous time bounded and context bounded conferences and researches on impact of covid-19 on sustainable development in relation to the aforementioned disciplines world over. Similarly, numerous conferences and researches on the role of these sciences amidst the pandemic within and outside Nigeria have been and are still been conducted. One may ask – what impact do these efforts have on sustainable development amidst the pandemic which still pervades the world? If there is any serious impact, then the state of development in Nigeria would not have been what it is now or different from what is obtained in the developed nations. My guess then is, the present predicament of development should first of all be clearly understood for immediate redress in order to achieve the desired development in its full manifestation and at the same time to strategize towards minimizing the effects covid-19 might have had on it. Hence, the need for this paper presentation on the topic captioned – overviewing the challenges of sustainable development in Nigeria amidst COVID-19 pandemic (James, 2014; Obasanjo, 2012; Nicolai, 2003)

Therefore, the presentation is based on the following issues: the crisis and state of art before the COVID-19, Natural and applied sciences, education, technology, arts, literature and vocational subjects in the pandemic era and quest for sustainable development strategies. However, the presentation begins with operationalizing Disparity crisis to fight or plight and

Overviewing the challenges of Sustainable ... (Garba, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8370706>

sustainable development. It is of no doubt that the wave of COVID-19 pandemic had posed a serious challenge to all spheres of human life in total manifestation resulting to an avoidable setback which call for an immediate line of action in order to set the wheel rolling. Experiences emanating from the consequences of COVID -19 had shown the wider gap between theories and acquired practical knowledge and skills not only in education but across all discipline. It suffices to state that COVID- 19 pandemic arrival to Nigeria not only created impending challenges but had equally portray gaps and lapses as the impending crises between policy making and Policy implementation (Yakasai, 2021) as well as the deficits in our value system and orientations that have been in existence quite for time immemorial in our school subjects. Yakasai (2021) opined that the present predicament of education should first of all be addressed before thinking of mending the impact covid-19 might have had on its delivery. As concentration on mending the impact will not salvage the decaying education, rather it will decompose it even further.

Conceptualization of Disparity Crises

The concept of disparity crises may mean different things to many particularly to the academic communities and intelligentsia, however depending on one's philosophical orientation and inclination. Disparity crises may be evident when a friction occurs between intent and action, it may equally be explained as an observed gap or lack of congruence between stipulated policies and implementation mechanism. It can also be seen as a discrepancy between theoretical contents of knowledge in a particular discipline or subject area and its practical application towards meeting societal demand. As well as those resulting from human-made disasters and natural afflictions that negatively affect the attainment of national development.

Concept of sustainable development

Sustainable development is a measure or index that explains the possession of adequate national resources, the availability of capital, industrial expertise, technological know-how and an educated labour force for better living standard. Development itself is a process where by a country achieves reasonable self- substantiating qualitative and quantitative improvement which enhances industrial and technological advancement in the interest of its citizens (Kazi, 2012). Some of the pre-requisites for this type of development are; the application of modern science and technology, reasonable political stability, coupled with efficient administration and organization. In a similar vein Wadak (2017) opined that development not only involve economic growth but also conditions in which people in a country have adequate food, security, less poverty, reduced unemployment and income inequality. He maintains that to this point in 1977 “self-reliance “was added to the indices of development. The idea of sustainable development originated from the concept of generative power of how social sciences can influence society. This was coined in 1980 and had been extremely successful in the agenda- setting of international organizations (Ahmad, 2015). It can be discerned from the foregoing that a country can be regarded as a developed nation when the following elements have been achieved:

1. It entails quality and quantity
2. Educated labour force derived from various discipline or sciences
3. Alleviation or total eradication of poverty
4. Reduction in the level of unemployment or total employment for the people
5. Equal distribution of income and
6. The country must be self- reliant. (Garba,2015)

Reflection from the past, present and mirror's the future

It is of no doubt to assert that various subject matters or disciplines either individually or collectively have contributed substantially to Nigeria development. However, the recorded breakthrough of these subject areas cannot be unconnected with embedding the learning process with both theory and practical as well as skill acquisitions in the past prior to the emergence of existing crises which predated the covid 19 pandemic. This is in line with the Nigeria policy document on education which stated that the aims and objectives of education should be directed towards; “ the inculcation of national consciousness and national unity, the right type of values and attitude for the survival of the individual and the Nigerian society, the training of the mind in the understanding of the world around us and the acquisition of appropriate skills, abilities and competence both mental and physical as equipment for the individual to live and contribute to the development of the society. These ratifications were arrived at as a result of the belief that not only is education the greatest force that can be used to bring about redress, it is also the greatest investment that the nation can make for the quick development of the economic, political, sociological and human resources (FGN, 2013)

Overviewing the challenges of Sustainable ... (Garba, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8370706>

A reflection into the past has it on record that teaching of all natural and applied sciences, technology and vocations are complemented by practical experiences which is hoped to be translated into action to meet the scientific and technological aspirations of the society. The same is true for education, arts and literature. For example, 30- 40 years ago, majority of our secondary schools by then were provided with highly equipped and functional laboratories, workshops, as well as farmlands for practical and demonstration purposes. That was the tradition while establishing science colleges, technical and vocational or grammar secondary schools. In this direction teacher training schools were not left behind. The essence, rational and justification of making these provisions are glaringly clear to all, is simply to strike a balance between theoretical knowledge and practical as well as skill acquisition more realistic aimed at achieving desired goals and objectives for national development. Not only that, there is also a close link between schools taught subjects and the realities operating within the immediate environments of the learners in terms of arts and craft. These relations enable learners to appreciate and see relevance of the various school subjects as worthy of study, and also acknowledge their importance for individual self-growth and national development. Putting the claim in other words, a bond of continuity between local crafts such as weaving, leather work, dying, black smith and farming had been firmly rooted in the mind of the learners, of which motivated them intrinsically and extrinsically to strive for perfection, translating into scientific and technological progression. Those are the days in which the child feels excited and elated by virtue of scientific, technological and cultural exhibitions in the forms of young scientists, young engineers, young farmers, young... young in multiple areas. Where are they now? And what happens in the link between theoretical knowledge and practical as well as skill acquisitions? And also, what are the status of laboratories, workshops and school farmlands? Answers to these questions amount to an attempt to resolve one of the crises that pre-dated COVID-19 impetuses to sustainable development

In a parallel dimension one cannot dismiss the link between the various subject matters towards ensuring sustainable development. There is a direct link between agricultural products with either the study of natural and applied sciences, technology or arts and literature. Same consideration goes to the close link between education, science and technology. Furthermore, one cannot separate the connectivity between crafts, science and vocation which stand to be the gateways to sustainable development. For example, agricultural science in all its spheres provide substances for use in pharmacology, which in turn feeds medicine, culminating into healthcare delivery that can be adjudged as an index of development. Equally speaking same agricultural sciences becomes the sole gateway for food production in terms of consumable hydrocarbons, fats and acids, vegetables as well as other mineral resources which are essential for balance diet required to maintain physiological needs of the body to a level of sound equilibration. This impliedly means that a nation capable of feeding itself is regarded as a developed society.

Where people have attained maximum food security there is the likely hood that psychological wellbeing is maximized and can translate into sound labour force. In the same line of argument, a single common source will equally pave way for industrialization by providing raw materials like timber, hide and skin, ground nuts, sesame, kernel nuts and coffee that can be processed or exported for additional economic empowerment and growth of the nation. Same field would become a means for creating job opportunities in multiple ways to absorb the teeming population. This would add another layer of security to the society as all citizens are likely to be engaging in gainful employment, there by closing the room for idleness and unemployment. In essence it's right to assert that the importance of the various subject disciplines as potential means and not an end to sustainable development cannot be underscored. Having seen the extent to which a single vocational subject like agriculture can impact to latitude of a nation's developmental area, with emphasis to food and job security, resources for industrial uses and a feeder to technological and scientific breakthrough. One might ask whether the subject is accorded the status it deserves or not. And why is that the hide and skin derived from animal husbandry which is a unit in the study of agriculture formerly been either locally processed in our local tanneries or exported for economic gain is nowadays been consume to replenish the body instead of healthy meat derived from same common source? Can these drawbacks be attributed to covid 19 pandemic? And if this continues unresolved what would be the future?

Overview of School Subjects Before the Pandemic

A cursory look at the position of arts and literature subjects before the covid 19 pandemic, can reasonably informed us of their contributions to manpower training and human resources for sustainable growth and development prior to the existing disparity crises. These subject areas were believed to be solely responsible for inculcating the right type of attitude and positive value orientations as enshrined in the policy document for education in Nigeria. According to Hogan (1973), as cited in Ononuju, et al. (2013), moral behaviour is determined by five factors as identified below;

1. Socialization; becoming aware as a child of society and parents' rules of conduct for being good

Overviewing the challenges of Sustainable ... (Garba, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8370706>

2. Moral judgement; learning to think reasonably about our own ethics and deliberately deciding on our own moral standards
3. Moral feelings; the internalization of our own moral beliefs to the degree that we fell shame and guilt when we fail to do what we should
4. Empathy; the awareness of other people's situations, feelings and needs so that one is compelled to help those in need
5. Confidence and knowledge; knowing the steps involved in helping others and believing that one is responsible for and capable of helping.

To augment the claims made earlier by Hogan that arts and literature subjects are responsible for training moral values. As subjects of study their relevance in promoting sustainable development squarely stands unique and hinges on the extent to which they are seen as promising means. Hence arts and literature are subjects that train the mind in the matters of moral values. To support this point Mahatma Gandhi of India maintained that;

“If wealth is lost nothing is lost”

“If the health is lost something is lost”

“If character is lost everything is lost”

“Best of all things is character”.

In another vein to buttress the role of these subjects in the inculcation and attainment of moral values, Mkp (1987) classified values as; spiritual values, family life values, social values, moral values, political values, personal values, economic values as well as scientific and technological values. A holistic attainment of these values will culminate into sustainable development.

Quality Education For Sustainable Development

To vindicate the role of education either as a discipline or as a system in paving the way for sustainable development before the covid 19 pandemic one cannot dismiss the claim that education is an effective weapon whose effect depends on who holds it in his hand and at whom it is aimed. The general concern of education centered on bringing about a desirable and permanent change in the behaviour of the individual. And for this change to occur certain conditions must be met, not only that the change should be evident in manifestation across the cognitive, affective and psycho-motor domains of the individual. Where these changes are made possible, then a valid conclusion and generalization is possible in relation to the attainment of outlined educational objectives enshrined in the policy document on education towards sustainable development. In discussing the relevance of education Obasanjo (2012), outlined what is required of education to become more relevant to our developmental process as,

1. It must train the individual for a better appreciation of his own cultural traditions whilst at the same time equipping him with the ability to absorb new ideas, new information and new data for resolving the constantly changing problems of his environment
2. It must train the individual to relate and interact meaningfully with other individuals in the society and to appreciate the importance of effective organization for human progress
3. It must develop the creative ability of individuals especially in the cultural and technological realms
4. It must foster in the individuals those values which make for good citizenship, such as honesty, selflessness, tolerance, dedication, hard work and personal integrity, all of which provide the rich soil from which good leadership spawned.
5. It must promote the culture of productivity by enabling every individual to discover the creative genius in him.

Obasanjo (2012) further argued that, despite the significant role of education in taking Nigeria to the promising land of sustainable development, yet its quality is declining, this is mainly due to the fact that the quality in some of our schools is deplorable and we now face the specter of ever poorer performance in national examinations. James (2014) lend credence to this point where he express his position that, “ the concern about the quality of education in Nigeria is traceable to the fact that an x-ray of the essential elements of quality of education in Nigeria all shows a deficit in terms of societal participation and ownership of programmes, democratic formulation of policy and adaptability to local conditions, management autonomy, responsive curriculum, qualitative and motivated teaching force, curriculum-driven infrastructure, user friendly materials as well as funding. To catalyze these positions, Enoh (2013) declares that, through the length and breadth of Nigeria, there is overwhelming agreement among both the educated and uneducated that quality at all levels of the system has greatly fallen to unprecedented levels. Most people reflect over the years of educational glory when such and such was the case and find, using different parameters, extreme decline at all levels. In his words Enoh (2013) reiterated that, much of the nations educational problems emanate from underutilization of philosophy of education in training teachers and in decision-making; that the

Overviewing the challenges of Sustainable ... (Garba, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8370706>

policies and decisions which drive, the education system and which to my best understanding have turned it into an educational wasteland are the direct consequences of this neglect.

The positions of Obasanjo (2012), Enoch (2013) and James (2014) are all self-explanatory evidences to the fact that education as a subject matter and a means to sustainable development had greatly suffered from multiple damages in different times which all pre-dated COVID-19 pandemic. These claims also suggested the existing disparities that had plagued the system which inhibit it from enabling Nigeria to reach a level of sustainable development as expected, it is still hazy and the future is becoming a mirage.

Hence, in matters relating to education either as a means or an end product, two principal areas must come to mind for consideration in relation to development, as they ought to be, these are quality and equity. In education quality comes first, but equity is almost of equal importance in the particular context of Nigeria. For one thing education is a universal birth right; for another reason, Nigeria as a state was founded on the democratic promise of ensuring equal opportunity to all citizens, regardless of ethnic, religious, social status or political region. Quality of education depends on several factors most of which have been discussed extensively in many essays, such as curriculum, infrastructure, methods, and environment all have their special value, but quality also depends on teachers, political will and commitment as well as the value system and orientations of the society in addition to the duality of theory and practice. Teachers must be qualified and trained; they should have proper aptitude and commitment. Teachers are not mere conduits of learning; they are viable heroes whom the students would like to admire and emulate. It would therefore, be necessary to make the profession honourable, governmentally as well as socially. And honour would depend not on words but on the personal respect accorded to them in terms of both prestige and financial provision. To qualify this there is an adage that “a poor teacher is not an effective teacher”.

According to Yakasai (2021), long before the advent of corona disease (COVID-19) and the resultant lockdown, the delivery of education in Nigeria was hampered by many pandemics. In fact, the educational system which would have been under state of emergency was characterized by poor academic achievement and other decays in standards. Political will and commitment determine government involvement and investment in education. The UNESCO report on education recommended that at least 26% of the annual budget should be allocated to education at all tiers of government. The claim is amply justified on the simple ground that in our circumstances education is the most productive sector for investment, more than civil administration and military defence. An informed mind would never sell his vote, equally an informed mind hardly compromise standard neither breach the stated rules, nor does he engage in destructive acts. Investment in education would among other things create directly and consequentially employment which is *sine qua non* for economic development.

Another major obstacle that presently hindered quality education is the deliberate separation of experimental or practical knowledge from theoretical knowledge. The teaching of most natural and applied sciences, as well as vocations and education are purely made to become lecture oriented with little or no regard to practical experiences. This changing trend and orientation have grown over the years, peculiarly to save cost and to the inclination of authorities to have graduates over loaded with theoretical content knowledge at the detriment of competent individuals who possess mastery in both theory and standard required for the practices of the various subject matters. Therefore, it is excellently neither right to say, education does not endure nor does it become creative unless given through the blended medium of integrating theory and practice/experiments.

Equity and Quality Issue in Nigerian Education

In Nigeria prior to covid 19 pandemic as quality suffers same goes to equity. The problem of ensuring equity persists, turning from bad to worse. The state is expected to intervene but it does not, because the state itself is metamorphosing into a capitalist society both in ideology and practice. The nation is unequal and polarized, so is across to education. To my believe inequality is destructive, and to employ education in widening the societal gulf instead of bridging it, amount to preparation for anarchy with all its antecedent consequences and underdevelopment. In Nigeria today evidences are bound were the children of the privileged and the elites are opportune to have access to quality education in the somewhat equipped private schools despite their exorbitant cost. Whilst the children of the downtrodden masses who constitute the majority and the electorate whose vote counts, were left with no option rather than the public schools which are ill-equipped, dilapidated, with less or no teaching resources, lack laboratories and in addition to inefficient teachers, who are poorly trained and living in abject / total poverty. Ahmad (2015) contends that social or economic deprivations have its link to government in sensitivity and in-efficacy upon which citizens are dichotomize into “affiliated” and “marginalized”. This is a phenomenon that needs very thorough going into, not only for the sake or interest of education but also that of the wellbeing of the people who are expected to be the potential instruments for sustainable development. Education is a significant human right and the world community has long advocated it for all people in all situations because, education is not only significant as a right, it is also very important in

Overviewing the challenges of Sustainable ... (Garba, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8370706>

enabling people to access other rights and to empower themselves. Obanya, (2002) as cited in Ejue (2014) asserted that, there is need for a shift of emphasis in education discourse from how much and how many to how well. From better and in fact to more of better, this is because the ultimate goal of education is improvement not simply increment.

State of the Art and the Challenges

Over the years a number of policies were formulated and different programmes have been designed by different government of both military and civilian administration with the sole aim of attaining sustainable development. These policies, programme and projects were all directed to enhance quality and quantity in boosting education, agricultural output, scientific and technological mile stones, create job opportunities, improve health delivery and minimize poverty rate among the ever-increasing Nigerian population. Prominent among such government initiated sustainable developmental policies as identified by Margaret & Agnes (2013) include; National Accelerated Food Production Programme (NAFPP) 1972, the Operation Feed the Nation (OFN) 1976; the Green Revolution Programme (GRP) 1980; the Agricultural Development Project (ADP) 1985; The National Directorate of Employment (NDE) 1986; Directorate of Foods, Roads and Rural Infrastructures (DFRRI) 1987; Better life Programme for Rural Women (1987); Family Support Programme (FSP) 1993; the Vision 2020 1996; Family Economic Advancement Programme (FEAP) 1997; Poverty Alleviation Programme (PAP) 2000; National Poverty Eradication Programme (NAPEP) and the Seven (7) Point Agenda (2008). To all these well design and meaningfully enacted policies, one can easily conclude with a heart-felt sorrow that none of them last for more than a decade without been either totally wiped out or silently extinguished. Another similitude to the extinction of laudable project is the deplorable condition of the Nigerians giant and multi-purpose steel rolling mills located at Ajaokuta, to which trillions of naira had yearly been injected into it from inception to date. Shamefully the iron company is left abandoned unproductive/underutilize despite the substantial iron deposit in the country. Similar example could be cited with reference to the Nigerian oil and gas sector, even though the country is among the world's major exporter of crude oil, yet our refineries' hardly produce the required PSM for internal or domestic consumption.

This discussion would not be comprehensive if we fail to admit that as the world is moving from dependence in hydroelectric power supply to tapping and combating sunlight to solar energy, yet the net megawatt supply of energy in Nigeria is far below the required. Going by the available fertile landmass, natural flowing rivers, and abundant deposits of crude oil, iron ores, and other mineral resources, variant vegetation zones coupled with higher human resources, the effects of all these are hardly noted in sustaining development as expected. These poor trends in the identified sectors have impeded sustainable development in the country not because of the inefficiency of the various subjects of study in our school systems, neither to the multiplier effect of covid -19.

From the foregoing discourse it appears that sustainable development in Nigeria had been in either emergency or crises state which pre-dated COVID-19 pandemic. Both loud and silent emergencies have pervaded the possible avenues for development to strive. Loud emergencies that include human made disasters (like civil strife in forms of communal crises, banditry, kidnapping abduction and misplacement of priorities) and natural disasters (like, earthquakes, floods and pandemics) and silent emergencies that include HIV/AIDS, extreme poverty, children living in streets, (Pigozzi, 1999), compromising standard and poor value system and orientation in addition to lack of political will and commitments to policy implementation. Uemura (1999) asserted that, Emergency often result in situations where formal education system might be destroyed or damaged, teachers, education staff and students might be killed, abducted, injured or unable to resume normal school operations.

As noted, crises or emergency conditions differs in magnitude, directions and manifestations, this is also true to state that, while emergencies or crises created by a disaster may relatively last for a short term, crises or emergencies created by on-going conflicts, war or poor policy implementation, and value orientation may last for years if not decades. Yakasai (2021) have identified almost nine (9) major challenges or crises facing the Nigerian education sector as follows.

1. Poor academic performance
2. Poor governance and management of education
3. Poor funding and neglect of the education sector
4. Poor infrastructure and teaching facilities
5. Overcrowded classrooms/lecture rooms
6. Poor teachers welfare
7. Lack of dedication and commitment to work by teachers
8. Changes in learners value orientations

Overviewing the challenges of Sustainable ... (Garba, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8370706>

9. Influence of media technology
10. High rate of examination malpractice

These crises were all due to human made disasters that has a direct implications or impact to the teaching and learning of the various school subjects. They constitute a cog to the attainment of the nation's dream for sustainable development. These claims lend credence to view of Pigozzi, (1999), that loud and silent emergencies have pervaded the possible avenues for development to strive. Loud emergencies that include human made disasters (like civil strife in forms of communal crises, banditry, political bigotry, inefficiency greed and egocentrism) and natural disasters (like, earthquakes, floods and pandemics) and silent emergencies that include HIV/AIDS, extreme poverty, children living in streets,

In Nigeria today a number of school age children are roaming the streets, some are living in extreme poverty with many facing difficulties to have three square meals in a day, our systems are negatively affected by constant policy changes with none having withstood the test of time, and education system lacks the glory of duality between theory and practice. The aforementioned situation had resulted into putting Nigeria into an emergency position to which Sinclair, (2002) claimed its education should be "that which protects the wellbeing, foster learning opportunities and nurtures the overall development of children affected by conflicts and disasters. Nicolai (2003) further suggested that education should be seen as a priority component of emergency assistance as it lays an important role in meeting children's basic needs in both the short and long terms and help to reduce vulnerability to disaster. To this point Bensalah (2002) stated (5) five reasons why educational response in emergencies and reconstruction might be required;

1. Education helps meet the psychological needs of the children
2. It's a tool for protecting children in emergencies
3. It provides a channel for conveying health and survival messages for teaching new skills and values
4. It's a tool for social cohesion
5. Education is vital to the reconstruction of economic basis of the family and the larger society

Factors of Low level of Development in Nigeria

The low level of development in Nigeria may have its root from the following factors that have been lingering in its neck.

1. Disparity between policy and implementation mechanisms; despite the fact that successive government have evolved meaningful policies and projects geared towards sustainable development. Yet majority of these policies were left either half-baked or totally ignored before attaining their full maturation stage. These need immediate redress by government officials and those in positions of authority and mantle of power. Nigeria as a developing nation has substantial manpower that is blessed with the capacity to formulate policies required for any desired development.
2. Disparity in value system and orientation; there exist a wider gap between what is enshrined in our civic curriculum in terms of what constitute value systems and orientation and our attitude in real life situations. The disparity in value systems need to be re-evaluated by all to be in line with positive value system and orientations as suggested by Obasanjo, (2012). In essence a positive change is required, which is consonant with the ontological, epistemological as well as methodological concerns of what value system and orientation stands for.
3. Poor political will and commitment; noting that policies are only enacted by government, and it has been a tradition that each government comes up with its own policies, so doing should not negate the principle of continuity. Laudable policies ought to be considered whenever there is a change in government. Equivocally continuity of meaningful developmental projects emanating from sound and well-articulated policies would add vigour and taste to our claim for democratic dispensation or popular democracy
4. Compromising standard; in pursuance of sustainable development compromising standard need to be detested and shun off. Evidences are bound where standards have been compromised. For example, most recently built classrooms have become dilapidated, roads of nowadays hardly withstand pressure from loaded trucks whilst many of the commodities both consumable and non-consumables are either substandard or of low quality. Similarly standard at times are compromise in the selection and recruitment of teachers at various levels of our education system. These practices do have negative multiplier consequences on the students, parents, the system and the larger society. Where adequate preparations are made in terms of input there is a higher expectation of output. Hence reciprocal equity in education stem from the quality of the teachers.
5. Neglects of local trade and crafts; there is a need for a serious concern to reintegrate the local trades and crafts simultaneously with the school subjects. This is because of the immense role and significance in promoting mastery of vocational subjects taught in schools. Incorporating /integrating trades like metal works, dying, knitting, weaving, will

Overviewing the challenges of Sustainable ... (Garba, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8370706>

inevitably arose learners curiosity and motivation to related school subjects, in similar vein traditional medicine/ and herbal processing should also be given value in the teaching of science.

6. Appreciating the genius and creative inventions of our younger ones; As each individual is bestowed with latent potentialities which are only made known apparently through exhibition, if our scientific and technological quest for advancement is to become a reality, it then becomes necessary to appreciate our indigenous creative inventions and at the same time support them in all respect to boost their morale to continue with exploring their God given talents and abilities.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it suffices to reiterate my position by saying again that covid 19 pandemic has only exposes the shortfalls and weakness in Nigeria not by virtue of low or poor curriculum content of the school subjects. But rather due to the deficits that have been orchestrated by poor policy implementation, deliberate segregation of theory from practice and experiments coupled with poor and insensitive value systems orientations and compromising standards. These are disparity gaps need to be filled in holistically as they exemplified emergencies worthy to attend. The present predicament of under development in Nigeria should be seen from these lenses with reasonable attempt to address them before thinking of the impact covid-19 might have had on the school subject matters and their relations to sustainable development. As concentration on mending the Impact will not salvage the decay and rot in our quest for sustainable development, rather it will decompose it even further leaving the nation in a state of deepened crises to fight or flight.

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Parents' Social Variables and Youths' Dispirit for Tertiary Education in Anambra State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examined the influence of parents' social variables on youths dispirit for tertiary education in Anambra State. Two research questions and two null hypotheses were formulated to aid the study. The study adopted an ex post facto design. The population consisted of 934,825 youths in Anambra State. Sample of 1110 youths were selected for the study through purposive sampling technique. Data for the study were collected using a researcher developed instrument known as Parents' Social Variables and Youths Dispirit Questionnaire (PSVYDQ). The instrument was validated by three experts before the reliability test was conducted with 40 respondents who were not part of the sample. Cronbach Alpha was used to ascertain the reliability of the instrument. The instrument has an alpha reliability coefficient of 0.88 for youth dispirit for university education. Data collected were analyzed using analysis of variance at 0.05 level of significance. The result of data analysis for all the hypotheses were significant and therefore the null hypotheses were rejected. Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that parents' social variables have significant influence on youths dispirit for tertiary education in Anambra state. It was therefore recommended among others that sociologists of education and other spirited individuals and organizations should organized orientation programmes aimed at discouraging divorce, and child-birth before marriage especially among financially dependent youths. If marriages are helped to remain united, couples will be more likely to encourage their children to aspire for tertiary education.

Keywords: Youths dispirit, marital status and tertiary education

Introduction

In Nigeria, the consciousness of becoming graduates by both male and female students pervades anxiety for admission into foreign and local universities. Academic programmes learned in the tertiary institutions are designed to take cognizance of the needs of the society and the individuals. They are geared towards making the graduates functional in the society. Generally, tertiary education is seen as a means by which the societal needs and aspirations could be attained through the courses in the curriculum. Some of the advantages of the tertiary education include but not limited to assisting graduates to live a fuller and richer life and making them grow in knowledge and wisdom, as well as helping them develop some aesthetic sense and value (Okey-kalu, 2019). Some other scholars such as Olamide, and Tobiloba (2022) describe university education as a way of preserving the future and the way of life in which a people believe in as well as the modest way to live a comfortable life. It is seen as an essential channel for development if a society has to survive.

However, tertiary education, whether polytechnic, college of education or university education, has their own challenges, it may be seen to be difficult and demands endurance; it sometimes deprive undergraduates of social and freedom to roam about because of academic work load (Adams, 2019). Again, the Nigerian university system has been imperiled by misconceived government policies and poor funding; incessant disruption of academic activities; lack of employment opportunities for prospective graduates and so forth (Ali, 2021; Olaleye, 2022). Olaleye (2022) noted that only one percent of the total population pursues higher education. The uncertainties faced by many Nigerian youths over their future occasioned by incessant strikes and the decay of public institutions seem to contributes to discouraging many youths for aspiring for the university education. For example, the eight-month long strike of Non-Academic Staff Union of Universities, from February 14, to October 13, 2022, forced many youths in many universities to pick up skills to pass time and seek employment to earn a living. Moreover, Olaleye (2022) asserted that due to the rise in non-conventional jobs, tertiary education might seem unnecessary. According to Arnhold (2021), some people believed that you do not need a degree to learn almost anything on the internet. Adams (2019) in his study found that nearly two third of respondents are interested in doing an apprenticeship rather than going to university after leaving school. Due to low wages, graduate jobs that might have been prestigious or well-paid three decades ago are now bottom of the career ladder. Often a young person could go straight into work, get promoted, and then be earning significantly more money than they would be if they got into the same field after university (Preddy, 2019).

Parents' Social Variables and Youths ... (Onwuhanze, et al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8370752>

Most authors like Kalu (2019), Olaleye (2022) and Arnhold (2021) agreed that the level of parents' involvement in the schooling of their children is a significant indicator of the quality of schooling. This study investigates parent's educational qualifications and parents' marital status as family social variables that may influence youths' dispirit for tertiary education especially the university education. Parents' educational qualifications is the combination of knowledge, skills, understanding and attainment of the youths' parents in an organized and accepted educational institution. It is classified as a formal education, First School Leaving Certificate, Senior Secondary Certificate, Ordinary National Diploma, Bachelor Degree, Masters, Doctorate Degree, among others. Marital status is the parents' recognized position in the society in terms of marriage. Youths' dispirit refers to the youths' lack of enthusiasm toward furthering their tertiary education because they are depressed and dejected. Various researchers and authors are in agreement with the direct association of parents' literacy level with children's academic achievements and their decision to leave school (Tsolou & Babalis, 2020). Wulansari, Lisnawati, Sahid, wahyudi, (2023) asserts that parents' factors are very important in their children's educational interest. According to Gobena (2018) if learners are to maximize their potential from schooling, they will need the full support of their families.

Parental education has strong implications for parental orientations toward their children's achievement (Mortimer, 2015). Low literacy level leads to vicious cycle of illiteracy (Chugh, 2011) and children coming from educated families are reported to show high academic achievement and educational attainments (Tsolou & Babalis, 2020). Gobena (2018) found that children whose families are of high education scales have shown statistically far better changes of participating in tertiary education. Poorly educated parents usually earn low income, as a result, would not be able to sponsor the cost of qualitative education for their children (Ahmed, & Abdalrahman, 2022). Mortimer, (2015) found that financially strapped parent with the highest level of education may be especially concerned that their children maintain high expectation for the future despite transient economic difficulties. In contrast poorly educated parents appear to be the more vulnerable, as they are likely the most threatened by economic hardship. With the most limited prospect in labor market, their opportunities to improve their families' economic positions may be the most constrained. Children who observe their parents' plight may become discouraged, lessening their confidence in the economic realm.

Marital status classified people as divorced, widowed or in a relationship. A person is said to be divorced if he or she has officially ended his/her marriage to someone; widowed if his/his wife/husband is dead (Gobena et'al 2018). The level of instability in the home environment is also important to adolescents' academic career (Aguboshim, 2021). The cumulative effect of the loss or addition of a parental figure in the home may disrupt a child's sense of security and have negatively affected children's academic aspirations. Because of time constraints, dwindling assistance, new obligations, and the possible strain introduced to the parent-child relationship by divorce or start of a parent's new romantic relationship; single parents and those who are married to or are cohabiting with new partners may experience less closeness with their adolescents despite their best effort (Aguboshim, 2021). If children do not feel close to their parents, or if parents are not able to supervise their children's lives, parents influence on school achievement and course-taking decision may be undermined. Family disruptions may cause young people to be less optimistic about their future including their prospects of attending tertiary institutions (Gobena, 2018). Nanteza, Nasasira, Nabawanda and Katike (2021) in their study found that marital status has no direct effect on children's academic progress because it did not offer leverage in explaining how family instability related to students' academic factors like income and parental expectations.

A closer observation shows that in order to acquire wealth in their youthful age, some youths have become more interested in acquiring vocational occupation. The display of wealth, and the number of houses and vehicles owned by many business merchants and contractors who are not educated up to the tertiary education seems to impress the youths in Anambra State and believe that business without tertiary education is the quickest way to prosperity (Adams 2019). Ordinarily, this is not bad on itself but the future consequences of this should rather be imagined than seen. If this trend is not checked, the resultant effects will be that, in the nearest future Anambra State will have shortage of educated professionals to represent her in different fields of human endeavours both in Nigerian and in the world in general. There will equally be shortage of teachers from the primary to the tertiary levels. The State will retrogress to pre-colonial era where illiteracy reigns supreme. Against this background, the study is aimed at examining whether parents' social variables have any influence on youths' dispirit for tertiary education.

The findings of this study are hoped to add more to the existing body of knowledge in helping parents and youths to develop interest in tertiary education and for the light the study throws on parents' variables and youth dispirit for tertiary education. Further research related to this topic will also be facilitated.

Parents' Social Variables and Youths ... (Onwuhanze, et al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8370752>

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study was to determine how parents' social variables can influence youths dispirit for tertiary education in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the influence of parents' educational qualification on youths dispirit for tertiary education.
2. Determine the influence of parent's marital status on youths dispirit for tertiary education

Research Questions

1. To what extent does parents' educational qualification influences youths dispirit for tertiary education in Anambra State?
2. What is the extent to which parent's marital status influences youth dispirit for tertiary education in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at .05 level of significance:

1. Parents' educational qualifications do not significantly influence youths dispirit for tertiary education in Anambra State.
2. Parents' marital status does not significantly influence youths dispirit for tertiary education in Anambra State.

Methodology

This study adopted ex post facto design. It is a systematic enquiry in which the researcher has no control over the independent variables because, their manifestations have already occurred. The population for study was 934,825 young people between the ages of 14 and 24 years. A total of 1,110 youths were selected from the population as samples for the study using the purposive sampling technique. This technique was used because the researcher had no exert population of youths in each senatorial district in Anambra State who are not in any tertiary institution. Data for the study were obtained using a researcher-developed instrument known as Parents' Social Variables and Youths Dispirit Questionnaire (PSVYDQ). The instrument has two sections labeled section A & section B. Section A collected information on the respondents' parents' educational qualification and marital status, while section B collected information on youths dispirit for tertiary education (12 items). The questionnaire, which was validated by two Measurement experts, had a reliability coefficient of 0.88. The hypotheses were tested using analysis of variance (ANOVA) at 0.05 level of significance. If the calculated result is greater than the critical value at .05 level of significance, reject the null hypothesis, but otherwise retain the null hypothesis. The data were analyzed using Analysis of variance (ANOVA) and dependent t-test.

Results

Research Question 1

To what extent does parents' educational qualification influences youths dispirit for tertiary education in Anambra State?

Table 1: Mean scores of the influence of parents' educational qualifications on youths 'dispirit for tertiary education

Parents' Educational Qualifications	N	Mean
No formal education/FSLC	410	36.35
SSCE/GCE	434	36.15
OND/NCE	81	33.71
Bachelor Degree/HND/PGD	115	34.04
Masters and Above	70	33.51

The data presented in Table 1 show the mean scores of the influence of parents' educational qualifications on youths dispirit for tertiary education in Anambra State. This simply shows that youths whose parents have no formal education have the highest mean score of 36.35 for youths dispirit for tertiary education while those parents' educational qualification is masters and above had the lowest mean score of 33.51 for youths dispirit for tertiary education.

Research Question Two

What is the extent to which parent's marital status influences youth dispirit for tertiary education in Anambra State's

Parents' Social Variables and Youths ... (Onwuhanze, et al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8370752>

Table 2: Mean scores of the influence of parents' marital status on youths dispirit for tertiary education

Parents' Educational Qualifications	N	Mean
Unmarried	129	34.18
Married	613	33.63
Widowed	334	33.63
Divorced	134	35.71

The data presented in Table 2 show the influence of marital status on youths dispirit for tertiary education in Anambra State. Youths dispirit is higher among youths whose parents are divorced having a mean score of 35.71, followed by the unmarried parents (34.18).

Hypothesis 1

Parents' educational qualifications does not significantly influence youths dispirit for tertiary education in Anambra State.

Table 3: Analysis of Variance of the influence of parents' educational qualifications on youths dispirit for tertiary education

Sources of variance	SS	df	MS	F
Between Groups	519.2	4	129.8	8.85
Within Groups	16207.47	1105	14.67	

Level of significant = .05, critical value = 1.73

The data presented in Table 3 reveal the obtained F-value of 8.85. This value was tested for significance by comparing it with the critical F-value of 1.73 at .05 level of significance. The observed f-value was greater than the critical value of 1.73. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that parents' educational qualifications do not significantly influence youths dispirit for university education is rejected.

Hypothesis 2

Parents' marital status does not significantly influence youths dispirit for tertiary education in Anambra State.

Table 4: Analysis of Variance of the influence of parents' marital status on youths dispirit for tertiary education

Sources of variance	SS	df	MS	F
Between Groups	166.18	3	55.39	3.21
Within Groups	19097.55	1105	17.27	

Level of significant = .05, critical value = 1.73

The result of the analysis of variance presented in Table 4 show that the calculated F-value of 3.21 is greater than F-critical value of 1.73 at .05 level of significance. The null hypothesis which states that parents' marital status does not significantly influence youths dispirit for tertiary education in Anambra State is therefore rejected.

Discussions of Findings

The result of data analysis in Table 3 was significant due to the fact that the obtained F-value (8.85) was greater than the critical F-value (1.73) at .05 level of significance. This implies that there is significant influence of parents' educational qualifications on youths dispirit for tertiary education in Anambra state. Youths whose parents' highest educational qualification is first school leaving certificate (FSLC) were more dispirited than youths whose parents' highest education qualification was Master and above. This means that the lower the level of parents' educational qualifications, the higher the youths dispirit for tertiary education in Anambra state. This finding agrees with the studies of Chugh (2011) and (Tsolou & Babalis, 2020) that Low literacy level leads to vicious cycle of illiteracy and children coming from educated families show high academic achievement and educational attainments. The study also supports the findings of Gobena (2018), and Ahmed, and Abdalrahman (2022) that children whose families are of high education scales have a statistically far better changes of participating in tertiary education. Poorly educated parents usually earn low income, as a result, would not be able to sponsor

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the bills of qualitative education for their children. The study is in agreement with Mortimer, et'al (2015) that financially strapped parent with the highest level of education may be especially concerned that their children maintain high expectation for the future despite transient economic difficulties.

The result of the data analysis in Table 4 was significant due to the fact that the obtained F-value (3.21) was greater than the critical F-value (1.73) at 0.05 level of significance. This implies that there is significance influence of parents' marital status on youth dispirit for Tertiary education in Anambra State. Moderately stronger influence was found among youths whose parents are divorced (35.71) and moderately weak influence was found among youths whose parents are intact married couple (33.63). This means that youth whose parents are divorced and unmarried are more likely to be dispirited than youths whose parents are intact married partners. This finding is in agreement with the findings of Aguboshim (2021)) that the cumulative effect of the loss or addition of a parental figure in the home may disrupt a child's sense of security, and have negative implication for children's academic aspirations. The study agrees with Gobena (2018) that family disruptions may cause young people to be less optimistic about their future including their prospects of attending tertiary institutions. However, the study disagrees with the findings of Nanteza, et'al (2021) that marital status has no direct effect on children's academic progress.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, conclusions were drawn that social variables of parents' level of education and marital status significantly influence youths dispirit for tertiary education in Anambra state. Parents have remarkable role to play in determining the educational aspiration of their children or youths. Youths whose parents have lower educational qualifications and those whose parents are not married or divorced are more likely to show lack of enthusiasm to tertiary education.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Government and the non-governmental organizations should organize a behavioural change awareness campaign to enlighten parents on the importance of supporting youths to acquire tertiary education.
2. Sociologists in Education and Guidance Counsellors should organize orientation programmes aimed at discouraging divorce among married couples, and child birth before marriage especially among financially dependent youths.

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Python Coding amongst Undergraduate Student Teachers in a Nigeria Post-Secondary Institution: An Exploratory Study

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Abstract

This study explored coding errors, determined how preservice teachers in Obafemi Awolowo University (OAU) debugged coding error and investigated reasons for the errors. This was with an intention to assess preservice teachers learning and understanding of python programming in OAU. The study adopted exploratory research design with the population of all undergraduate students in Faculty of Education in OAU. Out of the population, 10 preservice teachers were interviewed to understand the nature of the study. The interviews were audio recorded, transcribed and thematically analysed. The study findings revealed four major errors committed in python programming by student teachers in the university. The finding further categorized approaches adopted by the students in debugging python programming errors into seven. Amongst these seven, 'help from friends and internet' were predominant while the least was 'doing it again'. The undergraduate students' teachers advanced six reasons for the errors often faced while learning programming. The paper concluded that undergraduate student teachers confront errors while learning python programming. It was strongly recommended that the pedagogy of computer programming should be taught inhouse to improve programming learning among undergraduate student teachers.

Keywords: Python Programming, Coding Errors, Undergraduate Student Teachers, Exploratory Research, Debugging

Introduction

The term coding and programming can be used interchangeably. San Ahmed, et al., (2018) regarded computer programming as the procedure for "writing, testing and debugging computer programs" using diverse programming languages (P. 27). This act of writing set of codes, testing and debugging could be referred to coding. Research argued that learning coding is complex (San Ahmed et al., 2018). Despite the complexity in coding, learning computer programming is no longer restricted to engineering and pure science students of Obafemi Awolowo University (OAU) only but also involving preservice students in the core science related studies. All students who enrolled to study Mathematics, Physics, Chemistry and Biology education are expected to register and pass the borrowed courses from Computer Department of the University. The programming courses consisted of both theoretical and practical. According to Muslihudin, et al., (2021), the reason for learning programming languages is to develop application software for users. Far above this, observation reveals that the purpose of student teachers learning the acts of coding in this present era is to develop the pedagogy of programming and thinking skills that would be required to teach Computer Studies in Nigerian primary and secondary schools. Since the pedagogy of computer programming might not be taught outside the domain of education faculty, the complexity of learning computer programming asserted by San Ahmed et al. (2018) is further strengthen.

Similarly, a good number of studies (Brenda, et al., 2023; Mwaba, 2022) have shown that there are few qualified teachers teaching Computer Studies in primary and secondary schools. This limitation could be traced to teachers' development in computer programming during their training in the tertiary institutions. Even undergraduate students who are outside education faculty but exposed to computer programming equally faced with coding challenges. For example, in a study conducted by Jegede, et al., (2019) to investigate java programming errors committed amongst computer science and engineering students in Southwestern universities in Nigeria. The study identified five key errors, namely; Invalid Symbol, Mismatch Symbol, Missing Symbol, Inappropriate Naming, and Excessive Symbol. However, Missing symbols (33%) and Invalid symbols (12%) were regarded as the highest and least committed errors respectively. Similarly, in recent research of Jegede, et al., (2023) which categorized the errors committed by engineering students in python programming into five. These errors include; Missing Symbols (30.0%), Invalid symbols (21.1%), Mismatched symbols (25.6%), Inappropriate naming (8.9%) and Excessive symbols (14.4%). The study further revealed that the topmost committed errors fall on Input and Output

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concepts (35.6%), as well as Loops (25.6%). Additionally, Kazemitabaar, et al., (2023) categories coding errors committed by learners into three; data-types, syntax, and semantics. These reviewed literatures revealed that divers programming errors are being committed by students. The researchers identified the errors. However, little attention was given to how these learners have been overcoming the complexity embedded in coding as they learn programming. Therefore, this current research intended to feel this gap by providing insight to how students teachers have been facing similar errors but debugging to get their codes running. It further provided implications for teaching and learning programming in Nigerian primary and secondary schools. To this end, the study assessed pre-service teachers' learning of python programming in Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Osun State.

The concepts of programming errors have been explained in the literatures. Prominent among the programming errors include Syntax Errors, Logic Errors, Runtime Errors, Semantic Errors, and Null Pointer Exceptions.

1. **Syntax Errors:** These errors occur when the code violates the rules of the programming language (Mase & Nel, 2021). Syntax Errors are committed due to invalid symbols, mismatched symbols, missing symbols, or inappropriate naming.
2. **Logic Errors:** Logic errors occur when the code does not produce the expected output due to flaws in the program's logic. These errors are often difficult to identify and can lead to unexpected behaviour or incorrect results. Ettles, et al., (2018) classified logic errors into three, namely; algorithmic errors, misinterpretation of the problem, and fundamental misconception.
3. **Runtime Errors:** Runtime errors occur during the execution of the program and can cause it to crash or terminate unexpectedly (Garion, et al., 2022). According to Kästner, et al., (2022) the errors are due to undefine or unspecify actions of the programming language in question. These errors can be caused by issues such as division by zero, accessing invalid memory, or using uninitialized variables (Liu et al., 2023).
4. **Semantic Errors:** Semantic errors occur when the grammatical rule of coding is violated or that the code is syntactically correct but does not perform the intended functionality (Silva, 2020). These errors are challenging to identify as they may not result in immediate errors or warnings.
5. **Null Pointer Exceptions:** Null pointer exceptions occur when a program attempts to access or manipulate an object or variable that has a null value. These errors can lead to program crashes and require careful handling of null values. Kästner et al. (2022) categorised dangling pointer accesses, invalid pointer dereferences and arithmetic, null pointer dereferences, misaligned dereferences, buffer overflows as Invalid pointer dereference and manipulation

To avoid these errors, it is essential to follow coding standards and best practices, use an integrated development environment (IDE) with syntax highlighting and error checking, and thoroughly test the code for all possible scenarios.

Objectives of the Study

Three specific objectives guided this study, these are to:

1. Assess the coding errors that preservice teachers in OAU do commit while learning python programming;
2. Determine how the OAU preservice teachers do debug the errors in python programming;
3. Examine the reasons informing the errors committed by the preservice teachers in python programming?

Research Questions

Three research questions were raised from the objective. These are:

1. What coding errors do preservice teachers in OAU commit while learning python programming?
2. How do OAU preservice teachers debug the errors in python programming?
3. Why do the OAU preservice teachers commit the errors in python programming?

Methodology

This paper adopted exploratory research design to elicit in-depth data from seven undergraduate student teachers. The sample size of 10 was randomly drawn from the population consisted of all students in the Department of Science and Technology Education in Faculty of Education, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria. According to Creswell and Creswell, (2017) researchers could estimate between 10 and 50 participants as being appropriate depending on type of research and research questions. Based on this assertion the selection of 10 participants could be termed appropriate. This sample size was used to give in depth insight to the study. Similarly, the department was purposively selected since it was the only one offering computer programming in the Faculty of Education. An interview guide was used to elicit data from the participants. The trustworthiness of the interview was obtained. In this study, the transcribed audio recordings (using Notta software) of the interviews were read, coded, and organised into themes (Dhlamini, 2022). To obtain the trustworthiness of the study, the

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researchers read the transcribed lesson study cycle, lesson observation notes, audio recordings repeatedly to understand what the undergraduate teachers were saying in the course of the interview. The trustworthiness of qualitative research could be established using four strategies, these are: audibility, confirmability, credibility and transferability. The data was Thematic Analysis Approach for the analysis (Creswell & Creswell, 2017). A thematic analysis approach was used to identify patterns and themes in the participants’ responses. The analysis process involved several steps, including familiarity of the data, coding of the data, and identification of themes. The themes were then further analysed descriptively to draw meaningful insights and results obtained.

Results

Research Question 1

What coding errors do preservice teachers in OAU commit while learning python programming?

Table 1: Coding errors committed by student teachers while learning python programming

Comments
<i>Spk1: ... but sometimes, I missed some commands like all those commas, and the computer shows some errors but not running.</i>
<i>Spk2: ...Using the wrong functions, hmm maybe skipping some step, and not inputting the right commands</i>
<i>Spk3: ...maybe where I am supposed to put dot, where I'm supposed to use some marks and stuffs like that.</i>
<i>Spk6: ...understanding the concept of loops, functions and modules. I also found it difficult to debug my code when I encountered such errors</i>
<i>Spk7: ...I found it difficult to remember the syntax and what I needed to use or do</i>
<i>Spk9: from full-stop, commas</i>

From the excerpts in Table 1 above, the student teachers identified six coding errors. Prominent among these errors were; missing commands, syntax errors, use of wrong functions and modules, skipping steps, logics, and looping. Additionally, Figure 1 was used to represent the preservice teachers’ comments regarding the coding errors often committed quantitatively.

Figure 1: Thematic Analysis of Python Errors Among Preservice Teachers from OAU

From Figure 1, 36% of the preservice teachers in Obafemi Awolowo University, commit missing commands errors, 22% syntax errors, 14% logics and use of wrong function/modules errors, while 7% commit looping and skipping steps. It can be concluded that off all these errors, the students’ teachers mostly committed missing command errors, followed by Syntax which often involved issues such as missing or misplaced punctuation, incorrect indentation, and incorrect use of python keywords.

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Research Question 2

How do OAU preservice teachers debug the errors in python programming?

With respect to the above research question, the student teachers were interviewed and audio recorded. The excerpts of their comments were illustrated in Table 2 below to show the different ways by which the preservice teachers were able to debug the various errors encountered during their learning of python programming.

Table 2: Debugging strategies adopted by student teachers while learning python programming

	Comments
Speaker 1	<i>...doing it again and trying to know why it's bringing the errors, ... I read through the lower part of the python interface or something, there is a red node that shows that this one is due to syntax, so I see some of those arrows and you can easily say, oh this is where I make a mistake and just fixing the writing, I get good results.</i>
Speaker 3	<i>...at least little ideas from my friends and everybody around that had understanding about it and, some people browsed the internet so I was able to get some helpful materials and all of that</i>
Speaker 4	<i>... I do like create a file to use to access it and, doing trial and error most times but my friends have been helpful.</i>
Speaker 5	<i>...I don't know, probably trial and error sha to see if it works out or not or get assistance from my friends.</i>
Speaker 6	<i>...by practicing more, watching online tutorials, and asking for help from my friends, classmate and instructors. I also tried to breakdown the concept into smaller parts and understand them one at a time</i>
Speaker 7	<i>...I did everything on my own by practicing more and using online resources like YouTube videos and python documentation</i>
Speaker 8	<i>...by creating a personal cheat sheet for functions and libraries that I use often. I tried to understand the logic behind each function and how it can be applied in each scenario</i>
Speaker 9	<i>...scanned through my work, and saw where I did not put full-stop, commas and some little things and then corrected it</i>
Speaker 10	<i>...I tried as much as possible to read and watch YouTube videos before going for practical</i>

From the excerpts in Table 2 above, the students identified seven strategies which they used to debug coding in Python. First; *doing it again*, help from friends, help from internet (YouTube), practicing more, creating file/sheet to access it better, trial and error and understanding the logic and breaking it down in order to debug it properly. The strategies used are represented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Python Programming Debugging Methods

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From Figure 2, the result showed seven strategies that the student teachers adopted to solve errors while coding in python. These strategies are help from friends (32%), help from internet (YouTube) (21%), understanding the logic and breaking it down (11%), trial and error (11%), creating file/sheet to access it (10%), practicing more (10%), and doing it again (5%). The most commonly mentioned strategy was peer collaboration, seeking help from friends that are good programming, followed was using online resources such as YouTube videos and other python documentations to find solutions to their coding errors and also to have more knowledge about python at large. Some preservice teachers also went ahead to practice more on their own as a strategy to debugging coding errors. While trying to do it over again was least of the strategies used in debugging coding errors.

Research Question 3

Why do OAU preservice teachers commit the errors in python programming?

With respect to the above research question, the student teachers were interviewed and audio recorded. The excerpts of their comments were illustrated in Table 3 to show reasons the categories of errors faced while learning of python programming.

Table 3: Reasons informing python programming errors committed by student teachers

	Comments
Speaker 1	<i>...some instructors or lecturers who make it even more tough. It's something you're learning, it should be interesting but then they make it look very hard and you know, it should be fun and interesting, ... if students can get their own personal laptop which they can be using to learn on a practical note, ... eh not so good environment to learn</i>
Speaker 2	<i>...like more practical should be included, like more of training, physical training. Students been invited to the lab to actually practice what they are been taught and to put their manuals into use.</i>
Speaker 3	<i>...basically, it's a tip of the iceberg that we are doing here. They are not too detailed on it, ... institution like OAU should employ more programming experts not only on python programming. They should encourage it because it's kind of something people are really into now</i>
Speaker 4	<i>... organize maybe physical class and not this kind of online of a thing where we can have a one-on-one interactions with lecturers and the lecturers would be able to help us out or put us through in learning it better</i>
Speaker 5	<i>... probably give us more examples, and make it more explanatory so that they get to know what we are doing if we are doing the right thing</i>
Speaker 6	<i>... opportunities for hands on learning and real-world projects would be helpful. It would also be helpful to have one-on-one support and resources for debugging and error handling</i>
Speaker 7	<i>... materials and equipment available to students and also, a one-on-one encountered should be okay and also, ...hands-on practice and more opportunities to collaborate with other students</i>
Speaker 8	<i>... enough facilities and instructors</i>
Speaker 9	<i>... more instructors to student ratio because we have not so many lecturers taking the course and also, make it a form of class tutorial</i>
Speaker 10	<i>... intelligent instructors to help facilitate learning process</i>

From the excerpts in Table 3 above, the preservice teachers identified six reasons why they committed the errors while learning python programming in OAU. The reasons include; Bad learning environment, limited practical's, limited instructors/experts in the field, limited facilities for learning, no detailed explanations and little or no examples to backup what they have learnt.

Figure 3: Reasons for Python Programming Errors Amongst OAU Students

The analysis of the interview data was categorized into six reasons why the student teachers committed the coding errors while learning python programming. One common reason was lack of detailed explanation on the part of the instructors, thinking that students already know what python and coding is all about. Preservice teachers also gave reasons that there were limited instructors and experts to explain in details what they should know about python programming. Also, another major reason OAU preservice teachers commit the errors in python programming is due to the fact that there are limited facilities which can go round once in the learning process as some students might miss out on some important information which the instructor would have passed across to the first batch as there is no uniformity. A few preservice teachers also said insufficient examples, limited practical and bad learning environment played a major factor as to the reasons they committed coding errors while learning python programming as they were unable to explore more due to lack of proper understanding.

Discussion of Findings

The study findings indicate six coding errors. These errors were 36% missing commands errors, 22% syntax errors, 14% logics and use of wrong function/modules errors, while 7% commit looping and skipping steps. The most prevalent of these errors was missing commands errors followed by syntax errors. This finding is consistent with previous research of Jegede et al. (2019) who found missing symbols and syntax toping errors committed by novice programmer. Similarly, Kazemitabaar et al. (2023) and Jegede et al. (2023) identified syntax errors as one of the errors often committed by learners. The prevalence of syntax error among other errors committed by students learning programming suggested that undergraduate student teachers may need more programming courses taught within their faculties, practice more, organised programming tutorials as well as guidance in understanding and applying the correct syntax in their code.

The findings also highlighted seven debugging strategies adopted by the undergraduate student teachers. These strategies are, help from friends (32%), help from internet (YouTube) (21%), understanding the logic and breaking it down (11%), trial and error (11%), creating file/sheet to access it (10%), practicing more (10%), and doing it again (5%). In previous study, use of YouTube to find help for codes and material, shared were suggested as a strategy to debugging (Weisberg, Schinazi, Ferrario, & Newcombe, 2023).

The study furthermore revealed six reasons why the student teachers committed the errors while learning coding. The reasons include: no detailed explanation (30%), limited instructors/experts (25%), limited practical (15%), limited facilities (15%), insufficient examples (10%) and bad learning environment (5%). The most mention challenge was no detailed explanation (30%), followed by limited instructors/experts (25%) while bad learning environment (5%) was less mentioned. The finding is similar to that of Jegede et al. (2023) who pointed out the need for efficient programming practical classes organised to build students coding skills amongst university undergraduates. Providing students with sufficient practice exercises and detailed explanations and opportunities for peer collaboration can mitigate these challenges and improve their overall coding skills.

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Conclusion

The findings revealed that student teachers faced coding bugs like missing commands errors, syntax errors, logics and use of wrong function/modules errors, as well as looping and skipping of steps errors. The student teachers also strategies various approaches to debug the errors confronting them while coding in python programming language. The findings also provided valuable insights to reasons for facing these challenges. Based on all these, this paper provided suggestions to enhance the teaching and learning of programming amongst preservice teachers.

Recommendations

The paper recommended that:

1. Pedagogy of programming languages should be taught in house the teachers training faculties across the country to improve preservice teachers' skills in programming languages;
2. Practical tutorial should be organised for undergraduate student teachers;
3. Access to internet facilities should be provided so that students learning programming can find help using YouTube and other resources

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Reconsidering Policy Implementation of Vocational Technical Education using 6-3-3-4 System of Education in Curbing Societal Problems

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Abstract

Vocational and Technical education as preserved in the Nigerian national policy on education, is connected with producing adequate and qualitative technological human resources directed towards a producing of trained, experienced and self-reliant craftsmen, technologists and technicians in the field of technical and vocational education for the general development of the country and its citizenry. However, the training of technical personnel has witnessed many hindrances and challenges originating from unrealistic policies, unclear curriculum that has little correlation with the needs of the society. In addition, misappropriation of fund meant for education development purposes, lack of qualified teachers, inadequate funding and cases of bribery and corruption are all connected to the poor implementation of the policy. This paper is aimed at providing a rethink in the implementation of 6334 system of education by examining the issues, challenges and the way forward in curbing out societal problems through Vocational and Technical Education.

Keywords: Education Policy, Vocational and Technical Education, 6-3-3-4 System of Education, Societal Problems

Introduction

The Nigerian education system has experienced a lot of changes in her educational policy. Education policy is directed towards increasing the quality of people's life. Education is a potent tool for all round development of an individual or a nation. Ebete., (2014) stressed that, education is a great investment of any nation economy. It increases the quality of the individuals in a nation and this helps to speed up the race for economic development. For this reason, the Federal government of Nigeria has adopted education as an instrument per excellence for effecting national development. In view of this, the government has reviewed the national policy severally in order to make it more functional and to meet up with the changes in the world of technology. One of Nigeria's national goals is to build a great and dynamic economy. The federal government came up with these policies that aim at transforming the economics standing of citizens and would want to use education to actualize these objectives. Various polices have been formulated but not well implemented or given enough time to evaluate the result. Unfortunately, not much has been achieved. (Eru, et al., 2019).

Prior to 1977 Nigeria functioned an educational policy inherited from British government at independence. The failure of this policy to satisfy the national aspiration of the country render it unpopular. In 1969 a national curriculum conference was organized which reviewed the inherited curriculum and identified new national goals for Nigerians education. A national seminar was organized by the National Education Research and Development Council (NERDC) in 1973 under the chairmanship of Chief S.O. Adebo. This gave rise to the National Policy on Education in 1977 which is derived from the National philosophy of the country (Mba & Ugulashi, 2022).

The national policy is anchored on Nigerian policy on education as expressed through the nation's objectives. Nigeria has five (5) main national objectives as provided by the second National Development Plan and accepted as the necessary foundation for the national policy on education. They are the building of: a free and democratic society; a just and egalitarian society; a united strong and self-reliant nation; a great and dynamic economy; a land of bright and full opportunities for all citizens (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2014).

Concept of Education Policy

The education policy of Nigeria is a general statement containing principles, regulations and rules, that govern many of the decisions on how to educate children, where to get them educated, where to get them employed, who to teach them, how to finance their education, what to teach, how to impact skills, goals, objectives and even the philosophy (Irhue.,2016). Okoye, and Arimonu., (2006) described policy as, a fundamental process through which an institution attains stability and undertakes changes as part of its ultimate goal. Policies are written or unwritten statement that guides the present and future thinking initiatives. It directs the decision of management. They are written when there are documents for reference purposes and are unwritten when made in form of pronouncements, that is, policy statement by people in power and authority (Babalola, 2019). In other words, policies are guides that usually provide latitude for operations. (Nwalado and Nwalado,2015). There should be a check in frequent changes in the system because policy inconsistency affects standards. Policies that followed the due process of law and public acceptability should not be thrown to the wind, by succeeding administration; instead areas of amendment could be identified and addressed for the purpose of continuity. Improvement on policy implementation in education is a noticeable national problem that has taken centre stage in Nigeria. Okoroma., (2006) observed that, there is a gap between educational policies and goal attainment due to inadequate implementation of policies. Formulation of policy sets the stage for implementation which according to (Irhue, 2016) is the most important aspect of planning.

In Nigeria, policy making at times is a mere attempt to rationalize political decisions. Actions are hastily and expediently conceived. The consequence of this is that many of Nigeria's educational policies are not reduced to those goals and objectives which can easily be attained given the range of problems and feasibilities involved in the allocation and utilization of available human and material resources.

Brief History of Policy Implementation from Pre-Independence Era to Date

Pre-Independence Era 1842-1960:

In 1883, the Portuguese missionaries are the sole providers of education in Nigeria. In 1892 Phelps Stokes (a philanthropic organization in America) presented a report which leads to the issuance of memorandum on education in British colonial territory in 1925. In 1952 the then director of education approves the opening of standard schools and the closure of sub-standard ones. When political parties come on board in the North, East and west, they had their education policies, this resulted in the formation of Universal Primary Education (UPE), free primary education in the west in 1955 and in the eastern region in 1957 with an attempt to increase access to formal education (Oladeji.,2018).

Education Policy During the First Republic 1960-1966:

The remarkable education policy of this era followed Eric Ashby report in 1960 which investigate Nigerians need in the field of post primary school certificate and higher education over the next 20 years. Four (4) universities were established and developed, they are Nsukka, Lagos, Ile-Ife and Zaria (Asiwaju, 1972).

Education Policy During Military Era 1966-1979:

After the civil war, the federal colleges were called UNITY SCHOOLS in all the states of the federation in a bid to encourage national reconciliation after the civil war. In addition, there is a policy to take over schools in which government exercised more control over the education system. A one-week national curriculum conference involving the entire cross-section of Nigerian populace was held in 1969. This was done bearing in mind the need of youths and adults in the task of nation building. After the acceptance of the white paper recommendation of the conference, a seven-man implementation committee was set up in 1977 as well as the establishment of NERC (National Education Research Council), introduction of Universal Primary Education and the number of universities in the country was increased to thirteen (13). Another great achievement is the establishment of JAMB to boost admission in to universities as well as setting up of NTI (National Teachers Institute) and NBTE (National Board for Technical Education) (Oladeji.,2018).

Education Policy During Second Republic to Second Military Era (1979-1999):

During this era, the NPE (National Policy on Education) was revised in 1981 and the introduction of 6-3-3-4 system of education in 1984. (Okoroma,2006). During this time, there is serious harsh economic condition and education system suffered a serious set-back. Oyeranmi., (2010) observed that, between 1983-1999 the country had five different regimes, and ministers of Education. The states were not exonerated from these changes. Each of the presidents, ministers, Governors and commissioners had different conceptions and policies on education for implementation during their tenure. With such instability in the system of governance most of the policies were abandoned half way probably because funds were not provided. The political and administrative inconsistencies were so much that they affected both policies and programs in the educational sector. Oyeranmi, (2010) noted the incessant changes and paucity of technocrats within the government. These resulted to lack

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of continuity of programs, fallen standards, and inconsistency. Nigeria has not earned a pass mark in this regard. In the light of these objectives there is needed to re-assess the steps taken by government to realize these noble objectives in education. For this reason, educational planners need to examine these fundamental problems in education.

Education Policy from 1999- Date:

The important features of Nigeria's Education policy as at 1998 is that of a philosophy for the country's education, which promotes teaching of Nigerian languages, and the introduction of prevocational and vocational technical subjects (FRN, 2014). This policy was also characterized by a 6-3-3-4 educational structure, which required a Nigerian child would spend a minimum of 6 years primary education, 3 years in both junior and senior secondary school and a minimum of 4 years in the university. In 2004, the policy on education was revised. Despite the latest policy incorporated the features of the previous one, the 2004 policy had a few new additions being 9-3-4 education structure. The 9-3-4 structure requires 9 years of basic education (which combines 6 years of primary and 3 years of junior secondary education) 3 years of senior secondary education and a minimum of 4 years of university education (Oranu.,2004).

6-3-3-4 System of Education:

It is believed that the 6-3-3-4 objectives was geared towards self-realization, better human relationship, national consciousness, national unity as well as social, cultural, economic, political scientific and technological progress. (Fabunmi., 1986). The 6-3-3-4 system of education has helped in the following areas:

1. It has assisted in the attainment of some of the objectives of National Policy on education, i.e. emphasis is now placed on yearning and aspirations of Nigerian society.
2. Students (both boys and girls) to some extents are now staying longer in schools.
3. The system has produced more matured youths who are able to take decisions on their own.
4. The system has reduced to some extent the rate of dropout in schools as opportunities are made available for students to develop their talents to the fullest.
5. The system has helped Nigeria nation to develop technologically as we have various Technical Colleges, Polytechnics and Universities of Technology in the country today that have produced more technicians and technologists.
6. The system to some extent has helped in catering for individual differences which pre-supposes differences in intelligence, physical ability and interest, and individual achievement-oriented goal and aspirations. This affords the individual learner the opportunity to develop his/her potentials.

However, with all these lofty achievements, the system has failed. It is an understatement that, the system of education being implemented in Nigeria today has lost the quality of 6-3-3-4 (Fabunmi,1986). If not for a handful of Nigerians who through dent of handwork, still reflects the indices of being educated, we should be taking of a total collapse of the sector.

Problems Associated with Policy Implementation

For more than thirty years the nation has not been able to successfully implement National policy on Education. The problem of policy implementation is traceable to the planning stage which according to (Marah.,2006) comes immediately after policy formulation. For policies and programmes to achieve desired result there should be proper planning. Most policies in education require long term planning and monitoring. For policies and programs to succeed, there should be stable government funds available, all the structures and facilities that will facilitate its implementation should be readily available. Adesina., (2012) noted that, planned implementation is constrained by the following factors.

1. Over estimation of available resources: This is a situation where estimated resources are greater than the actual available resources to implement programme.
2. Under estimation of cost implementing a plan: this happens when cost estimated does not make adequate provisions for inflation and actual implementation costs becomes unmanageable.
3. Over reliance upon external assistance: plans that substantially rely upon assistance from foreign sources for their implementation run into hitches when such aid fails to comes.
4. Inaccurate statistical data: planning education requires accurate and up-to-date data plan, this is usually not available and it leads to implementation problems. Ability to implement policies and programmes can be hindered by these additional factors such as; incompetent staff, insufficient information, distortions in the communication process, inconsistencies in the channel of communication, lack of political support Insubordination and Conflict (Reko & Maxwell., 2016).

Rethink in the Implementation of Vocational Technical Policy on Education in Nigeria through 6-3-3-4 system of Education

Nigeria, being a developing country, has been in continuous search for ways to become a developed country. This explains the reason why the government came up with the 6-3-3-4 policy on education. The 6-3-3-4 concept of education allows the child to spend six years at the primary level, three years at the junior secondary school level, another three years at the senior secondary level, and four years at the tertiary level.

1. Primary education with regard to the 6-3-3-4 system of education is the elementary type of education for children between ages 6 to 11 years. This is the foundation of education upon which all others are built. It therefore determines the success or failure of the whole system.
2. According to the FGN, (1984) “the broad aims of secondary education, with the overall education policy are:
 - a) Preparation for useful living within the society and
 - b) Preparation for higher education
3. Tertiary education which is the post-secondary education given in the higher institution aims at (i) the acquisition, development and inculcation of the proper value orientation for the survival of the individual and society at large; (ii) the development of the intellectual capabilities of individuals to understand and appreciate their environments (iii) the acquisition of both physical and intellectual skills which will enable individuals to develop, and (iv) the acquisition of the objective view of local and external environments” (Egugbo & Salami, 2021).

The 6-3-3-4 system of education was introduced in 1988 to replace the 6-5-4 system of education. This educational system was structured and designed to bring functionality in the system by producing graduates that make use of their head, heart and hands. The 6-3-3-4 system of education is job oriented because its emphasis is on manual activities, technical proficiency, and respect for dignity of labour and economic efficiency. It aimed at providing the child with basic tools to prepare him for local craft (Habeeb.,2022). In the secondary stage emphasis is on the acquisition of vocational skills; while it is professionally oriented at the tertiary stage. From the foregoing, it is very clear that the 6-3-3-4 system of education in Nigeria was introduced to cater for the needs of the individuals as well as the country. The world is dynamic and as such much emphasis is laid on Science and Technology. The nature of the present world shows that, the countries that are very serious with science and technology are far more developed than countries that have low level of science and technology development. Science and technology no doubt helps in the economic diversification with its attendant benefits such as employment generation, low level of poverty as well as reduction in the level of insecurity (Ibukun & Aboluwodi.,2010).

The 6-3-3-4 policy on education has encountered a surplus of challenges which made it not to achieve its desired objectives. A policy can be said to be successful if it achieves the desired goals. The 6-3-3-4 policy on education was formulated to ensure that students particularly in the secondary level acquire skills through vocational training that would enable them to be self-reliant upon graduation at different levels of their education. This is to say that, students who were unable to get to the senior secondary level would have acquired some skills at the junior secondary level which they can use to start their own job. Same with those who are able to finish the senior secondary education but are not able to proceed to tertiary institutions would have also acquired skills that would enable them to be self-reliant. Those who are able to get to tertiary institutions and graduate would have also acquired skills that would enable them to be self-reliant (Agbakosi & Akande., 2019).

The essence of the policy is that graduates from different educational levels have skills that would enable them to start their own job and not waiting for government to provide them with white collar jobs. If the policy had succeeded, the high level of unemployment and poverty as we have in Nigeria today would not have been the order of the day (Egugbo & Salami.,2021).

Challenges of 6-3-3-4 Educational Policy

The challenges facing the 6-3-3-4 policy on education include but not limited to the following:

1. **Inadequate skilled manpower.** As at the time the 6-3-3-4 policy on education was introduced, the country lacked and still lacks enough skilled manpower to train the students in various vocations as visualized by the policy-makers. The end result of this is that the vocational aspect of the policy did not succeed as expected (Egugbo & Salami, 2021).
2. **Lack of necessary instructional and infrastructural facilities.** Vocational training cannot be possible where there is shortage of instructional and infrastructural facilities such as well-equipped laboratories and workshops, and vocational equipment. Since the 6-3-3-4 policy on education emphasizes vocational training, there is no way the policy would have succeeded in an environment with inadequate or total lack of the necessary equipment needed for such vocational training (Okoye & Udoudo. 2015).

Reconsidering Policy Implementation ... (Suleiman & Ibrahim, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8370831>

3. **Epileptic power supply.** This is also another major challenge of the 6-3-3-4 policy on education. Issue of power has been a recurring challenge in Nigeria since the inception of the Nigerian state. Nigeria over the years has been experiencing epileptic power supply. Even in places where there is the availability of equipment, epileptic power supply serves as impediment to efficient and effective use of the available equipment (Egugbo & Salami.,2021).
4. **Lack of adequate funding.** It is very obvious that the education sector is not properly funded. The 6-3-3-4 policy on education requires proper funding to make it to succeed. The budgetary provision for education over the years has been very poor and nothing to write home about. There is no way the 6-3-3-4 educational policy would achieve its goals in the midst of poor funding (Nwafor et al., 2015)
5. **Lack of proper planning.** Dimock. *et al*, (1983) argued that, in its broadest sense: “Planning is thinking before acting, establishing goals before setting out, and appreciating the limitations of planning as well as the essential need for it”. The terrible failure of the 6-3-3-4 educational policy shows that, proper planning was not done before the formulation of the policy. According to Fafunwa (1982) “the training and procurement of teachers must precede all other considerations”. Fafunwa say that “the development of any educational level pre-supposes the availability of teachers in sufficient number to man the institutes. Widespread of curriculum reforms in schools to introduce technical education will be useless, unless qualified teachers are procured”.

Curbing Societal Problems through VTE

Unemployment and poverty among Nigerians, especially the youth is a major cause of insecurity and violent crimes in Nigeria (Ewetan & Urhie., 2014). Youth unemployment have contributed to the rising cases of violent conflict in Nigeria. According to the Nigeria Bureau of statistics, the rate of unemployment in Nigeria increased from 16.18% in the third quarter of 2017 to 17.72% in fourth the quarter of 2018. As of 2021, the rate of youth unemployment is 19.61% and it is as a result of this geometric increase in unemployment that has plunged Nigeria further into poverty. To confirm this, the result from world poverty clock in June 2018, shows that, Nigeria has the highest number of extremely poor individuals in the whole world above India. It is said that idle hands are the devil’s workshop, energetic youth who have nothing worthwhile to do will likely think of something bad or evil to do and this is the situation of millions of Nigerian youths today (Ewetan, & Urhie., (2014); Yang, Jin (2008).

Nigeria should be one of the countries where foreign investors are willing to invest because of its numerous natural resources and large population. However, Insecurity in Nigeria is on an increasing rate and it’s very worrisome to the extent that even the Nigerian security men that should protect the citizens have been attacked in their base several times and also government official has become victims of kidnapping and abduction. Countries around the globe are enthusiastically implementing technical and vocational education in order to provide employable skill to its citizens so as to ensure national integration and cohesion. It is believed that the more people are self-employed, the stronger the economy, the higher the standard of living, the more cohesive and well-integrated the citizenry of a nation. It is in this direction that (Habeeb., 2022) posits that the present democratic government is vigorously pursuing vocational and technical education towards providing employable skills to its citizens so as to ensure national integration and cohesion. This is because it follows that the more citizens of a nation are self-employed, the stronger the economy and the higher the standard of living.

Furthermore, Sadiq, et al. (2006) lamented that, nation building does not only lie on how best our natural resources are harnessed or managed, but lies more or less on how best the human assets of the nation are progressively educated. Furthermore, this is where vocational and technical education play a vital role. In addition, it was assert that, education is capable of bringing about change of negative attitude and values of a people and can be used to inculcate in them positive attitude of cooperation and national consciousness which cuts across regional and state boundaries. Nigeria is seen as a nation of division, conflict and diversity, which ranges from indiscipline, poor attitude to work, robbery, arson, bomb blast, religious and ethnic bigotry, all of which are evidence of national disintegration and lack of cohesion. Vocational/Technical education is capable of eradicating such social vices in the society which will bring about the desired national amalgamation and unity.

Conclusion

A careful examination of the 6-3-3-4 policy on education shows that, it is not only in the area of trained teachers the policy-makers did not consider appropriately but also in the area of power supply, availability of instructional materials and other infrastructure to support the policy as well as funding. All these factors are supposed to have been put into consideration before the 6-3-3-4 policy on education is made. The solution to the aforementioned problems is for the government of the day to have a rethink in the proper implementation of 6-3-3-4 system of education. This will help in curbing out our present societal

Reconsidering Policy Implementation ... (Suleiman & Ibrahim, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8370831>

problem as well as national progress and cohesion. In addition, a body should be established to oversee the affairs of schools and the learning environment; more funds should be budgeted to schools and universities for research. Teachers should be trained constantly; this will give room to pass across new ideas and means of bringing effective teaching and learning processes in the various fields of learning. More funds, grants and other forms of monetary support should be made available by the government for educational purposes.

Recommendations

After thorough review of the literature in relation to Vocational Technical Education using 6-3-3-4 System of Education in Curbing Societal Problems the paper suggests the following points as recommendation:

1. Government should struggle hard to have a stable policy in respects to education in the country.
2. There is need for constant training and retraining of teachers in an attempt to handle the Technical and Vocational trade in our Vocational and Technical Colleges in the country.
3. The Federal government of Nigeria should improve in the provision of funds for educational policies and programmes.
4. As a matter of urgency, Government should come up with policies and schemes in relation to vocationalisation in order to absorb the teeming unemployed youth to have something doing, this will help a lot in curbing out societal problems.
5. Stable electricity will help a lot in job creation in the country.

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Relationship between Child Abuse and Academic Achievement of Junior Secondary School Students in Southern Kaduna Senatorial District, Kaduna State

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Abstract

The study examined relationship between Child Abuse, Self-Esteem and Academic Achievement of Junior Secondary School Students in Southern Kaduna Senatorial District, Kaduna State. Four research questions guided the conduct of the study and four hypotheses were tested. Correlational research design was used for this study. The population for the study comprised 3,621 JSSII students and the sample of 351 respondents was used for the study. Two instruments were used for data collection, a structured questionnaire named Child Abuse and Self-esteem of Students Questionnaire (CASESQ) and English Language Achievement Test (ELAT). Mean and Standard Deviation was used to analyze the four research questions while inferential statistics of Pearson's Product Moment Correlation was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that there is significant relationship between physical abuse, sexual abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary student in southern senatorial district Kaduna state. Based on the findings, the study recommended amongst others that Government and non-Governmental organizations should liaise to ensure that child abuse through physical means is prohibited and discouraged. Enact law prohibiting child physical abuse of children and ensure that offenders are prosecuted. This will enhance learning achievement in schools.

Keywords; Physical Abuse, Sexual Abuse and Academic Achievement

Introduction

Education is regarded as the catalyst for development as well as a process for bringing positive change in the society. The invaluable roles and contributions of education in the development of an individual and the society cannot be over emphasized. This implies that children are the leaders of tomorrow therefore, anything that affects them at home will definitely affect their level of academic achievement. Academic achievement refers to how well a student is accomplishing his or her task and studies. Academic achievement represents performance outcomes that indicate the extent to which a person has accomplished specific goals that were the focus of activities in instructional environments, specifically in school, college, and university. Academic achievement should be considered to be a multifaceted construct that comprises different domains of learning. Because the field of academic achievement is very wide-ranging and covers a broad variety of educational outcomes, the definition of academic achievement depends on the indicators used to measure it. Among the many criteria that indicate academic achievement, there are very general indicators such as procedural and declarative knowledge acquired in an educational system, more curricular-based criteria such as grades or performance on an educational achievement test, and cumulative indicators of academic achievement such as educational degrees and certificates. Tenina (2013), observed that all criteria have one thing in common that they represent intellectual endeavors and thus, more or less, mirror the intellectual capacity of a person. In developed societies, academic achievement plays an important role in every person's life. Academic achievement as measured by the GPA (grade point average) or by standardized assessments designed for selection purpose such as the SAT (Scholastic Assessment Test) determines whether a student will have the opportunity to continue his or her education (e.g., to attend a university). Therefore, academic achievement defines whether one can take part in higher education, and based on the educational degrees one attains, influences one's vocational career after education. Besides the relevance for an individual, academic achievement is of utmost importance for the wealth of a nation and its prosperity (Kaplan & Saccuzzo, 2014).

Relationship between Child Abuse and ... (Adikwu & Aruwa, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8371018>

This study will provide information about different indicators of a students' academic achievement; such information will be used to analyze the strengths and weaknesses of a student academic achievement and to guide educational policy decisions. Given the individual and societal importance of academic achievement, it is not surprising that academic achievement is the research focus of many scientists; for example, in psychology or educational disciplines, the article focuses on the explanation, determination, enhancement, and assessment of academic achievement as investigated by educational psychologists. The history of child abuse is as old as humanity. It persists from century to century with different outlooks and in severity. Child abuse is any physical or mental injury, mistreatment, neglect, beating, and sexual molestation of a child by a parent, guardian, someone or the public (Nweze & Owo, 2014). Child abuse is becoming a universal phenomenal in the current world societies despite the fact the child's right have been recognized even to some extent, protected by legislation and constitutions in many countries of the world. Child abuse may probably have some major economic implications for Nigeria schools and their students. In Nigeria cases of child abuse is as common as the air we breathe in, this is in view of the fact that there can hardly be a day without news report about child abuse. Many of these cases of child abuse went unreported. Child abuse has been defined by the African network for the prevention and protection against child abuse and neglect (ANPPCAN) as the intentional and unintentional acts which endanger the physical health, emotional, moral and the educational welfare of the child. Augustine and Abubakar (2016), opined that there is no safe place for children anymore because child abuse is rampant everywhere. There are three major categories of child abuse: physical abuse, psychological or emotional abuse and verbal abuse (Peter & Anake, 2015).

Child abuse has become an apparent endless vicious cycle that hurts the image of the country and the dignity of those involved. Child abuse can occur in a child's home or in the originations, school, or communities the child interacts with. There are several categories of child abuse: neglect, physical abuse, psychological or emotional child maltreatment, children used in rituals, battering, early marriage, child soldering, child prostitution, children used in hawking, human trafficking, child abandonment, any act and series of acts of commission by a parent or other caregiver that results in harm or threat of harm to a child (Leeb et al., 2018). The researcher opined that child abuse is any act which result in death, serious physical or emotional harm, sexual abuse and exploitation, an act and failure to act which present an immerse risk of serious harm, therefore, child abuse is caused by poverty and lack of parental care, other factors include unemployment, conflicts and polygamous homes. Denga (2012), opined that child abuse is exposing children to painful and unwanted suffering knowingly or unknowingly.

According to Nweze and Owo (2014), child abuse has emerged as one of the serious social problems that need the attention of everyone due to the fact that it may have devastating effects on the academic achievement of students. Child abuse is still a hidden subject in Nigeria because most people who witness it simply ignore it. Child abuse sometimes leads to low self-esteem and self-interest in most of the students in southern senatorial district of Kaduna state which in turn encourages them to engage in a variety of self-destructive behaviors that affects their academic achievement as stated in the junior WAEC result of 2017 where 75% passed and 25% failed, while in 2018 46% passed and 54% failed, and in2019, 42% passed and 58% failed English Language, as reported by Zonal office Kafanchan in 2021.

Physical abuse is one of the most common forms of child maltreatment. Physical abuse is the injury inflicted upon a person with cruel and/or malicious intent. Physical abuse can be punching, kicking, biting, burning, or harming a person physically. According to World Health Organization 2019, Physical abuse is an action or inaction which result in actual or potential physical harm, that are within the control of or preventable by parents, care givers, or authorized persons (such as school teachers). physical abuse is any intentional act causing injury or trauma to another person by way of bodily contact. In most cases, children are the victims as in cases of domestic violence, physical violence and physical assault. Physical abuse is intentional bodily injury like slapping, kicking, pinching, choking, shoving, or inappropriately using drugs or physical restraints on an individual. Physical abuse according to Elarousy and Shaqiqi (2017) is the intentional use of physical force against a person that can lead to harm for the individual's health, survival and development. Physical abuse can be anything that causes pain to any part of the body like slapping, hitting or kicking. Physical abuse can be in a form of domestic violence or family violence. Physical abuse is when a parent, a primary caregiver, or any other person who has responsibility for the person through an action like beating or stabbing, causes injury, death, emotional harm, or risk of serious harm to an individual (Altafim & Linhares, 2016).

Sexual abuse is passive in every part of the world. The problem of sexual abuse has received the attention of scholars from a variety of life domains. (Menon et al, 2011). Its consequences are devastating as sexually abused victims may show many internalized and externalized behavioral, emotional and cognitive problems during childhood and adulthood. Sexual abuse has been defined as the involvement of a person in sexual activity that he or she does not fully comprehend and is unable to give informed consent to and for which the person is not developmentally prepared. According to Murray (2014), sexual

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abuse towards children and adolescents is a stark reality worldwide. Most children and families do not report cases of abuse and exploitation probably because of stigma, fear and lack of trust in the authorities. The National Demographic Health Survey (NDHS) report in 2008 suggest that over 25% of adolescents in Nigeria often experience the first sexual abuse at the age of 15 years. However, cases reported are less than unreported cases by parents and guidance of the victim. A common misconception about sexual abuse is that it is a rare event against girls by male in poor inner-city areas. Sexual abuse is a global phenomenon that may occur across cultures and socio-economic groups might have profound long term negative consequences.

That a child needs academic achievement to succeed in life is a fact that is unquestionable. Despite the increase in effort by both the Nigerian government and Kaduna State in particular towards improving the quality of learning in the State secondary school education, poor academic achievement persists especially in English language within the southern senatorial district of the state. The incessant poor performance of student at the junior WAEC examination in English Language is worrisome. In 2017, 75% passed while 25% failed, in 2018, 46% passed and 54% failed, in 2019, 42% passed and 58% failed report by Zonal office kafanchan. This became a source of concern to the researcher. Academic achievement liberates people from the shackles of illiteracy and make one a better citizen in the society. Humans continue to acquire knowledge right from childhood till death. It is a fact that human gives birth to baby with empty brain that is no form of knowledge in the brain during child birth which is what psychologist called *Tabula Rasa*. As human grow in life they continue to acquire knowledge right from childhood. This happens to be a period in life where the human brain is much active to receive knowledge. Physically abused children seem to perform worst in school compared with non-abused peers. The researcher observed that children that are subject to physical and sexual abuse, might lack self-confidence, and find it tough to perform better in school. Nekesa (2009), carried out a study on the influence of child abuse on children's attendance and discipline in secondary schools in Kampala District, Uganda. The study was carried out after evidence of increased child abuse in different parts of Uganda. The design for the study was survey. The population of the study was 83 students randomly selected from 8 schools of Kampala District. The methods of data collection were questionnaire and interview and the method of data analysis was chart and percentage. The study found out that there was a strong positive correlation between child abuse and school attendance. There were many cases of children who failed to go to school because of child abuse. There were also more cases of indiscipline among children who experienced child abuse.

Obinaju (2010) conducted a study on the relationship between sexual abuse and academic performance of junior secondary school students Iseinyi, Oyo state, Ibadon. The subjects were 475 (282 males and 193 females). The subjects were JS III students who were in their final year of Junior Secondary School. They were from 12 selected secondary schools in the education zone within the area of study. When the sample was drawn, the students had sat for the Junior Secondary School Certificate Examination (JSCE) at the end of their third year in school. They had also resumed Senior Secondary One (SS1) at the time of the data collection. The classes used were randomly selected. The sample of 480 students (20 students from each of 12 schools) was drawn from the educational zone. Five of the 480 students were not accounted for in the study, making the subjects to be 475. A four-point likert scale questionnaire was used for data collection. Data were analyzed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). From his findings he mentions female genital mutilation as one form of child abuse. This also falls under child abuse. This also falls under child sexual abuse because it causes harm to the sexual emotion of the girl child. Wrong statistical tools were used in the previous study and a larger sample size was used compare to the present study. The former study was carried out in the western region of Nigeria while the present study will be carried out in Northwest Nigeria.

Elarousy (2017) conducted a study on physical abuse and academic achievement of students in Government secondary school Jeddah. Three research questions were raised. Non probability convenience sampling was used to select 200 participants for the study; data analyzed using IBM, SPSS software package version 20.0. Qualitative data was described using number and percentage, while quantitative was described using minimum and maximum mean and standard deviation. The study found that physical abuse has a significant effect on academic achievement of secondary school students. The finding also confirms physical abuse includes inflicting pain on the physical body of the individual. The previous study was carried out outside Nigeria, while the present is in Nigeria. The two studies varied in their geographical locations, the former was carried out in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia while the present study will be carried out in Northwest, Nigeria. Onyeonu (2013) studied relationship between sexual abuse and academic achievement of secondary school students in Ikwere, River state. The researcher's targeted population consisted of teachers and students in Ikwere Local Government. 40 and 80 was sampled from teachers and students respectively. The instrument used for data collection by the researcher was a 25-item questionnaire well validated was used. Data collected were analyzed using Pearson product moment correlation. The findings revealed that there is positive relationship between sexual abuse and academic performance of secondary school students. Based on the findings, recommendations were made on the need to affectionate and intensified campaigns for awareness creation on the menace of

Relationship between Child Abuse and ... (Adikwu & Aruwa, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8371018>

sexual abuse as they deaden the future of the child, family and society. The researcher chooses Kaduna south Senatorial District as the focal area of study because it is one of the zones that have the loudest out-cry of number of out of school children which is not in tune with national policy on education. Therefore, these variables are selected because little or no attention has been given to them by the previous researchers in the area of study. The thrust of this study therefore, is to examine the relationship between Child-abuse and academic achievement of Junior Secondary School students in Southern Senatorial District, Kaduna State.

Objectives of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to examine the relationship between child abuse, self-esteem and academic achievement of junior secondary school students in southern Kaduna senatorial district, Kaduna State. Specifically, the sought to:

1. Examine the relationship between physical abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary school students in southern senatorial district, Kaduna state.
2. To determine the relationship between sexual abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary school students.

Research Questions

1. What is the relationship between physical abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary school students in southern senatorial district, Kaduna State?
2. Is there a relationship between sexual abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary school students?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between physical abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary school students.
2. There is no significant relationship between sexual abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary school students

Methodology

Correlational survey research design was used in this study. Correlational survey establishes relationships or association between two or more variables. It establishes the direction and magnitude of relationships or association between and among variables (Uzoечи, 2015). The population of the study comprises of 3,621 JSS11 students in the Southern Kaduna Senatorial District, of Kaduna State. The sample for this study was 351 respondents drawn from 8 junior secondary schools in the study area using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table for determining sample size from a given population. Simple random and proportionate sampling technique were used. Two instruments were used for data collection. A structured Questionnaire named child abuse and self-esteem of students' questionnaire (CASESQ) was constructed by the researcher, and an achievement test was conducted in English Language (termed English Language Achievement Test, ELAT) to measure the student's performance. The instrument is divided into four section A and B which contained questions on the research objectives. Experts subjected the instruments to critical appraisal for face construct and content validity which gave .81 for CASESQ and .86 for (ELAT) as rated by the experts. It yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.83. Mean and standard deviation was used to analyze the descriptive data. Any average mean value below 3.00 is considered low while those above it were considered high. Inferential statistics of Pearson's product moment correlation was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the relationship between physical abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary school students in southern senatorial district, Kaduna State?

Relationship between Child Abuse and ... (Adikwu & Aruwa, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8371018>

Table 1: Mean and standard Deviation Showing Relationship between Physical Abuse and Students' Academic Achievement and Academic Performance of Secondary School Students

SN	Relationship between Physical Abuse and Academic Achievement	Mean	Std. Deviation	Remarks
1	I feel bad when others inflict pain on me	3.02	0.70	Agree
2	I feel okay when I am beaten	2.82	1.13	Agree
3	More task makes me refrain from causing injury to others	3.02	0.70	Agree
4	Home assignment makes it difficult for me to cause pain to others	2.84	1.15	Agree
5	Fear from physical injury can affect my studies	2.79	1.35	Agree
6	Being physically insulted makes me want to refrain from going to school	2.76	1.32	Agree
7	Feeling sad from experiencing physical abuse affects my grades	2.74	0.68	Agree
8	Unnecessary been beating by teachers and classmates before and during assessment affects my studies	3.03	0.71	Agree
Average mean		2.88		

Table 1 shows the views of respondents on relationship between physical abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary school students in southern senatorial district, Kaduna State. Results show that mean values of 3.02, 2.82, 3.02 and 2.84, 2.79, 2.76, 2.74 and 3.03 was obtained while standard deviation values of 0.70, 1.13, 0.70, 1.15, 1.35, 1.32, 0.68 and 0.71 was obtained. The average mean was given as 2.88. This value is above the acceptance mean value of 2.50. Hence, there is a high relationship between physical abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary school students in southern senatorial district, Kaduna State.

Research Question 2

What is the relationship between Sexual abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary school students in southern senatorial district, Kaduna State

Table 2: Mean and standard Deviation Showing Relationship between Sexual Abuse and Students' Academic Achievement and Academic Performance of Secondary School

SN	Relationship between Sexual Abuse and Academic Achievement	Mean	Std. Dev	Remarks
9	I use to have sex with known persons	2.70	1.23	Agree
10	My parents taught me that my body is my own	2.76	0.70	Agree
11	I have never been forced to have sex	2.74	0.68	Agree
12	I have not engaged in sexual relationship	2.77	1.21	Agree
13	I feel highly uncomfortable when an elderly person make sex advances towards me	3.53	0.63	Agree
14	I have ever been forced to have sex with my siblings	2.49	1.27	Disagree
15	Illicit sexual experience hinders me to relate freely with people	2.76	0.70	Agree
16	Illicit sex makes me feel tired during class	2.76	0.70	Agree
Average mean		2.81		

Table 2 shows the views of respondents on relationship between sexual abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary school students in southern senatorial district, Kaduna State. Results show that mean values of 2.70, 2.76, 2.74 and 2.77, 3.53, 2.49, 2.76 and 2.76 was obtained while standard deviation values of 1.23, 0.70, 0.68, 1.21, 0.63, 1.27, 0.70 and 0.70 was obtained. The average mean was given as 2.81. This value is above the acceptance mean value of 2.50. Hence, there is a high relationship between sexual abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary school students in southern senatorial district, Kaduna State.

Relationship between Child Abuse and ... (Adikwu & Aruwa, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8371018>

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between physical abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary school students.

Significance of Relationship between physical abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary school students.

Variables	N	R	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision
Physical abuse	351	0.67	0.001	Reject H ₀
Academic achievement	351			

$\alpha = 0.05$

From table the calculated value of Pearson’s product moment statistics is given as 0.67 while the p-value (probability value) is given as 0.001. Hence, $p: 0.001 < 0.05$. Since the p- value of Pearson’s product moment correlation (0.001) is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, it implies there is a significant relationship between physical abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary school students in southern senatorial district, Kaduna State.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant relationship between sexual abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary school students in southern senatorial district, Kaduna State

Table 4: Significance of Relationship between sexual abuse and Academic Achievement of Junior Secondary School Students.

Variables	N	R	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision
Physical abuse	351	0.73	0.000	Reject H ₀
Academic achievement	351			

$\alpha = 0.05$

From table 4, the calculated value of Pearson’s product moment statistics is given as 0.73 while the p-value (probability value) is given as 0.000. Hence, $p: 0.000 < 0.05$. Since the p- value of Pearson’s product moment correlation (0.000) is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, it implies there is a significant relationship between sexual abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary school students in southern senatorial district, Kaduna State.

Discussion of Findings

The findings from hypothesis one revealed there is a significant relationship between physical abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary school students in southern senatorial district, Kaduna State. This finding is similar to the findings of Elarousy (2017) which showed a significant relationship between physical abuse and academic achievement of students in Government secondary school Jeddah. In addition, Adejobi et al (2013) posited that Physical child abuse refers to any disciplinary method that leaves a mark on the child. Physically abused school children may continue to function more poorly than the non-maltreated peers on a variety of academic and socio emotional measures. They may also have lower grades, more suspensions, and more grade repetitions, show less academic engagement, more social skill deficits and lower ego resiliency than the non-maltreated children, manifest multiple forms of academic risk and might show more externalizing and internalizing behavior problems.

The findings from hypothesis two revealed there is a significant relationship between sexual abuse and academic achievement of junior secondary school students in southern senatorial district, Kaduna State. This finding is in agreement with those of Onyeonu (2013) which showed positive relationship between sexual abuse and academic performance of secondary school students. According to Alokun (2018), sexually abused children may function poorly than non-sexually abused peers on a variety of academic and socio emotional measures. They may also manifest multiple forms of academic risk and show more externalizing and internalizing behavior problems and may also loss interest in academic activities (Elarousy &Shaqiqi, 2017). Burnham (2019) opined that sexually abused students may suffer from lower social and emotional competence, diminished academic achievement and fear of more sexual abuse in sexually abused students, cognitive ability and memory scores as well as academic achievement may be lower than their peers, they may score lower on cognitive assessments and standardized tests of academic achievement, and might get suspended from school.

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Conclusion

Based on the findings that emerged from this study, it was concluded that each form of child abuse had independently related to physical abuse and sexual abuse as they results showed a significant relationship on students' academic achievement. Child abuse can affect all domains of development- physical abuse and sexual abuse all of which are interrelated.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the researchers recommend that:

1. The government and non-governmental organizations should liaise to ensure that child abuse through physical means is prohibited and discouraged. There laws prohibiting child physical abuse of children should be activated to ensure that offenders are prosecuted. This will enhance learning achievement in schools.
2. Parents and the society at large should be sensitized on the dangers of child sexual abuse. This should be done using mass media. With the help of NGO'S and members of the public, parents or guardians who are guilty should be arrested and prosecuted appropriately. This will ensure parents and guardians are responsible enough to enhance child academic achievement.

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Reliability Index of Revised Two-Factor Study Process Questionnaire (R-SPQ-2F) for Assessing Learning Approaches of Nigerian University Education Students

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Abstract

This research assessed reliability index of revised two-factor study process questionnaire (R-SPQ-2F) among Nigerian university education students. Ex post facto design was used. The study used 101 students as samples drawn from the university. The Revised Two-Factor Study Process Questionnaire (R-SPQ-2F) was adopted to measure learning approaches and analysis of the Cronbach's Alpha and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient statistical tools were used to get the index level of reliability of R-SPQ-2F. One hypothesis was formulated and tested. The analysis revealed that this instrument scored .77 on Cronbach Alpha levels, which displayed a very high positive relationship and the result of the analysis of PPMC index level of reliability of R-SPQ-2F was .626, which indicates a high positive relationship as well.

Keywords: learning approaches, reliability index, Cronbach's Alpha, Pearson Product Moment Correlation

Introduction

University education in Nigeria has nowadays becomes the yearnings and aspirations of our teeming young men and women in the country. These youth will come into the university environment with varying motives and strategies about learning at the university level. There emerged the need to study how and why students at higher institution of learning came to study. Many scholars have delved into developing instruments to monitor students' learning at this level. These include Approaches to Study Inventory (ASI) by (Entwistle & Ramsden, 1983) Learning and Study Strategies Inventory by Weinstein, Schult, & Palmer, (1987) Study Process Questionnaire by Biggs (1987) and Revised Two-Factor Study Process Questionnaire (R-SPQ-2F) was later developed by Biggs, Kember, & Leung (2001).

The study on how students approach their learning has just begun in Nigeria, using the concepts: *deep* approach and *surface* approach to learning. This theory which begun in Europe, has found wider acceptance and usage in Asia. Marton and Säljö (1976) was the pioneer of the study of students learning approaches in higher education. These scholars worked on how and why students engage in learning at the University of Gotenburg, Sweden, and came to discover that there were two categories of approaches students adopt in their studies, namely, *deep* approach and *surface* approach. That is to say, Marton and Säljö (1976a & 1976b) came up with the idea of "approach to learning", which became the point of departure and therefore the emerging conceptual framework known generically as "student approaches to learning" (SAL) theory (Biggs, 1993a; Entwistle & Waterston, 1988). SAL theory has in fact become a meta-theory for conceptualizing teaching and learning, which has gone in two major directions: phenomenography (Marton, 1981; Prosser & Trigwell, 1998) and constructivism and systems theory (Biggs, 1999; Dart & Boulton-Lewis, 1998). The questionnaire was also developed before the insights into approaches to learning gained from the intensive study of the approaches of Asian students (Kember, 1996; Watkins & Biggs, 1996). For this simple two-factor version of the SPQ the intention was not to develop scales which fully characterized the possible combinations of understanding and memorizing. The work, though, was utilized to ensure that the deep and surface approach items were consistent with the clearer descriptions which had emerged from this body of work. It was on these concepts many higher education researchers built on in their studies. Several scholars have established that the learning approach adopted by a student is related to the quality of his learning outcome (Subasinghe and Wanniachchi, 2013 and Valadas, 2013).

Negash, Eshete and Hanago (2022) stated that, learning approaches are strategies applied to learning that are critical to success, considered essential for acquiring good grades, and useful for learning throughout one's life. According to Mel (2021), deep learning is a committed approach to learning where the learner uses higher-order cognitive skills to master

Reliability Index of Revised Two-Factor ... (Gurjiya & Muhammad) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8371059>

academic content, work collaboratively and think and interact critically and actively with the content being learned. While surface learning is more concern with passing the course with little effort, and many times engage in memorization of learning material. Sagar (2020) put forth that, the deep learning approach encourages learners to think critically, understand meaning and can apply what they learn to new situations and contexts. In addition, Amadi and Ironanya (2020) also stated that the essence of deep learning understands true knowing. However, for surface learning, learners tend to avoid the hard work and instead rely on single source of information, and as a result, they learn only what is required but nothing more (Biggs 1999 in Mel, 2021), (Hussin, Hamed and Jam 2017). Furthermore, the surface learning is a rather passive approach to learning where students scraping the surface of the material being studied and concentrating only on the assessment requirements without getting into the details, with the only intention of passing the exams or test (Mel, 2021). Meanwhile, Pute, Abdul-Latif, Mansor and Halid (2018) also stated that a student using a surface approach only intended to capture contents in total, rather than understand it thoroughly.

According to D'cruzand, Rajaratnam (2018) pointed out that, the surface learning approach is memorizing, syllabus-bound, and exam-oriented, whereas the deep approach to learning is seeking for meaning, relating ideas, and using evidence in learning. While Brown, White, Wakeling and Naiker (2015) stated that, a deep approach to learning can help students to understand the concept and improve their academic performance. Students may follow the surface learning approach due to fear of failure, stress, and lack of purpose.

The surface approach is totally in distinction with the deep approach. Therefore, it is important for the educators to understand the different ways how the students learn and interpret. Understanding the learner types among our students is very important in helping and guiding them in their more meaningful learning process. This is because of the learning approaches will influence the academic attainment. According to Cetin and Mart (2016), the massive gaps between deep and surface approaches have been consistently established across a large variety of qualitative and quantitative studies in numerous countries and study fields through diverse testing methods. Learning approaches have been linked to the performance of students' learning outcomes, which may depend to the evaluation approach used. Desierto, Maio, Rourke and Edith (2019) put forth that, in moving from surface to deep learning strategies, students can alternate between both learning approaches depending on their academic tasks or when struggling with their workloads.

A sample of health science students from a university in Hong Kong were asked to complete the questionnaire. A total of 229 usable questionnaires were returned, with a high return rate since the questionnaires were handed out for completion in class. The Cronbach alpha values are 0.73 for Deep Approach and 0.64 for Surface Approach in the sample, which are considered as acceptable.

Negash, Eshete and Hanago (2022) conducted research on Students' learning approaches as a factor of academic achievement at selected public universities: A cross-sectional study a cross-sectional study was conducted on 123 anesthesia students. All 3rd- and 4th-year students were recruited for the study. Approaches to Study Skills Inventory for Students (ASSIST) were used to assess students' learning approaches. Perceived performance, cumulative grade point average (CGPA), and 100 Multiple Choice Questions items were used to assess academic achievement. Data were entered into Epi-data and exported to SPSS for statistical analysis. An independent *t*-test was used to determine the presence of a difference in academic achievement across learning approaches. Bivariate and multivariable linear regressions were fitted to assess the association of students' characteristics and learning approaches with their academic achievement. A *P*-value of less than 0.05 was used to declare the statistical significance.

Gurjiya (2021) conducted an investigation on gender disparity in learning approaches and academic performance among Colleges of Education students in Katsina state. The researcher used 333 students as samples drawn from three tertiary institutions. The study did not find any significant difference in the academic performance of male deep learners and female deep learners' approach. So also, the study did not find any significant difference in the academic performance of male surface learners and female surface learners.

Roslandb and Abdullah (2021) examined students' intention to engage in deep learning with the aim to understand them better. According to their finding, majority of students practice surface learning approach. They used Theory of Planned Behavior, where they related the components of the theory with main quest of students' intention to engage in deep learning, where the attainable predictors are students' attitude, subjective norm, and perceived behavioral control. Online survey was conducted and analyzed both statistically and descriptively, revealed that students are deep learners. The model was also found significant, with all three predictors were positive and significantly contributing to students' intention to engage in deep learning. Nonetheless, detailed analysis suggests that none of the predictors appeared to have a stronger effect over the others.

Reliability Index of Revised Two-Factor ... (Gurjiya & Muhammad) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8371059>

The findings from their study confirm the applicability of the Theory of Planned Behavior in explaining students' intention to engage in deep learning.

Samosa (2021) investigated on Cooperative Learning Approach as Innovation to Improve Students' Academic Achievement and Attitude in Teaching Biology. The study sought to determine the effectiveness of cooperative learning approach against conventional teaching. The study employed the experimental type of research. The design compared the result obtained from researcher – made - achievement test and attitude survey in biology in experimental sample which is cooperative learning approach with the control sample exposed to Direct Instruction. The study revealed that the gained scores of the experimental group gained 41.86 % from the pre- and post-achievement test greater than the controlled group gained score of 36.49 %. Furthermore, in the attitude survey showed that the experimental group gained 81.90 % from the pre- and post-attitude survey which was greater than the control group gained 81.69%. Using t- test of significance in both control group and experimental group showed that there is no significance difference between pre – achievement test and post – achievement test at probability level of greater than 0.05. In F -test revealed that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of pre-attitude score and post- attitude score of the control and experimental groups.

Mel (2021) conducted study on Deep versus Surface Learning: A Study among Thermodynamics Students in Politeknik Kuching Sarawak, Malaysia. The study showed that deep learning approach was the most dominant learning approach used by the students. Then, the study also showed that the deep learning approach had positive correlation with academic attainment while the surface learning approach was inversely proportional with academic attainment. Therefore, students are encouraging to become a deep learner rather than surface learner. Furthermore, the study also revealed that the significant of educators to teach awareness to the students on the different approaches in their learning. Thus, by promoting or inducing the deep learning approach among students, it is hope that the surface approach to learning can be minimized. Educators also need to be aware that their teaching practices can affect the intention of the students to learning too.

The two broad learning approaches, deep and surface have consistently emerged through research in this area. Students' learning approaches are particularly important to teachers because they are not fixed traits and are susceptible to outside influences, especially the learning environment, teaching methods and assessment tools. With knowledge of strategies, which encourage deep learning and surface learning by teachers, students' learning at higher level of education will be improved. This paper investigated the reliability index of Revised Two-Factor Study Process Questionnaire (R-SPQ-2F) learning approach instrument among Nigerian university education students of Sule Lamido University, Kafin Hausa, Jigawa State, North West, Nigeria.

Objective of the Study

The objective of this study is to assess whether Revised Two-Factor Study Process Questionnaire (R-SPQ-2F) is a reliable instrument for assessing learning approach among Nigerian university education students.

Hypothesis

Revised Two-Factor Study Process Questionnaire (R-SPQ-2F) is not a reliable instrument for assessing learning approach among Nigerian university education students.

Methodology

Data about students' learning approaches was obtained via Revised Two-Factor Study Process Questionnaire (R-SPQ-2F) developed by Biggs, Kember and Leung (2001). The instrument used in the study was the 20-item revised Two-Factor Study Process Questionnaire (R-SPQ-2F) developed by Biggs, Kember and Leung (2001) which had a reliability index of .66 was adopted. It has two sections: Section A contains personal information of the participants and Section B contains the 20-item 5-Point Likert Statements loaded with deep/surface learning approaches.

The sample of the study was 101 education students drawn from Sule Lamido University, Kafin Hausa, Jigawa State, North-West, Nigeria. The researcher used one day in the institution to administer the questionnaire with the assistance of the lecturer holding lectures at the time of the visit. The subjects were then requested to fill in and submit the questionnaire there and then. The data collected were at the interval and the hypothesis was tested using Cronbach's Alpha and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient statistics.

Results

Hypothesis Testing

Revised Two-Factor Study Process Questionnaire (R-SPQ-2F) is not a reliable instrument for assessing learning approaches of Nigerian university education students.

Table 1: Analysis of the Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Statistics of R-SPQ-2F (N = 101)

VV Cronbach's Alpha	Nn	N of Items
...7 .770	222	2

Table 1 presents the result of analysis of the Cronbach's Alpha index level of reliability of R-SPQ-2F. The analysis revealed that the instrument scored .77 Alpha levels, which displayed a very high reliability index. This has invariably indicated that the instrument is reliable in identifying both the deep and surface variables among university students given the Alpha level the instrument scored.

Discussion of Findings

The result of the study revealed that Revised Two-Factor Study Process Questionnaire (R-SPQ-2F) is a reliable instrument for assessing learning approaches of Nigerian university education students. In order words, the instrument has been found to have good items that can fish out deep learners and surface learners among students. The result is concurrent with that of Gurjiya (2015), Biggs, Kember, & Leung, (2001), who also reported a significant relationship in learning approach between deep learning approach sub-scale and surface learning approach. The students have now understood the expectation of the learning environment and the assessment tools being in use by the teachers in the university. Where a course requires one to use deep approach or surface approach, the students were quick at switching to the mode that gives greater advantage of getting higher grades.

Conclusion

The study concludes that Revised Two-Factor Study Process Questionnaire (R-SPQ-2F) has an index of .77 hence, is a reliable instrument for assessing learning approaches of university education students in Nigerian.

Recommendation

The Revised Two Factors study process questionnaire should be employed by teachers as a tool for evaluating classroom instructions and researching on students' learning approaches.

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Students' Psycho-social Disposition and its Influence on Mathematics Achievement of Senior Secondary Schools in FCT, Abuja

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Abstract

This study is on Students' Psycho-social Disposition and its influence on Mathematics achievement of senior secondary schools in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. The purpose of this study therefore is to investigate students' Psycho-social Disposition and as it influences their achievement in mathematics. Three objectives and research questions guided this study. Using Krejcie and Morgan (1970), a sample size of 384 respondents were randomly selected from school with total population of 24,771 students through simple random sampling techniques. Data was collected the use of two instruments. Mean score and standard deviation and t-test was used to test the formulated null hypotheses. All statistical analysis was conducted with a significant level of 0.05. There is a significant influence of students' attitudes on mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students of FCT, Abuja. It was recommended that Mathematics teachers should be creative in adopting various in the teaching and learning of mathematics so that the anxiety associated with mathematics can be controlled in such a way that learners develop the needed confidence that will improve their academic achievement.

Keywords: Psycho-socio Deposition, Attitude, Anxiety and academic achievement

Introduction

Mathematics like any other compulsory and examinable subject offered in both primary and secondary school levels in Nigeria plays a key role in shaping how individuals deal with various spheres of private, social and civil life (Anthony & Walshaw, 2009). The Government of Nigeria acknowledges the importance of Mathematics and Sciences in achieving Sustainable Development Goals and in the attainment of the Vision 2030 as would provide the necessary manpower to steer the country into new technological and industrial development. This is evidenced by the concerted effort by the Government through the Ministry of Education to improve the performance both in primary and secondary mathematics through the implementation of SMASSE project. However, the low performance in the subject has persisted despite the desperate attempts to provide enough teachers, facilities and in-service training for teachers and provision of other necessary materials posing a lot of concerns to all stakeholders in Education. This implies that there are other factors at play that need to be further investigated. An analysis of performance in Basic Certificate Examination results below reveals that Mathematics is among the poorly performed subject which also is the case in most schools in the country.

All subjects have their areas of application in real life activities, but among them; Mathematics is the most important. Mathematics is a tool that can be used in our daily activities to provide solution to some difficulties faced in life. The knowledge of Mathematics is so relevant to the extent that it has been considered as one of the most important core subjects in the school curriculum. With the advancement in information communication technology, Mathematics has also gained more attention and importance. It is so necessary today for people of all ages to be effectively and efficiently knowledgeable in Mathematics for application and analysis of their works in order to be successful citizen in this information age (Peteros, et.al; 2019).

Because of these immeasurable benefits of Mathematics in the society, the poor Mathematics achievement of students becomes a thing of concern in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. The researcher has observed that achievement in mathematics is a function of many interrelated variables which can be grouped as student factors, school factors and home factors. Student factors are regarded by some researchers as a key factor to be taken into account when attempting to understand and explain the student achievement in Mathematics.

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In psychology, an attitude refers to a set of emotions, beliefs, and behaviours towards a particular object, person, things or event. Attitudes are often the result of experience or upbringing. While attitudes are enduring, they can also change (Kendra, 2022). Attitude takes into account of organization of concepts, beliefs, habits and motives associated with a particular object. The concepts and belief associated with an attitude are often referred to as the cognitive component of attitude, the habit as the action component, and motives as the affective component. Attitude can be understood as a tendency which prepares a person to behave in a certain way towards a specific object or a class of objects subjects to conditions prevailing in the environment (Mangal, 2019). Therefore, the way that one thinks, feels, and reacts express one's attitude towards a particular object and these are formed under different conditions.

For Mangal (2019) attitudes are formed under the condition of integration of experience, differentiation of experiences, and trauma of experience and adaptation of the available attitudes. In another words, attitude can be formed by an individual personally or by observing, imitating and learning from the environment. Mensah, et.al (2013) affirmed that attitude is seen as more or less positive and encompass emotions, belief, values and behavioral and hence affect individual way of thinking, acting and behaving which has a lot of implications to teaching and learning. Therefore, some students' disposition towards Mathematics could be positive or negative which probably are determinants of high or low achievement in Mathematics.

The researcher observed that students' attitudes towards Mathematics probably influence the achievement of student in Mathematics. Some students view Mathematics as their Waterloo, as a result, they perform poorly in Mathematics. The attitude of the student apparently showed that Mathematics is a difficult and boring subject and this tends to make students develop lesser interest and lose confidence in Mathematics.

Dowker, et.al (2016) expressed that Mathematics anxiety is another students' attitude, which is a feeling of tension that interferes with students' abilities in solving Mathematical problems and that Mathematics anxiety could be traced to the students own learning experiences in school. Belbase (2013) explained that when one thinks about Mathematics anxiety, two things may come to one's mind, one is 'anxiety as a progressive thinking' and the other is 'anxiety as a regressive thinking'. All anxiety is not worthless things. Therefore, some students seem to experience progressive thinking when they are puzzling in a Mathematics problem for a few days and trying to solve it in a variety of ways without losing passion. Then certainly it is a good thing. Anxiety is mostly taken as regressive thinking in the situation where some students tend to have anxiety and trying to go away or get rid of Mathematical problem simply by avoiding it and taking it negatively. For instance, where the subject performance in most cases is ranked the last, students appear to associate the subject with failures. They see the nature of Mathematics to cause panic, unnecessary anxiety, fear and hatred during Mathematics lesson. Some get nervous to ask questions during classes and see working on their assignment as a stressful task. Mostly, they feel tensed when preparing for a Mathematics tests, quizzes and examinations. As a result, they tend to avoid and ignore the subject and probably prefer to engage in other activities that they anticipate will result in reward (Dowker, et.al 2016).

Poor Mathematics achievement of students in internal and external Examination is a reflection of the problem and challenges facing the educational system in Nigeria today and Federal Capital Territory, Abuja in particular. These poor students' Mathematics achievement has been of great concern to parents, teachers, counselors, school administrators, curriculum planners, students themselves and researchers. Despite the availability of suitable teaching facilities, qualified and competent teachers, all guidance programs and counseling strategies, conducive environment, regular payment of teachers' salaries and parental involvement to improve students' Mathematics achievement, poor Mathematics achievement are recorded yearly in senior secondary schools FCT, Abuja and this has become necessary to find out the variables that influence such poor achievement (Belbase, 2013). Poor Mathematics achievement usually brings about sadness and frustration to the individual concerned and to his or her parents as well as other education stakeholders. There has been wide cry each year for poor achievement when WAEC or NECO releases their annual results. Candidates' achievement at the Senior School Certificate Examinations (SSCE) conducted by WAEC and NECO has consistently remained poor in Mathematics.

Student attitudes towards Mathematics appear to be responsible for these ugly trends as they are key factors that probably influence Mathematics achievement. The disposition that Mathematics is difficult, logical and boring seem to make students think they cannot understand mathematics and that Mathematics is meant for only talented students. Alphine (2015) conducted research on students' attitudes and their effects on learning and achievement in Mathematics in public secondary schools in Kikuyu Kiambu County, Kenya. The objectives of the study are to determine the perception of students about Mathematics in public secondary schools in Kiambu county, to examine the factors influencing students' attitudes towards mathematics, to investigate how the students' attitudes affect their learning and achievement in mathematics and to seek recommendations on how to improve students' attitudes towards learning and achievement in Mathematics. The sample size

Students' Psycho-social Disposition ... (Adikwu & Aruwa, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8371116>

was 140 students from seven sampled schools with about 700 form four students. The sampled schools were selected using multi-stage sampling methods so as to bring about the expected variability, make the sample more representative.

Descriptive survey design was used for the study. The main instrument used for the study was questionnaire. The percentages obtained were used in making comparisons and conclusion. The result obtained was presented using bar chart. Also, the results of the previous grades of the students from end of the term were used to gauge their performance in Mathematics. The result indicated that the students have positive attitude towards Mathematics and therefore expected to perform better.

Jerry, et.al (2019) carried out a study on The Effects of Mathematics Anxiety on the Achievement of Senior Secondary Two Students in Jos North Local Government Area of Plateau State. The purpose of the study was to determine the extent at which Mathematics anxiety affects students' achievement in Mathematics and to suggest ways of raising students interest in Mathematics. The targeted group for the study comprised of all co-educational Governments owned senior Secondary schools in Jos North Local Government Area of Plateau State. The population for the study consisted of all 4,234 Senior Secondary two students within Jos North Local Government of Plateau State. Random sampling technique was adopted in selecting 120 students made up of 30 from each of the for selected secondary schools used for this study. Survey research design was adopted. Two instruments were used for data collection. A Mathematics Anxiety Scale Questionnaire (MASQ) adopted from Driscoll structured to elicit information required by the research question and it was based on a four-points scale. The rule used to distinguish between significance and insignificance of the responses was the average four –points scale which is below 2.50. Any mean score up to 2.50 and above is regarded as positive while any mean score below 2.50 is regarded negative. Achievements were measured by using scores already awarded or the students' mock examination which was the reason the researcher selected SS2 for this study because of all co-educational Government s owned senior secondary schools Jos North Local Government Area of Plateau State do sit for mock examination in SS2. The data collected were analyzed using average percent and chi square statistic. The research was answered using mean and standard deviation while the research hypothesis was done using SPSS package. The result showed that students agreeing that Mathematics anxiety to large extent exist among them because all the statements have mean score greater than the cutoff point of 2.50. This implies that all students generally agreed that Mathematics anxiety exist among students and has great effects on their achievement in Mathematics.

Fung et al (2018), carried out a study on student Engagement and Mathematics Achievement: Unravelling main and interactive effects. The study explored the relationship between student engagement and Mathematics achievement. The population of 295,416 from 11,767 secondary schools in 34 countries who participated in the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) 2012. Only school students aged between 15years 3months and 16years 2months at the beginning of the PISA assessment period were invited to participate in PISA 2012. This study used data from PISA 2012 PISA 2012 was sponsored and administered internationally by PISA International consortium. The respondents' preferences were determined using a four –points scale, Three-level (students, school and country level) HLM was used to examined the main effect of different pairwise combination of engagement. Students in countries were sampled using a two-stage strategy. From each of the school sampled, 35 students or fewer were sampled with equal probability from a list of all students within the school. Independent samples t-tests were next employed to address research objective 2 of the study, namely to examine whether students benefited from having higher levels of engagement in two different components simultaneously. The result showed that components of students' engagement (affective, behavioural, and cognitive) were individually related to their Mathematics achievement. A comparison of the HLM results for the relationship between different components of students' engagement and their achievement showed that students 'behavioural engagement, as measured by their participation in different Mathematics learning activities inside and outside the classroom, made only a small difference to their achievement when compared to those for affective or cognitive engagement. The above study was conducted over the shore of Nigeria to explore the relationship between student engagement and Mathematics achievement. While the present study is aim at investigate the influence of student attitudes on Mathematics achievement of senior secondary school Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria. Using the component of students' attitudes towards Mathematics, mathematics anxiety and behavioral-engagement of students on Mathematics to justified Students' Psycho-social Disposition and its influence on Mathematics achievement of senior secondary schools in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja.

Objectives of the Study

Specially, the study sought to;

1. Examine the influence of students' attitudes towards Mathematics achievement in senior secondary school students of FCT, Abuja.

Students' Psycho-social Disposition ... (Adikwu & Aruwa, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8371116>

2. To determine the influence of mathematics anxiety on Mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students of FCT, Abuja.
3. Assess the influence of behavioral-engagement of students on Mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students of FCT, Abuja.

Research Questions

1. To what extent does students' attitude towards Mathematics influence the achievement in Mathematics of senior secondary school students of FCT, Abuja?
2. To what extent does Mathematics anxiety influence Mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students of FCT, Abuja?
3. To what extent does behavioural-engagement influence Mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students of FCT, Abuja?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant influence of students' attitudes on Mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students of FCT, Abuja.
2. There is no significant influence of Mathematics anxiety on Mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students of FCT, Abuja.
3. There is no significant influence of behavioural-engagement on Mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students in FCT, Abuja.

Methodology

A descriptive survey design was adopted for this study. The population of this study is 24,771 of 77 public senior secondary schools in FCT, Abuja. The sample for the study was 384 students using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sampling table. Simple random sampling technique was used. Two self-structure question was used. The questionnaire was designed to find out the extent of Students' Psycho-social Disposition and its influence on Mathematics achievement of secondary school students. The instrument was divided into four sections A, B and C. Section A covers 1-10 on students' attitude. Section B takes care of items 11-20 on students' Mathematics anxiety while Section C was from items 21-30 on students behavioral-engagement on Mathematics. The responses were on the continuum of four-point rating scale. The instruments yielded logical validity indices of 0.83 and 0.74 and resulted to an average index of 0.79. with a reliability index of 0.81. The data collected would be analyzed using mean score and standard deviation and t-test would be used to test the formulated null hypotheses. All statistical analysis was conducted with a significant level of 0.05.

Results

Research Question 1

To what extent does students' attitude towards Mathematics influence the achievement in Mathematics of senior secondary school students of FCT, Abuja?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation Showing Respondents' Views on the extent to which Students' Attitude Towards Mathematics influence the achievement of Mathematics of senior secondary school students of FCT, Abuja

SN	Items	Mean	Std Dev	Remarks
1	Learning mathematics requires much effort.	2.87	0.82	Agree
2	Mathematics is a boring subject.	3.05	1.19	Agree
3	On my own I can take initiative in learning Mathematics.	2.91	0.96	Agree
4	I do not have mathematics abilities and skills to solve complex problems.	2.56	1.11	Agree
5	There is no sex difference in understanding Mathematics	2.67	1.16	Agree
6	I do not require high knowledge and performance in mathematics to excel	2.98	0.78	Agree
7	I believe I can understand the content in the mathematics courses.	2.92	1.01	Agree
8	Mathematics is important in our daily interactions	2.67	1.08	Agree
9	I rate mathematics equally high as other core subjects	2.94	0.96	Agree
10	Mathematics is useful in life.	2.79	1.01	Agree
	Average mean	2.84	1.01	

Students' Psycho-social Disposition ... (Adikwu & Aruwa, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8371116>

Table 1 shows the views of respondents on the extent to which students' attitude towards mathematics influence the achievement in mathematics of senior secondary school students in FCT, Abuja. An overview of the table shows that the mean responses based on questionnaire items answered by respondent were generally high. The grand mean (overall mean) is given as 2.84. This value is above the accepted scale mean of 2.50. It implies therefore that students' attitude towards mathematics has high influence on achievement in mathematics of senior secondary school students of FCT, Abuja.

Research Question 2

To what extent does Mathematics anxiety influence Mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students of FCT, Abuja?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation Showing Respondents' Views on the Extent to which Mathematics Anxiety Influence Mathematics Achievement of Senior Secondary School students of FCT, Abuja

SN	Items	Mean	Std Dev	Remarks
11	Anxiety and fear grip my mind during mathematics lesson.	2.87	0.82	Agree
12	I feel stressed when listening to mathematics instructors in class.	2.79	1.02	Agree
13	I am afraid to give an incorrect answer during my mathematics class.	2.83	1.00	Agree
14	Working on mathematics homework is stressful for me.	2.81	1.08	Agree
15	I believe I can learn well in a mathematics course.	2.99	0.82	Agree
16	I get tense when I prepare for a mathematics test.	2.65	1.00	Agree
17	I worry that I will not be able to get a good grade in my math's examinations.	3.10	0.82	Agree
18	I get panicked due to constant failure in mathematics examinations.	3.26	0.76	Agree
19	I worry that I do not know enough mathematics to do well in future mathematics courses	2.60	1.14	Agree
20	I feel confident enough to ask questions in my mathematics class	2.84	0.85	Agree
	Average mean	2.87	0.93	

Table 2 shows the views of respondents on the extent to which Mathematics anxiety influence Mathematics achievement in senior secondary school students of FCT, Abuja. An overview of the table shows that the mean responses based on questionnaire items answered by respondent were generally high. The grand mean (overall mean) is given as 2.87. This value is above the accepted scale mean of 2.50. It implies therefore that Mathematics anxiety has a high influence of Mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students of FCT, Abuja

Research Question 3

To what extent does behavioural-engagement influence Mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students of FCT, Abuja?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation Showing Respondents' Views on the Extent to which Behavioural-Engagement Influence Mathematics Achievement of Senior Secondary School students of FCT, Abuja

SN	Items	Mean	Std Dev	Remarks
21	I pay attention in mathematics classes.	2.87	0.82	Agree
22	I work hard on my mathematics homework.	2.56	1.11	Agree
23	I avoid any form of distractions when studying mathematics	2.67	1.16	Agree
24	I enjoy talking about mathematics problems with friends	2.98	0.78	Agree
25	I study hard for mathematics tests.	2.92	1.01	Agree
26	I find it pleasurable participating in mathematics competitions.	2.67	1.08	Agree
27	I do mathematics more than other subjects two hours daily outside school.	3.10	0.82	Agree
28	I always have confidence when I want to attempt mathematics	3.26	0.76	Agree
29	I do not always study hard for test and examinations and I have been having poor grade.	2.60	1.14	Agree
30	I persevered until I understand mathematics contents,	2.84	0.85	Agree
	Average mean	2.85	0.95	

Table 3 shows the views of respondents on the extent to which behavioral-engagement influence Mathematics achievement of senior secondary school of FCT, Abuja. An overview of the table shows that the mean responses based on questionnaire items answered by respondent were generally high. The grand mean (overall mean) is given as 2.85. This value is above the

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accepted scale mean of 2.50. It implies therefore that behavioral-engagement has a high influence on mathematics achievement of senior secondary school in FCT, Abuja

Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant influence of students' attitudes on Mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students, FCT, Abuja.

Table 4: t-test Statistic showing the Influence of Students' Attitudes on Mathematics Achievement of Senior Secondary School Students, FCT, Abuja

S/N	Variables	N	Mean	Std Dev	df	t – cal	p-value	sig	Decision
1	Students Attitude	384	2.84	1.01	383	56.33	0.000	0.05	Significant
2	Academic Achievement	384	46.45	6.35					

**Significant at $\alpha = 0.05$

Table 4 indicates the significance of influence of students' attitudes on Mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students, FCT, Abuja. It is observed from the table the value of chi-square statistics is 56.33 with 383 given as degree of freedom at $p: 0.000 < 0.05$. Since the p- value of calculated t-test (0.000) is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, it implies that there is a significant influence of students' attitudes on Mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students, FCT, Abuja.

Hypothesis 2:

There is no significant influence of Mathematics anxiety on Mathematics achievement of senior secondary school FCT, Abuja.

Table 5: T-Test Statistic showing the Influence of Mathematics Anxiety on Mathematics Achievement of Senior

S/N	Variables	N	Mean	Std Dev	df	t – cal	p-value	sig	Decision
1	Mathematics Anxiety	384	2.87	0.93	383	65.24	0.000	0.05	Significant
2	Academic Achievement	384	46.45	6.35					

Secondary School FCT, Abuja

**Significant at $\alpha = 0.05$

Table 5 indicates the significance of influence of mathematics anxiety on Mathematics achievement of senior secondary school FCT, Abuja. It is observed from the table the value of t-test statistics is 65.24 with 383 given as degree of freedom at $p: 0.000 < 0.05$. Since the p- value of t-test (0.000) is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, it implies that there is a significant influence of mathematics anxiety on mathematics achievement of senior secondary school FCT, Abuja.

Hypothesis 3:

There is no significant influence of behavioural-engagement on Mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students in FCT, Abuja.

Students' Psycho-social Disposition ... (Adikwu & Aruwa, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8371116>

Table 6: T-Test Statistic showing the Significant Influence of Behavioral-Engagement on Mathematics achievement of Senior Secondary School Students in CT, Abuja.

S/N	Variables	N	Mean	Std Dev	df	t – cal	p-value	sig	Decision
1	Behavioural Engagement	384	2.85	0.95	383	56.33	0.000	0.05	Significant
2	Academic Achievement	384	46.45	6.35					

**Significant at $\alpha = 0.05$

Table 6 indicates the significance of influence of behavioural-engagement on mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students in FCT, Abuja. It is observed from the table the value of t-test statistics is 56.33 with 383 given as degree of freedom at $p: 0.000 < 0.05$. Since the p- value of calculated of t-test (0.000) is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, it implies that there is a significant influence of behavioural-engagement on mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students in FCT, Abuja.

Discussion of findings

The findings of this study have been discussed based on the hypothesis. The finding from hypothesis one reveal that there is a significant influence of students' attitudes on mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students, FCT, Abuja. This finding is in agreement with findings from the study of Alphine (2015) which showed that students' attitude had significant effects on learning and achievement in mathematics in public secondary schools in Kikuyu Kiambu County, Kenya. Mensah et al (2013) further noted that if positive attitude is developed towards Mathematics, high academic performance could be achieved. This positive attitude in this regard is a valid objective of mathematics education; it owns that if nurtured, the students' feelings would interact and influence the mental abilities and thereby having positive influence on learning and achievement of the subject. Students' attitudes towards Mathematics determine the success in the subject, their ability, willingness to learn the subject, and to work on variety of assigned tasks available. In general, the conceptions students hold about Mathematics determines how they approach Mathematics tasks leading them into either productive or non-productive orientations. In many cases, students have been found to approach Mathematics as procedural and rule oriented. This prevents them from experiencing the richness of Mathematics and the many approaches that could be used to develop competence in the subject (Alphine, 2015).

The findings from hypothesis two revealed there is a significant influence of mathematics anxiety on mathematics achievement of senior secondary school Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. This finding is similar to those of Jerry, et al (2019) which showed significant Effects of Mathematics Anxiety on the Achievement of Senior Secondary Two Students in Jos North Local Government Area of Plateau State. Mutegei, et al (2021) in their findings discovered there is a significant relationship between mathematics Anxiety, attitude and performance among secondary school students in Embu, Kenya.

The findings from hypothesis three indicates there is a significant influence of behavioral-engagement on mathematics achievement of senior secondary school students in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. Findings from Manmin, et al. (2021) showed that there was a significant influence of Student Engagement on Mathematical Achievement among Secondary School Students in Selangor, Malaysia. In addition, Manmin, et al., (2021) showed in their findings showed there was a significant relationship between student engagement and mathematics achievement. More so, Dylmoon, et al (2019) asserted that Student behavioral engagement contributes to meaningful learning. If students are behaviorally engaged, they will be involved during the class, and they have a sense of belonging to the class. This sense of belonging will make students experience the enjoyment of learning, recognize the meaning of learning, and not only come to the class just for getting by. It is the goal of a classroom as a learning community Dylmoon et al, 2019). On the contrary, if students are not engaged in the classroom, they lose the opportunity to learn more.

Conclusion

The study concludes that attitudes can have powerful influence over behaviour; while attitudes are enduring, they can also change. Mathematics anxiety could be traced to the students' own learning experiences in school. Students, who are behaviorally-engaged, work hard on Mathematics homework, discuss Mathematics problems with friends, attend classes

Students' Psycho-social Disposition ... (Adikwu & Aruwa, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8371116>

regularly and put more effort in their school work. They are more capable of overcoming initial difficulties and connecting their learning to individual mathematical concepts.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study the researcher recommends that:

1. Students in public senior secondary schools in the FCT, Abuja should be sensitized through workshops and seminars on the need to develop a positive attitude towards the learning of mathematics so as to ensure there is improvement in their academic achievement in mathematics.
2. Mathematics teachers should be creative in adopting various in the teaching and learning of mathematics so that the anxiety associated with mathematics can be controlled in such a way that learners develop the needed confidence that will improve their academic achievement.
3. Learners should be actively engaged in school and at home with a series of mathematical problems. They should be continuously drilled until they develop interest in the subject for the purpose of improving their academic achievement.

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The Role of Educational Psychology in Achieving Sustainable National Development: A Review of Literature

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Abstract

This paper examines the relationship between educational psychology and sustainable national development. Sustainable national development is defined as the process of improving the economic, social, and environmental well-being of a nation in a manner that ensures the well-being of future generations. Educational psychology is concerned with the study of human learning, motivation, and development in educational settings. The paper reviews the literature on the role of educational psychology in achieving sustainable national development. The review identifies several ways in which educational psychology can contribute to sustainable national development, including promoting environmental education, fostering positive attitudes towards sustainability, and enhancing students' critical thinking skills. The review also highlights some challenges and limitations in the application of educational psychology in achieving sustainable national development.

Keywords: Educational psychology, Sustainability, Challenges and limitations

Introduction

Sustainable national development is a complex and multifaceted concept that encompasses economic, social, and environmental dimensions. It is a process of improving the well-being of a nation in a manner that ensures the well-being of future generations. Achieving sustainable national development requires a comprehensive and integrated approach that takes into account the interdependence of economic, social, and environmental factors. Educational psychology can play a critical role in achieving sustainable national development by providing insights into human learning, motivation, and development in educational settings.

One way in which educational psychology can contribute to sustainable national development is by promoting environmental education right from early years, because that is a period when Montessori believes that children acquire most knowledge effortlessly Montessori, (1949). *The Absorbent Mind*. New York: Henry Holt and Company. Environmental education is the process of providing individuals with the knowledge, skills, and attitudes needed to understand and appreciate the natural world and to take responsible action to protect it. Environmental education believes that sustainable development is possible and warns against indiscriminate development that disregards ecological balance. It aims at creating a future society where people are aware of their civic responsibilities and are ready to play useful roles as producers and citizen's conscious of their environmental impact (ICSE, 2000). People need to be aware of what their environments look like, what it requires to stabilize it and what to avoid to protect it from natural disasters like erosion, earth quake among others. Educational psychology can help to design effective environmental education programs by providing insights into the cognitive, affective, and behavioral processes involved in learning about the environment. Research has shown that environmental education programs that are based on sound educational psychology principles are more effective in promoting environmental awareness and action.

Educational Psychology and Sustainability

Määttä and Uusiautti (2020) explored the role of educational psychology in sustainability education. They proposed that sustainable happiness education, focusing on human happiness and life satisfaction, can be a guiding principle for sustainability education. The authors emphasize the need to understand the reasons behind individuals' behaviors and the influence of habits and norms. They discussed the transition from consumerism to constructive behaviors and highlight the importance of individual responsibility and choices in achieving sustainable lifestyles. Their article suggests that a profound understanding of what is sufficient can promote happiness, satisfaction, and responsibility towards oneself, others, and the environment. Positive education is proposed as a means to enhance well-being, resilience, and sustainable behaviors. The authors argued for the integration of sustainable happiness education into teaching and curricula at all levels of education. They also emphasize the need for positive support and hope in promoting pro-environmental behavior. Overall, the article calls for educational psychology to contribute to sustainability education and foster positive change.

The Role of Educational Psychology in Achieving ... (Yusuf, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8371138>

Ronen and Kerret (2020) explored the concept of wellbeing and its connection to positive psychology and environmental sustainability. It highlights the limitations of using gross domestic product (GDP) as a measure of wellbeing and discusses alternative indicators such as the sustainable development goals, better life index, and happy planet index. The paper proposes an integrative policy approach to defining and promoting both human and environmental wellbeing using principles from positive psychology and environmental sustainability. It emphasizes the role of the educational system in promoting wellbeing and suggests a holistic sustainable wellbeing model that integrates positive psychology, environmental sustainability, and cognitive-behavioral therapy principles. The article concludes that a joint model of sustainable wellbeing can enhance personal wellbeing while fostering responsible global citizenship and caring for the planet's future. The definitions of wellbeing in positive psychology and sustainability are discussed, and the need for an interdisciplinary definition that considers the interdependencies between individuals and natural systems is emphasized. The concept of sustainable wellbeing is introduced, which focuses on improving individual wellbeing while also considering the wellbeing of others and the natural environment. This approach aligns with complex systems thinking and the World Health Organization's definition of mental health.

Moolla (2011) observed that a solid psychological perspective is urgently needed to address the environmental, social, and economic sustainability issues that our biosphere is currently facing. This perspective should complement biological, technological, and economic perspectives. In his article, he discusses positivistic and constructive psychology and provide a summary of major environmental problems and their implications for society and the economy. He also presents essential psychological reasoning related to these problems, including the commons dilemma model, different behavioral processes and strategies for behavior change, and various aspects of human quality of life. The authors argue that psychologists can play a crucial role in analyzing and mitigating the biggest sustainability problems, such as population growth, resource-intensive consumption, and harmful technologies. However, he explained how everything requires aligning psychological research with other environmental sciences, improving the incentive structure for this work, and paying more attention to the collective side of human behavior. He emphasizes the importance of sustainable development, environmental psychology, and behavior change strategies.

Educational psychology can also contribute to sustainable national development by fostering positive attitudes towards sustainability. Attitudes are important predictors of behavior, and positive attitudes towards sustainability can lead to pro-environmental behavior. Educational psychology can provide insights into the factors that shape attitudes towards sustainability, such as cognitive dissonance, social norms, and self-efficacy. By understanding these factors, educators can design interventions that promote positive attitudes towards sustainability. Attitude is one of the most important factors of learning because while knowledge and skills give a person potential, attitude is what determines their level of performance. This is because attitude controls a person's level of motivation. People can also be exposed to mindfulness, eating and activity habits to form their attitude towards sustainability of environmentally friendly activities.

Challenges and Limitations

Despite the potential benefits of educational psychology for achieving sustainable national development, there are some challenges and limitations in its application. One challenge is the lack of integration between educational psychology and environmental science. There is a need for greater collaboration between these disciplines to ensure that environmental education programs are based on sound educational psychology principles. Another challenge is the lack of emphasis on sustainability in educational psychology curricula. There is a need for greater attention to sustainability in the training of educational psychologists to ensure that they have the knowledge and skills needed to contribute to sustainable national development.

Conclusion

Educational psychology has the potential to make a significant contribution to sustainable national development by promoting environmental education, fostering positive attitudes towards sustainability, and enhancing critical thinking skills. However, there are some challenges and limitations that need to be addressed to ensure that educational psychology is effectively integrated into sustainability efforts. Greater collaboration between educational psychology and environmental science and greater emphasis on sustainability in educational psychology curricula are needed to maximize the potential of educational psychology for achieving sustainable national development.

The Role of Educational Psychology in Achieving ... (Yusuf, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8371138>

Recommendations

The followings are recommendations base on the findings of this paper:

1. **Integration of educational psychology and environmental science:**
2. There is a need for greater collaboration between these two disciplines to ensure that environmental education programs are based on sound educational psychology principles.
3. **Emphasis on sustainability in educational psychology curricula:** The training of educational psychologists should include a focus on sustainability to ensure that they have the knowledge and skills needed to contribute effectively to sustainable national development.
4. **Promotion of critical thinking skills:** Educators should prioritize the teaching of critical thinking skills to enhance students' ability to make informed decisions about complex issues such as sustainability.
5. **Increased awareness and education:** Efforts in schools from primary to tertiary levels should be made to increase awareness about environmental issues and educate people about sustainable practices to encourage individuals to adopt eco-friendly habits.
6. **Mindfulness and conservation:** Media programs can be introduced to educate citizens on being mindful about consumption habits and actively conserving resources can make a significant difference in the environment. For instance, turning off lights and electronic devices when not in use, taking shorter showers, and using reusable bags instead of single-use plastic bags can help reduce waste and conserve resources.
7. **Taking responsibility:** Individuals should be encouraged to take personal responsibility for their environmental impact and make conscious decisions about what they buy, where they shop, and how they dispose of their waste.
8. **Adopting a long-term perspective:** Nigerian Government should recognize the importance of sustainability and adopting a long-term perspective is another essential attitude. By focusing on long-term benefits, such as clean air and water, we can prioritize environmental protection over short-term gains.
9. **Critical thinking:** educational psychology can also contribute to sustainable national development by enhancing students' critical thinking skills. Critical thinking skills are important for making informed decisions about complex issues such as sustainability. Educational psychology can provide insights into the cognitive processes involved in critical thinking, such as problem-solving, reasoning, and decision-making. By teaching students' critical thinking skills, educators can help them to become informed and active citizens who are capable of making responsible decisions about sustainability.

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Towards Enhancing Literacy and Numeracy Skills among Students in Inclusive Education Settings

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Abstract

This paper, “Towards Enhancing Literacy and Numeracy Skills among Students in Inclusive Education Settings” explores effective strategies for achieving inclusive education and enhancing literacy and numeracy skills. The importance of improving literacy and numeracy skills is emphasized, as they are crucial for success in education and life. The paper discusses various strategies for improving these skills, including making the material relevant, providing feedback, using technology, incorporating visuals, encouraging practice, promoting group work, and making learning enjoyable. Additionally, the paper examines the challenges faced by educators in implementing inclusive education strategies and proposes potential solutions to overcome them. The research aims to provide practical recommendations for educators and policymakers to promote inclusive education and enhance literacy and numeracy skills among all learners. The paper discusses the role of Inclusive Education in providing equitable opportunities for students with diverse learning needs, ensuring that every learner can participate actively and achieve their fullest potential. The findings of this study contribute to the existing literature on inclusive education and provide insights for effective educational practices.

Keywords: Inclusive education, Literacy skills, Numeracy skills, Effective strategies, Visuals, Practice,

Introduction

Inclusive education has emerged as a paramount concern in educational systems worldwide, aiming to provide equitable access and opportunities for all learners, regardless of their diverse backgrounds and abilities (UNESCO, 2019). It emphasizes the importance of creating learning environments that foster the development of essential skills, such as literacy and numeracy, for every student. Recognizing that literacy and numeracy skills form the foundation for academic success and lifelong learning, educators and policymakers have increasingly sought effective strategies to ensure the inclusion and progression of all learners.

This article delves into the exploration of strategies that can effectively enhance literacy and numeracy skills within inclusive education settings. By understanding and analyzing these strategies, educational stakeholders can make informed decisions and implement evidence-based practices to support diverse learners in their literacy and numeracy development. The significance of this study lies in its potential to shed light on inclusive education practices that promote the acquisition of literacy and numeracy skills for learners across a broad spectrum of abilities, including students with disabilities, English language learners, and those from marginalized backgrounds. By identifying and investigating effective strategies, this research aims to contribute to the ongoing discourse on inclusive education, providing educators, researchers, and policymakers with valuable insights to guide their decision-making and foster positive outcomes for all learners.

To accomplish this, we will review existing literature on inclusive education, focusing specifically on strategies aimed at enhancing literacy and numeracy skills. For instance, research has shown that the implementation of differentiated instruction, which involves tailoring teaching methods and content to meet individual student needs, can significantly improve literacy and numeracy outcomes for diverse learners (Tomlinson, 2017). Additionally, assistive technology tools, such as text-to-speech software and adaptive learning platforms, have demonstrated efficacy in supporting learners with disabilities in their literacy and numeracy development (West, 2020).

Drawing on a wide range of scholarly sources, including empirical studies, theoretical frameworks, and best practices, we will explore the diverse approaches and interventions that have shown promise in fostering inclusive learning environments. This article will also examine the underlying principles and theories that inform inclusive education practices, such as Universal Design for Learning (UDL), differentiated instruction, and assistive technology (Rose & Meyer, 2002). By examining these

Towards Enhancing Literacy and Numeracy Skills ... (Yusuf, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8371317>

theoretical foundations, we can better understand the rationale behind inclusive strategies and their potential impact on literacy and numeracy outcomes.

Inclusive Education

Inclusive education is an approach that seeks to ensure that all students, including those with disabilities, have access to and are supported in their education within the regular education system. Inclusive education also refers to the educational approach that aims to provide equitable access and opportunities for all learners, regardless of their diverse backgrounds, abilities, or characteristics (UNESCO, 2009). It is based on the principle that every student has the right to participate fully in the learning process and receive appropriate support to achieve their maximum potential. Inclusive education promotes the belief that diversity in the classroom should be recognized, valued, and celebrated. It goes beyond mere integration or placement of students with disabilities or special educational needs in mainstream classrooms. Instead, it focuses on creating inclusive learning environments that embrace and accommodate the individual differences of all students.

A number of theories have also been formulated to explain inclusive education, like the social model of disability, which is a prominent theoretical framework within inclusive education. It emphasizes that disability is not solely an individual's impairment but is also influenced by societal barriers and attitudes. According to Oliver (1996), "the social model of disability proposes that disability results from the interaction between individuals with impairments and the disabling barriers present in society". Inclusive education, within this framework, aims to eliminate these barriers and create an inclusive learning environment that accommodates the diverse needs of all students.

Universal Design for Learning (UDL) is another influential theory in inclusive education. UDL promotes the design of flexible learning environments and instructional materials that can be accessed and utilized by all students, regardless of their diverse abilities or learning styles. According to Rose and Meyer (2002), UDL is an approach to curriculum and teaching that provides multiple means of representation, expression, and engagement. By offering multiple means of access, expression, and engagement, UDL aims to ensure that all students can actively participate and succeed in the learning process.

Critical pedagogy is another theory that was developed by Freire (1970), which promotes an inclusive approach to education that focuses on social justice and empowering marginalized students. It encourages educators to critically examine and challenge societal structures and power dynamics that perpetuate inequality in education. According to McLaren and Kincheloe (2007), critical pedagogy challenges the hidden assumptions that support and sustain institutionalized forms of oppression. Inclusive education within a critical pedagogy framework aims to foster critical consciousness, promote student agency, and actively address issues of social justice within society.

These theories contribute to the development of inclusive education practices by challenging traditional models, promoting equity and accessibility, and emphasizing social justice. They provide educators with frameworks and perspectives that support the creation of inclusive classrooms where all students can participate, learn, and thrive.

Strategies to Ensure Inclusiveness

A number of strategies have been developed to support the diversity in classrooms; this paper employs the following approaches:

- 1. Universal Design for Learning (UDL):** UDL is an approach that seeks to create flexible learning environments that can accommodate the learning needs of all students, including those with disabilities. UDL uses a variety of teaching methods, materials, and technologies to provide multiple ways of learning and engaging with information. Universal Design for Learning (UDL) is an educational framework that is based on the principles of Universal Design, which is an approach to design that seeks to create products and environments that are accessible and usable by the widest range of people possible, regardless of their abilities or disabilities. UDL is a flexible approach to teaching and learning that provides multiple means of representation, expression, and engagement to support the diverse learning needs of all students. The most important principles of Universal Design for Learning include: Multiple means of representation, Multiple means of action and expression, as well as Multiple means of engagement, which when adopted and incorporated into instructional practices, educators can design learning experiences that are accessible, inclusive, and effective for all students, including those with disabilities or diverse learning needs. Research has also shown the positive impact of UDL on student learning outcomes. For example, a study by Dalton and Strangman (2006) found that students who received instruction following the UDL principles demonstrated higher levels of engagement, motivation, and academic achievement compared to those in traditional instruction settings. Another study by Meyer et al. (2014) showed that UDL implementation improved student performance and reduced achievement gaps among students with diverse backgrounds and abilities.

Towards Enhancing Literacy and Numeracy Skills ... (Yusuf, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8371317>

2. **Collaborative Teaching:** This approach involves a general education teacher and a special education teacher working together to teach a class of students with diverse learning needs. Both teachers share responsibilities and work together to create an inclusive learning environment that supports the needs of all students. Collaborative teaching, also known as co-teaching, is an educational approach in which a general education teacher and a special education teacher work together in the same classroom to teach a diverse group of students. Both teachers share responsibility for planning, teaching, and assessing student learning, and they work collaboratively to create an inclusive learning environment that meets the needs of all students. Collaborative teaching provides several benefits for students, including: Increased access to support, more individualized attention, Differentiated instruction and improved socialization. In addition, there are different models of collaborative teaching, including co-teaching, team teaching, and parallel teaching.
3. **Peer Support:** Peer support is an approach that involves pairing students with disabilities with peers who can provide support and assistance in the classroom. This approach helps to build relationships between students and promotes social inclusion. Peer support is an inclusive educational approach that involves students with disabilities receiving support from their peers in a variety of educational settings. This approach focuses on building relationships and fostering a sense of community within the classroom by promoting positive interactions and providing opportunities for peer-to-peer support. Peer support can take many different forms, depending on the needs and abilities of the students involved. Some examples of peer support include: peer tutoring, Peer modeling and Peer counseling,
4. **Individualized Education Plans (IEPs):** An IEP is a plan that is developed for each student with disability. The plan outlines the student's learning goals and the accommodations and support they need to meet those goals (Smith & Johnson, 2010). IEPs are developed in collaboration with parents, teachers, and other professionals (Brown & Martinez, 2015), and they come together for the common goal of improving the lives of learners with inclusive educational needs. Jones & Williams (2018) on the other hand, explained Individualized Education Plan (IEP) as a legal document that outlines the educational goals, services, and accommodations that are tailored to meet the individual needs of a student with disability. The purpose of an IEP is to ensure that students with disabilities receive a free and appropriate public education (FAPE) in the least restrictive environment possible. The IEP process involves a collaborative effort between the student's parents, teachers, and other professionals who work with the student, such as special education teachers, therapists, and administrators. The process begins with an evaluation of the student's strengths and needs, which is used to develop goals and objectives for the student's education. The IEP team then determines the services and accommodations that are necessary to help the student achieve those goals.
5. **Assistive Technology (AT):** Smith & Johnson (2010) described Assistive Technology as any technology or tool that is used to support the learning and participation of students with disabilities. Examples of assistive technology include text-to-speech software, speech recognition software, and screen readers. Jones & Williams (2018), also analysed AT as devices, software, or equipment that are designed to help individuals with disabilities or impairments perform daily tasks, increase their independence, and improve their quality of life. AT can include simple tools such as canes, hearing aids, and magnifying glasses, as well as more complex devices such as prosthetics, communication aids, and mobility devices. AT can be used to address a wide range of disabilities, including visual, auditory, physical, cognitive, and developmental disabilities. It can help individuals with disabilities access education, employment, and social opportunities, and enhance their ability to participate fully in their communities.

Strategies to Enhance Literacy and Numeracy in Inclusive Education

There are several strategies Educators can adopt to enhance literacy and numeracy in inclusive education settings. Here are some effective strategies:

1. **Differentiated instruction:** Teachers should tailor their instruction to meet the needs of each individual student. This can involve providing additional support and resources to struggling learners, while providing more challenging materials and activities to advanced learners.
2. **Multisensory learning:** Multisensory learning is an approach to learning that engages multiple senses simultaneously to enhance the learning experience. This approach recognizes that learners have different learning styles and that some learners may be more receptive to certain types of information when presented through certain sensory channels. For example, some learners may prefer visual stimuli, while others may prefer auditory or tactile stimuli. Multisensory learning leverages this understanding by incorporating various types of sensory input into the learning process. This can involve incorporating visuals, sounds, tactile experiences, and even smells and tastes.

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Conclusion

In conclusion therefore, inclusive education has emerged as a crucial focus in educational systems worldwide, aiming to provide equitable access and opportunities for all learners regardless of their diverse backgrounds and abilities. The development of literacy and numeracy skills is fundamental for academic success and lifelong learning, and it is essential to ensure that inclusive education practices effectively support the progression of all learners. This article explored strategies and interventions that have demonstrated efficacy in enhancing literacy and numeracy skills within inclusive education settings. The paper also shed more light on inclusive education practices that promote the acquisition of literacy and numeracy skills for diverse learners, including students with disabilities, English language learners and those from marginalized backgrounds, through identification, investigation of effective strategies that provides valuable insights for educators, researchers and policy makers. It also discussed the assistive technologies used to enhance literacy and numeracy skills in inclusive educational settings. Overall, the promotion of inclusive education and the enhancement of literacy and numeracy skills go hand in hand. By implementing effective strategies, utilizing assistive technologies and fostering collaboration, educational systems can create inclusive learning environments that support the development of essential skills for all learners.

Recommendations

The following recommendations will go a long way in enhancing literacy and numeracy skills in an inclusive educational setting:

1. **Implement differentiated instruction:** Educators should adopt differentiated instruction strategies to tailor teaching methods and content to meet the diverse needs of learners.
2. **Incorporate assistive technology:** Government and School Proprietors should employ assistive technology tools into their instructional practices, for example text to speech software, adaptive learning platforms, among other assistive technologies for learners with disabilities to make institutions of learning more inclusive.
3. **Provide professional development and support:** Government and Educational Institutions should offer professional development opportunities for educators to enhance their understanding and implementation of inclusive education practices. **Foster collaboration and cooperation:** Collaboration among educators, researchers, policy makers and other stakeholders is vital to ensure the success of inclusive education initiatives by working together to share best practices, exchange knowledge and collectively contribute to the improvement of literacy and numeracy outcomes in inclusive education settings.
4. **Continuously evaluate and adapt to effective strategies:** It is crucial to continuously evaluate the effectiveness of strategies and interventions aimed at enhancing literacy and numeracy skills within inclusive education, by collecting data and feedback, educators and policy makers can identify arrears for improvement and make necessary adjustments to ensure positive outcomes for all learners.

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Trends in the Use of Wireless Fidelity on Campus among Undergraduates in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto

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Abstract

This study investigates the trends in the use of wireless fidelity (Wi-Fi) on campus among undergraduates in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto (UDUS). Four objectives were formulated at the onset of this study. Survey research design was adopted, and simple random sampling technique was used to select three hundred and ninety-six (396) students as sample using questionnaire as instrument for data collection. It was found that undergraduate make use of wireless fidelity available to them basically for academic purposes. Amount of time students spend carrying textbooks is reducing drastically because of access to wide variety of materials on the internet through Wi-Fi. Also, abuse of the wireless fidelity (Wi-Fi) for illicit purpose is low based on the findings of the study. It was also found that some students don't have access to internet enabled devices. Usage of wireless fidelity has positively influenced the undergraduates' academic performance. The students faced a lot of challenges such as power failure; low internet bandwidth; poor computer operating skills; unreliability of internet connection and small area coverage. Hence, the study concluded that there is a healthy usage of wireless fidelity on campus by undergraduates in the Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto. Thus, it was recommended among others, that management of UDUS should increase their broadband network in order to enable the students have free flow of information access on the internet.

Keywords: Education, Wireless Fidelity, Campus, and Internet.

Introduction

The world has experienced a technological revolution that has emerged rapidly in all fields including education field. The advent of information and communication technology (ICTs) in higher education and the remarkable development of their uses have completely revolutionized the relationship between knowledge and the pedagogical practices. This idea has been confirmed by United Nations, Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization UNESCO (2016) who clearly stated that ICT in the education programme focuses on the potential of ICT in achieving quality education for all. Yusuf (2010) identified that Nigeria, being a developing country with an emerging thrust in technology and gradually deploying technology because of its prowess, has failed to consider evaluating the impact of technology on the system it is deployed for. The academic community has undergone profound transformation during these years, assuming new dimensions influenced by technology-driven applications. The internet is a priceless source of information for students and a tool to enhance their productivity (Kirschner & Karpinski, 2010). This has made students to be heavy users of the Internet compared to the general public (Judd & Kennedy, 2010). This is why many universities now make provision for internet facility within the campus premises.

Adekunmisi *et al* (2018) reported that access to internet by university students impacts education in a positive way by increasing communication with classmates and professors, increasing access to libraries and educational databases, and improving study hours and study habits. However, despite the positive impact of the internet on academic performance, Akhter, (2018) found that excessive internet usage adversely affects one's physical health, family life and academic performance. Some literature shows that internet usage is on the increase from the adolescent to undergraduate students (Kunnuji, 2019). It was also revealed that these groups of users harness the benefits embedded in making use of Internet facilities such as Wi-Fi (Ofodu, 2012; Udende, 2010). Alshammari (2016) confirms that there is a huge number of learning materials embedded on the internet and the students can get a quick access to the information.

Recently, deep-seated changes have been witnessed in the structure and functions of higher institution of learning by the advent of information and communication technology (ICT) with the aid of computers that store, retrieve and process information as well as the Internet that connect computer and people together (Ilo & Ifijeh, 2010). According to Nguyen *et al* (2012), the term 'ICT' can be defined as "forms of technology which can be used for creating, displaying, storing, manipulating,

Trends in the Use of Wireless Fidelity on Campus ... (Idris & Isah, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8371331>

and exchanging information”. ICTs can also be described as computer-based technologies such as desktops, laptops, tablets, smartphones, and software and internet-based technologies including email, websites, and social networking sites which can be used for teaching, learning, and for other things.

Wireless fidelity often known as Wi-Fi, according to Bakare and Minah-Eeba (2018) is the technology that allows a personal computer (PC), laptop, mobile phone, or tablet device to connect at high speed to the internet without the need for a physical wired connection. The technology uses radio signals to transmit information between Wi-Fi enabled devices and the internet, allowing the device to receive information from the web in the same way that a radio or mobile phone receives sound. The internet usage has grown rapidly during the last decade in almost every country in the world and in Nigeria specifically which makes millions of individuals in the country to be connected to a global network. Almarabeh *et al* (2016) asserts that internet has become the backbone of the information economy. Internet is now being used by individuals and group of people in many sectors like education and communication.

The internet according to Adomi (2017) is very important to Nigerian university students in helping them to have access to timely, accurate and relevant information. Internet has brought a great change in the education sector in terms of teaching and learning unlike in the olden days. Alshammari (2016) confirms that there is a huge number of learning materials embedded on the internet and the students can get a quick access to the information. This is because the world is now on “palms”, and this was why Buhari (2018) posits that the internet is one of the recent advancements in the world of technology and it became useful instrument that has fostered process of making the world a global village. The internet is a platform that serves as global reservoir of knowledge for researcher and students to share common knowledge in a diverse way, they have often taken advantage of the virtual library to publish, interact and share findings (Hassan & Jacob, 2012).

Wi-Fi hotspots offered free of charge in public places that anyone could use to access the internet (Powell, 2018), thereby allowing the students access all the electronic information needs. The presence of Wi-Fi within a define range of hotspot enables the student to avoid the trouble of accessing information through the cable LAN which restricts the student from mobility, as Wi-Fi is proving to be the default internet access technology. Given the widespread adoption of mobile technology among students, combined with increased possibilities for network access (such as Wi-Fi connections in classrooms and across university campuses), and extended battery life, it is understandable that more and more students bring laptops to the classroom. In this sense, the students themselves make computers an important part in their educational activities. Ogunlade *et al* (2018) in their study revealed that majority of students had a positive attitude towards the use of internet facilities, and they believe internet facilities could generally provide better learning experience.

Salaam and Adegboro (2010) studied the internet access and use by students at private universities in Ogun State revealed that internet facilities are available in all the private universities studied. In the same vein, Fasae and Aladeniyi (2019) conducted a study on internet use by students of faculty of science in two Nigerian universities; they found out that majority of the science students use the internet for educational purposes. However, the impact of internet usage on academic performance was studied by Osunade *et al* (2018) using two universities as case study. The contact group did not have access to internet, while the experimental group had access to internet. The result showed a significant difference between the academic performances of the two groups. Additionally, Anasi (2016) investigated the pattern of internet use by undergraduates at the University of Lagos, main campus, Akoka, Lagos. The study discovered that even though the level of internet use was low among undergraduates from both the faculty of law and education. Further, it showed that internet use has a very high impact on the academic/career related activities of the students.

Studies by Sahin (2010) revealed that the internet has many benefits to the academic cycle; these include provision of round-the-clock access to a wide variety of information sources globally and the ability to discuss and share experience with colleagues to be able to derive maximum benefits from the attributes of ICT. Ugwulebo and Okoro, (2016) further submitted that the internet is a valuable source of information used by student in projects and assignments. With over 50million websites on the net, the chances are that information on any subject however obscure can be found using appropriate search tools. It also serves as a useful tool for lecturers in helping to prepare lesson plans using a number of sites dedicated to providing educational material. There are great possibilities for higher education at all levels through the use of internet because curricula can be developed collaboratively and educational materials distributed and updated more cheaply, offering additional ways for students to interact with their study materials as well as their instructors.

Notwithstanding, Paul *et al* (2012) asserts that time spends on online social networks pose significant negativity on academic performance of the students. This view was further supported by Kirschner and Karpinski (2010) saying that, excess involvement or obsession with social networking by students can have negatively impact on their academic performance. Similarly, Mohammed *et al* (2017), measured problems of students in using internet services, the study gathered that majority

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of the respondents indicated the problem of power failure, some reported the problem of slow internet speed and poor computer skills, while few reported problem of inadequate numbers of personal computers. Their finding is similar to that of (Quadri, 2013, Shehu, Urhefe & Promise, 2015). Rosenberg (2015) also observed that speed and reliability of internet connection is a major challenge faced by students in retrieving resources. Similarly, Luambo and Nawe (2014) reveal that the slow internet connections attributable to small bandwidth is also a major factor hindering internet access and use in Africa.

A survey conducted by Englander *et al* (2010) showed a negative relation between the amount of time spent on the internet per week and student's exam performance in a micro-economic class. In 2019, Smith and Salaway (2019) gathered that majority of all higher education students owned a laptop computer. This percentage may not be the same in UDUS but quite a number of students own a laptop computer. Since many universities like UDUS offer ubiquitous access to the internet, a laptop computer allows students to research, collaborate, and collect information almost anywhere within the university environment including the classroom (McCrea, 2010).

In UDUS, the entire university community has access to this wireless fidelity. The goal of which is to create an ICT proficient environment to aid the objective of the institution. It was gathered that this facility is available in selected nook and cranny of the university campus, thus there is a wide access and utilization of this internet facility by the students as access to the wireless fidelity helps in facilitating free flow of communication among the students, improve research proficiency of students and faculties at large. However, some students go to the extreme by taking advantage of this facility to download and watch movies ranging from TV series to pornography and music videos, gaming and entertainments etc., as a matter of fact it was observed that many students overstayed in the library or any other location where internet is available just to take advantage of good internet bandwidth. The rhetoric question is, could it mean that utilization of the wireless fidelity for other activities not captured within their academic curriculum implies that the essence of the wireless fidelity has been defeated? or does the fact that there is a huge rate of acceptability and utilization of the wireless fidelity mean it is being used for the original purpose by the students. Based on the foregoing, the study seeks to investigate the trends in the use of wireless fidelity (Wi-Fi) on campus among undergraduates in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto (UDUS).

Objectives of the Study

The major aim of this study is to investigate the trends in the use of wireless fidelity (Wi-Fi) on campus among undergraduates in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto (UDUS). The specific objectives are to:

1. find out the relevance of use of wireless fidelity on campus by undergraduates in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto;
2. ascertain the frequency of use of wireless fidelity on campus by undergraduates in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto;
3. investigate the impact of the usage of wireless fidelity on academic performance of undergraduate students in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto;
4. determine the challenges of using wireless fidelity on campus by undergraduates in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto;

Research Questions

1. What is the relevance of use of wireless fidelity on campus by undergraduates in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto?
2. What are the frequencies of use of wireless fidelity on campus by undergraduates in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto?
3. What are the impacts of the usage of wireless fidelity on academic performance of undergraduate students in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto?
4. What are the challenges of using wireless fidelity on campus by undergraduates in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto?

Methodology

Survey research design was adopted, and simple random sampling technique was used to select three hundred and ninety-six (396) students as sample using questionnaire as instrument for data collection. The population for the study covered undergraduate students across the fifteen (15) faculties in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto (UDUS). The estimated number of students in UDUS is 19,481 as at 2023/2024 academic session. In order to determine the required sample for the population, Slovin's Formula was used to compute the sample size. The simple random sampling technique gave equal chance to the respondents (undergraduates) across the faculties in the university to be selected for the sample. The demographic variables of the study cut across departments such as library and information science, veterinary science, geography, agriculture and mass communication departments with academic level from 100-500 level, both males and female respondents, age range between 15yrs to 30yrs. Descriptive analysis including relative frequencies and percentages were used with the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) computer software for analysis.

Trends in the Use of Wireless Fidelity on Campus ... (Idris & Isah, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8371331>

Results

Research Question 1

What is the relevance of use of wireless fidelity on campus by undergraduates in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto?

Table 1: Frequencies and mean scores on relevance of use of wireless fidelity on campus by undergraduates in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto (N=396)

ITEMS	No		Yes		Mean
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	
Academic purpose	47	11.9%	349	88.1%	.53
Mails	129	32.6%	267	67.4%	.67
Education and Research purposes	87	22.0%	309	78.0%	.78
Fun	63	15.9%	333	84.1%	.84
Communication purposes	114	28.8%	282	71.2%	.71
Sports and game information	188	47.5%	208	52.5%	.53

(Source: Field-Data, 2023)

More than half of the respondents use the Wi-Fi for academic purposes ($\bar{x}=0.53$); Majority of them ($\bar{x}=0.67$) use it for mails; a considerable high number of them use it for education and research purposes ($\bar{x}=0.78$); Almost all of them use it for fun ($\bar{x}=0.84$); Many of them use it for communication ($\bar{x}=0.71$); while slightly above half of them use it for sports and game information ($\bar{x}=0.53$).

Research Question 2

What are the frequencies of use of wireless fidelity on campus by undergraduates in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto?

Table 2: Frequencies and mean scores of use of wireless fidelity on campus by undergraduates in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto (N=396)

ITEMS	1	2	3	4	Mean	SD
Academic purpose	22	79	165	130	3.02	.867
	5.6%	19.9%	41.7%	32.8%		
Mails	6	34	192	164	3.30	.688
	1.5%	8.6%	48.5%	41.4%		
Education and Research purposes	43	103	145	105	2.79	.958
	10.9%	26.0%	36.6%	26.5%		
Fun	68	64	117	147	2.87	1.098
	17.2%	16.2%	29.5%	37.1%		
Communication purposes	75	115	148	58	2.48	.961
	18.9%	29.0%	37.4%	14.6%		
Sports and game information	113	68	111	104	2.52	1.161
	28.5%	17.2%	28.0%	26.3%		

(Source: Field-Data, 2023)

Table 2 shows the frequency of use of wireless fidelity by undergraduates in UDUS. All the items in this category receive more frequent usage by the undergraduates because most of them use the Wi-Fi for several purposes if not every day at least occasionally. $\bar{x}=3.02$, $SD=0.867$ indicates that most of the undergraduate make use of the wireless fidelity frequently for academic purposes. The frequency at which they use it for other purposes include; Mails ($\bar{x}=3.30$, $SD=0.688$); Education and Research Purposes ($\bar{x}=2.79$, $SD=0.958$); Fun ($\bar{x}=2.87$, $SD=1.098$); Communication purposes ($\bar{x}=2.48$, $SD=0.961$) and Sports and Game information ($\bar{x}=2.52$, $SD=1.161$).

Research Questions 3

What are the impacts of the usage of wireless fidelity on academic performance of undergraduate students in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto?

Trends in the Use of Wireless Fidelity on Campus ... (Idris & Isah, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8371331>

Table 3: Frequencies of impacts of the usage of wireless fidelity on academic performance of undergraduate students in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto (N=396)

ITEMS	No		Yes		Mean
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	
Using the wireless fidelity has increased my information quotient	35	8.8%	361	92.1%	.91
Increased my studying habits	220	55.6%	176	44.4%	.44
Improved access to quality information	87	22.0%	309	78.0%	.78
Through the Wi-Fi I have access to a wide variety of material on any topic	47	11.9%	349	88.1%	.88
Improved frontiers of knowledge	74	18.7%	322	81.3%	.81

(Source: Field-Data, 2023)

As shown in Table 3, there are 5 items used to evaluate the impact of usage of wireless fidelity on academic performance of undergraduates. It was gathered that usage of Wi-Fi has improved the information quotient of the respondents with mean value 0.91. However, more than half of the respondents (55.6%, $\bar{x}=0.44$) indicated that the use of Wi-Fi has reduced their study habit. Majority of them ($\bar{x}=0.78$) also noted that they have improved access to quality information through Wi-Fi. Similarly, almost all of them ($\bar{x}=0.88$) indicated that through Wi-Fi, they have access to a wide variety of materials on any topic. And lastly, a number of the respondents ($\bar{x}=0.81$) indicated that usage of Wi-Fi has improved their frontiers of knowledge.

Research Question 4

What are the challenges of using wireless fidelity on campus by undergraduates in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto?

Table 4: Frequencies of the challenges of using wireless fidelity on campus by undergraduates in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto (N=396)

ITEMS	No		Yes		Mean
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	
Limited internet enabled devices	25	6.3%	371	93.7%	.94
Power failure	39	9.8%	357	90.2%	.90
Poor computer operating skill	201	50.8%	195	49.2%	.49
Unreliability of internet connection	188	47.5%	208	52.5%	.53
Low bandwidth	11	2.8%	385	97.2%	.97
Small area coverage	64	16.2%	332	83.8%	.84

(Source: Field-Data, 2023)

Table 4 shows the various challenges faced by the undergraduates across the five selected departments in UDUS. All the items in this category were agreed to be a challenge faced by the students except poor computer operating skill which more than half of the respondents ($\bar{x}=0.49$) indicated that it is not a challenge. The specific challenges faced by the students are limited internet enabled devices ($\bar{x}=0.94$); Power failure ($\bar{x}=0.90$); Unreliability of internet connection ($\bar{x}=0.53$); Low bandwidth ($\bar{x}=0.97$) and small area coverage ($\bar{x}=0.84$). Apart from the structured question in this category, the respondents were given the opportunity to indicate other challenges they faced using an open-ended question type. Other challenges indicated by the respondents through open-ended questions are broadband network is only available in limited locations.

Discussion of Findings

Demographically, majority of the respondents are drawn from library and information science followed by geography, mass communication, agriculture, and veterinary science department respectively. Also, respondents in 300level make up the large number of the sample followed by those in other levels. The few ones in 500level are students from the department of Agriculture. Furthermore, the study revealed that more of the respondents are male while the rest of them are female in which many of them are those between 21 to 30years, very few are less than 20years and some are also slightly above 30years. This implies that majority of the respondents are still very young.

Trends in the Use of Wireless Fidelity on Campus ... (Idris & Isah, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8371331>

Findings of this study in respect to first research question show that undergraduates in UDUS make use of internet facility for several purposes checking mails and academic purposes are predominant. This corroborates the findings of Udende and Azeez (2010) who reported that most students of universities admitted that they mostly use the internet for academic purpose and for mails. Other purposes of using wireless fidelity as indicated by the respondents include; education and research purpose, fun, communication purposes, sports and game information.

The result gathered on the frequency of use of Wireless Fidelity by undergraduate revealed that undergraduates in the UDUS observe a frequent use of the wireless Fidelity available to them, meanwhile it is worthy of note that the frequency of use also varies depending on what they are using it for particularly. This is similar to the findings of Udende and Azeez (2010) who reported that majority of university students use the internet frequently, few agreed that they used the internet daily and average used the internet on weekly basis.

The results gathered on the impact of usage of wireless fidelity on academic performance of undergraduates further stresses the importance of the same to UDUS students. It was found that using the wireless fidelity on campus had positive impact on the academic performance of the students. This disagrees with the findings of Paul *et al* (2012) that conducted a study and found that the time spends on the internet pose significant negativity on academic performance of the students, while this is not completely because it only applies to certain instances where the students don't use the Internet service provided for them for the right course. Anything good can be bad if not channeled towards the right thing. This view was further supported by Kirschner and Karpinski (2010) saying that excess involvement or obsession with social networking by students can have negatively impact on their academic performance.

Subsequently, usage of wireless fidelity was found to have been improving the student's frontiers of knowledge, giving them access to quality education, and a wide variety of materials on any topic. This implies that wireless fidelity which is a product of ICT has a positive effect on students learning and it corroborates the assertions of Abbas *et al* (2019); and Verbrianto *et al*, (2011) who stated that ICT can positively affect students learning outcomes. However, many of the students indicated that the use of wireless fidelity has greatly reduced their studying habits. When this was further looked into, many of the students explained that because they usually make use of their phones and other devices to access the school Wi-Fi, it has greatly reduced the rate at which they read the traditional books, because they completely rely on online sources for any information they need.

The fourth finding reveals that students of UDUS faced diverse challenges in the use of the available wireless fidelity on campus. These challenges, as found out during the study are so high that almost all the students expressed their displeasure. The challenges faced by the students include; limited internet enabled devices; power failure; low internet bandwidth; poor computer operating skills; unreliability of internet connection and small area coverage. This corroborates the findings of Alshammari (2016) who confirmed as he discovered that student at University of Botswana lacked skills, and this greatly affected their meaningful exploration of the internet. Also, Muhammad *et al* (2017) measured the problems of students in using internet services, it was gathered that majority of the respondents indicated the problem of power failure, some reported that they encountered the problem of slow internet speed, while some had poor computer skills, few had the problem of inadequate numbers of personal computers. Their finding is similar to that of (Quadri, 2011, Shehu, Urhefe & Promise, 2015). While Quadri (2011) found that the major challenge faced by the students while using the internet was power outage with majority of the participants. Shehu, Urhefe and Promise (2015) underlined several challenges faced by the participants while accessing the internet in Nigeria libraries.

Conclusion

Availability of wireless fidelity on campus has been found to be of great benefits to the students. It is a tool that can help the university to easily achieve its mandate of teaching, learning, and research. But its availability does not determine usage and its usage may not necessarily mean it is being used for the right purpose. The school Wi-Fi can be abused if the students engaged use it for practices such as cybercrime, gambling, pornography etc. Also, wireless fidelity on campus can be more productive if the institution can try and overcome specific challenges associated with ICTs like power, broadband speed, among others. Even with the shortcomings that were identified in this study, it can be concluded that there is a healthy usage of wireless fidelity on campus by undergraduates in UDUS.

Trends in the Use of Wireless Fidelity on Campus ... (Idris & Isah, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8371331>

Recommendations

Based on the findings and identified gaps, the following recommendations were proffered:

1. Not all students have internet enabled devices. The school should go back to the days of providing internet enabled devices for the students at entry level.
2. Students should also be taught on how to connect to wireless network during computer related courses in class.
3. Governments should also make efforts to provide alternative power supply to the institution to overcome the challenges posed by power outage.
4. Funds should also be disbursed to the institutions in order to procure necessary, but expensive internet providing gadgets like router, LAN etc. across all the departments across the institutions.
5. The management of UDUS should increase their broadband network in order to enable the students have free flow of information access on the internet.

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Use of Instructional Methods and Materials in Teaching Fine and Applied Arts in Colleges of Education in South-West, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study determines the use of instructional methods and materials in teaching Fine and Applied Arts in colleges of education in South-West, Nigeria. The research design adopted for the study was descriptive research using survey methods. Therefore, all 141 Fine and Applied Arts lecturers in government owned were purposively selected for the study. The instrument for data collection was research designed questionnaire titled use of instructional methods and materials in teaching Fine and Applied Arts in colleges of education in South-West, Nigeria. The questionnaire was validated by three curriculum experts and three Fine and Applied Arts lecturers for face and content validity. Test re-test method was used for reliability study while the instrument was subjected to analysis using Cronbach alpha statistic. The value yielded 0.82, 0.77, 0.81, 0.71 and 0.67 respectively. Research questions 1, 3 and 5 were answered using mean rating while research questions 2 and 4 were answered using frequency count and percentage. The results indicated that project method, lecture method and discovery method were mostly used by the lecturers. Lecturer integrated Fine and Applied Arts students into the practical activities and used the equipment and materials regularly. The lecturers usually covered minimum standards. The major problem encountered by Fine and Applied Arts lecturers was inadequate time for practical work. Based on the finding of this study, it was recommended among others that the Fine and Applied Arts lecturers should be encouraged to attend seminars, workshops and conferences to update themselves in their teaching skills.

Keywords: Instructional method, Materials, Fine and Applied Arts,

Introduction

Any system that is resistant to change is heading to extinction. Change in this context also includes periodic evaluation of the state of performance and growth of the system. The system is dynamic. A dynamic system is a living system. A living system is such, that is, constantly updated and is consistent with (state-of-the-art) that is, the merging technology and innovations in principles and practice of all affairs, including educational affairs. Contextually, state-of-the-art refers to the integration of emerging technology in the teaching and learning of fine and applied art in schools. This corroborates Bisong (2012) who asserts that: We live in a dynamic society where social, political and technological conditions are changing continuously, so education providers should be aware of the trend in order to key into the current instructional approaches and curricular methods that will make teaching and learning processes to be improved and attractive so as to prepare the learner for the real-life challenges in our global community. Fine Art is an important subject area in the school system which the teaching and learning of other subject areas depend on for their successful instructional processes (Bassey & Nya, 2019).

The existence and growth of fine art in the primary and secondary school levels, which are the foundations of artistic development depends on the quality of Art teachers produced by the Colleges of Education. This implies that the quality of Art teachers produced by the Colleges of Education in Nigeria is sine-quo-non to the quality and growth of fine Art in the schools in Nigeria. Udosen (2007) opined that the quality of products is also a function of the method of teaching adopted in the teaching-learning process at the various levels of education. The author opined that assessment of instructional utilization strategies provides the standard for the types of education during the teaching-learning process.

At the College of Education level, the subject is studied as Fine and Applied Arts. There is no hard rule about the definition of Fine and Applied Arts. It has dual operational contents. Fine Arts is viewed as those artworks, created primarily

Use of Instructional Methods and ... (Kareem & Ayelaagbe, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8371345>

for aesthetic reasons, sometimes considered as arts-for-art-sake, rather than for commercial or functional use (Visual Art Encyclopedia, 2019). The document added that Fine Arts typically denotes such expressions as drawing, painting, printmaking and sculpture. It deals with aesthetics and the intellectual stimulation of the viewer while Applied Arts creates utilitarian works, these include architecture, digital art, photography, industrial design, fashion design, interior design as well as decorative arts. Fine or Applied Arts are both visual in nature. Fine and Applied Arts is important for the growth of the individual and the nation at large. Fine and Applied Arts enhance the process of learning, nourishes the system, which includes our integral sensory, attentional, cognitive, emotional capacities, which are in fact, the driving force behind all other learning (Jensen, 2011).

Koketso (2013) who reported that team teaching is an instructional technique in which two or more teachers get together to plan, implement and evaluate a teaching activity. Most teachers used team teaching as the main teaching strategy. Capon and Kuhn (2004) asserted that lecture method allowed more material to be covered in particular the multiple and varied exemplars that have been associated with superior acquisition and transfer. It is the most economical method of transmitting knowledge, but it does not necessarily hold the student's attention or permit active participation. Finding also revealed that the major problems encountered by Fine and Applied Art lecturers' positive attitude toward teaching. Chukwuemeka (2014) opined that teaching methods (also referred to as instructional methods) are primarily descriptions of learning objective-oriented activities, and flow of information between the teacher and the learners. Teaching methods is one of the ingredients necessary for effective teaching and learning activities. Teacher use various methods to implement the Art curriculum in the classroom teaching environment such as discussion, lecture, project, inquiry and discovery method.

Curriculum is an instrument that dictates the affairs of every educational system. It is the vehicle through which knowledge and other learning activities are disseminated. This indicates that the curriculum is a road map for learning and as such focuses on knowledge and skills that deemed fit for learning. Mkpa and Izuagba (2009) defined curriculum as the planned and guided learning experiences and intended learning outcomes, formulated through the systematic reconstruction of knowledge and experience under the auspices of the school for the learner's continuous and willful growth and personal social competence.

Curriculum implementation involves the dissemination of the structured set of learning experiences, the provision of resources to effectively execute the plan, and the actual execution of the plan in the classroom setting where teacher-learner interactions take place (Ivowi, 2009). In curriculum implementation, the learner for whom the programme is being planned interacts with the contents and materials in order to acquire the necessary skills, attitudes and abilities (Mkpa and Izuagba, 2009). They went further to define curriculum implementation as the actual engagement of the learner with the planned learning opportunities. This means that curriculum implementation is that stage of the curriculum process where the learner through the guide of a teacher interacts with learning activities so as to maximize learning as will be noticed in the learner's new behaviour/new approach to issues.

Another name for the teacher is curriculum implementer. The teacher is one who translates the curriculum document into operating curriculum through a joint effort of hers/his, the learners and other interest groups (Omoniyi, 2009). This implies that the task of implementing the curriculum lies on the teacher. The teacher does not just implement the content as it is; rather he breaks the content into teachable units. Precisely what comes to the teacher is not the curriculum plan rather the syllabus which he breaks down to get the scheme of work, down to the unit of plan and finally to the lesson plan which is being used daily in his/her teaching.

In a study, the National Center for Education Statistics (NCES) (2017) conducted on curriculum fidelity and professional development, teachers self-reported fidelity rates when implementing an English language learner (ELL) program. The authors, who used a log to rate the level and amount of time spent on using the curriculum as prescribed, found that 16% of participants recorded decreased levels of fidelity, 51% recorded average levels of fidelity, and 30% recorded consistent fidelity of implementation, as prescribed by the curriculum developers. Previous researchers have shown a need to identify the factors that contribute to teacher concerns and which barriers prevent full curriculum implementation (Lochner, Conrad & Graham, 2015). Understanding the barriers to complete implementation of a new curriculum could provide education administrators with tools to address teacher concerns and could provide vital training for successful implementation (American Institute for Research (AIR), 2016).

Fine and Applied (or Industrial) Arts is an academic subject that is divided into two major fields of study just as the name suggests "Fine" and "Applied", with different sub-divisions as areas of specialization. The philosophy of this programme is to provide academic and professional training for NCE teachers in Fine and Applied Arts. It aims at developing student's aesthetic perception, artistic talents and expression as well as stimulates interest and enquiries in the practical and theoretical

Use of Instructional Methods and ... (Kareem & Ayelaagbe, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8371345>

areas, particular as they affect the teaching of art at the primary and junior secondary school levels (Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN), 2020). The Fine and Applied Arts objectives are as follows:

1. Training professional art teachers to fill the manpower needs of the primary and junior secondary schools;
2. Equipping and providing the teachers with knowledge, understanding and skills in Fine and Applied Arts;
3. Equipping students with the necessary knowledge and skills for the promotion of Nigerian and world's artistic and cultural heritage;
4. Developing in the would-be teachers the ability to communicate effectively through the arts; and
5. Preparing teachers to qualify for and benefit from teacher education at the university level
6. Equipping NCE graduates with manipulative skills which will enhance their entrepreneurial skills to make them self-reliant and job creators (Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN), 2020).

Adeyemo (2012) summarizes Fine and Applied Arts as visual arts. He posits that visual arts are art forms that create works which are primarily visual in nature, such as ceramics, drawing, painting, sculpture, printmaking, design, crafts and often modern visual arts (photography, video, and filmmaking) and architecture. The state-of-the-art in the teaching is expressed through the integration of electronic technologies as an instructional mode in the school system. The conventional method of teaching of Fine and Applied Arts had been such that depended solely on the teacher and the analogue method which was boring because the teacher only depended on what they knew, as such references and interactivity which are important in teaching and learning of fine and Applied Arts, especially at the budding stage of artistic development, was limited and sometimes non-existent. It is unbecoming and embarrassing to say that, Fine and Applied Arts graduates from the Colleges of Education in Nigeria may not fit into the modern workplaces and art practices because they were not taught using the state-of-the-art instructional facilities (e-technology) to move with the time, some of the graduate artists have to go through another computer-based training after graduation to meet up with the expectations of today's clientele (Bassey & Nya, 2019).

For instance, a graphic artist who depends on the manual production process of graphic work such as banners and other adverts cannot match up with the speed and precision of the computerized machines for the production of flex banners and other digital items. This assertion is in line with, Lehman (2001) who asserts that "evidence of the effectiveness of arts for instance, in embracing student's creativity and producing more prepared citizens (artists) for the workplace for tomorrow, can be found documented in studies held in many varied settings from school campuses to the corporate world. If the school system lag behind in its instructional approaches the future of the nation's educational system will also lag, thus, retarding progress and development. The integration of electronic technology into the instruction of Fine and Applied Arts is apt and timely in the face of the prevailing circumstances confronting the growth of art in the school system and the circular world. Integrating electronic technology into the instructions of Fine and Applied Arts may enhance the quality of teaching and learning in the school system, and ultimately improve the performance and skills of learners in various learning experiences including specializations in Fine and Applied Arts.

Minimum standards curriculum implementation deals with effectiveness and successful execution of planning of curriculum to bring out desire result. The usefulness of any minimum standards is carried out in the lecture room and studio while the lecturer can be referred to as major implementers or executer of planned minimum standards. Sule and Igunu (2019) worked on assessment of planning and implementation process of the ministry of education in North-central geopolitical zone, Nigeria. The findings revealed that the ministry of education ensure that the purpose and mission of education at different levels are achieved through effective planning and implementation process in North-central geopolitical zone, Nigeria. Ogunbiyi (2019) also examined the evaluation of teachers' implementation of social studies curriculum in upper basic schools in Irepodun L.G.A of Kwara state. The result shows that the methods used in teaching Social Studies was lecture method to explain Social Studies concept to students.

However, both researchers focused on basic education and secondary schools' curriculum but none focused on implementation of minimum standard of colleges of education. The problems are essential far effective and successful implementation of new minimum standard curriculum in colleges of education for teaching Fine and Applied Arts. These include lecturers' incompetence, lack of availability and utilization of learning resource, lack of conducive learning environment, readiness and interest of the learners, methodology and lack of time for Fine and Applied Arts courses, for those reasons, the researcher intends to work on the use of instructional methods and materials for teaching Fine and Applied Arts in colleges of education in South-west, Nigeria.

Use of Instructional Methods and ... (Kareem & Ayelaagbe, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8371345>

Objectives of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to determine the use of instructional methods and materials in teaching fine and applied arts in colleges of education in South-West, Nigeria. Specifically, this study was designed to:

1. Determine teaching methods utilized in colleges of education.
2. Examine the extent of integrating fine and applied arts students' activities in colleges of education.
3. Assess the extent of the use of equipment and materials in colleges of education.
4. Determine the extent of content coverage in fine and applied arts in colleges of education.
5. Find out the problem lecturers encounter in the teaching fine and applied arts in colleges of education.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What are the methods used in teaching Fine and Applied Arts in colleges of education?
2. How often do lecturers integrate Fine and Applied Arts students into practical activities?
3. How often do the lecturers use the Arts equipment and materials for teaching Fine and Applied Arts in colleges of education?
4. How effective are lecturers in the covering of Fine and Applied Arts curriculum in the minimum standards in colleges of education?
5. What are the problems lecturers encountered in teaching of Fine and Applied Arts in colleges of education?

Methodology

The research design adopted for the study was descriptive research using survey method. The population for the study was all Fine and Applied Arts lecturers in government and private owned colleges of education in South-west, Nigeria. Purposive sampling technique was used to select all 141 Fine and Applied Arts lecturer in government owned colleges of education in South-West, Nigeria. The instrument for data collection was research designed questionnaire titled: Use of instructional methods and materials in teaching Fine and Applied Arts in colleges of education in South-West, Nigeria. The questionnaire was divided into six sections: A, B, C, D, E and F. Section A consist of general information on the name of the college and the state. Section B of the questionnaire composed eight items on the methods used in teaching Fine and Applied Arts in colleges of education. Section C was on the lecturers' integration of Fine and Applied Arts students into practical activities. Section D of the questionnaire contained 12 items on the lecturers' use of equipment and materials for teaching Fine and Applied Arts in colleges of education. Section E was on the content coverage of minimum standard in colleges of education. While section F comprised of eight items on the problem lecturers' encounter in teaching Fine and Applied Arts. 4-point Likert – scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) was used for section B, D and F. 3-point Likert - scale of regularly, fairly and not at all was used for section C and E. The instrument was validated by three curriculum expert and three Fine and Applied Arts lecturers for face and content validity. The reliability of the instrument was tested and the retrieved copy of questionnaire was subjected to analysis using Cronbach alpha statistic. The values obtained for the variables include method use, practical activities, uses of equipment and materials, content coverage and problem encounter in teaching Fine and Applied Art are 0.82, 0.77, 0.81, 0.71 and 0.67 respectively. Research questions 1, 3 and 5 were answered using mean rating with criterion mean of 2.50 while research questions 2 and 4 were answered using frequency count and percentage.

Results

Research Question 1

What are the methods used in teaching Fine and Applied Arts in colleges of education?

Use of Instructional Methods and ... (Kareem & Ayelaagbe, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8371345>

Table 1: The method used in teaching Fine and Applied Arts in colleges of education

S/N	Statement	Mean	Rank
1	I use lecture method to explain Fine and Applied Arts concept to students.	3.27	2 nd
2	Discussion method helps Fine and Applied Arts students to understand the concept.	2.52	5 th
3	Problem solving method is used for practical work in Fine and Applied Arts.	1.76	6 th
4	Discovery method is necessary in Fine and Applied Arts for students' creativity.	3.05	3 rd
5	It is necessary to dictate notes for Fine and Applied arts students	2.58	4 th
6	I adapt to the use of inquiry method to Fine and Applied Arts students	1.65	8 th
7	Team teaching is allowed in teaching Fine and Applied Arts students.	1.55	8 th
8	Project method guide and develop Fine and Applied Arts students.	3.49	1 st

Criterion mean = 2.50

Table 1 shows the methods used in teaching Fine and Applied Arts students in colleges of education. Out of a maximum of 4.6 point, the following mean score are obtained. Project method had a mean score of 3.49 (1st), lecture methods had a mean score of 3.27 (2nd), discovery method had a mean score of 3.05 (3rd), dictate notes to students had a mean score of 2.58 (4th) discussion method had a mean score of 2.52 (5th), problem solving method had a mean score of 1.76 (6th), inquiry method had a mean score of 1.65 (7th) while team teaching had a mean score of 1.55 (8th) respectively. This indicate that project method, lecture method and discovery method (creativity) were mostly used by the lecturers in teaching Fine and Applied Arts in colleges of education.

Research Question 2

How often do the lecturers integrate Fine and Applied Arts students into practical activities?

Table 2: The integration of Fine and Applied Arts into practical activities

Lecturers integrate students to practical activities	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Regularly	117	82.98
Fairly	24	17.02
Not	NIL	NIL
Total	141	100

Table 2 reveals that out of 141 Fine and Applied Arts lecturers in government own colleges of education in south-West, Nigeria. There were 117 representing (82.98%) regularly integrate the Fine and Applied Arts students into practical activities while 24 representing (17.02%) fairly integrate the Fine and Applied Arts students into practical activities. This shows that lecturers integrate Fine and Applied Arts the students into the practical activities.

Research Question 3

How often do the lecturers use the arts equipment and materials for teaching Fine and Applied Arts in colleges of education?

Table 3: The lecturers use of equipment and materials for teaching Fine and Applied Arts in colleges of education

S/N	Statement	Mean	Rank
1	I use poster colour (different colour) for teaching	3.32	2 nd
2	I use modeling tools (wooden and metal spatulas) for teaching	2.33	8 th
3	I use of canvas for teaching	2.94	4 th
4	I use screens squeegees printing frames for teaching	1.60	12 th
5	I use chisels (assorted sizes) for teaching	2.45	7 th
6	I use oil paints for teaching	2.87	5 th
7	I use drawing boards	3.41	1 st
8	I use screen printing inks (different colours) for teaching	1.72	11 th
9	I use plaster of paris for teaching	1.82	10 th
10	I use easel for teaching	2.67	6 th
11	I use welding machine for teaching	2.00	9 th
12	I use sabc brushes points for teaching	3.09	3 rd

Criterion mean = 2.50

Use of Instructional Methods and ... (Kareem & Ayelaagbe, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8371345>

Table 3 indicates that 141 respondents participated in this study. The equipment and materials used for teaching Fine and Applied Arts in colleges of education. Out of the maximum of 4.0 point, the following mean score are obtained. The use of drawing boards had a mean score of 3.41 (1st), poster colour had a mean score of 3.32 (2nd), the use of sable brushes had a mean score of 3.09 (3rd), the use of canvas had a mean score of 2.94 (4th), the use of oil points had a mean score of 2.87 (5th), the use of easel had a mean score of 2.67 (6th), the use of chisels had a mean score of 2.45 (7th), the use of modeling tools had a mean score of 2.33 (8th), the use of welding machine had the mean score of 2.00 (9th), the use of plaster of Paris had the mean score of 1.82 (10th), the use of screen printing inks had the means score of 1.72 (11th), while the use of screens squeegees and printing frames had the mean score of 1.60 (12th). This indicates that the Fine and Applied Arts lecturers used the equipment and materials regularly.

Research Question 4

How effective are lecturers in the covering of Fine and Applied Arts curriculum in the minimum standards in colleges of education?

Table 4: Content coverage of Minimum Standards in college of education

Content coverage of minimum standard	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Regularly	89	63.12
Fairly	38	26.95
Not	14	9.93
Total	141	100

Table 4 reveals that out of the 141 Fine and Applied Arts lecturers that participated in the study 89 representing (63.12%) Fine and Applied Arts lecturers regularly covered Fine and Applied Arts minimum standards, 38 representing (26.93%) Fine and Applied Art lecturers fairly covered minimum standards while 14 representing (9.93%) Fine and Applied Arts lecturers do not cover Fine and Applied Arts minimum standards. This shows that majority of Fine and Applied Arts lecturers cover Fine and Applied Arts in minimum standards in colleges of Education in South-West, Nigeria.

Research Question 5

What are the problems lecturers encounter in teaching Fine and Applied Arts in colleges of education?

Table 5: The problems lecturers encounter in teaching Fine and Applied Arts in colleges of education.

S/N	Statement	Mean	Rank
1.	You have financial constraints	2.90	3 rd
2.	School timetable will enhance the use of equipment and materials	2.47	5 th
3.	You lack support from college administration	2.31	6 th
4.	There is inadequate pre-service training	3.35	1 st
5.	Lecturers' low morale affect motivative approach to teaching	1.63	8 th
6.	You lack experience of handling some courses in minimum standards	2.67	4 th
7.	Needed resources, equipment and materials are not found in the school	3.07	2 nd
8.	You have too little or inadequate time for practical work	1.74	7 th

Criterion mean = 2.50

Table 5 indicates the major problem encountered by lecturers in teaching Fine and Applied Arts in colleges of education. Out of the maximum of 4.0 point, the following mean scores are obtained. There is inadequate pre-service training had a mean score of 3.35 (1st), needed resources, equipment and materials are not found in the school had a mean score of 3.07 (2nd), financial constraints had a mean score of 2.90 (3rd), lack of experience in handling some courses in minimum standards 2.67 (4th), school timetable will enhance the use of equipment and materials had the mean score of 2.47 (5th), lack of support from college administration 2.31 (6th), too little or inadequate time for practical work 1.74 (7th) while Lecturers' low morale

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affects motivative approach to teaching has a mean score of 1.63(8th). This shows that the major problem lecturer encountered in teaching Fine and Applied Arts in college of education was inadequate time for practical work and lecturers' attitude toward teaching.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study based on five research questions revealed that project method, lecturer method and discovery method were mostly used by the lecturers for teaching Fine and Applied Arts in colleges of Education. This finding supports the finding of Chukwuemeka (2014) who reported that teachers use various methods to implement the Arts curriculum in the classroom teaching environment such as discussion, lecture, project, inquiry and discovery method, which when appropriately utilized inculcate the described reflective, critical thinking and problem-solving skill to the learners. Furthermore, this present study negates that of Koketso (2013) who reported that most teachers used team teaching as the main teaching strategy.

Findings further revealed that lecturers integrated Fine and Applied Art students into the practical activities. This finding is in agreement with Adeyemo (2012) who summarized Fine and Applied Arts as Visual arts which are primarily visual in nature, such as ceramics, drawing, painting, sculpture, printmaking, design, crafts and other practical work for both lecturers and Fine and Applied Arts students. Also, findings revealed that Fine and Applied Arts instructors used the equipment and materials regularly. This finding agreed with the FRN (2020) who suggested one art technical officer, who must possess OND/NCE in Art to supervise Arts studio and galleries with equipment and materials as follows poster colours, sable brushes paints, digital camera, digital photo printer, oil paints among other.

It was also discovered in this study that majority of the Fine and Applied Arts lecturers in this study regularly covered Fine and Applied Arts in minimum standards in colleges of education. Capon and Kuhn (2004) asserted that lecture method allowed more material to be covered in particular the multiple and varied exemplars that have been associated with superior acquisition and transfer. It is the most economical method of transmitting knowledge, but it does not necessarily hold the student's attention or permit active participation. Finding also revealed that the major problems encountered by Fine and Applied Art lecturers' positive attitude toward teaching. The finding agreed with the finding of Ogunbiyi (2019) found that teachers who are crucial agents in interpreting and implementing the curriculum were not involved in the curriculum development process in Nigeria.

Conclusion

Findings revealed that project method, lecture method and discovery method were mostly used by Fine and Applied Arts lecturers in teaching Arts in colleges of Education in South-West, Nigeria. It was also discovered that lecturers integrated Fine and Applied Arts students into the practical work. The equipment and materials used in teaching Fine and Applied Arts were poster colour, modeling tools, canvas, screen squares, printing, frame, chisels, oil paints, drawing boards, screen printing inks, plaster of Paris, easel, welding machine, sable brushes among other. Furthermore, the majority of Fine and Applied Art lecturers cover Fine and Applied Art minimum standard in colleges of education and the major problem lecturers encountered in teaching Fine and Applied Arts was inadequate time for practical work and lecturers' attitude toward teaching.

Recommendation

The following recommendations are made based on the findings of the study.

1. Fine and Applied Arts lecturers should be encouraged to attend seminars, workshops, and conferences to update themselves in order to improve the quality of their teaching skills.
2. There is need for college administrators to give the Fine and Applied Arts lecturers incentive which will serve as motivation. This will encourage them in carrying out their teaching effectively.
3. The college administrators should allocate adequate time to the practical work of Fine and Applied Arts on the school time table.
4. Fine and Applied Arts lecturers should improve their teaching techniques by using art equipment, materials and good method of teaching.
5. Lecturers should encourage Fine and Applied Arts students to participate in Arts activities both theories and practical work

Use of Instructional Methods and ... (Kareem & Ayelaagbe, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8371345>

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